

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

Function Spaces XIII

8-12 July 2024

Faculty of Mathematics
and Computer Science
Adam Mickiewicz University
in Poznań

*In memory of
Henryk Hudzik
and Julian Musielak*

Invited speakers

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Function Spaces 13

Conference Proceedings

In memory of Henryk Hudzik and Julian Musielak

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The submitted articles are summaries of lectures and have not been reviewed.

Contents

About	9
Scientific Committee	9
Organizing committee	9
Invited Speakers	10
Diana Caponetti , <i>On some generalizations of Ascoli-Arzelà theorem</i>	10
Marek Cúth , <i>(Isometries on) paces of Lipschitz functions and their preduals</i>	36
Andreas Defant , <i>Projection constants for spaces of multivariate polynomials</i>	53
Dorothee D. Haroske , <i>Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces</i>	78
Anna Kamińska , <i>Overview of Musielak-Orlicz-Sobolev spaces</i>	98
Lech Maligranda , <i>Henryk Hudzik (1945–2019). With memories and appreciation</i>	126
Valeria Marraffa , <i>Convergence results for varying measures</i>	175
Alexander Meskhi , <i>Multilinear fractional integrals: boundedness criteria and sharp estimates</i>	200
Enrique A. Sánchez Pérez , <i>Non-linear variants of factorization theorems for operators on Banach function spaces</i>	227
Witold Wnuk , <i>Professor Julian Musielak, an outstanding member of the Poznań School of Mathematics</i>	257
Talks	267
Beata Deręgowska , <i>On maximal projection constants</i>	267
Tomasz Kiwerski , <i>The spaces Ces_∞ and ces_∞ are not isometric, yet still isomorphic</i>	274
Ryszard Paweł Kostecki , <i>Geometric properties of noncommutative Orlicz spaces with p-Amemiya norms in the context of metric and Brègman projections</i>	284
Barbara Lewandowska , <i>On the value of the fifth maximal projection constant</i>	307
Włodzimierz Łeński and Bogdan Szal , <i>Seminormwise approximation by matrix means of Fourier series</i>	317
Piotr Pikul , <i>Joint backward extensions of weighted shifts on directed trees</i>	331
Alejandro Santacruz Hidalgo , <i>Interpolation theory of Down spaces over general measure spaces</i>	339
Juliusz Stochmal , <i>Bochner representable operators on variable exponent Lebesgue spaces</i>	346
Sandra Thampi , <i>Discrete Wiener-Hopf operators on Orlicz sequence spaces</i>	358
List of Participants	379
About the faculty	381
Sponsors	383

The International Conferences on Function Spaces have a 38-year tradition. The previous conferences were held in:

- Poznań (1986, 1989, 1992, 1998, 2003, 2012);
- Zielona Góra (1995, 2015);
- Wrocław (2001);
- Będlewo - Banach Conference Center (2006);
- Kraków (2009,2018);
- Poznań (2021) - the conference has been postponed due to COVID-19.

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On some generalizations of Ascoli-Arzelà theorem

Diana Caponetti

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To apply the theory of measure of noncompactness is useful to calculate or estimate the class theorem, the problem has been widely considered in the literature. Our aim is to give estimates, which in some cases reduce to precise formulas, of the Kuratowski and the Hausdorff measures in very general Banach spaces of vector-valued functions. Precisely, in spaces of vector-valued bounded functions and of vector-valued bounded differentiable functions. To this end, we use a quantitative characteristic modeled on a new equicontinuity-type concept and classical quantitative characteristics related to pointwise relative compactness. We obtain new regular measures of noncompactness in the spaces taken into consideration. The results are extended to obtain quantitative versions of theorems about compactness in groups of group-valued mappings, endowed with a topology which generalizes the topology of convergence in measure. The Ascoli-Arzelà theorem is generalized to a wide class of function spaces.

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- [1] D. Caponetti, A. Trombetta, G. Trombetta, *Compactness in groups of group-valued mappings*, *Mathematics*, 10(21), 3973, 2022.
- [2] D. Caponetti, A. Trombetta, G. Trombetta, *Regular measures of noncompactness and Ascoli-Arzelà type compactness criteria in spaces of vector-valued functions*, *Banach J. Math. Anal.* 17, 3(48), 2023.

On some generalizations of Ascoli-Arzelà theorem

Diana Caponetti

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Our aim is to give estimates of the Kuratowski measure of noncompactness, useful to characterize relatively compactness, in very general Banach spaces of vector-valued functions:

- spaces of vector-valued bounded functions
- spaces of vector-valued bounded differentiable functions.

We use a quantitative characteristic modeled on a new equicontinuity-type concept and classical quantitative characteristics related to pointwise relative compactness. We obtain new regular measures of noncompactness in the spaces taken into consideration. The estimates reduce to precise formulas in some cases. We obtain Ascoli-Arzelà type compactness criteria in a wide class of vector-valued function spaces.

Results are extended to obtain quantitative versions of theorems about compactness in groups of group-valued mappings, endowed with a topology which generalizes the topology of convergence in measure.

Outline

- 1 Known compactness criteria
- 2 Measure of noncompactness (MNC)
 - Ambrosetti's formula.
 - Nussbaum's inequalities, ω_N "measures the lack of equicontinuity".
- 3 Ω topological space, Y Banach space. $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$ Banach space of all bounded functions, endowed with the supremum norm.
 - The classical ω "generalized measure of non-equicontinuity" which, together with the quantitative characteristics μ_α , and σ_α , has allowed to study compactness in the space $\mathcal{TB}(\Omega, Y)$ of totally bounded functions, is not adequate in the general case.
- 4 Introduction of a new equicontinuity-type concept and of the corresponding quantitative characteristic. New inequalities and compactness criteria in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$ and generalization to the space $\mathcal{BC}^k(\Omega, Y)$ of all functions k -times continuously differentiable and bounded with all differentials up to k , defined on an open subset Ω of a Banach space.
- 5 Compactness in pseudonormed groups of group-valued mappings.

3 / 47

Compactness criteria

Ascoli-Arzelà Theorem

A family of real continuous functions defined on a compact metric space is compact if and only if it is closed, bounded and equicontinuous.

Bartle (1955) characterized the relatively compact subsets of the space $\mathcal{BC}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$ of real bounded and continuous functions defined on a topological space Ω .

The following statements are equivalent for a bounded subset M of $\mathcal{BC}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$

- M is relatively compact;
- For any $\varepsilon > 0$ there is a finite partition $\{A_1, \dots, A_n\}$ of Ω such that if $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and x, y belong to the same A_i , then $|f(x) - f(y)| \leq \varepsilon$, for all $f \in M$.

4 / 47

Compactness criteria

- E. De Pascale, G. Lewicki, G. Marino [Analysis (2002)] gave sufficient conditions for relative compactness of subsets of the spaces $\mathcal{BC}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$ and $\mathcal{BC}(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^n)$.
- D. C., G. Lewicki, G. Trombetta [Novi Sad J. Math. (2002)], quantitative version of the result.
- F. Cianciaruso, V. Colao, G. Marino, H.-K. Xu, [Ann. Mat. Pura Appl. (2013)] characterize the relative compactness of subsets of the space of **vector-valued functions** defined, k -times continuously differentiable and bounded with all differentials up to the order k on unbounded intervals: $\mathcal{BC}^k([0, +\infty), Y)$.
- A. Arab, R. Allahyari, A. Shole Haghghi [Bull. Iranian Math. Soc. (2017)] characterize the relative compactness of subsets of the space of **real-valued functions** defined, k -times continuously differentiable on a compact subset Ω of \mathbb{R}^n : $\mathcal{C}^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$.

5 / 47

MNC J. Banaś, K. Goebel, Lect. Notes Pure Appl. Math. vol. 60. Marcel Dekker, New York (1980).

- E Banach space, - \mathfrak{M}_E the family of all nonempty and bounded subsets of E
- \mathfrak{K}_E its subfamily consisting of relatively compact sets.

A set function $\mu : \mathfrak{M}_E \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is said to be a measure of noncompactness (MNC) in E if the following conditions hold for $M, N \in \mathfrak{M}_E$:

- $\ker \mu = \{M \in \mathfrak{M}_E : \mu(M) = 0\}$ is nonempty and $\ker \mu \subseteq \mathfrak{K}_E$;
- $M \subseteq N$ implies $\mu(M) \leq \mu(N)$;
- $\mu(\overline{M}) = \mu(M)$;
- $\mu(\text{co}M) = \mu(M)$;
- $\mu(\lambda M + (1 - \lambda)N) \leq \lambda\mu(M) + (1 - \lambda)\mu(N)$, for $\lambda \in [0, 1]$;
- if $(M_n)_n$ is a sequence of closed sets from \mathfrak{M}_E such that $M_{n+1} \subseteq M_n$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu(M_n) = 0$, then the intersection set $M_\infty = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} M_n$ is nonempty.

6 / 47

MNC

Regular MNC are full, sublinear measures with the maximum property:

- $\ker \mu = \mathfrak{N}_E$
- sublinear

$$\mu(\lambda M) = |\lambda| \mu(M) \text{ for } \lambda \in \mathbb{R}, \text{ and } \mu(M + N) \leq \mu(M) + \mu(N),$$

- maximum property

$$\mu(M \cup N) = \max\{\mu(M), \mu(N)\}.$$

Given a set M in \mathfrak{N}_E

- the Kuratowski MNC $\alpha(M)$ is the infimum of all $\varepsilon > 0$ such that M can be covered by finitely many sets of diameters not greater than ε ;
- the Hausdorff MNC $\gamma_E(M)$ is the infimum of all $\varepsilon > 0$ such that M has a finite ε -net in E .

7 / 47

Result of Ambrosetti

To apply the general theory of MNC it is useful to have precise formulas or estimates of the measure of noncompactness.

Theorem (A. Ambrosetti (1967))

$C(\Omega, Y)$, with Ω compact metric space and Y Banach space.

If $M \subseteq C(\Omega, Y)$ is bounded and equicontinuous then

$$\alpha(M) = \sup_{x \in \Omega} \alpha(M(x)),$$

where $M(x) = \{f(x) : f \in M\} \subseteq Y$.

8 / 47

Result of Nussbaum

Theorem (R. Nussbaum (1971))

$\mathcal{C}(\Omega, T)$, with (Ω, d) compact metric space and (T, s) metric space.

Let M a bounded set in $\mathcal{C}(\Omega, T)$, then

$$\max\left\{\sup_{x \in \Omega} \alpha(M(x)), \frac{1}{2}\omega_N(M)\right\} \leq \alpha(M) \leq \sup_{x \in \Omega} \alpha(M(x)) + 2\omega_N(M).$$

$\omega_N(M) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \omega_N(M, \varepsilon)$, where for $\varepsilon > 0$

$\omega_N(M, \varepsilon) = \sup\{s(f(x), f(y)) : x, y \in \Omega; d(x, y) \leq \varepsilon, f \in M\}$.

 9 / 47

MNC in the Space $\mathcal{BC}([0, +\infty), \mathbb{R})$

Measures of noncompactness have been investigated in the space of real-valued functions defined, continuous and bounded on unbounded intervals. **For example,**

- J. Banaś, N. Merentes, B. Rzepka, Chp 1, in *Advances in Nonlinear Analysis via the Concept of MNC*, 2017.

Let M be a nonempty and bounded subset of the space $\mathcal{BC}([0, +\infty), \mathbb{R})$. Let $\varepsilon > 0$ and $T > 0$ and a function $f \in M$. Next, consider

$$\omega^T(M, \varepsilon) = \sup\{|f(x) - f(y)| : x, y \in [0, T], |x - y| \leq \varepsilon, f \in M\}.$$

Then they put

$$\omega_0^T(M) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \omega^T(M, \varepsilon)$$

and define the quantity $\omega_0(M)$ in the following way:

$$\omega_0(M) = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \omega_0^T(M).$$

The set function ω_0 is not a measure of noncompactness in $\mathcal{BC}([0, +\infty), \mathbb{R})$.

 10 / 47

MNC in the space $\mathcal{BC}([0, +\infty), \mathbb{R})$

Next, they consider the function $a(M)$ defined in the following way:

$$a(M) = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \sup_{f \in M} \{ \sup\{|f(x)| : x \geq T\} \} \right\}$$

and define

$$\mu_a(M) = \omega_0(M) + a(M).$$

Then μ_a is a measure of noncompactness and

$$\gamma(M) \leq 2\mu_a(M)$$

The measure μ_a is sublinear and has the maximum property, but is not regular. Its kernel consists of all bounded subsets M of $\mathcal{BC}([0, +\infty), \mathbb{R})$ such that functions from M are locally equicontinuous on $[0, +\infty)$ and tend to zero at infinity with the same rate. The inequality provide only sufficient condition for relative compactness.

11 / 47

Setting - $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$

- Ω topological space.
- $(Y, \|\cdot\|)$ Banach space.
- $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$ Banach space of all bounded Y -valued functions, defined on Ω , endowed with the sup norm $\|\cdot\|_\infty$.
- $\mathcal{TB}(\Omega, Y)$ Banach space of all Y -valued functions defined and totally bounded on Ω , i.e. such that $f(\Omega)$ is relatively compact.
- $\mathcal{BC}(\Omega, Y)$ Banach space of all Y -valued functions defined, bounded and continuous on Ω .
- \mathcal{H} Banach subspace of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$, endowed with $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ - $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{H}}$ nonempty bounded subsets of \mathcal{H} .

12 / 47

The quantitative characteristics ω , μ_α and σ_α

First of all let us look at the quantitative characteristics, based on the classical results on compactness which have been useful tools for the study of compactness in spaces of totally bounded functions. Given $M \in \mathfrak{M}_B$, the quantity

$$\omega(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there is a finite partition } \{A_1, \dots, A_n\} \text{ of } \Omega \\ \text{such that, for all } f \in M, \text{diam}(f(A_i)) \leq \varepsilon \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n\},$$

generalizes ω_N , the “measure of non-equicontinuity” of Nussbaum. Moreover, let

$$\mu_\alpha(M) = \sup_{x \in \Omega} \alpha(M(x)), \quad \text{where } M(x) = \{f(x) : f \in M\}$$

and

$$\sigma_\alpha(M) = \alpha(M(\Omega)), \quad \text{where } M(\Omega) = \bigcup_{x \in \Omega} M(x).$$

13 / 47

The quantitative characteristics ω , μ_α and σ_α

Heinz in [Nonlinear Anal. (1981)] proved the following inequalities for bounded subsets of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$:

$$\max \left\{ \mu_\alpha(M), \frac{1}{2} \left(\omega(M) - \sup_{f \in M} \sigma_\alpha(\{f\}) \right) \right\} \leq \alpha(M) \leq \mu_\alpha(M) + 2\omega(M). \quad (1)$$

Observe that if $M \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{TB}}$ then $\sup_{f \in M} \sigma_\alpha(\{f\}) = 0$, so that $\ker(\mu_\alpha + 2\omega) = \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{TB}}$ and consequently inequalities (1) furnish a criteria of compactness in the space $\mathcal{TB}(\Omega, Y)$ of totally bounded functions (see also, A. Avallone, G.Trombetta, Boll. Un. Mat. Ital. B (1991)).

14 / 47

The quantitative characteristics ω , μ_α and σ_α - Examples

Example (1)

Let $\Omega = [0, +\infty)$ and $Y = \ell_\infty$. Define for $k = 1, 2, \dots$ $f_k \in \mathcal{B}([0, +\infty), \ell_\infty)$ by setting

$$f_k(x) = \begin{cases} e_n & \text{for } x = k - \frac{1}{n}, \text{ for } n = 1, 2, \dots \\ \theta & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Set $M = \{f_k : k = 1, 2, \dots\}$.

Then $\mu_\alpha(M) = 0$, $\omega(M) = 1 = \sup_{f \in M} \sigma_\alpha(\{f\})$ so that

$$\max \left\{ \mu_\alpha(M), \frac{1}{2} \left(\omega(M) - \sup_{f \in M} \sigma_\alpha(\{f\}) \right) \right\} = 0,$$

while $\alpha(M) = 1$.

The left-hand side of (1) can be equal to zero for a given set $M \in \mathfrak{M}_B$ without being $\alpha(M) = 0$, which means that the left-hand side of (1) vanishes on sets $M \notin \mathfrak{N}_B$.

15 / 47

The quantitative characteristics ω , μ_α and σ_α - Examples

Example (2)

Assume the Banach space Y to be infinite-dimensional and $\Omega = B(Y)$.

Let I be the identity function on $B(Y)$ and $M = \{I\}$ in $\mathcal{B}(B(Y), Y)$. Then

$$\alpha(M) = \mu_\alpha(M) = 0, \quad \sigma_\alpha(M) = \omega(M) = 2.$$

In particular, $M \in \mathfrak{M}_B$ but the right-hand side of (1) does not vanish on M .

The quantitative characteristics ω , μ_α and σ_α cannot be used in general to characterize compactness in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$.

Compactness in Banach subspaces of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$

\mathcal{H} - Banach subspace of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$

New equicontinuity-type concept in our general setting.

Definition

We say that a set $M \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{H}}$ is extendedly equicontinuous if for any $\varepsilon > 0$ there are a finite partition $\{A_1, \dots, A_n\}$ of Ω and a finite set $\{f_1, \dots, f_m\}$ of functions in \mathcal{H} such that, for all $f \in M$, there is $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ with $\text{diam}((f - f_j)(A_i)) \leq \varepsilon$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$.

17 / 47

Compactness in Banach subspaces of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$

The quantitative characteristic $\omega_{\mathcal{H}}$.

Definition

$\omega_{\mathcal{H}} : \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{H}} \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$

$$\omega_{\mathcal{H}}(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there are a finite partition } \{A_1, \dots, A_n\} \text{ of } \Omega$$

and a finite set $\{f_1, \dots, f_m\}$ in \mathcal{H} such that,
for all $f \in M$, there is $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ with
 $\text{diam}((f - f_j)(A_i)) \leq \varepsilon$ for $i = 1, \dots, n\}$.

Recall that $\mu_{\alpha}, \sigma_{\alpha} : \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{H}} \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ are so defined:

$$\mu_{\alpha}(M) = \sup_{x \in \Omega} \alpha(M(x)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{\alpha}(M) = \alpha(M(\Omega)).$$

Observe: $\mu_{\alpha}(M) \leq \sigma_{\alpha}(M)$.

18 / 47

Compactness in Banach subspaces of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$

The main result in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$ provides new estimates of the Kuratowski MNC, which allow to characterize relatively compactness of bounded subset of the space.

Theorem

Let \mathcal{H} be a Banach subspace of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$ and $M \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{H}}$. Then

$$\max\{\mu_{\alpha}(M), \frac{1}{2}\omega_{\mathcal{H}}(M)\} \leq \alpha(M) \leq \mu_{\alpha}(M) + 2\omega_{\mathcal{H}}(M). \quad (2)$$

- The result in $\mathcal{BC}(\Omega, Y)$ hold when Ω is not necessarily compact and the functions are not necessarily totally bounded, so we generalize at the same time the result of Nussbaum and the Bartle criterion.

Compactness in Banach subspaces of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$

Let \mathcal{H} be a Banach subspace of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$.

Ascoli-Arzelà-type compactness criteria

Corollary

A subset M of \mathcal{H} is relatively compact if and only if it is bounded, extendedly equicontinuous and pointwise relatively compact.

Ambrosetti-type formula

Corollary

Assume that $M \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{H}}$ is extendedly equicontinuous. Then

$$\alpha(M) = \mu_{\alpha}(M).$$

Compactness in Banach subspaces of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$

Regular MNC in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$

Corollary

The set function $\mu_\alpha + 2\omega_{\mathcal{H}} : \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{H}} \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is a regular measure of noncompactness in \mathcal{H} equivalent to the Kuratowski measure α .

If \mathcal{H} is a Banach subspace of $\mathcal{TB}(\Omega, Y)$, we have $\omega_{\mathcal{H}} = \omega$ and moreover the quantitative characteristic σ_α can be used to improve the left-hand side of (2).

Theorem

If $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{TB}(\Omega, Y)$ and $M \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{H}}$, then

$$\max\{\sigma_\alpha(M), \frac{1}{2}\omega(M)\} \leq \alpha(M) \leq \mu_\alpha(M) + 2\omega(M).$$

 21 / 47

A remark in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$ when Y is a Lindenstrauss space

A real Banach space Y is said to be an L_1 -predual provided its dual Y^* is isometric to $L^1(\mu)$ for some measure μ . Such spaces are often referred to as Lindenstrauss spaces and play a central role in the Banach space theory. The Banach space $\mathcal{C}(K, \mathbb{R})$ of real-valued functions defined and continuous on the compact Hausdorff space K , under the supremum norm, is the most natural example of a Lindenstrauss space.

We find a better lower estimate for the Kuratowski MNC of bounded and pointwise relatively compact subsets of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega, Y)$.

Theorem

Assume that Y is a Lindenstrauss space and that $M \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{B}}$ is pointwise relatively compact. Then

$$\omega_{\mathcal{B}}(M) \leq \alpha(M) \leq 2\omega_{\mathcal{B}}(M).$$

The inequalities are the best possible.

 22 / 47

$\mathcal{BC}^k(\Omega, Y)$, Ω open subset of a Banach space Z

Ω open subset of a Banach space Z .

$\mathcal{BC}^k(\Omega, Y)$ Banach space of all Y -valued functions defined, k -times continuously differentiable and bounded with all differentials up to the order k on Ω , endowed with the norm

$$\|f\|_{\mathcal{BC}^k} = \max\{\|f\|_\infty, \|df\|_\infty, \dots, \|d^k f\|_\infty\},$$

where the differentiability is considered in the Fréchet sense.

Put $W_p = \mathcal{L}(Z^p, Y)$.

- Each $d^p f$ is an element of the space $\mathcal{C}(\Omega, W_p)$.
- α_p denotes the Kuratowski measure of noncompactness in W_p .
- Given $M \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{BC}^k}$, we set

$$M^p = \{d^p f : f \in M\} \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\Omega, W_p)$$

 23 / 47

Quantitative characteristics in $\mathcal{BC}^k(\Omega, Y)$

Then for $M \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{BC}^k}$ we define

$$\mu_{\bar{\alpha}}(M) = \max_{p=0}^k \mu_{\alpha_p}(M^p).$$

We call M pointwise k -relatively compact if $\mu_{\bar{\alpha}}(M) = 0$.

Definition

$\omega_{\mathcal{BC}^k}(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0: \text{there are a finite partition } \{A_1, \dots, A_n\} \text{ of } \Omega$
and a finite set $\{f_1, \dots, f_m\}$ in $\mathcal{BC}^k(\Omega, Y)$ such that,
for all $f \in M$, there is $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ with
 $\max_{p=0}^k \text{diam}_{W_p}(d^p(f - f_j))(A_i) \leq \varepsilon \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n\}$.

We call M extendedly k -equicontinuous if $\omega_{\mathcal{BC}^k}(M) = 0$.

 24 / 47

Compactness in $\mathcal{BC}^k(\Omega, Y)$

Theorem

Let $M \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{BC}^k}$, then

$$\max\{\mu_{\bar{\alpha}}(M), \frac{1}{2}\omega_{\mathcal{BC}^k}(M)\} \leq \alpha(M) \leq \mu_{\bar{\alpha}}(M) + 2\omega_{\mathcal{BC}^k}(M).$$

Corollary

A subset M of $\mathcal{BC}^k(\Omega, Y)$ is relatively compact if and only if it is bounded, extendedly k -equicontinuous and pointwise k -relatively compact.

Corollary

Let $M \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{BC}^k}$ be extendedly k -equicontinuous. Then

$$\alpha(M) = \mu_{\bar{\alpha}}(M).$$

25 / 47

Compactness in $\mathcal{BC}^k(\Omega, Y)$, Ω open subset of \mathbb{R}

If Ω is an open subset of \mathbb{R} we obtain new criterion of compactness in $\mathcal{BC}^k(\bar{\Omega}, Y)$, which in particular recovers the case $\mathcal{BC}^k([0, +\infty), Y)$.

Corollary

Let Ω be an open subset of \mathbb{R} and let M be a subset of $\mathcal{BC}^k(\bar{\Omega}, Y)$. Then M is relatively compact if and only if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (i) each M^p , for $p \in \{0, \dots, k\}$, is bounded and pointwise relatively compact,
- (ii) M is extendedly k -equicontinuous.

26 / 47

Compactness $\mathcal{BC}^k(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$, Ω open subset of \mathbb{R}^n

Corollary

Let Ω be an open bounded subset of \mathbb{R}^n and let M be a subset of $\mathcal{C}^k(\overline{\Omega}, \mathbb{R})$. Then the following are equivalent:

- (i) M is $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{C}^k(\overline{\Omega}, \mathbb{R})}$ -relatively compact,
- (ii) M is $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{C}^k(\overline{\Omega}, \mathbb{R})}$ -bounded and $\omega_{\mathcal{C}^k}(M) = 0$,
- (iii) M^p is $\|\cdot\|_{\infty}$ -bounded and equicontinuous for all $p = 0, \dots, k$,
- (iv) $M^\alpha = \{D^\alpha f : f \in M\}$ are $\|\cdot\|_{\infty}$ -bounded and equicontinuous for all $0 \leq |\alpha| \leq k$.

$$\|D^\alpha f\|_{\infty} = \sup\{|D^\alpha(x)| : x \in \Omega\}, \quad |\alpha| = \alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_n \quad \text{and} \quad D^\alpha f = \frac{\delta^{\alpha_1}}{\delta x_1^{\alpha_1}} \dots \frac{\delta^{\alpha_n}}{\delta x_n^{\alpha_n}} f.$$

In particular, the above condition (iv) recovers Theorem 2.1 of R. Arab, R. Allahyari, A. Shole Haghighi (2017).

27 / 47

Pseudonormed groups of group-valued mappings

- Setting $(\mathcal{F}(\Omega, G), \|\cdot\|_\eta)$

- $G = (G, \|\cdot\|)$ normed commutative additive group
- $\mathcal{F}(\Omega) = \mathcal{F}(\Omega, G)$ group of all G -valued mappings defined on a nonempty set Ω
- \mathcal{A} algebra in $\mathcal{P}(\Omega)$

Now let $\mu : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow [0, +\infty]$ be a submeasure, and consider $\eta : \mathcal{P}(\Omega) \rightarrow [0, +\infty]$ its extension to $\mathcal{P}(\Omega)$

$$\eta(B) = \inf\{\mu(A) : A \in \mathcal{A} \text{ and } B \subseteq A\}.$$

Then, we consider a natural generalization of the topology of convergence in measure, that is, the topology generated on the group $\mathcal{F}(\Omega)$ by the **group pseudonorm**

$\|\cdot\|_\eta : \mathcal{F}(\Omega) \rightarrow [0, +\infty]$ defined by setting

$$\|f\|_\eta = \inf\{a > 0 : \eta(\{x \in \Omega : \|f(x)\| \geq a\}) \leq a\}.$$

28 / 47

Pseudonormed subgroups of $(\mathcal{F}(\Omega, G), \|\cdot\|_\eta)$

- $\mathcal{F}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega) = (\mathcal{F}(\Omega), \|\cdot\|_\eta)$.
- If $\eta(\emptyset) = 0$ and $\eta(B) = +\infty$ if $\emptyset \neq B \in \mathcal{P}(\Omega)$, the pseudonorm $\|\cdot\|_\eta$ coincides with the standard supremum seminorm $\|\cdot\|_\infty$.
- $\mathcal{H}(\Omega)$ subgroup of $\mathcal{F}(\Omega)$, possibly $\mathcal{F}(\Omega)$ itself.
- $\mathcal{H}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega) = (\mathcal{H}(\Omega), \|\cdot\|_\eta)$.
- $\mathcal{TM}(\Omega) = \mathcal{TM}(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \eta, G)$ subgroup of all *totally \mathcal{A} -measurable* mappings, that is, the closure in $\mathcal{F}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$ of the group of all *\mathcal{A} -simple* mappings.

$$\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\infty}(\Omega) \subseteq \mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega) \text{ for any } \eta, \text{ and}$$

$$(\mathcal{TM}(\Omega, \mathcal{P}(\Omega), \eta_\infty, G), \|\cdot\|_{\eta_\infty}) = \mathcal{TB}_{\|\cdot\|_\infty}(\Omega).$$

MNC [J. M. Ayerbe Toledano; T. Dominguez Benavides, G. Lopez Acedo, Birkhäuser Verlag, Basel, 1997]

L given commutative group - $\nu : \mathcal{P}(L) \rightarrow [0, +\infty]$ MNC

- (i) $\nu(M) = 0$ if and only if M is totally bounded;
- (ii) $\nu(M) = \nu(\overline{M})$;
- (iii) $\nu(M \cup N) = \max\{\nu(M), \nu(N)\}$;

The following properties can be deduced by these axioms:

- (iv) $M \subseteq N$ implies $\nu(M) \leq \nu(N)$;
- (v) $\nu(S) = 0$ for every one-element set S in L .

Moreover we require

- (vi) $\nu(M + N) \leq \nu(M) + \nu(N)$;
- (vii) $\nu(f + M) = \nu(M)$ for any $f \in L$.

- Hausdorff measure of noncompactness

$$\gamma_L(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : M \subseteq F + B_L(\theta, \varepsilon), F \subseteq L, F \text{ finite}\}.$$

γ Hausdorff MNC in the group G .

Compactness in pseudonormed subgroups of $\mathcal{F}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$

Let us recall the **Fréchet Šmulian criterion of compactness**.

A family M of real-valued Lebesgue totally measurable functions on a measurable subset E of \mathbb{R}^n is relatively compact with respect to convergence in measure if and only if given $\varepsilon > 0$ there is a finite measurable partition $\{A_1, \dots, A_n\}$ of E , a number $a > 0$ and for each $f \in M$ a measurable set D_f with $\lambda(D_f) \leq \varepsilon$, such that

$$\sup\{|f(x) - f(y)| : x, y \in A_i \setminus D_f\} \leq \varepsilon \quad i = 1, \dots, n,$$

and

$$\sup\{|f(x)| : x \in E \setminus D_f\} \leq a.$$

In other words, M is relatively compact with respect to convergence in measure if and only if it is equimeasurable and uniformly quasibounded.

31 / 47

Compactness in pseudonormed subgroups of $\mathcal{F}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$

Definition

A subset M of $\mathcal{H}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$ is said to be extendedly equimeasurable if for any $\varepsilon > 0$ there are a finite partition $\{A_1, \dots, A_n\}$ of Ω in \mathcal{A} and a finite set $\{f_1, \dots, f_m\}$ in $\mathcal{H}(\Omega)$ such that, for all $f \in M$, there are $D_f \subseteq \Omega$ with $\eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon$ and $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ with

$$\text{diam}((f - f_j)(A_i \setminus D_f)) \leq \varepsilon, \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, n.$$

Definition

A subset M of $\mathcal{H}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$ is said to be extendedly uniformly quasibounded if for any $\varepsilon > 0$ there are a set G_0 in G with $\gamma(G_0) \leq \varepsilon$, a finite set $\{g_1, \dots, g_k\}$ in $\mathcal{H}(\Omega)$ such that for each $f \in M$ there are $D_f \subseteq \Omega$ with $\eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon$ and $s \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ with

$$(f - g_s)(\Omega \setminus D_f) \subseteq G_0.$$

32 / 47

Compactness in pseudonormed subgroups of $\mathcal{F}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$

The quantitative characteristics $\omega_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}$ and $\sigma_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}$.

$$\omega_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}, \sigma_{\mathcal{H}_\eta} : \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{H}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)) \rightarrow [0, +\infty]$$

$$\omega_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there are a finite partition } \{A_1, \dots, A_n\} \text{ of } \Omega \text{ in } \mathcal{A} \\ \text{and a finite set } \{f_1, \dots, f_m\} \text{ in } \mathcal{H}(\Omega) \text{ such that, for each } f \in M, \\ \text{there are } D_f \subseteq \Omega \text{ with } \eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon \text{ and } j \in \{1, \dots, m\} \text{ with} \\ \text{diam}((f - f_j)(A_i \setminus D_f)) \leq \varepsilon, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n\}$$

$$\sigma_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there are a set } G_0 \text{ in } G \text{ with } \gamma(G_0) \leq \varepsilon, \text{ a finite set} \\ \{g_1, \dots, g_k\} \text{ in } \mathcal{H}(\Omega) \text{ such that, for all } f \in M, \\ \text{there are } D_f \subseteq \Omega \text{ with } \eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon \text{ and } s \in \{1, \dots, k\} \text{ with} \\ (f - g_s)(\Omega \setminus D_f) \subseteq G_0\}.$$

- M extendedly equimeasurable if and only if $\omega_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M) = 0$.
- M extendedly uniformly quasibounded if and only if $\sigma_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M) = 0$.

33 / 47

Compactness in pseudonormed subgroups of $\mathcal{F}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$

Theorem

Let M be a subset of $\mathcal{F}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$, then

$$\gamma_{\mathcal{F}_\eta}(M) \leq 2(\sigma_{\mathcal{F}_\eta}(M) + \omega_{\mathcal{F}_\eta}(M)).$$

Let M be a subset of $\mathcal{H}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$, then

$$\max\left\{\sigma_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M), \frac{1}{2}\omega_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M)\right\} \leq \gamma_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M) \leq 4(\sigma_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M) + \omega_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M)).$$

34 / 47

Compactness in pseudonormed subgroups of $\mathcal{F}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$

Fréchet-Šmulian-type compactness criterion.

Corollary

A subset M of $\mathcal{H}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega)$ is totally bounded if and only if

$$\omega_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M) = \sigma_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}(M) = 0,$$

that is, if and only if M is extendedly equimeasurable and extendedly uniformly quasibounded.

The set function $\sigma_{\mathcal{H}_\eta} + \omega_{\mathcal{H}_\eta}$ is a measure of noncompactness in $\mathcal{H}_\eta(\Omega)$ equivalent to the Hausdorff measure of noncompactness.

35 / 47

Application: Compactness in subgroups \mathcal{H}_{τ_η} of $\mathcal{F}_{\tau_\eta}(\Omega)$, τ_η topology of local convergence in measure

$$\mathcal{F}_{\tau_\eta}(\Omega) = (\mathcal{F}(\Omega), \tau_\eta)$$

- $\mathcal{A}_0 = \{A \in \mathcal{A} : \eta(A) < +\infty\}$
- τ_η generated by the family of group-pseudonorms

$$\{\|\cdot\|_{\eta,A} : A \in \mathcal{A}_0\},$$

where

$$\|f\|_{\eta,A} = \inf\{a > 0 : \eta(\{x \in A : \|f(x)\| \geq a\}) \leq a\} = \|f\chi_A\|_\eta.$$

The topology τ_η generalizes the classical topology of local convergence in measure.

36 / 47

Compactness in subgroups \mathcal{H}_{τ_η} of $\mathcal{F}_{\tau_\eta}(\Omega)$

For a subgroup $\mathcal{H}(\Omega)$ of $\mathcal{F}(\Omega)$ we write $\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}(\Omega)$ for $(\mathcal{H}(\Omega), \tau_\eta)$

The generalized Hausdorff MNC $\gamma_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M)$ of a set M in a topological group $\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}(\Omega)$, following Sadoskij, is that generated by the family of group-pseudonorms.

For a set M , $\gamma_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M)$ is the set function $\gamma_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M) : \mathcal{A}_0 \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ where

$$\gamma_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M)(A) = \gamma_{\|\cdot\|_{\eta,A}}(M),$$

that is, the infimum of all $\varepsilon > 0$ such that M has a finite ε -net in $\mathcal{H}(\Omega)$, with respect to the group-pseudonorm $\|\cdot\|_{\eta,A}$.

37 / 47

Compactness in subgroups \mathcal{H}_{τ_η} of $\mathcal{F}_{\tau_\eta}(\Omega)$

Analogously our quantitative characteristics will be those generated by the family of group-pseudonorms. $\omega_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M), \sigma_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M) : \mathcal{A}_0 \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$

$$\omega_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M)(A) = \omega_{\mathcal{H}_{\|\cdot\|_{\eta,A}}}(M) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M)(A) = \sigma_{\mathcal{H}_{\|\cdot\|_{\eta,A}}}(M),$$

where

$$\omega_{\mathcal{H}_{\|\cdot\|_{\eta,A}}}(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there are a finite partition } \{A_1, \dots, A_n\} \text{ of } A \text{ in } \mathcal{A}_0,$$

a finite set $\{f_1, \dots, f_m\}$ in $\mathcal{H}(\Omega)$ such that, for all $f \in M$,
there are $D_f \subseteq \Omega$ with $\eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon$ and $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ with
 $\text{diam}((f - f_j)(A_i \setminus D_f)) \leq \varepsilon$ for $i = 1, \dots, n\}$

$$\sigma_{\mathcal{H}_{\|\cdot\|_{\eta,A}}}(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there are a set } G_A \text{ in } G \text{ with } \gamma(G_A) \leq \varepsilon, \text{ a finite set}$$

$\{g_1, \dots, g_k\}$ in $\mathcal{H}(\Omega)$ such that, for all $f \in M$,
there are $D_f \subseteq \Omega$ with $\eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon$ and $s \in \{1, \dots, k\}$
with $(f - g_s)(A \setminus D_f) \subseteq G_A\}$.

38 / 47

Compactness in subgroups \mathcal{H}_{τ_η} of $\mathcal{F}_{\tau_\eta}(\Omega)$

Theorem

Let M be a subset of a given subgroup $\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}(\Omega)$ of $\mathcal{F}_{\tau_\eta}(\Omega)$, then

$$\max \left\{ \sigma_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M), \frac{1}{2} \omega_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M) \right\} \leq \gamma_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M) \leq 4(\sigma_{\tau_\eta}(M) + \omega_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M)).$$

Consequently, the set M is τ_η -totally bounded if and only if $\omega_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M) = \sigma_{\mathcal{H}_{\tau_\eta}}(M) = 0$.

$(\mathcal{M}(\Omega, G), \tau_\eta)$ (see [DS, Chapter III]) - \mathcal{A} -measurable mappings
the space of all $f \in \mathcal{F}(\Omega)$ such that $f\chi_A$ is totally \mathcal{A} -measurable for any $A \in \mathcal{A}_0$,
endowed with the topology τ_η .

A subset M of $(\mathcal{M}(\Omega, G), \tau_\eta)$ is τ_η -totally bounded if and only if it is extendedly τ_η -equimeasurable and extendedly τ_η -uniformly quasibounded.

39 / 47

$\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega, G)$ totally \mathcal{A} -measurable mappings

$\omega_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\eta}(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there are a finite partition } \{A_1, \dots, A_n\} \text{ of } \Omega \text{ in } \mathcal{A}$
such that for all $f \in M$ there exists $D_f \subseteq M$, with $\eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon$ and
 $\text{diam}(f(A_i \setminus D_f)) \leq \varepsilon$ for $i = 1, \dots, n\}$,

$\sigma_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\eta}(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there are a set } G_0 \text{ in } G \text{ with } \gamma_G(G_0) \leq \varepsilon$
such that for all $f \in M$ there exists $D_f \subseteq M$, with $\eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon$ and
 $f(\Omega \setminus D_f) \subseteq G_0\}$.

Recall that $\omega_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\infty}(M)$ and $\sigma_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\infty}(M)$ do not depend on exceptional sets D_f .

Theorem (Avallone- Trombetta (1991), Theorem 2.1 and p. 579)

$$\max \left\{ \sigma_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\eta}(M), \frac{1}{2} \omega_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\eta}(M) \right\} \leq \gamma_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\eta}(M) \leq \sigma_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\eta}(M) + \omega_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\eta}(M),$$

and if $Y = \mathbb{R}$

$$\gamma_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\infty}(M) \leq \sigma_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\infty}(M) + \frac{1}{2} \omega_{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{M}_\infty}(M).$$

40 / 47

Another approach: Monotonicity and total boundedness in $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$

- $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

$$\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$$

$$\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R}) \subseteq \mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$$

In the literature (Appell, Banas Merente J. Math. Anal. Appl. (2010)), some quantities related to monotonicity of functions have been considered for real-valued functions defined and bounded or continuous on a compact interval of the reals. We consider similar quantities in $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$.

Monotonicity and total boundedness in $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$

Let f be a function in $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\eta}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$, $\{A_1, \dots, A_n\}$ a finite partition of Ω in \mathcal{A} and $D \subseteq \Omega$ be given, then we introduce the modulus of \mathcal{A} -decrease of f

$$d(f, \{A_1, \dots, A_n\}, D) = \max_{i=1}^n \sup \left\{ \left| f(s) - f(t) \right| - \left[f(s) - f(t) \right] : t, s \in A_i \setminus D, t < s \right\},$$

and the modulus of \mathcal{A} -increase of f

$$i(f, \{A_1, \dots, A_n\}, D) = \max_{i=1}^n \sup \left\{ \left| f(s) - f(t) \right| - \left[f(t) - f(s) \right] : t, s \in A_i \setminus D, t < s \right\}.$$

Monotonicity and total boundedness in $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_n}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$

$\omega(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there are a finite partition } \{A_1, \dots, A_n\} \text{ of } \Omega \text{ in } \mathcal{A}$
 such that for all $f \in M$ there exists $D_f \subseteq M$, with $\eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon$ and
 $|f(x) - f(y)| \leq \varepsilon \quad \forall x, y \in A_i \setminus D_f \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n\}$,

$d(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there are a finite partition } \{A_1, \dots, A_n\} \text{ of } \Omega \text{ in } \mathcal{A}$
 such that for all $f \in M$ there exists $D_f \subseteq M$, with $\eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon$ and
 $|f(s) - f(t)| - [f(s) - f(t)] \leq \varepsilon \quad \forall t, s \in A_i \setminus D_f, t < s \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n\}$,

$i(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there are a finite partition } \{A_1, \dots, A_n\} \text{ of } \Omega \text{ in } \mathcal{A}$
 such that for all $f \in M$ there exists $D_f \subseteq M$, with $\eta(D_f) \leq \varepsilon$ and
 $|f(s) - f(t)| - [f(t) - f(s)] \leq \varepsilon \quad \forall t, s \in A_i \setminus D_f, t < s \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n\}$.

43 / 47

Monotonicity and total boundedness in $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_n}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$

Theorem

Let $M \subseteq \mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_n}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$ Then

$$\frac{1}{2} \max\{d(M), i(M)\} \leq \omega(M) \leq (d + i)(M).$$

$\sigma(M) = \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \text{there is } a \geq 0 \text{ such that } \eta(\{x \in \Omega : |f(x)| \geq a\}) \leq \varepsilon, \forall f \in M\}$.

Corollary

Let $M \subseteq \mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_n}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$. Then

$$\max\{\sigma(M), \frac{1}{4}d(M), \frac{1}{4}i(M)\} \leq \gamma(M) \leq (d + i)(M) + \sigma(M)$$

44 / 47

Monotonicity and total boundedness in $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$

Theorem

Let M be a subset of $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$. Then

$$\omega(M) = \frac{1}{2} \max\{d(M), i(M)\}.$$

Corollary

Let M be a subset of $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$. Then

$$\max\{\sigma(M), \frac{1}{4}d(M), \frac{1}{4}i(M)\} \leq \gamma(M) \leq \sigma(M) + \frac{1}{4} \max\{d(M), i(M)\}.$$

In particular, if $\sigma(M) = 0$ we have

$$\gamma(M) = \frac{1}{4} \max\{d(M), i(M)\}.$$

45 / 47

Monotonicity and total boundedness in $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$

We obtain a Bartle type criterion of compactness in the space $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$, which can be formulated as follows: A bounded subset M of $\mathcal{TM}_{\|\cdot\|_\infty}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$ is totally bounded if and only if $d(M) = i(M) = 0$.

As a consequence, if Ω is a compact space, we obtain an Ascoli-Arzelà type theorem: A bounded subset M of $\mathcal{C}(\Omega, \mathbb{R})$ is compact if and only if $d(M) = i(M) = 0$.

46 / 47

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(Isometries on) spaces of Lipschitz functions and their preduals

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Given a metric space (M, d) with a distinguished point $0_M \in M$ we consider the Banach space

$$\text{Lip}_0(M) := \{f : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : f \text{ is Lipschitz and } f(0_M) = 0\}$$

endowed with the norm

$$\|f\| := \sup\left\{\frac{|f(x)-f(y)|}{d(x,y)} : x \neq y \in M\right\}.$$

There is also a natural (and nowadays quite widely studied) predual of $\text{Lip}_0(M)$ known under the names Lipschitz-free space, Arens-Eells space, or transportation cost space.

The talk will be divided into two parts. In the first part I will try to survey some of the known Banach space properties of the space $\text{Lip}_0(M)$ and its predual, and also mention some open problems.

In the second part of the talk, I will mention results from our recent paper [1], where we study the structure of linear surjective isometries of the space $\text{Lip}_0(M)$ and its predual. For example, we prove that for quite a surprisingly rich class of metric spaces (including all 3-connected graphs or non-abelian Carnot groups with horizontally strictly convex norms) every surjective linear isometry of the predual of $\text{Lip}_0(M)$ is generated by a surjective dilation (i.e. rescaled isometry) of the metric space itself.

References

[1] M. Cúth, M. Doucha, T. Titkos, Isometries of Lipschitz-free Banach spaces, preprint available at arxiv.org

(Isometries on) Spaces of Lipschitz functions and their preduals

Marek Cúth

Function spaces 13, Poznan 2024

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(Isometries on) Spaces of Lipschitz functions and their preduals

First part

PART 1: GENTLE INTRODUCTION TO SPACES OF LIPSCHITZ FUNCTIONS AND THEIR PREDUALS

1.1 Spaces of Lipschitz functions

Marek Cúth

(Isometries on) Spaces of Lipschitz functions and their preduals

Setting: $(M, \rho, 0)$ is a metric space with a distinguished point 0.

- $\text{Lip}_0(M) := \{f : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : f \text{ is Lipschitz and } f(0) = 0\}$,

- $\text{Lip}_0(M)$ with a norm $\|f\|_{\text{Lip}} := \sup \left\{ \frac{|f(x) - f(y)|}{\rho(x,y)} : x \neq y \in M \right\}$ is a Banach space.

(IN THIS TALK - ALL BANACH SPACES OVER REALS)

Examples:

- $\text{Lip}_0(I) \cong L_\infty(I)$
(the isometric mapping is $\text{Lip}_0(I) \ni f \mapsto f' \in L_\infty(I)$)
- $\text{Lip}_0(\mathbb{Z}) \cong \ell_\infty$
(the isometric mapping is $\text{Lip}_0(\mathbb{Z}) \ni f \mapsto (f(n+1) - f(n))_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \in \ell_\infty$)

Closely related - smooth functions: Consider $C^1([0, 1]^n)$ endowed with the norm

$$\|f\| := \max\{|f(x)|, |\partial_i f(x)| : x \in [0, 1]^n, i = 1, \dots, n\}.$$

$C^1([0, 1]) \not\cong C^1([0, 1]^n)$, $n \geq 2$ (Kisiljakov 1975).

OPEN: $C^1([0, 1]^2) \simeq C^1([0, 1]^3)$?

OPEN: Is $\text{Lip}_0(\mathbb{R}^2) \simeq \text{Lip}_0(\mathbb{R}^3)$?

- $\text{Lip}_0(\mathbb{R}) \not\cong \text{Lip}_0(\mathbb{R}^n)$, $n \geq 2$ (Naor+Schechtman 2007)

- $\text{Lip}_0(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is linearly isomorphic to

- $\text{Lip}_0(M)$ whenever $M \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ has nonempty interior (Kaufmann 2015),
- $\text{Lip}_0(\mathbb{Z}^d)$ (Candido+C+Doucha 2019),

- $\text{Lip}_0(\mathbb{R}^d, \|\cdot\|^a) \simeq \ell_\infty$ whenever $a \in (0, 1)$ and $d \in \mathbb{N}$ (Albiac+Ansorena+C+Doucha 2021)

Sample of further known results:

- $\ell_\infty \hookrightarrow \text{Lip}_0(M)$ isometrically (C+Joharis 2017),
- $\text{Lip}_0(C(K)) \simeq \text{Lip}_0(C_0)$ whenever K is metric compact (Dutrieux+Ferenczi 2006)
- $\text{Lip}_0(\ell_p) \simeq \text{Lip}_0(L_p)$ (Candido+C+Doucha 2019)
- If Φ is Orlicz function satisfying the Δ_2 -condition, then

$$\text{Lip}_0(L_\Phi) \simeq \bigoplus_{\infty} \text{Lip}_0(\ell_{\Phi/n})$$

OPEN:

- For which Orlicz functions do we have $\text{Lip}_0(L_\Phi) \simeq \text{Lip}_0(\ell_\Phi)$?
- Is it even true that $\text{Lip}_0(X) \simeq \text{Lip}_0(\mathbb{R}^2)$ for every separable Banach space X with $\dim X \geq 2$?

1.2 Canonical predual of $\text{Lip}_0(M)$

The canonical predual

Consider the evaluation operator $\delta : M \rightarrow \text{Lip}_0(M)^*$ given by

$$\delta(m)(f) := f(m), \quad m \in M, f \in \text{Lip}_0(M).$$

Then $\delta : M \rightarrow \text{Lip}_0(M)^*$ is (nonlinear) isometric embedding.

Definition

Given $(M, \rho, 0)$, we define the *Lipschitz-free space over M* by

$$\mathcal{F}(M) := \overline{\text{span}}\{\delta(m) : m \in M\} \subset \text{Lip}_0(M)^*.$$

Universal property

Proposition (Universal property)

Let $(M, \rho, 0)$ be as above. There exists only one (up to isometry) Banach space $\mathcal{F}(M)$ such that

there is an isometry $\delta : M \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(M)$ such that

- (i) $\delta(M)$ is linearly independent with $\overline{\text{span}}\delta(M) = \mathcal{F}(M)$, and
- (ii) for every Banach space Z and for every $f \in \text{Lip}_0(M, Z)$ there exists $\hat{f} \in \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{F}(M), Z) : \hat{f} \circ \delta = f$ and $\|\hat{f}\| = \|f\|_{\text{Lip}}$.

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 M & \xrightarrow{f} & Z \\
 \downarrow \delta & \nearrow \hat{f} & \\
 \mathcal{F}(M) & &
 \end{array}
 \quad \text{in particular, we have} \quad
 \begin{array}{ccc}
 M & \xrightarrow{f} & \mathbb{R} \\
 \downarrow \delta & \nearrow \hat{f} & \\
 \mathcal{F}(M) & &
 \end{array}$$

So $\mathcal{F}(M)^* \cong \text{Lip}_0(M)$.

Lipschitz-free spaces in nonlinear geometry of Banach spaces

Lipschitz structure of metric spaces corresponds to the linear structure of the corresponding Lipschitz-free spaces.

Marek Cúth

(Isometries on) Spaces of Lipschitz functions and their preduals

Lipschitz-free spaces in nonlinear geometry of Banach spaces

Lipschitz structure of metric spaces corresponds to the linear structure of the corresponding Lipschitz-free spaces. Indeed, if $f : M \rightarrow N$ is a Lipschitz map then it “extends” to a linear map $\widehat{f} : \mathcal{F}(M) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(N)$:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} M & \xrightarrow{f} & N \\ \downarrow \delta & & \downarrow \delta \\ \mathcal{F}(M) & & \mathcal{F}(N) \end{array}$$

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$$\begin{array}{ccc} M & \xrightarrow{f} & N \\ \downarrow \delta & & \downarrow \delta \\ \mathcal{F}(M) & \xrightarrow{\widehat{f}} & \mathcal{F}(N) \end{array}$$

In particular, if M and N are Lipschitz isomorphic (that is, there is a Lipschitz bijection with Lipschitz inverse) then $\mathcal{F}(M) \simeq \mathcal{F}(N)$ as Banach spaces.

In particular, if M and N are Lipschitz isomorphic (that is, there is a Lipschitz bijection with Lipschitz inverse) then $\mathcal{F}(M) \simeq \mathcal{F}(N)$ as Banach spaces.

Application: Let X be a Banach space

- (Godefroy+Kalton, 2003): X has (BAP) iff $\mathcal{F}(X)$ has (BAP).
- Corollary: if X has (BAP) and is Lipschitz-isomorphic to Y then

$$X \text{ has (BAP)} \Rightarrow \mathcal{F}(X) \text{ has (BAP)}.$$

Since $\mathcal{F}(X) \simeq \mathcal{F}(Y)$, we obtain that $\mathcal{F}(Y)$ has (BAP) and so Y has (BAP).

Conclusion: the notion of (BAP) is preserved by Lipschitz isomorphisms.

Relation to projection constant: Given metric spaces $N \subset M$ we let

$t(N, M) := \inf\{C > 0: \text{given Banach space } Z \text{ and 1-Lipschitz map } f : N \rightarrow Z$
there is extension of f to a C -Lipschitz map $F : M \rightarrow Z\}$

We let $ae(n) := \sup\{t(N, M) : N \subset M \text{ and } |N| \leq n\}$.

Lee+Naor+Rabani:

$$c\sqrt{\log(n)} \leq ae(n) \leq C \frac{\log n}{\log(\log n)}$$

Basso: $ae(3) = \frac{4}{3}$.

Connection to projection constants: We have $t(N, M) = \lambda(\mathcal{F}(N), \mathcal{F}(M))$.

1.3 Relation to transportation cost

Relation to transportation cost

(M, d) a metric space. A function $f : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a *transportation problem* ($f \in TP(M)$ for short) if it has finite support and

$$\sum_{m \in M} f(m) = 0.$$

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(Isometries on) Spaces of Lipschitz functions and their preduals

Relation to transportation cost

(M, d) a metric space. A function $f : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a *transportation problem* ($f \in TP(M)$ for short) if it has finite support and

$$\sum_{m \in M} f(m) = 0.$$

Picture: $M = \{x_1, \dots, x_7\}$, $f(x_1) = 3$, $f(x_2) = -4$, $f(x_3) = 5$, $f(x_4) = -2$, $f(x_5) = -3$, $f(x_6) = 8$, $f(x_7) = -7$

Solution to the problem f is a plan $a_1(\mathbb{1}_{y_1} - \mathbb{1}_{z_1}) + \dots + a_n(\mathbb{1}_{y_n} - \mathbb{1}_{z_n}) = f$, the cost of this solution is $a_1 d(y_1, z_1) + \dots + a_n d(y_n, z_n)$.

$$\|f\|_{TC(M)} := \inf\{a : a \text{ is cost of a solution to the problem } f\}.$$

We have

$$\mathcal{F}(M) \equiv \overline{(TP(M), \|\cdot\|_{TC(M)})}.$$

(the linear isometry is given by $\delta(x) \mapsto \mathbb{1}_x - \mathbb{1}_{0_M} \in TP(M)$)

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(Isometries on) Spaces of Lipschitz functions and their preduals

Relation to Wasserstein spaces

Reformulation: Given $x, y \in M$, $x \neq y$, let the *normalized elementary molecule* be

$$m_{x,y} := \frac{\mathbb{1}_x - \mathbb{1}_y}{d(x,y)} \in TP(M).$$

Then $\mathcal{F}(M)$ is the completion of $TP(M) = \text{span}\{m_{x,y} : x \neq y \in M\}$ endowed with the norm

$$\|m\|_{\mathcal{TC}(M)} := \inf \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n |a_j| : m = \sum_{j=1}^n a_j m_{x_j, y_j} \right\}, \quad m \in TP(M).$$

We also have

$$\|m\|_{\mathcal{TC}(M)} = \sup \{f(m) : f \in \text{Lip}(M), \|f\| \leq 1\},$$

where $f(m) := \sum_{x \in M} f(x)m(x)$.

Wasserstein space: Metric space $W_1(M)$ consisting of Borel probability measures on M endowed with the metric

$$W_1(\mu, \nu) := \sup \left\{ \int f d(\mu - \nu) : f \in \text{Lip}(M), \|f\| \leq 1 \right\}.$$

The mapping $W_1(M) \ni \mu \mapsto \mu - \delta_0 \in \text{Lip}_0(M)^*$ is isometry into $\mathcal{F}(M)$.

Second part

PART 2: ISOMETRIES ON LIPSCHITZ-FREE SPACES

Goal

Given a Banach space X , describe all isometries (the group of isometries) of X .

Recall:

Mazur-Ulam theorem

Let X be a real Banach space and $f : X \rightarrow X$ a surjective isometry. Then f is affine, i.e. a composition of a linear isometry with a translation.

Conclusion

We may safely focus just on linear isometries.

All linear isometries in this talk will be surjective!

Banach-Stone theorem

Let K be a compact Hausdorff space. Then every linear isometry T of $C(K)$ is of the form

$$T(f)(x) = h(x)f(\phi(x)), \quad f \in C(K), x \in K,$$

where $h : K \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ is continuous and $\phi : K \rightarrow K$ is a homeomorphism.

One direction is clear. That is, the content of the theorem is that there are no “surprising” linear isometries.

Let (X, Σ, μ) be a measure space and let $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a measurable bijection. Denote by $T^*\mu$ the pushforward of the measure μ by T . T is called *measure class preserving* if $\mu \sim T^*\mu$, i.e. μ and $T^*\mu$ share the same null-sets.

If μ is σ -finite and T is measure class preserving, then we can apply the Radon-Nikodym theorem to obtain a non-negative valued function $\frac{dT^*\mu}{d\mu}$ such that for every $A \in \Sigma$ we have

$$T^*\mu(A) = \mu(T^{-1}(A)) = \int_A \frac{dT^*\mu}{d\mu} d\mu.$$

Banach-Lamperti theorem

Let (X, Σ, μ) be a σ -finite measure space and let $p \in [1, \infty) \setminus \{2\}$. Then every linear isometry T of $L_p(\mu)$ is of the form

$$T(f)(x) = h(x)f(\phi(x))\left(\frac{d\phi^*\mu}{d\mu}(x)\right)^{1/p}, \quad f \in L_p(\mu), x \in X,$$

where h is measurable and a.e. 1 or -1 , and $\phi : X \rightarrow X$ is measure class preserving.

There has been an extensive research on isometries of other Banach spaces. We refer to monographs *R.J. Fleming and J.E. Jamison, Isometries on Banach spaces*, volume I and II.

Lipschitz-free Banach spaces

Our project (C+Doucha+Titkos 2024)

To describe isometries of (a large class of) Lipschitz-free Banach spaces.

(Note: This might describe also isometries of $\text{Lip}_0(M)$ spaces.

OPEN: given isometry $T : \text{Lip}_0(M) \rightarrow \text{Lip}_0(N)$, does there exist an isometry $S : \mathcal{F}(N) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(M)$ with $S^* = T$? The answer is yes if M is bounded or if it is Banach space.)

Recall that a map $f : M \rightarrow N$ between metric spaces is called a *dilation* if there is a positive constant $K_f > 0$ such that for all $x, y \in M$ we have

$$d_N(f(x), f(y)) = K_f d_M(x, y).$$

Definition

Call a metric space M *Lipschitz-free rigid* (or just rigid if there is no risk of misunderstanding) if every linear isometry of $\mathcal{F}(M)$ is of the form $\pm T_f$, where $f : M \rightarrow M$ is a surjective dilation and T_f is defined by

$$T_f(\mathbb{1}_x - \mathbb{1}_y) = \frac{1}{K_f} (\mathbb{1}_{f(x)} - \mathbb{1}_{f(y)}).$$

Marek Cúth

(Isometries on) Spaces of Lipschitz functions and their preduals

Lipschitz-free Banach spaces

Recall: $m_{x,y} := \frac{\mathbb{1}_x - \mathbb{1}_y}{d(x,y)} \in \mathcal{F}(M)$ is the *normalized elementary molecule*.

Definition

Call a metric space M *Lipschitz-free rigid* (or just rigid if there is no risk of misunderstanding) if every linear isometry of $\mathcal{F}(M)$ is of the form $\pm T_f$, where $f : M \rightarrow M$ is a surjective dilation and T_f is defined by

$$T_f(m_{x,y}) = m_{f(x),f(y)}.$$

Main task

Which metric spaces are Lipschitz-free rigid?

Parallel research: Study the structure of isometries of $W_1(M)$ spaces

- rigid spaces: W_1 (Hilbert spaces), W_1 (countable graph)
- non-rigid space: $W_1([0, 1])$

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(Isometries on) Spaces of Lipschitz functions and their preduals

Extreme points in Lipschitz-free spaces

Extreme points: Given a Banach space X and $x \in B_X$, we say x is *extreme point* in B_X (write $x \in \text{ext } B_X$) supposing that whenever $y, z \in B_X$ are such that $x = \frac{y+z}{2}$, then $y = z = x$.

Extreme points of Lipschitz-free spaces: Given $x, y \in M$, $x \neq y$ we let

$$[x, y] = \{z \in M : d(x, y) = d(x, z) + d(z, y)\}.$$

We have $m_{x,y} \in \text{ext } B_{\mathcal{F}(M)}$ if and only if $[x, y] = \{x, y\}$

(Aliaga+Pernecká+Petitjean+Procházka 2020).

OPEN: Let $\mu \in \text{ext } B_{\mathcal{F}(M)}$. Is then $\mu = m_{x,y}$ for some $x, y \in M$?

(YES: if M is compact or uniformly discrete (Aliaga 2022; Aliaga+Pernecká+Smith 2024))

Preserved extreme points of Lipschitz-free spaces: $\mu \in B_{\mathcal{F}(M)}$ is extreme point in $B_{\mathcal{F}(M)**}$ if and only if $\mu = m_{x,y}$ for some $x, y \in M$ satisfying not only $[x, y] = \{x, y\}$ but also the following stronger condition:

$$\forall \varepsilon > 0 \exists \delta > 0 \forall z \in X :$$

$$\min\{d(x, z), d(y, z)\} \geq \varepsilon \Rightarrow d(x, y) < d(x, z) + d(z, y) - \delta.$$

(Weaver 1995, Aliaga+Guirao 2019)

If every $x, y \in M$, $x \neq y$ satisfies the condition above, we say M is *uniformly concave*.

Theorem (Mayer-Wolf (1981)/ Weaver (1999))

Any uniformly concave metric space is Lipschitz-free rigid.

Denote

$$E_{\text{ext}}(M) := \{(x, y) : m_{x,y} \text{ is an extreme point in } B_{\mathcal{F}(M)**}\}.$$

Given any isometry $T : \mathcal{F}(M) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(M)$ there exists $\sigma : E_{\text{ext}}(M) \rightarrow E_{\text{ext}}(M)$ with $T(m_{x,y}) = m_{\sigma(x,y)}$.

Prague spaces

Recall: $E_{\text{ext}}(M) = \{(x, y) : m_{x,y} \text{ is an extreme point in } B_{\mathcal{F}(M)^{**}}\}$.
 Put $V_{\text{ext}}(M) := \{x \in M : (x, y) \in E_{\text{ext}}(M) \text{ for some } y \in M\}$,
 Finally, $G_{\text{ext}}(M) := (V_{\text{ext}}(M), E_{\text{ext}}(M))$ the corresponding directed graph.

Prague spaces

We say a metric space M is *Prague space* if $V_{\text{ext}}(M)$ is dense subset of M , $G_{\text{ext}}(M)$ is connected graph and for every $x, y \in V_{\text{ext}}(M)$ we have

$$d(x, y) = \inf \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n d(x_i, y_i) : (x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n) \text{ is } E_{\text{ext}}(M)\text{-path from } x \text{ to } y \right\}.$$

Examples:

- Uniformly concave metric spaces.
- $M \oplus_2 N$, where $|M| \geq 3$ and N is uniformly concave without isolated points.
- Connected graphs $G = (V, E)$ with the shortest-path distance.
- Heisenberg group \mathbb{H}^n endowed with a metric induced by the Heisenberg-Korányi norm.

Inspired by similar results proved for finite metric spaces by Alexander+Fradelizi+García Lirola+Zvavitch 2020:

Main Theorem 1

Let M be a Prague space. Then there is a one-to-one correspondence between surjective linear isometries on $\mathcal{F}(M)$ and bijections $\sigma : E_{\text{ext}}(M) \rightarrow E_{\text{ext}}(M)$ satisfying

- $E' \subset E_{\text{ext}}(M)$ is a symple cycle iff $\sigma(E') \subset E_{\text{ext}}(M)$ is a symple cycle, and
- $\frac{d(x,y)}{d(\sigma(x,y))}$ is constant on each symple cycle $E' \subset E_{\text{ext}}(M)$.

Symple cycle: A cycle which is not a concatenation of two proper subcycles.

3-connected graph: A graph G is n -connected, for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, if after removing $n - 1$ vertices from G the graph is still connected.

Theorem: Let $G = (V, E)$ be a 3-connected graph and let $\sigma : E \rightarrow E$ be a simple cycle-preserving bijection. Then there is a bijection $f_\sigma : V \rightarrow V$ satisfying $\sigma(\{v, w\}) = \{f_\sigma(v), f_\sigma(w)\}$ for every $\{v, w\} \in E$.

Main Theorem 2

Let M be a Prague space such that $G_{\text{ext}}(M)$ is 3-connected. Then M is Lipschitz-free rigid.

Examples of Lipschitz-free rigid metric spaces which are Prague:

- Uniformly concave metric spaces.
- 3-connected graphs $G = (V, E)$ with the shortest-path distance.
- $(\mathbb{Z}^d, \|\cdot\|_1)$ for every $d \in \mathbb{N}$
In particular, $\text{Lip}_0((\mathbb{Z}^2, \|\cdot\|_1)) \not\cong \text{Lip}_0((\mathbb{Z}^3, \|\cdot\|_1))$
- Heisenberg group \mathbb{H}^n endowed with a metric induced by the Heisenberg-Korányi norm.

Examples of further Lipschitz-free rigid metric spaces:

- $M \oplus_2 N$, where $|M| \geq 3$ and N is uniformly concave.
- $I \cup \{(1, 0)\} \subset (\mathbb{R}^2, \|\cdot\|_2)$, where $I = \{0\} \times [0, 1]$.

Main Theorem 3

Any metric space may be isometrically embedded into a Lipschitz-free rigid space with only three more points.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION ;)

Projection constants for spaces of multivariate polynomials

Andreas Defant

IS

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We discuss several aspects of an ongoing project with D. Galicer, M. Mansilla, M. Mastyło, and S. Muro.

The general problem we address is to develop new methods within the study of projection constants of Banach spaces of multivariate polynomials. The relative projection constant $\lambda(X, Y)$ of a subspace X of a Banach space Y is the smallest norm among all possible projections from Y onto X , and the (absolute) projection constant $\lambda(X)$ is the supremum of all relative projection constants of X taken with respect to all possible super spaces Y . This is one of the most significant notions of modern Banach space theory. We sketch a few abstract ideas which allow to handle in a unified way a wide variety of Banach spaces of polynomials, and emphasize on polynomials on Boolean cubes, Dirichlet polynomials on the complex plane, and polynomials on euclidean spheres.

Projection constants for spaces of multivariate polynomials

Andreas Defant

Function Spaces XIII

Adam Mickiewicz University Poznań, July 8-12, 2024

Joint work with D. Galicer, M. Mansilla, M. Mastyło, and S. Muro

Team

Projection constants: The definition

Relative projection constant

Let X be a subspace of a Banach space Y . Then

$$\lambda(X, Y) := \inf \{ \|P\| : P \in \mathcal{L}(Y) \text{ projection onto } X \}$$

Applications in numerous fields of analysis, e.g. approximation theory ...

Let $P \in \mathcal{L}(Y)$ be a projection onto X . Then for any $y \in Y$

$$\text{dist}(y, X) \leq \|y - Py\| \leq (1 + \lambda(X, Y)) \text{dist}(y, X).$$

Absolute projection constant

$$\lambda(X) := \sup \lambda(X, Y),$$

the supremum is taken over all Y containing X as an isometric copy.

Crucial for our purpose

For every **fin.-dim.** subspace S of $C(K)$

$$\lambda(S) = \lambda(S, C(K)),$$

and then there is a so-called **minimal projection** $P \in \mathcal{L}(C(K))$ onto S , that is,

$$\lambda(S) = \|P : C(K) \rightarrow S\|$$

3

A first orientation: The theorem of Kadets-Snobar

Hahn-Banach theorem

$$\lambda(\mathbb{C}) = \lambda(\mathbb{R}) = 1$$

Kadets-Snobar Theorem 1971

For every fin.-dim. Banach space X

$$\lambda(X) \leq \sqrt{\dim X}$$

4

Projection constants of ℓ_p^n 's

Again, the Hahn-Banach theorem ...

$$\lambda(\ell_\infty^n(\mathbb{C})) = \lambda(\ell_\infty^n(\mathbb{R})) = 1$$

Grünbaum 1960

$$\lambda(\ell_1^n(\mathbb{C})) = \int_{\mathbb{T}^n} \left| \sum_{k=1}^n z_k \right| dz = \int_0^\infty \frac{1 - J_0(t)^n}{t^2} dt,$$

where J_0 is the zero Bessel function, and

$$\lambda(\ell_1^n(\mathbb{R})) = \int_{\{-1,1\}^n} \left| \sum_{k=1}^n \omega_k \right| d\omega = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{n+2}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{n+1}{2})} & n \text{ odd} \\ \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{n+1}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{n}{2})} & n \text{ even} \end{cases}$$

5

Rutovitz 1965

$$\lambda(\ell_2^n(\mathbb{C})) = n \int_{\mathbb{S}_{\mathbb{C}}^{n-1}} |x_1| dx = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \frac{\Gamma(n+1)}{\Gamma(n+\frac{1}{2})}$$

$$\lambda(\ell_2^n(\mathbb{R})) = n \int_{\mathbb{S}_{\mathbb{R}}^{n-1}} |x_1| dx = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{n+2}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{n+1}{2})}$$

6

Gordon 1968 and König-Schütt-Tomczak 1999

For $1 \leq p \leq \infty$

$$\lambda(\ell_p^n) \sim \begin{cases} n^{\frac{1}{2}} & 1 \leq p \leq 2 \\ n^{\frac{1}{p}} & 2 \leq p \leq \infty, \end{cases}$$

and for $1 \leq p \leq 2$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(\ell_p^n)}{\sqrt{n}} = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} & \text{real case} \\ \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} & \text{complex case} \end{cases}$$

7

Aims of our project

We study the projection constants of

- spaces of trigonometric polynomials on compact abelian groups,
- or, more generally, spaces of **'polynomials on compact spaces with a generic group structure'**

and

- spaces of polynomials on fin.-dim. Banach spaces

Our program includes applications to spaces of

Dirichlet polynomials, functions on Boolean cubes, polynomials on fin.-dim. Hilbert spaces, spherical harmonics, and the trace class, ...

8

Inspiring examples

- Lozinski-Kharshiladze 1948:

$$\lambda(\text{Trig}_{\leq d}(\mathbb{T})) = \int_{\mathbb{T}} \left| \sum_{|k| \leq d} z^k \right| dz = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \log(d+1) + o(1)$$

- Ryll-Wojtaszczyk 1983: In the complex case

$$\lambda(\mathcal{P}_d(\ell_2^n)) = \frac{\Gamma(n+d)\Gamma(1+\frac{d}{2})}{\Gamma(1+d)\Gamma(n+\frac{d}{2})}$$

- D-Frerick 2011: For $1 \leq r \leq \infty$ and in the real/complex case

$$\lambda(\mathcal{P}_d(\ell_r^n)) \sim_{C^d} \left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right)^{d(1 - \frac{1}{\min\{r, 2\}})}$$

9

A unifying strategy

We consider triples $((K, \mu), (G, m), \varphi)$, where

- K is a compact space together with a probability measure μ ,
- G a compact group with its Haar measure m ,
- and φ a multiplicative and continuous mapping

$$\varphi : G \longrightarrow \text{Hom}(K), \quad g \mapsto \varphi_g,$$

where $\text{Hom}(K)$ denotes the space of all homeomorphisms on K .

We call $((K, \mu), (G, m), \varphi)$ a **Rudin triple**, whenever

R1 $\forall x, y \in K \exists g \in G: \varphi_g x = y$

R2 $\forall g \in G \forall f \in C(K): \int_K f \circ \varphi_g d\mu = \int_K f d\mu$

R3 There is a dense family $(S_j)_{j \in I}$ of fin.-dim. subspaces in $C(K)$ such that $f \circ \varphi_g \in S_j$ for all $f \in S_j, g \in G$, and $j \in I$.

Invariance and accessibility

Let S be a **fin.-dim. subspace of $C(K)$** , where $((K, \mu), (G, m), \varphi)$ forms a Rudin triple.

- We call S **φ -invariant** whenever $f \circ \varphi_g \in S$ for all $f \in S, g \in G$.
- Let S be φ -invariant and π_S the orthogonal projection from $L_2(\mu)$ onto S . Then $\pi_S : C(K) \rightarrow S$ commutes with all φ_g if

$$\pi_S(f \circ \varphi_g) = \pi_S(f) \circ \varphi_g \text{ for all } f \in C(K), g \in G.$$

- We call S **(μ, φ) -accessible** if S is φ -invariant and $\pi_S : C(K) \rightarrow S$ is the unique projection that commutes with all φ_g .

11

Averaging projections

Let S be a **fin.-dim. and (μ, φ) -accessible subspace of $C(K)$** , where $((K, \mu), (G, m), \varphi)$ forms a Rudin triple. Find

$$\lambda(S) = \lambda(S, C(K))$$

- Define

$$\Phi : G \longrightarrow \mathcal{L}(C(K)), \quad g \mapsto [\Phi_g : f \mapsto f \circ \varphi_g]$$

Then, given any projection $\mathbf{Q} : C(K) \rightarrow S$, the projection

$$\int_G \Phi_g^{-1} \circ \mathbf{Q} \circ \Phi_g \, dm(g) : C(K) \rightarrow S$$

commutes with all φ_g , and hence it coincides with π_S .

- By the 'triangle inequality': $\lambda(S, C(K)) = \|\pi_S : C(K) \rightarrow S\|$

12

Summing up ...

Let $((K, \mu), (G, m), \varphi)$ be a Rudin triple. Then for every fin.-dim. and (μ, φ) -accessible subspace S of $C(K)$

$$\lambda(S) = \|\pi_S : C(K) \rightarrow S\| = \int_K |\mathbf{k}_S(x, \cdot)| d\mu,$$

where $x \in K$ is arbitrary.

Reproducing kernel

There is a unique continuous function $\mathbf{k}_S : K \times K \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ such that for all $x \in K$

$$(\pi_S f)(x) = \langle f, \mathbf{k}_S(x, \cdot) \rangle_{L_2(\mu)} \quad \text{for all } f \in L_2(\mu).$$

Moreover, these unique kernels \mathbf{k}_S cooperate nicely with the group structure of K ...

13

Trigonometric polynomials on compact abelian groups

Let $K = G$ be a compact abelian group itself. Find

$\lambda(S)$, given a fin.-dim. subspace S of $C(G)$

Any such group G defines a Rudin triple

Consider the Haar measure m on G together with the translation map

$$\varphi : G \longrightarrow \text{Hom}(G), \quad g \mapsto [\varphi_g : h \mapsto gh]$$

Then

- **R1** and **R2**: ✓
- **R3**: Take the dense family (S_j) of all subspaces of $C(G)$ spanned by finitely many characters

14

Theorem - team

Let G be a compact abelian group, and S a fin.-dim. invariant subspace of $C(G)$. Then S is accessible, and in particular

$$\lambda(S) = \|\pi_S : C(G) \rightarrow S\| = \int_G |\mathbf{k}_S(x, \cdot)| dm,$$

where $x \in K$ is arbitrary.

Corollary

Given a set $\Gamma = \{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n\}$ of characters on G , let $\text{Trig}_\Gamma(G)$ be the Banach space of all trigonometric polynomials $\sum_{1 \leq k \leq n} c_k \gamma_k$. Then

$$\lambda(\text{Trig}_\Gamma(G)) = \int_G \left| \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \right| dm$$

15

Again: Lozinski-Kharshiladze 1948

$$\lambda(\text{Trig}_{\leq d}(\mathbb{T})) = \int_{\mathbb{T}} \left| \sum_{|k| \leq d} z^k \right| dz = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \log(d+1) + o(1)$$

Again: Grünbaum 1960

Identify each $(c_k) \in \ell_1^n(\mathbb{C})$ with $\sum_{1 \leq k \leq n} c_k z_k \in \mathcal{C}(\mathbb{T}^n)$. Then

$$\lambda(\ell_1^n(\mathbb{C})) = \int_{\mathbb{T}^n} \left| \sum_{k=1}^n z_k \right| dz = \int_0^\infty \frac{1 - J_0(t)^n}{t^2} dt$$

Dirichlet polynomials

Definition

Given a frequency $\omega = (\omega_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ and a finite index set $J \subset \mathbb{N}$, denote by $\mathcal{H}_\infty^J(\omega)$ the linear space of all ω -Dirichlet polynomials

$$D(s) = \sum_{n \in J} a_n e^{-\omega_n s}, \quad s \in \mathbb{C}$$

which together with the sup-norm taken on $[Re > 0]$ forms a Banach space.

Basic examples

- $\omega = (n)$
- $\omega = (\log n)$

Problem

$$\lambda(\mathcal{H}_\infty^J(\omega)) = ?$$

Main particular case

$$\lambda(\mathcal{H}_\infty^{\leq x}) = ?,$$

where $\mathcal{H}_\infty^{\leq x}$ stands for the Banach space of all ordinary Dirichlet polynomials $\sum_{n \leq x} a_n n^{-s}$ of length x .

How to find a proper isometric embedding

$$\mathcal{H}_\infty^J(\omega) \hookrightarrow C(G),$$

where G is a compact abelian group?

18

D-Schoolmann 2019

A pair (G, β) is said to be a ω -Dirichlet group, whenever

- G is a compact abelian group,
- $\beta : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow G$ a continuous homomorphism with dense range,
- and there is a sequence $(h_{\omega_n})_n$ in \widehat{G} such that for all n

$$\begin{array}{ccc} G & \xrightarrow{h_{\omega_n}} & \mathbb{T} \\ \beta \uparrow & & \nearrow e^{-i\omega_n \bullet} \\ \mathbb{R} & & \end{array}$$

Examples

- The Bohr compactification of \mathbb{R} serves as a universal ω -Dirichlet group for all frequencies ω ,
- and, more naturally, \mathbb{T} for $\omega = (n)$ and \mathbb{T}^∞ for $\omega = (\log n)$.

19

Embedding theorem

Given a ω -Dirichlet group (G, β) , the mapping

$$\mathcal{B} : \mathcal{H}_\infty^J(\omega) \hookrightarrow C(G), \quad \sum_{n \in J} a_n e^{-\omega_n s} \mapsto \sum_{n \in J} a_n h_{\omega_n}$$

defines an isometric embedding, and moreover

$$\int_G f \, dm = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T f \circ \beta \, dt, \quad f \in C(G).$$

Theorem - team

$$\lambda(\mathcal{H}_\infty^J(\omega)) = \int_G \left| \sum_{n \in J} h_{\omega_n} \right| dm = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T \left| \sum_{n \in J} e^{-i\omega_n t} \right| dt$$

20

Main application - team

$$\lambda(\mathcal{H}_\infty^{\leq x}) = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T \left| \sum_{n \leq x} n^{-it} \right| dt \sim \frac{\sqrt{x}}{(\log \log x)^{\frac{1}{4}}}$$

Harper 2019

The asymptotically correct formula for the integral is a recent deep result of Harper in probabilistic analytic number theory, resolving long standing problems ...

21

Polynomials on Boolean cubes

Fourier analysis on Boolean cubes

- Consider the group $G = \{-1, +1\}^N$ with its Haar measure.
- The dual group of $\{\pm 1\}^N$ is formed by so-called Walsh functions:

$$x^A = \prod_{n \in A} x_n, \quad A \subset \{1, \dots, N\}$$

- Every function $f : \{\pm 1\}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ has a Fourier-Walsh expansion:

$$f(x) = \sum_{A \subset \{1, \dots, N\}} \hat{f}(A) x^A$$

A very active field, among others in

computer sciences, combinatorics, social choice theory, graph theory, cryptography, **low-degree learning of functions on Boolean cubes** or **quantum observables**, ...

Banach spaces of functions on Boolean cubes

Given a family \mathcal{A} of subsets in $\{1, \dots, N\}$, we write

- $\mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{A}}^N \subset C(\{\pm 1\}^N)$ for the subspace of all functions

$$f(x) = \sum_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \widehat{f}(A) x^A, \quad x \in \{\pm 1\}^N$$

- and $\mathcal{B}_{=d}^N$, whenever \mathcal{A} consists of all A 's with $\text{card}(A) = d$

Find

$\lambda(\mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{A}}^N)$, for a given family \mathcal{A} of subsets in $\{1, \dots, N\}$

23

Theorem - team

For each family \mathcal{A} of subsets in $\{1, \dots, N\}$

$$\lambda(\mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{A}}^N) = \frac{1}{2^N} \sum_{x \in \{\pm 1\}^N} \left| \sum_{A \in \mathcal{A}} x^A \right|$$

Problem

Fixing d , how fast does $\lambda(\mathcal{B}_{=d}^N)$ increase in N ?

24

Motivation: König-Schütt-Tomczak 1999

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(\mathcal{B}_{=1}^N)}{\sqrt{\dim \mathcal{B}_{=1}^N}} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(\ell_1^N(\mathbb{R}))}{N^{1/2}} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}}$$

Problem

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(\mathcal{B}_{=d}^N)}{\sqrt{\dim \mathcal{B}_{=d}^N}} = ?$$

25

Main theorem - team

Fix some d , then

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(\mathcal{B}_{=d}^N)}{\sqrt{\dim \mathcal{B}_{=d}^N}} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|h_d(t)|}{\sqrt{d!}} e^{-t^2/2} dt \\ &= \frac{2^{7/4}}{\pi^{5/4}} \frac{1}{d^{1/4}} \left(1 + O\left(\frac{1}{d^2}\right) \right), \end{aligned}$$

where h_d is the d -th Hermite polynomial given by

$$h_d(t) := (-1)^d e^{t^2/2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right)^d e^{-t^2/2}, \quad t \in \mathbb{R}.$$

26

Polynomials on Hilbert spaces

Again: Ryll-Wojtaszczyk 1983

$$\lambda(\mathcal{P}_d(\ell_2^n(\mathbb{C}))) = \frac{\Gamma(n+d)}{\Gamma(n-1)\Gamma(1+d)} \int_0^1 (1-t)^{n-2} t^{\frac{d}{2}} dt$$

Two surprisingly interesting problems

- $\lambda(\mathcal{P}_d(\ell_2^n(\mathbb{R}))) = ?$
- $\lambda(\mathcal{P}_{p,q}(\ell_2^n(\mathbb{C}))) = ?$, where $\mathcal{P}_{p,q}(\ell_2^n(\mathbb{C}))$ is the Banach space of all (p, q) -bihomogeneous polynomials f , that is,

$$f(z) = \sum_{|\alpha|=p, |\beta|=q} c_{(\alpha, \beta)} z^\alpha \bar{z}^\beta, \quad z \in \mathbb{C}^n$$

Euklidean spheres as Rudin triples

In the real and complex case the $(n - 1)$ -dimensional euklidean sphere \mathbb{S}^{n-1} together with the action of the **orthogonal resp. unitary group** forms a canonical Rudin tripel.

Given $\alpha, \beta > -1$, we need the sequence

$(P_d^{\alpha, \beta})_{d \in \mathbb{N}_0}$ of Jacobi polynomials on the interval $[-1, 1]$. They are uniquely determined by being d -homogeneous, orthogonal with respect to the inner product

$$\langle P, Q \rangle = \int_{-1}^1 P(t)Q(t) (1 - t)^\alpha (1 + t)^\beta dt,$$

and normalized by $P_d^{\alpha, \beta}(1) = \binom{d+\alpha}{d}$.

28

Real case

Theorem - team

For each $n > 2$ and $d \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\lambda(\mathcal{P}_d(\ell_2^n(\mathbb{R}))) = c(n, d) \int_{-1}^1 |P_d^{\frac{n-1}{2}, \frac{n-1}{2}}(t)| (1-t^2)^{\frac{n-3}{2}} dt,$$

where

$$c(n, d) := \frac{2^{n-2} \Gamma(\frac{n}{2})}{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(n-1)} \frac{\Gamma(\lceil \frac{d}{2} \rceil + \frac{n}{2})}{\Gamma(\lceil \frac{d}{2} \rceil + \frac{1}{2})} \frac{\Gamma(\lfloor \frac{d}{2} \rfloor + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{n}{2})}{\Gamma(\lfloor \frac{d}{2} \rfloor + 1)} \frac{\Gamma(d+1)}{\Gamma(d + \frac{n}{2} + \frac{1}{2})}$$

The proof needs a careful study of

$$\lambda(\mathcal{H}_d(\mathbb{S}_{\mathbb{R}}^{n-1})),$$

the projection constant of the Banach space of all d -homogeneous spherical harmonics.

29

Complex case

Theorem - team

For $n \geq 2$ and $p, q \geq 0$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \lambda(\mathcal{P}_{p,q}(\ell_2^n(\mathbb{C}))) \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(n + p \vee q)}{\Gamma(n - 1)\Gamma(1 + p \vee q)} \int_0^1 |P_{p \wedge q}^{n-1, |p-q|}(2t-1)| (1-t)^{n-2} t^{\frac{|p-q|}{2}} dt \end{aligned}$$

The proof needs a careful study of

$$\lambda(\mathcal{H}_{p,q}(\mathbb{S}_{\mathbb{C}}^{n-1})),$$

the projection constant of the Banach space of all (p, q) -bihomogeneous spherical harmonics

30

The trace class

Definition

The Schatten p -class $\mathcal{S}_p(\ell_2^n)$, $1 \leq p \leq \infty$ is the Banach space of all operators on ℓ_2^n endowed with the norm

$$\|u\|_p = \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |s_k(u)|^p \right)^{1/p},$$

where $(s_k(u))_{k=1}^n$ is given by the eigenvalues of $|u| = (u^*u)^{1/2}$.

31

Gordon-Lewis 1974

- $\lambda(\mathcal{S}_p(\ell_2^n)) \sim n$ for $1 \leq p \leq \infty$
- $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(\mathcal{S}_\infty(\ell_2^n))}{n} = \frac{\pi}{4}$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(\mathcal{S}_2(\ell_2^n))}{n} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}$
- $\frac{n}{3} \leq \lambda(\mathcal{S}_1(\ell_2^n)) \leq n$

Problem

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(\mathcal{S}_1(\ell_2^n))}{n} = ?$$

32

Theorem - team

For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\lambda(\mathcal{S}_1(\ell_2^n)) = n \int_{\mathcal{U}_n} |\operatorname{tr}(V)| dV$$

Moreover,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(\mathcal{S}_1(\ell_2^n))}{n} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}$$

How to use the general scheme?

$$\mathcal{S}_1(\ell_2^n) \hookrightarrow C(\mathcal{U}_n), V \mapsto [U \mapsto \operatorname{tr}(VU)] \quad \text{isometrically}$$

33

Articles by the team

- Asymptotic insights for projection, Gordon-Lewis, and Sidon constants of Boolean Cube function spaces; International Mathematical Research Notices 2024
- Projection constants for spaces of Dirichlet polynomials; Mathematische Annalen 2024
- An integral formula for the projection constant of the trace class; Analysis&PDE 2024
- Minimal projections onto spaces of polynomials on real euclidean spheres; submitted 2024
- Projection constants of spaces of bihomogeneous polynomials on complex euclidean spheres; in preparation 2024
- Projection constants of spaces of multivariate polynomials; an arXiv manuscript 2022 that is gradually improved ...

34

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

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In the recent past, smoothness spaces of Besov or Triebel-Lizorkin type, built upon Morrey spaces $\mathcal{M}_{u,p}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $0 < p \leq u < \infty$, have been studied intensively. These scales $\mathcal{N}_{u,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and $\mathcal{E}_{u,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $s \in \mathbb{R}$, $0 < q \leq \infty$, have become popular in connection with applications in PDE, but are also interesting for their own sake. They generalise the well-known scales of Besov and Triebel-Lizorkin spaces, $B_{p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and $F_{p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$, since $\mathcal{M}_{p,p}(\mathbb{R}^d) = L_p(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $0 < p < \infty$. Following a similar intention, the Besov-type and Triebel-Lizorkin-type spaces $B_{p,q}^{s,\tau}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and $F_{p,q}^{s,\tau}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $\tau \geq 0$, were introduced and systematically studied in the last years.

Now we follow an idea of Mizuhara and Nakai who introduced in the beginning of the 1990's generalised Morrey spaces $\mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, where $\varphi : (0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ stands for a function belonging to a so-called \mathcal{G}_p class, $0 < p < \infty$, and the special setting $\varphi(t) \sim t^{d/u}$, $0 < t < \infty$, covers the case $\mathcal{M}_{u,p}(\mathbb{R}^d)$. In a parallel way one can generalise the spaces $B_{p,q}^{s,\tau}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and $F_{p,q}^{s,\tau}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ with the help of such a function φ .

We studied basic properties of these new scales of spaces as well as embeddings, decompositions, and local singularity behaviour of distributions in such spaces. One might think, at first glance, that replacing one index (u or τ) by some function $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$ will presumably make the situation more complicated, rather than more transparent and comprehensible. And we admit, that this assumption is surely true in view of the proofs and their technicalities. However, looking at our first results, it turned out that some peculiarities of our recent findings can now be much better classified in the new setting. Roughly speaking, the number of cases to be distinguished when studying embeddings, growth envelopes etc., is reduced to some qualitative limit behaviour of the function φ . We give some survey of our recent results in this direction.

This is joint work with Zhen Liu (Jena), Susana Moura (Coimbra), and Leszek Skrzypczak (Poznań).

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Dorothee D. Haroske

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Function Spaces XIII

Poznań, July 8 - 12, 2024

joint work with Zhen Liu (Jena); Susana Moura (Coimbra),
and Leszek Skrzypczak (Poznań)

The talk is based on our joint papers:

D.D. Haroske and Z. Liu.

Generalized Besov-type and Triebel-Lizorkin-type spaces.

Studia Math., 273(2):161–199, 2023.

D.D. Haroske, Z. Liu, S.D. Moura, and L. Skrzypczak.

Embeddings of generalized smoothness spaces of Morrey type.

Acta Math. Sin. (Engl. Ser.), accepted.

D.D. Haroske, S.D. Moura, and L. Skrzypczak.

Wavelet decomposition and embeddings of generalised Besov-Morrey spaces.

Nonlinear Anal., 214(1), 112590, 2022.

D.D. Haroske, S.D. Moura, and L. Skrzypczak.

On a bridge connecting Lebesgue and Morrey spaces in view of their growth properties.

Anal. Appl. (Singap.), 22(4):751–790, 2024.

Morrey Spaces

- Reminder: 'Classical' Morrey spaces
- Digression: Growth envelope functions
- Generalised Morrey spaces

Morrey smoothness spaces

- Smoothness spaces
- Smoothness Spaces of Morrey Type
- Comparison

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

- Definition and basic properties
- Embeddings within and between the scales
- Da capo: Results on envelopes in $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$

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Morrey Spaces

Starting point: 'Classical' Morrey spaces

$0 < p \leq u < \infty$, Morrey space $\mathcal{M}_{u,p}$: $f \in L_p^{\text{loc}}$ with

$$\|f\|_{\mathcal{M}_{u,p}} = \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d, R > 0} R^{d(\frac{1}{u} - \frac{1}{p})} \left(\int_{B(x,R)} |f(y)|^p dy \right)^{1/p} < \infty$$

Rem. Charles B. Morrey Jr. (1938), Campanato, Brudnyi, Peetre,

Some properties:

- ▶ $\mathcal{M}_{u,p} = \begin{cases} \{0\}, & p > u \\ L_p, & p = u \end{cases} \rightsquigarrow u > p$ refined (local) integrability
- ▶ $\mathcal{M}_{\infty,p} = L_\infty$
- ▶ $L_u = \mathcal{M}_{u,u} \hookrightarrow \mathcal{M}_{u,p_1} \hookrightarrow \mathcal{M}_{u,p_2}, 0 < p_2 \leq p_1 \leq u < \infty$

All spaces are defined on \mathbb{R}^d unless stated otherwise.

Morrey Spaces

A first example

Let $0 < p < u < \infty$.

- ▶ $f(x) = |x|^{-\frac{d}{u}} \psi(x)$, ψ some cut-off function near 0

$\rightsquigarrow f \in \mathcal{M}_{u,p}$, but $f \notin L_u \dashrightarrow L_u \subsetneq \mathcal{M}_{u,p}$

- ▶ Let $m_k = (2^k, 0, \dots, 0)$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$

$$\rightsquigarrow g(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f(x - m_k) \in \mathcal{M}_{u,p} \setminus \bigcup_{r>0} L_r$$

Morrey Spaces

From the beginning: Strong motivation from PDE & theory of function spaces

C.B. Morrey.

On the solutions of quasi-linear elliptic partial differential equations.
Trans. Amer. Math. Soc. **43** (1938), 126–166.

J. Peetre.

On the theory of $\mathcal{L}_{p,\lambda}$ spaces,
J. Funct. Anal. **4** (1969), 71–87.

Y. Sawano, G. Di Fazio, and D.I. Hakim.

Morrey spaces. Introduction and Applications to Integral Operators and PDE's. Vols. I + II.

Monographs and Research Notes in Mathematics. Chapman & Hall CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 2020.

Not part of this talk here!

Why to generalise Morrey spaces?

Digression: growth envelope functions

$$f^*(t) = \inf \{s \geq 0 : |\{x \in \mathbb{R}^d : |f(x)| > s\}| \leq t\}, \quad t \geq 0$$

Definition 1

$X \subset L_1^{\text{loc}}$, **growth envelope function** $\mathcal{E}_G^X : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty]$

$$\mathcal{E}_G^X(t) \sim \sup_{\|f\|_X \leq 1} f^*(t), \quad t > 0$$

Properties:

- ▶ $X \hookrightarrow L_\infty \iff \sup_{t>0} \mathcal{E}_G^X(t) < \infty$
- ▶ $X_1 \hookrightarrow X_2 \implies \mathcal{E}_G^{X_1}(t) \leq c \mathcal{E}_G^{X_2}(t), \quad t > 0$
- ▶ X **rearrangement-invariant** with fund. fnt. φ_X : $\mathcal{E}_G^X(t) \sim \frac{1}{\varphi_X(t)}$

Example $\mathcal{E}_G^{L_{p,q}}(t) \sim t^{-\frac{1}{p}}, \quad 0 < p < \infty, 0 < q \leq \infty$

Growth envelope results

Some phenomenon in Morrey spaces

Rem.

- ▶ 'fine index' $u_G^X \rightsquigarrow \mathfrak{E}_G(X) = (\mathcal{E}_G^X, u_G^X)$ 'growth envelope'
- ▶ $\mathfrak{E}_G(L_{p,q}) = (t^{-\frac{1}{p}}, q)$, $0 < p < \infty$, $0 < q \leq \infty$

Proposition 2

Let $0 < p \leq u \leq \infty$, then $\mathcal{E}_G^{\mathcal{M}_{u,p}(\mathbb{R}^d)}(t) \sim \begin{cases} t^{-1/p}, & p = u, \\ = \infty, & p < u, \\ 1, & u = \infty, \end{cases} \quad t > 0$

Rem.

- ▶ $u = \infty$: $\mathcal{M}_{u,p}(\mathbb{R}^d) = L_\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $0 < p = u < \infty$: $\mathcal{M}_{u,p}(\mathbb{R}^d) = L_p(\mathbb{R}^d)$
- ▶ $0 < p < u < \infty$: H./Moura (2016), idea: consider example $g(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f(x - m_k)$, $m_k = (2^k, 0, \dots, 0)$, $f(x) = |x|^{-\frac{d}{u}} \psi(x)$

What really happens when $p \uparrow u$ in $\mathcal{M}_{u,p}(\mathbb{R}^d)$? Way out: $\mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}(\mathbb{R}^d)$?

Generalised Morrey spaces

The setting

recall:

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{\mathcal{M}_{u,p}} &= \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d, R > 0} R^{\frac{d}{u} - \frac{d}{p}} \left(\int_{B(x,R)} |f(y)|^p dy \right)^{1/p} \\ &\sim \sup_{\text{dyadic cubes}} |Q|^{\frac{1}{u}} \left(\frac{1}{|Q|} \int_Q |f(y)|^p dy \right)^{1/p} \\ &= \sup_{\text{dyadic cubes}} \varphi(\ell(Q)) \left(\frac{1}{|Q|} \int_Q |f(y)|^p dy \right)^{1/p} \end{aligned}$$

with $\ell(Q)$... side length of Q , $\varphi(t) = t^{\frac{d}{u}}$, $0 < p \leq u \leq \infty$

Idea: consider more general functions $\varphi : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, $\varphi \not\equiv 0$, and consider all $f \in L_p^{\text{loc}}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ such that

$$\|f\|_{\mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}} = \sup_{\text{dyadic cubes}} \varphi(\ell(Q)) \left(\frac{1}{|Q|} \int_Q |f(y)|^p dy \right)^{1/p} < \infty$$

Rem. Nakai (1994), Mizuhara (1991)

Generalised Morrey spaces

Which functions φ ?

Examples

$$\blacktriangleright \varphi(t) = t^{\frac{d}{u}}, p \leq u: \mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}(\mathbb{R}^d) = \begin{cases} \mathcal{M}_{u,p}(\mathbb{R}^d), & 0 < p < u < \infty \\ L_p(\mathbb{R}^d), & 0 < p = u < \infty \\ L_\infty(\mathbb{R}^d), & u = \infty (\varphi \equiv 1) \end{cases}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \varphi(t) = t^{-\sigma} \chi_{(0,1)}(t), -\frac{d}{p} \leq \sigma < 0: \\ \mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}(\mathbb{R}^d) = \mathcal{L}_p^\sigma(\mathbb{R}^d) \quad \text{local Morrey spaces (Triebel 2013)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sigma = -\frac{d}{p}: \mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}(\mathbb{R}^d) = \mathcal{L}_p(\mathbb{R}^d) \quad \text{uniform Lebesgue space}$$

usual assumption: $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$, that is, $\varphi : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ nondecreasing and $\varphi(t)t^{-d/p}$ nonincreasing

Rem. justification, see Nakamura/Noi/Sawano (2016), Sawano (2018):

$$\blacktriangleright \mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}(\mathbb{R}^d) \neq \{0\} \iff \sup_{t>0} \varphi(t) \min(t^{-\frac{d}{p}}, 1) < \infty$$

$$\blacktriangleright \text{If } \sup_{t>0} \varphi(t) \min(t^{-\frac{d}{p}}, 1) < \infty, \text{ then } \exists \varphi^* \in \mathcal{G}_p: \mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}(\mathbb{R}^d) = \mathcal{M}_{\varphi^*,p}(\mathbb{R}^d)$$

Generalised Morrey spaces

Properties and examples of $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$

$$\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p, 0 < p < \infty \iff 1 \leq \frac{\varphi(r)}{\varphi(t)} \leq \left(\frac{r}{t}\right)^{d/p}, \quad 0 < t \leq r < \infty$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathcal{G}_{p_2} \subset \mathcal{G}_{p_1}, \quad 0 < p_1 \leq p_2 < \infty$$

$$\blacktriangleright \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(t)t^{-\frac{d}{p}} \in [0, \varphi(1)] \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) \in [0, \varphi(1)] \quad \text{exist}$$

Examples

$$\blacktriangleright 0 < u, v < \infty \rightsquigarrow \varphi_{u,v}(t) = \begin{cases} t^{d/u} & \text{if } t \leq 1, \\ t^{d/v} & \text{if } t > 1, \end{cases} \in \mathcal{G}_{\min(u,v)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 0 < v < \infty, u = \infty \rightsquigarrow \varphi(t) = \max(t^{d/v}, 1) \in \mathcal{G}_v$$

$$\blacktriangleright 0 < u < \infty, v = \infty \rightsquigarrow \varphi(t) = \min(t^{d/u}, 1) \in \mathcal{G}_u$$

$$\blacktriangleright \varphi(t) = t^{d/u} (\log(L+t))^a \in \mathcal{G}_u, \text{ with } L \text{ suff. large, } 0 < u < \infty, a \leq 0$$

Since $\varphi \sim \tilde{\varphi}$ leads to $\mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}(\mathbb{R}^d) = \mathcal{M}_{\tilde{\varphi},p}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $0 < p < \infty$, we shall usually assume $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$ with $\varphi(1) = 1$ in the sequel.

Generalised Morrey spaces

Some known embeddings

$\varphi_i \in \mathcal{G}_{p_i}$ with $\varphi_i(1) = 1$, $0 < p_i < \infty$, $i = 1, 2$

Proposition 3

► If $0 < p_2 \leq p_1 < \infty$, then

$$\mathcal{M}_{\varphi_1, p_1}(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow \mathcal{M}_{\varphi_2, p_2}(\mathbb{R}^d) \iff \varphi_1 \lesssim \varphi_2.$$

► If $0 < r \leq p < \infty$, then

$$\mathcal{M}_{\varphi, p}(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow L_r(\mathbb{R}^d) \iff r = p \text{ and } \varphi(t) \sim t^{d/p}, \quad t > 1.$$

► $\mathcal{M}_{\varphi, p}(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow L_\infty(\mathbb{R}^d) \iff \inf_{t>0} \varphi(t) > 0$,

$$L_\infty(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow \mathcal{M}_{\varphi, p}(\mathbb{R}^d) \iff \sup_{t>0} \varphi(t) < \infty$$

Rem. Gunawan/Hakim/Limanta/Masta (2017), Sawano (2018),
Sawano/Di Fazio/Hakim (2020)

Generalised Morrey spaces

Growth envelopes in $\mathcal{M}_{\varphi, p}$

recall: $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p \rightsquigarrow \exists \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(t) t^{-\frac{d}{p}} \in [0, 1]$, $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) \in [0, 1]$

Proposition 4

Let $0 < p < \infty$, $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$, $\varphi(1) = 1$. Then

$$\mathcal{E}_G^{\mathcal{M}_{\varphi, p}}(t) \sim \begin{cases} 1 & \iff \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) > 0, \\ t^{-1/p} & \iff \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) = 0 \ \& \ \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t^{-d/p} \varphi(t) > 0, \\ \infty & \iff \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) = 0 \ \& \ \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t^{-d/p} \varphi(t) = 0. \end{cases}$$

Rem.

► H./Moura/Skrzypczak (2024)

► $\mathcal{M}_{\varphi, p}$ 'bridge' between L_p and Morrey spaces, only limits distinguish cases

► $0 < p < u < \infty$, $\varphi(t) \sim t^{d/u} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{E}_G^{\mathcal{M}_{\varphi, p}}(t) \sim \mathcal{E}_G^{\mathcal{M}_{u, p}}(t) = \infty$

Morrey Spaces

Reminder: 'Classical' Morrey spaces

Digression: Growth envelope functions

Generalised Morrey spaces

Morrey smoothness spaces

Smoothness spaces

Smoothness Spaces of Morrey Type

Comparison

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Definition and basic properties

Embeddings within and between the scales

Da capo: Results on envelopes in $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$

Classical Smoothness Spaces

Sobolev spaces on \mathbb{R}^d

- ▶ classical: $1 \leq p < \infty$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$

Sobolev space $W_p^k = \{f \in L_p : D^\alpha f \in L_p \text{ for } \alpha \in \mathbb{N}_0^d, |\alpha| \leq k\}$

$$\|f|W_p^k\| = \sum_{|\alpha| \leq k} \|D^\alpha f|L_p\|$$

- ▶ via Fourier analysis: $1 < p < \infty$, $s \in \mathbb{R}$

Sobolev space $H_p^s = \{f \in \mathcal{S}' : \mathcal{F}^{-1}(1 + |\xi|^2)^{s/2} \mathcal{F}f \in L_p\}$

$$\|f|H_p^s\| = \|\mathcal{F}^{-1}(1 + |\xi|^2)^{s/2} \mathcal{F}f|L_p\|$$

with

$$\mathcal{F}f(\xi) = (2\pi)^{-d/2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} e^{-ix\xi} f(x) dx, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^d$$

- ▶ $1 < p < \infty$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$: $W_p^k = H_p^k$ (equivalent norms)

Classical Smoothness Spaces

From Sobolev to Besov

starting point:

$$\|f|H_2^s\| \sim \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} 2^{2js} \|\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f|L_2\|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sim \left\| \left(2^{js} \|\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f)|L_2\| \right)_j \right\|_{\ell_2}$$

$0 < p, q \leq \infty$, $s \in \mathbb{R}$, $(\varphi_j)_j$ smooth dyadic partition of unity

$$\varphi_j \in C_0^\infty, \text{supp } \varphi_j \subset \{x \in \mathbb{R}^d : 2^{j-1} < |x| < 2^{j+1}\}, \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \varphi_j(x) = 1$$

$$\text{Besov space } B_{p,q}^s \subset \mathcal{S}' : \|f|B_{p,q}^s\| = \left\| \left(2^{js} \|\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f)|L_p\| \right)_j \right\|_{\ell_q}$$

Classical Smoothness Spaces

Spaces of Besov and Triebel-Lizorkin type

$0 < p \leq \infty$, $0 < q \leq \infty$, $s \in \mathbb{R}$, $\{\varphi_j\}_j$ dyadic partition of unity

$$\|f|B_{p,q}^s\| = \left\| \left(2^{js} \|\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f)|L_p\| \right)_j \right\|_{\ell_q}$$

$$\|f|F_{p,q}^s\| = \left\| \left\| \left(2^{js} \mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f)(\cdot) \right)_j \right\|_{\ell_q} \right\|_{L_p}$$

Rem.

- ▶ (classical) Besov spaces $0 < p, q \leq \infty$, $s > d(\frac{1}{p} - 1)_+$

$$\|f|B_{p,q}^s\| \sim \|f|L_p\| + \left(\int_0^1 \left(\frac{\omega_m(f, t)_p}{t^s} \right)^q \frac{dt}{t} \right)^{1/q}, \quad m > s$$

- ▶ $B_{\infty, \infty}^s = C^s$, $s > 0$ Hölder-Zygmund spaces
- ▶ $F_{p,2}^s = H_p^s$, $1 < p < \infty$, $s \in \mathbb{R}$
- ▶ $F_{p,2}^k = W_p^k$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $1 < p < \infty$ Sobolev spaces

Approach 1: Morrey smoothness spaces

The spaces $\mathcal{N}_{u,p,q}^s$ and $\mathcal{E}_{u,p,q}^s$

$0 < p \leq u < \infty$, $q \in (0, \infty]$, $s \in \mathbb{R}$, $\{\varphi_j\}_j$ smooth dyadic res. of unity

(i) Besov-Morrey space $\mathcal{N}_{u,p,q}^s$: $f \in \mathcal{S}'$ with

$$\|f | \mathcal{N}_{u,p,q}^s\| = \left\| \left(2^{js} \|\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f) | \mathcal{M}_{u,p}\| \right)_j | \ell_q \right\| < \infty$$

(ii) Triebel-Lizorkin-Morrey space $\mathcal{E}_{u,p,q}^s$: $f \in \mathcal{S}'$ with

$$\|f | \mathcal{E}_{u,p,q}^s\| = \left\| \left\| \left(2^{js} |\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f)(\cdot)| \right)_j | \ell_q \right\| | \mathcal{M}_{u,p} \right\| < \infty$$

Rem.

- Kozono/Yamazaki ('94), Mazzucato ('03), Tang/Xu ('05), Sawano ('07-)

H. Kozono and M. Yamazaki

Semilinear heat equations and the Navier-Stokes equation with distributions in new function spaces as initial data.

Comm. Partial Differential Equations, 19 (1994), 959–1014.

A.L. Mazzucato

Besov-Morrey spaces: function space theory and applications to non-linear PDE.

Trans. Amer. Math. Soc., 355 (2003), 1297–1364 (electronic).

- $\mathcal{N}_{p,p,q}^s = B_{p,q}^s$, $\mathcal{E}_{p,p,q}^s = F_{p,q}^s$, $\mathcal{N}_{u,p,q}^s = \mathcal{E}_{u,p,q}^s = \{0\}$ if $p > u$
- $\mathcal{E}_{u,p,2}^0 = \mathcal{M}_{u,p}$, $1 < p \leq u < \infty$, i.e., $\mathcal{E}_{p,p,2}^0 = L_p$, $1 < p < \infty$

Approach 2: Morrey smoothness spaces

The spaces $B_{p,q}^{s,\tau}$ and $F_{p,q}^{s,\tau}$

$0 < p, q \leq \infty$, $\tau \geq 0$, $s \in \mathbb{R}$, $\{\varphi_j\}_j$ dyadic res. of unity, \mathcal{Q} dyadic cubes

(i) Besov-type space $B_{p,q}^{s,\tau}$: $f \in \mathcal{S}'$ with

$$\|f | B_{p,q}^{s,\tau}\| = \sup_{P \in \mathcal{Q}} \frac{1}{|P|^\tau} \left\| \left(2^{js} \|\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f) | L_p(P)\| \right)_{j \geq (j_P)_+} | \ell_q \right\| < \infty$$

(ii) Triebel-Lizorkin-type space $F_{p,q}^{s,\tau}$: $f \in \mathcal{S}'$ with

$$\|f | F_{p,q}^{s,\tau}\| = \sup_{P \in \mathcal{Q}} \frac{1}{|P|^\tau} \left\| \left\| \left(2^{js} |\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f)(\cdot)| \right)_{j \geq (j_P)_+} | \ell_q \right\| | L_p(P) \right\| < \infty$$

Rem.

- El Baraka ('02), Yuan/Sickel/Yang (2010-)

W. Yuan, W. Sickel and D. Yang,

Morrey and Campanato Meet Besov, Lizorkin and Triebel.

Lecture Notes in Mathematics 2005, Springer, Berlin, 2010.

- $B_{p,q}^{s,0} = B_{p,q}^s$, $F_{p,q}^{s,0} = F_{p,q}^s$, $B_{p,q}^{s,\tau} = F_{p,q}^{s,\tau} = \{0\}$ if $\tau < 0$, elem. properties
- $\text{bmo} = B_{2,2}^{0,1/2} = F_{p,2}^{0,1/p}$, $0 < p < \infty$

New approach to Morrey smoothness spaces

Rem.

- ▶ Triebel: local spaces (2013), hybrid spaces (2014): $L^r B_{p,q}^s, L^r F_{p,q}^s$, $0 < p, q \leq \infty, s \in \mathbb{R}, -\frac{d}{p} \leq r < \infty$

H. Triebel
Local function spaces, heat and Navier-Stokes equations.
EMS Tracts in Mathematics 20, EMS Publishing House, Zürich, 2013.

H. Triebel
Hybrid Function Spaces, Heat and Navier-Stokes Equations,
EMS Tracts in Mathematics 24, EMS Publishing House, Zürich, 2015.

- ▶ $L^r B_{p,q}^s = B_{p,q}^{s,\tau}, L^r F_{p,q}^s = F_{p,q}^{s,\tau}, \tau = \frac{1}{p} + \frac{r}{d}$

new approach: ϱ -clans of spaces $A_{p,q}^s$, share similar properties, encompasses $A_{p,q}^{s,\tau}, \mathcal{A}_{u,p,q}^s, L^r \mathcal{A}_{p,q}^s$, number $|\varrho|$ replaces usual 'slope' d in many respects

D.D. Haroske and H. Triebel.
Morrey smoothness spaces: A new approach.
Sci. China Math., 66(6):1301–1358, 2023.

Morrey smoothness spaces

So far ...

- ▶ two scales of Morrey smoothness spaces: $s \in \mathbb{R}, 0 < q \leq \infty, 0 < p < \infty$
 - ▶ $\mathcal{N}_{u,p,q}^s, \mathcal{E}_{u,p,q}^s, p \leq u < \infty$
 - ▶ $B_{p,q}^{s,\tau}, F_{p,q}^{s,\tau}, \tau \geq 0$
- ▶ generalise $B_{p,q}^s, F_{p,q}^s$, motivated by application to PDE
- ▶ interplay of local-global arguments
- ▶ $F_{p,q}^{s,\tau} = \mathcal{E}_{u,p,q}^s$ with $\tau = \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{u}, 0 < p \leq u < \infty$
- ▶ $\mathcal{N}_{u,p,q}^s \hookrightarrow B_{p,q}^{s,\tau}$ with $\tau = \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{u}$

coincidence (only) if $\tau = 0$ or $q = \infty$, i.e., $\mathcal{N}_{u,p,\infty}^s = B_{p,\infty}^{s, \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{u}}$

convention: $A \in \{B, F\}, \mathcal{A} \in \{\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{E}\} \dashrightarrow A_{u,p,q}^s, A_{p,q}^{s,\tau}$

Can this be reasonably generalised? How?

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Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Generalised approach 1: the spaces $\mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$

$0 < p < \infty$, $q \in (0, \infty]$, $s \in \mathbb{R}$, $\{\varphi_j\}_j$ smooth dyadic res. of unity,
 $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$, $\varphi(1) = 1$

(i) generalised Besov-Morrey space $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$: $f \in \mathcal{S}'$ with

$$\|f\|_{\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s} = \left\| \left(2^{js} \|\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f)\|_{\mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}} \right)_j \right\|_{\ell_q} < \infty$$

(ii) generalised Triebel-Lizorkin-Morrey space $\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$: $f \in \mathcal{S}'$ with

$$\|f\|_{\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s} = \left\| \left\| \left(2^{js} |\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f)(\cdot)| \right)_j \right\|_{\ell_q} \right\|_{\mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}} < \infty$$

where, in case of $q < \infty$, we assume that the ε -condition holds,
 that is, there exist $C > 0$, $\varepsilon > 0$ such that

$$\frac{t^\varepsilon}{\varphi(t)} \leq \frac{Cr^\varepsilon}{\varphi(r)} \quad \text{for } t \geq r.$$

Rem.

S. Nakamura, T. Noi, and Y. Sawano, Generalized Morrey spaces and trace operator, Sci. China Math. 59 (2016), no. 2, 281-336.

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces $\mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$

Basic properties, embeddings

$s \in \mathbb{R}$, $0 < p < \infty$, $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$ with $\varphi(1) = 1$, $0 < r, q \leq \infty$, assume the ε -condition if $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{E}$ and $q < \infty$

- ▶ $\mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,q}^s \hookrightarrow \mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,r}^s$ if $q \leq r$
- ▶ $\mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,q}^{s+\varepsilon} \hookrightarrow \mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,r}^s$ if $\varepsilon > 0$
- ▶ $\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,2}^0 = \mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}$ if $1 < p < \infty$ (Sawano/Hakim/Gunawan 2015)
- ▶ $\varphi_0 \equiv 1$: $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi_0,p,q}^s = B_{\infty,q}^s$, $\mathcal{E}_{\varphi_0,p,\infty}^s = F_{\infty,\infty}^s = B_{\infty,\infty}^s = \mathcal{N}_{\varphi_0,p,\infty}^s$
- ▶ $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,\min(p,q)}^s \hookrightarrow \mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$
- ▶ If $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} t^{-\frac{d}{p}} \varphi(t) < \infty$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} t^{-\frac{d}{p}} \varphi(t) > 0$, then

$$\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s \hookrightarrow \mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q_0}^s \iff q_0 \geq \max(p, q).$$

Otherwise, $\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s \hookrightarrow \mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q_0}^s \iff q_0 = \infty$.

Rem.

- ▶ last result in H./Liu/Moura/Skrzypczak (2024)
- ▶ $\varphi(t) \sim t^{d/u}$, $0 < p \leq u < \infty$: $\mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d) = \mathcal{A}_{u,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Generalised approach 2: The spaces $A_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}$

$0 < p < \infty$, $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$, $\varphi(1) = 1$, $s \in \mathbb{R}$, $\{\varphi_j\}_j$ dyadic res. of unity

(i) generalised Besov-type space $B_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}$: $f \in \mathcal{S}'$ with

$$\|f\|_{B_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}} = \sup_{P \in \mathcal{Q}} \frac{\varphi(\ell(P))}{|P|^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left\| \left(2^{js} \|\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f)\|_{L_p(P)} \right)_{j \geq (j_P)_+} \right\|_{\ell_q} < \infty$$

(ii) generalised Triebel-Lizorkin-type space $F_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}$: $f \in \mathcal{S}'$ with

$$\|f\|_{F_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}} = \sup_{P \in \mathcal{Q}} \frac{\varphi(\ell(P))}{|P|^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left\| \left(2^{js} |\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\varphi_j \mathcal{F}f)(\cdot)| \right)_{j \geq (j_P)_+} \right\|_{\ell_q} \Big|_{L_p(P)} < \infty,$$

where in case of $q < \infty$ we assume the ε -condition again

Rem.

- ▶ inspired by $A_{p,q}^{s,\tau} = A_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}$, $\varphi(t) \sim t^{d(\frac{1}{p}-\tau)}$, $0 \leq \tau < \frac{1}{p}$, introduced in

D.D. Haroske and Z. Liu.

Generalized Besov-type and Triebel-Lizorkin-type spaces.

Studia Math., 273(2):161–199, 2023.

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces $A_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}$

Basic properties, elementary embeddings

$s \in \mathbb{R}$, $0 < p < \infty$, $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$ with $\varphi(1) = 1$, $0 < r, q \leq \infty$,
assume the ε -condition if $A = F$ and $q < \infty$

- ▶ $A_{p,q}^{s,\varphi} \hookrightarrow A_{p,r}^{s,\varphi}$ if $q \leq r$
- ▶ $A_{p,q}^{s+\varepsilon,\varphi} \hookrightarrow A_{p,r}^{s,\varphi}$ if $\varepsilon > 0$
- ▶ $B_{p,\min(p,q)}^{s,\varphi} \hookrightarrow F_{p,q}^{s,\varphi} \hookrightarrow B_{p,\max(p,q)}^{s,\varphi}$

Rem. H./Liu (2023)

Further results for the spaces of type $\mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$ and $A_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}$ are available, like

- ▶ atomic decomposition,
- ▶ wavelet decomposition,
- ▶ lift operators, ...

--> **talk of Zhen Liu** (coming next)

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Embeddings between the scales

$s \in \mathbb{R}$, $0 < p < \infty$, $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$, $0 < q \leq \infty$, assume the ε -condition if
 $A = F$ or $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{E}$ and $q < \infty$

Theorem 5

- ▶ $F_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}(\mathbb{R}^d) = \mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$
- ▶ $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow B_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$
 - ▶ If $q = \infty$, then $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,\infty}^s(\mathbb{R}^d) = B_{p,\infty}^{s,\varphi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$.
 - ▶ If $q < \infty$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t)t^{-\frac{d}{p}} = \infty$ or $\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \varphi(t)t^{-\frac{d}{p}} = 0$,
then $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is a **proper subspace** of $B_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

Example $\varphi(t) \sim t^{d/u} \sim t^{d(\frac{1}{p}-\tau)}$, $0 < p < u < \infty$, $\tau < \frac{1}{p}$

$$\hookrightarrow F_{p,q}^{s,\tau}(\mathbb{R}^d) = \mathcal{E}_{u,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d),$$

$$\mathcal{N}_{u,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow B_{p,q}^{s,\tau}(\mathbb{R}^d) \text{ with } \mathcal{N}_{u,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d) = B_{p,q}^{s,\tau}(\mathbb{R}^d) \iff q = \infty$$

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Embeddings within the scales: $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$

$$s_i \in \mathbb{R}, 0 < p_i < \infty, \varphi_i \in \mathcal{G}_{p_i}, 0 < q_i \leq \infty, i = 1, 2$$

Notation:

$$\alpha_j = \sup_{\nu \leq j} \frac{\varphi_2(2^{-\nu})}{\varphi_1(2^{-\nu})^\varrho}, j \in \mathbb{N}_0, \quad \varrho = \min(1, \frac{p_1}{p_2}), \quad \frac{1}{q^*} = \left(\frac{1}{q_2} - \frac{1}{q_1} \right)_+$$

Theorem 6

Then

$$\mathcal{N}_{\varphi_1,p_1,q_1}^{s_1}(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow \mathcal{N}_{\varphi_2,p_2,q_2}^{s_2}(\mathbb{R}^d)$$

if, and only if,

$$\sup_{\nu \leq 0} \frac{\varphi_2(2^{-\nu})}{\varphi_1(2^{-\nu})^\varrho} < \infty \quad \text{and} \quad \left\{ 2^{j(s_2-s_1)} \alpha_j \frac{\varphi_1(2^{-j})^\varrho}{\varphi_1(2^{-j})} \right\}_j \in \ell_{q^*}.$$

The embedding $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi_1,p_1,q_1}^{s_1}(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow \mathcal{N}_{\varphi_2,p_2,q_2}^{s_2}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is never compact.

Rem. H./Moura/Skrzypczak (2022), covers results for spaces $\mathcal{N}_{u,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Embeddings within the scales: $\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$

Preparation: consider

- ▶ $\mathcal{G}_p^{\text{loc}} = \{ \varphi : (0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, \infty) : t^{-\frac{d}{p}} \varphi(t) \geq s^{-\frac{d}{p}} \varphi(s), 0 < t \leq s < 1 \},$
- ▶ $\mathcal{G}^{\text{loc}} = \bigcup_{p>0} \mathcal{G}_p^{\text{loc}} = \lim_{p \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{G}_p^{\text{loc}}$
- ▶ $r_\varphi = \sup \{ p : \varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p^{\text{loc}} \}, \quad \varphi \in \mathcal{G}^{\text{loc}}$

Then

- ▶ $\mathcal{G}_p \subset \mathcal{G}_p^{\text{loc}}, p > 0$
- ▶ $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}^{\text{loc}} \text{ and } r_\varphi < \infty \implies \varphi \in \mathcal{G}_{r_\varphi}^{\text{loc}}$
- ▶ $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}^{\text{loc}} \text{ and } r_\varphi = \infty \implies \varphi = \text{const on } (0, 1)$

Example $0 < u, v \leq \infty, \varphi_{u,v}(t) = \begin{cases} t^{\frac{d}{u}}, & \text{if } t \leq 1, \\ t^{\frac{d}{v}}, & \text{if } t > 1, \end{cases} \quad \curvearrowright \quad r_{\varphi_{u,v}} = u$

We assume now $r_\varphi < \infty$.

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Embeddings within the scales: $\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$

$s_i \in \mathbb{R}$, $0 < p_i < \infty$, $\varphi_i \in \mathcal{G}_{p_i}$, $r_{\varphi_i} < \infty$, $0 < q_i \leq \infty$, assume the ε -condition if $q_i < \infty$, $i = 1, 2$, $\alpha_j = \sup_{\nu \leq j} \frac{\varphi_2(2^{-\nu})}{\varphi_1(2^{-\nu})^\varrho}$, $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $\varrho = \min(1, \frac{p_1}{p_2})$

Theorem 7

Then $\mathcal{E}_{\varphi_1,p_1,q_1}^{s_1}(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow \mathcal{E}_{\varphi_2,p_2,q_2}^{s_2}(\mathbb{R}^d)$

if, and only if,

$$\sup_{\nu \leq 0} \frac{\varphi_2(2^{-\nu})}{\varphi_1(2^{-\nu})^\varrho} < \infty \quad \text{and} \quad \left\{ 2^{j(s_2-s_1+\frac{d}{r_{\varphi_1}}(1-\varrho))} \alpha_j \right\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}} \in \ell_\infty,$$

where in case of $p_1 \geq p_2$ we assume, in addition, $q_1 \leq q_2$ when $s_1 = s_2$, and in case of $p_1 < p_2$, that $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \varphi_1(t) t^{-\frac{d}{r_{\varphi_1}}} \leq c < \infty$.

The embedding $\mathcal{E}_{\varphi_1,p_1,q_1}^{s_1}(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow \mathcal{E}_{\varphi_2,p_2,q_2}^{s_2}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is never compact.

Rem. H./Liu/Moura/Skrzypczak (2024), covers results for spaces $\mathcal{E}_{u,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$, more details --> talk of Zhen Liu

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Special case: Embedding of $\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$ into L_r , $r < \infty$

$s_i \in \mathbb{R}$, $i = 1, 2$, $0 < p_1 < \infty$, $1 < p_2 < \infty$, $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_{p_1}$, $r_\varphi < \infty$, $0 < q \leq \infty$, assume the ε -condition if $q < \infty$

Corollary 8

- ▶ If $p_1 \geq p_2$, then

$$\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p_1,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow L_{p_2}(\mathbb{R}^d)$$

if, and only if, $p_1 = p_2$, $\varphi(t) \sim t^{\frac{d}{p_1}}$, $t \geq 1$, and $\left\{ 2^{-j(s+\frac{d}{p_2})} \varphi(2^{-j})^{-1} \right\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}} \in \ell_\infty$ with $s > 0$ or $s = 0$ and $q \leq 2$.

- ▶ If $p_1 < p_2$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \varphi(t) t^{-\frac{d}{r_\varphi}} \leq c < \infty$, then

$$\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p_1,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow L_{p_2}(\mathbb{R}^d)$$

if, and only if, $\varphi(t) \sim t^{\frac{d}{p_1}}$, $t \geq 1$, and $s_1 \geq \frac{d}{r_\varphi} \left(1 - \frac{p_1}{p_2}\right)$.

Rem. H./Liu/Moura/Skrzypczak (2024), more details --> talk of Zhen Liu

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Special case: Embedding of $\mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$ into L_∞

$s \in \mathbb{R}$, $0 < p < \infty$, $\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$, $0 < q \leq \infty$, $\frac{1}{q'} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{q}\right)_+$, assume the ε -condition if $q < \infty$ and $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{E}$

Proposition 9

- ▶ Then $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow L_\infty(\mathbb{R}^d) \iff \{2^{-js}\varphi(2^{-j})^{-1}\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}_0} \in \ell_{q'}$.
- ▶ Assume $0 < \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t^{-\frac{d}{r_\varphi}} \varphi(t) \leq \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} t^{-\frac{d}{r_\varphi}} \varphi(t) < \infty$. Then

$$\mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d) \hookrightarrow L_\infty(\mathbb{R}^d) \iff \begin{cases} s > \frac{d}{r_\varphi}, & \text{or} \\ s = \frac{d}{r_\varphi}, & \text{and } 0 < p = r_\varphi \leq 1. \end{cases}$$

Rem. $L_\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ can be replaced by $C(\mathbb{R}^d)$,
H./Moura/Skrzypczak (2022, 2024), H./Liu/Moura/Skrzypczak (2024)

Embeddings for $\mathcal{A}_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}$? Recall $F_{p,q}^{s,\varphi} = \mathcal{E}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$. First results for $B_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}$.

--> talk of Zhen Liu

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

Da capo: First results on envelopes in $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s$

$\varphi \in \mathcal{G}_p$, $0 < p < \infty$

$$\text{recall: } \mathcal{E}_G^{\mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}}(t) \sim \begin{cases} 1 & \iff \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) > 0, \\ t^{-1/p} & \iff \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) = 0 \ \& \ \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t^{-d/p} \varphi(t) > 0, \\ \infty & \iff \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) = 0 \ \& \ \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} t^{-d/p} \varphi(t) = 0. \end{cases}$$

in H./Moura/Skrzypczak (2024) results for $\mathcal{E}_G^{\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s}(t)$, with $s \in \mathbb{R}$, $0 < q \leq \infty$ such that $\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d) \subset L_1^{\text{loc}}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, split into the cases

$$\mathcal{E}_G^{\mathcal{N}_{\varphi,p,q}^s}(t) \sim \begin{cases} \infty, & \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(t) t^{-\frac{d}{p}} = 0, \\ \mathcal{E}_G^{B_{p,q}^s}(t), & 0 < \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(t) t^{-\frac{d}{p}} \leq \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) t^{-\frac{d}{p}} < \infty, \\ \dots, & 0 < \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(t) t^{-\frac{d}{p}} \leq \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) t^{-\frac{d}{p}} = \infty, \ s = 0, \\ \dots, & 0 < \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(t) t^{-\frac{d}{p}} \leq \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) t^{-\frac{d}{p}} = \infty, \ s > 0, \end{cases}$$

with another splitting according to $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) = 0$ or $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \varphi(t) > 0$

--> almost complete results, demonstrate interplay between **smoothness** s and **local and global regularity** behaviour characterised by φ

Generalised Morrey smoothness spaces

The end

- ▶ (partly) **new scales of function spaces** $\mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $A_{p,q}^{s,\varphi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, which generalise $\mathcal{A}_{u,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $A_{p,q}^{s,\tau}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and thus $B_{p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $F_{p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$
- ▶ always: **local-global structure**, $\mathcal{A}_{\varphi,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$ built upon $\mathcal{M}_{\varphi,p}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ (Nakai 1994, Mizuhara 1991)
- ▶ applications in and motivation from **PDE** (not mentioned here)
- ▶ **better insight** into some phenomena for spaces $\mathcal{M}_{u,p}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $\mathcal{A}_{u,p,q}^s(\mathbb{R}^d)$ when $p \uparrow u$, or in $A_{p,q}^{s,\tau}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ when $\tau \downarrow 0$
- ▶ many questions still open, but a lot of **tools** (wavelets, atoms ...) already prepared
- ▶ ...
- ▶ **Dziękuję bardzo za uwagę.**
- ▶ **Thank you very much for your attention!**

Overview of Musielak-Orlicz-Sobolev spaces

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It is an overview of Musielak-Orlicz-Sobolev spaces (MOS spaces) that are Sobolev spaces defined within the frame of Musielak-Orlicz spaces. In particular they become Orlicz-Sobolev spaces or variable exponent Sobolev spaces dependently on the choice of the Musielak-Orlicz function. Recently MOS spaces have gained some interest in studies of their geometric structure as well as in applications to PDE. We will present the results on density of the space of compactly supported functions in MOS and if time allows some geometric properties of those spaces.

Density of smooth functions in Musielak-Orlicz-Sobolev spaces

Anna Kamińska

2 Early contribution by H.Hudzik

Articles by Henryk Hudzik on generalized Orlicz-Sobolev spaces, called also Musielak-Orlicz-Sobolev spaces

1. On generalized Orlicz-Sobolev space, Hudzik Henryk, *Funct. Approx. Comment. Math.* 4 (1976), 37–51. 49 citations
2. A generalization of Sobolev spaces. I, Hudzik H., *Funct. Approx. Comment. Math.* 2 (1976), 67–73. 10 citations
3. A generalization of Sobolev spaces. II Hudzik H., *Funct. Approx. Comment. Math.* 3 (1976), 77–85. 9 citations
4. On density of $C^\infty(\Omega)$ in Orlicz-Sobolev space $W_M^k(\Omega)$ for every open set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, Hudzik Henryk, *Funct. Approx. Comment. Math.* 5 (1977), 113–128. 6 citations
5. On problem of density of $C_0^\infty(\Omega)$ in generalized Orlicz-Sobolev space $W_M^k(\Omega)$ for every open set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, Hudzik H., *Comment. Math. Prace Mat.* 20 (1977/78), no. 1, 65–78. 5 citations

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6. On imbedding theorems of Orlicz-Sobolev space $W_M^k(\Omega)$ into $C^m(\Omega)$ for open, bounded, and starlike $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, Hudzik H., Comment. Math. Prace Mat. 20 (1977/78), no. 2, 341–363. 7 citations
 7. On continuity of the imbedding operation from $W_{M_1}^k(\Omega)$ into $W_{M_2}^k(\Omega)$, Hudzik Henryk, Funct. Approx. Comment. Math. 6 (1978), 111–118. 8 citations
 8. Density of $C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)$ in generalized Orlicz-Sobolev space $W_M^k(\mathbb{R}^n)$, Hudzik Henryk, Funct. Approx. Comment. Math. 7 (1979), 15–21. 8 citations
 9. The problems of separability, duality, reflexivity and of comparison for generalized Orlicz-Sobolev spaces $W_M^k(\Omega)$, Hudzik Henryk, Comment. Math. Prace Mat. 21 (1980), no. 2, 315–324.

4 Musielak-Orlicz (MO) functions

This material is a part of doctoral dissertation of Mariusz Żyluk under my supervision.

Definition

Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be a measurable subset of \mathbb{R}^d , a function $\Phi : A \times [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is called a Musielak-Orlicz function (MO function) if

- (a) for every $x \in A$, $t \mapsto \Phi(x, t)$ is convex,
- (b) for every $x \in A$, $\Phi(x, t) = 0$ if and only if $t = 0$,
- (c) for every $t \in [0, \infty)$, $x \mapsto \Phi(x, t)$ is Lebesgue measurable on A .

If Φ attains infinite values then it is called extended values *MO* function.

If for every $x \in A$, $\Phi(x, t) = \varphi(t)$, then it is Orlicz (or Young) function).

If $\varphi(t) = t^p$ for $1 \leq p < \infty$, then it is a power function.

We say that MO function Φ is **locally integrable** on A , if for every compact set $K \subset A$ and every $\lambda > 0$,

$$\int_K \Phi(x, \lambda) dx < \infty.$$

We also say that Φ satisfies the Δ_2 **condition**, a growth condition, if there exist a constant $C > 0$ and a positive function $h \in L^1(A)$, that is $\int_A h(x) dx < \infty$, such that

$$\Phi(x, 2t) \leq C\Phi(x, t) + h(x), \quad t \geq 0, \quad \text{a.a. } x \in A.$$

6 Examples of MO functions

The **weighted functions** $\Phi(x, t) = w(x)t^p$, $\Phi(x, t) = w(x)\varphi(t)$, $w(x) \geq 0$, $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, $t \geq 0$, $p \geq 1$, φ an Orlicz function; w is called a weight.

The **variable exponent** function $\Phi(x, t) = t^{p(x)}$, $t \geq 0$, $x \in A \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ where $p(x) \geq 1$ a.e. is a measurable function. It is well known that Φ satisfies condition Δ_2 if and only if the exponent $p(x)$ is essentially bounded on A .

Double phase functions,

$$\Phi_1(x, t) = t^p + a(x)t^q, \quad \Phi_2(x, t) = t^p + a(x)t^q \log(e + t),$$

$$\Phi_3(x, t) = (t - 1)_+^p + a(x)(t - 1)_+^q$$

with $1 \leq p < q < \infty$ and $a \geq 0$ a.e. Ω . The functions Φ_1 and Φ_2 are MO functions while Φ_3 satisfies properties (a) and (b) of MO function but not (c), it attains zero value for $t \in [0, 1]$.

7 Musielak-Orlicz (MO) spaces

Given a (Lebesgue) measurable set $A \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ and a MO function Φ define the functional

$$I_\Phi(f) = \int_A \Phi(x, |f(x)|) dx$$

for every $f \in L^0(A)$. It is a **convex modular** on $L^0(A)$. Then $L^\Phi(A)$ is **Musielak-Orlicz space** (MO space) associated with Φ and is defined as

$$L^\Phi(A) = \{f \in L^0(A) : \exists \lambda > 0 \ I_\Phi(\lambda f) < \infty\}.$$

Define also $E^\Phi(A)$, called the set of finite elements of $L^\Phi(A)$, by

$$E^\Phi(A) = \{f \in L^0(A) : \forall \lambda > 0 \ I_\Phi(\lambda f) \leq 1\}.$$

The following functional

$$\|f\|_\Phi = \inf \{\lambda > 0 : I_\Phi(f/\lambda) \leq 1\}$$

is the Minkowski functional of the convex set $\{f \in L^0(A) : I_\Phi(f) \leq 1\}$. It is the norm $\|\cdot\|_\Phi$ on $L^\Phi(A)$ called the **Luxemburg norm**. The space $L^\Phi(A)$ equipped with this norm is a Banach function space. Clearly $E^\Phi(A)$ is its closed subspace. If Φ is locally integrable then for every $K \subset A$ compact, the indicator function χ_K , is an element of $E^\Phi(A)$.

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open. A function $f \in L^0(\Omega)$ is said to be **locally integrable** if for any compact subset K of A

$$\int_K |f(x)| dx < \infty.$$

We denote the set of all locally integrable functions on Ω by $L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$.

Since in the further studies we will deal with the space of locally integrable functions $L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$ with open $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, recall its basic topological structure and compare them with $L^\Phi(\Omega)$. First notice that for any open subset Ω of \mathbb{R}^d there exists a family $\{K_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ of compact subsets of Ω such that

(K1) For every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we have $\overline{K_n} = K_n \subset K_{n+1}^\circ$,

(K2) $\bigcup_{n=1}^\infty K_n = \Omega$.

Conditions (K1) and (K2) imply that for any compact $K \subset \Omega$ there exists $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $K \subset K_n$. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we define a seminorm $\|\cdot\|_{K_n}$ on $L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$ via the formula

$$\|f\|_{K_n} = \|f \chi_{K_n}\|_1,$$

where $f \in L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$. We define also a function $d : L^1_{loc}(\Omega) \times L^1_{loc}(\Omega) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by the formula

$$d(f, g) = \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{1}{2^n} \frac{\|f - g\|_{K_n}}{1 + \|f - g\|_{K_n}}. \quad (1)$$

The following well known result shows that $L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$ equipped with the metric d is a **Fréchet space**. It is a complete linear metric space given by a countable family of seminorms.

Theorem

Let d be a function defined by (1). The following statements are true.

- (1) The function d is a metric on $L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$ and $(L^1_{loc}(\Omega), d)$ is a Fréchet space.
- (2) For any sequence $\{f_k\}_{k=1}^\infty \subset L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$ and any $f \in L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$, $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} d(f_k, f) = 0$ if and only if for all compact sets $K \subset \Omega$ we have

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int_K |f(x) - f_k(x)| dx = 0.$$

It follows from (2) of Theorem 2 that the topology generated by the metric d is independent of the choice of the family $\{K_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ satisfying conditions (K1) and (K2).

Theorem

Let Ω be an open subset of \mathbb{R}^d and Φ be a MO function defined on Ω . $L^\Phi(\Omega) \subset L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$ if and only if for any compact subset $K \subset \Omega$ there exists a constant $C_K > 0$ and a non-negative function $h_K \in L^1(K)$ such that for a.a. $x \in K$ and any $t \geq 0$ we have

$$t \leq C_K \Phi(x, t) + h_K(x). \quad (2)$$

Moreover, if $L^\Phi(\Omega) \subset L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$, then the inclusion map is continuous.

12 Musielak-Orlicz-Sobolev (MOS) spaces

To this end we need to recall the notion of weakly differentiable functions.

Definition

We say that a function $f \in L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$ is weakly k -differentiable if for every multi-index α with $|\alpha| \leq k$ there exists a function $f_\alpha \in L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$ such that for every $u \in C^\infty_c(\Omega)$ we have

$$\int_{\Omega} f(x) \partial^\alpha u(x) dx = (-1)^{|\alpha|} \int_{\Omega} f_\alpha(x) u(x) dx.$$

If the above identity holds, we denote $\partial^\alpha f = f_\alpha$ and say that f_α is a weak α -derivative of f .

Now we we can define the notion of a **Musielak-Orlicz-Sobolev** space

Definition

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and let Φ be a locally integrable MO function on Ω . For any $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we define the Musielak-Orlicz-Sobolev spaces (in short MOS spaces) as

$$W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega) = \{f \in L^0(\Omega) : \partial^\alpha f \in L^\Phi(\Omega), |\alpha| \leq k\},$$

$$E^{k,\Phi}(\Omega) = \{f \in L^0(\Omega) : \partial^\alpha f \in E^\Phi(\Omega), |\alpha| \leq k\}.$$

Clearly $E^{k,\Phi}(\Omega) \subset W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$. We endow $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ with the norm

$$\|f\|_{W^{k,\Phi}} = \sum_{|\alpha| \leq k} \|\partial^\alpha f\|_\Phi.$$

Let $\{f_n\}_{n=1}^\infty \subset W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ and $f \in W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$. We say that f_n converges to f in **modular** in $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ if there exists $\lambda > 0$ such that for any multi-index α with $|\alpha| \leq k$,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \Phi(x, \lambda |\partial^\alpha f_n(x) - \partial^\alpha f(x)|) dx = 0.$$

f_n converges to f in **norm** $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ if for all $\lambda > 0$ and for any multi-index α with $|\alpha| \leq k$,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \Phi(x, \lambda |\partial^\alpha f_n(x) - \partial^\alpha f(x)|) dx = 0.$$

If $\Phi(x, t) = t^{p(x)}$, where $t \geq 0$ and $p(x) \geq 1$ for a.a. $x \in \Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, is a variable exponent function, then the Musielak-Orlicz-Sobolev space is denoted by $W^{k,p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and it is called **variable exponent Sobolev space**.

CONVENTION: Any time we work with MOS spaces $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ or $E^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$, we assume that Φ is MO function locally integrable on an open subset $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$.

If Φ is locally integrable then for every $K \subset A$ compact, the indicator function χ_K , is an element of $E^\Phi(A)$.

The following theorem establishes the basic properties of MOS spaces.

Theorem

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open, Φ be a MO function on Ω such that $L^\Phi(\Omega) \subset L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The following statements hold true

- (1) $E^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ is a closed subspace of $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$.
- (2) $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ is a Banach space.
- (3) If Φ satisfies Δ_2 condition, then $E^{k,\Phi}(\Omega) = W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$.

17 standard approach for density results

Standard approach for density theorems is to construct the approximants by the means of **convolution with a mollifier**. Recall that the standard **mollifier** is the function $J : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ given by the formula

$$J(x) = Ce^{\frac{-1}{1-|x|^2}} \chi_{B(0,1)}(x),$$

where C is such that $\|J\|_1 = 1$. For any $r > 0$, we set $J_{(r)}(x) := \frac{1}{r^d} J\left(\frac{1}{r}x\right)$. For any $f \in W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ we extend it by 0 for $x \in \mathbb{R}^d \setminus \Omega$. Then for $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ we set

$$f_r(x) = (f * J_{(r)})(x)$$

and since f is a locally integrable function we get that $f_r \in C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and

$$\partial^\alpha f_r = (\partial^\alpha f) * J_{(r)}.$$

If f is compactly supported then f_r is a natural candidate for the approximant of f . Two natural questions arise: **what are conditions for f_r to be an element of $L^\Phi(\Omega)$ and for f_r to converge to f as r goes to 0?**

Let $f \in L^1_{loc}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $r > 0$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

$$\begin{aligned} |f_r(x)| &= \left| \frac{1}{r^d} \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} J\left(\frac{x-y}{r}\right) f(y) dy \right| \leq \frac{Ce^{-1}}{r^d} \int_{B(x,r)} |f(y)| dy \\ &\leq \frac{\sigma_d Ce^{-1}}{|B(x,r)|} \int_{B(x,r)} |f(y)| dy \\ &\leq \sigma_d Ce^{-1} \sup_{r>0} \frac{1}{|B(x,r)|} \int_{B(x,r)} |f(y)| dy = \sigma_d Ce^{-1} \mathcal{M}f(x), \end{aligned}$$

where \mathcal{M} is the Hardy-Littlewood maximal operator. Hence the **boundedness of that maximal operator** on $L^\Phi(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is sufficient at least for $f_r \in L^\Phi(\mathbb{R}^d)$. It turns out that it also suffices for convergence of f_r to f , when $r \rightarrow 0$ in the norm of $W^{k,\Phi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

For Orlicz space $L^\varphi(\mathbb{R}^d)$ this method works whenever φ satisfies Δ_2 condition.

Since MO space is not symmetric we cannot apply the similar approach.

There is no one universal approach to the problem of boundedness of maximal operator on $L^\Phi(\mathbb{R}^d)$. The methods lie on a spectrum between two extreme cases:

weighted L^p case, that this $\Phi(x, t) = t^p w(x)$, where $p \geq 1$ and w is a locally integrable weight $w : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow [0, \infty)$,

variable exponent case $\Phi(x, t) = t^{p(x)}$ where $p : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow [1, \infty)$ is a measurable function.

If $\Phi(x, t) = t^p w(x)$, then the maximal operator \mathcal{M} is bounded on $L^\Phi(\mathbb{R}^d)$ if and only if $p > 1$ and w is in Muckenaupt class A_p .

There is a plethora of results based on the ideas of Muckenaupt. For example A. Gogatishvili and V. Kokilashvili.

The breaking point in case $\Phi(x, t) = t^{p(x)}$ was the result by Diening who showed in 2004 that if one assumes that the exponent $p(\cdot)$ is constant outside of a compact set, strictly bigger than 1 and satisfies the **log-Hölder condition**

$$\left| \frac{1}{p(x)} - \frac{1}{p(y)} \right| \leq \frac{C}{\log(e + 1/|x - y|)}, \quad (3)$$

for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and some constant $C > 0$, then \mathcal{M} is bounded on $L^\Phi(\mathbb{R}^d) = L^{p(\cdot)}(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

Later Cruz-Uribe, Fiorenza, Martell, Perez in 2025 replaced the assumption of $p(\cdot)$ being constant outside a compact set by the **log-Hölder decay condition**

$$\left| \frac{1}{p(x)} - \frac{1}{p_\infty} \right| \leq \frac{c_2}{\log(e + |x|)},$$

$x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and some constants $c_2 > 0$, $p_\infty > 1$.

These conditions are **not necessary** for \mathcal{M} to be bounded.

The full description of boundedness of \mathcal{M} in the variable exponent case was given by Dienieng in 2005. It involves the so called generalized Muckenhaupt condition \mathcal{A} which, roughly speaking, says that a certain family of averaging operators is uniformly bounded on $L^\Phi(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

Even if the boundedness of \mathcal{M} is described by condition \mathcal{A} the condition itself is not necessarily easy to check. Hence there is a natural need for conditions that would guaranty boundedness of \mathcal{M} both on variable exponent spaces and spaces somehow similar to them, i.e. spaces given by MO functions that are essentially non-weighted.

An example of such conditions was given by Hästö in 2015 and they are conditions (A0), (A1), (A2).

On the other hand, the maximal operator approach to problem of density is restrictive in some aspects.

Boundedness of the maximal operator is, in general, **not required** for density of compactly supported smooth functions. For example $C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is dense in the Sobolev space $W^{1,1}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ but \mathcal{M} is not bounded in $L^1(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

The observation above suggests that there exist conditions **weaker** than required for boundedness of \mathcal{M} which are **sufficient** for density of smooth functions.

There are two papers that study the density of $C_C^\infty(\Omega)$ in $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ without an implicit or explicit assumption of boundedness of \mathcal{M} .

In the first paper in 2011, Benkirane, Douieb and Sidi El Vally that if Φ is locally integrable and satisfies the following condition.

$$\frac{\Phi(x, t)}{\Phi(y, t)} \leq t^{\log\left(\frac{A}{|x-y|}\right)}, \quad (4)$$

where $A > 0$, $x, y \in \Omega$ and $|x - y| < \frac{1}{2}$ and $t \geq 1$, then $C_C^\infty(\Omega)$ is dense in $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$. Moreover they require additional assumption about uniform continuity of some family of convolution operators.

The second paper in 2018 by Y. Ahmida, I. Chlebicka, P. Gwiazda, A. Youssefi.

Definition

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be an open set. Let Φ be a MO function defined on Ω . We say that Φ satisfies \mathcal{M}_2 if there exists a function $\omega : [0, 1/2] \times [1, \infty) \rightarrow [1, \infty)$ such that,

- (1) $\omega(s, \cdot)$ and $\omega(\cdot, t)$ are non-decreasing for every $s \in [0, 1/2]$, $t \geq 0$,
- (2) $\limsup_{t \rightarrow 0} \omega(t, Ct^{-d}) < \infty$ for any $C > 0$,
- (3) for every $x, y \in \Omega$ with $|x - y| \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and $t \geq 0$,

$$\Phi(x, t) \leq \omega(|x - y|, t)\Phi(y, t).$$

Under condition \mathcal{M}_2 the authors establish the density of $C_C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ in $W^{k,\Phi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

We will show the **density results under weaker** conditions than (4) or \mathcal{M}_2 . We will present that only **(A1) will be employed in characterizations of density of compactly supported functions** $C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ in $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ for open $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$.

26 Conditions (A0), (A1), (A2)

Definition

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and Φ be a MO function defined on Ω . We say that Φ satisfies (A0) if there exists $\beta \in (0, 1]$ such that for every $x \in \Omega$,

$$\beta \leq \Phi^{-1}(x, 1) \leq \frac{1}{\beta}.$$

Definition

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be an open set. Let Φ be an extended MO function defined on Ω . We say that Φ satisfies (A1) if there exist constants $\beta, \delta \in (0, 1)$ such that for all open balls B with $|B| < \delta$ and almost all $x, y \in B \cap \Omega$ we have for all $t \in \left[\Phi^{-1}(y, 1), \Phi^{-1}\left(y, \frac{1}{|B|}\right) \right]$,

$$\Phi(x, \beta t) \leq \Phi(y, t).$$

Definition

We say that ϕ satisfies (A2) if for every $s > 0$ there exist $\beta \in (0; 1]$ and $h \in L^1(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$ such that $\beta\phi^{-1}(xt) \leq \phi^{-1}(y, t)$ for almost every $x, y \in \Omega$ and every $t \in [h(x) + h(y), s]$.

Condition (A2) is sometimes called a **decay condition** (A2).

Condition \mathcal{M}_2 is in many cases stronger than (A1), and can be restrictive.

Corollary

Assume that a MO function Φ is defined on an open set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$. If Φ satisfies \mathcal{M}_2 and (A0), then it satisfies (A1).

Corollary

Assume $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ is an open and connected set. Define the function

$$\Phi(x, t) = t^{p(x)} \chi_\Omega(x) \quad \text{for every } x \in \Omega, \quad t \geq 0,$$

where $p(x) \geq 1$. If Φ satisfies \mathcal{M}_2 then $p(x) = C$ for some constant $C > 0$.

Now we compare the condition from Benkir (4) with (A1).

Theorem

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and connected. Let Φ be a MO function on Ω . Assume condition (4), that is

$$\frac{\Phi(x, t)}{\Phi(y, t)} \leq t^{\frac{A}{\log\left(\frac{1}{|x-y|}\right)}}, \quad (5)$$

where $A > 0$, $x, y \in \Omega$ and $|x - y| < \frac{1}{2}$ and $t \geq 1$. Then Φ satisfies (A1). In particular if $\Phi(x, t) = t^{p(x)}$, where $1 \leq p(x) < \infty$ a.e. on Ω and $p(\cdot)$ is log-Hölder continuous (3), then Φ satisfies (A1).

In the case of **variable exponent space** conditions (A0), (A1) and (A2) are natural.

Let $\Phi(x, t) = t^{p(x)}$, $p(x) \geq 1$. Then Φ satisfies (A0).

The variable exponent MO function satisfies (A1) if and only if $p(x)$ satisfies the log-Hölder condition.

The variable exponent MO function satisfies (A2) if and only if $p(x)$ satisfies the log-Hölder decay condition.

Lemma

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and Φ be a MO function defined on Ω . Assume that Φ satisfies (A1) and $\beta, \delta \in (0, 1)$ are the constants from this condition. For any open ball B with $|B| < \delta$ and almost all $x \in B \cap \Omega$, the following statements hold true.

(1)

$$\beta \frac{1}{|B \cap \Omega|} \int_{B \cap \Omega} \frac{1}{\Phi^{-1}\left(y, \frac{1}{|B|}\right)} dy \leq \frac{1}{\Phi^{-1}\left(x, \frac{1}{|B|}\right)} \leq \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{1}{|B \cap \Omega|} \int_{B \cap \Omega} \frac{1}{\Phi^{-1}\left(y, \frac{1}{|B|}\right)} dy.$$

(2)

$$\frac{\beta}{2} \frac{1}{|B|} \int_{B \cap \Omega} \frac{1}{\Phi^{-1}\left(y, \frac{1}{|B \cap \Omega|}\right)} dy \leq \|\chi_{B \cap \Omega}\|_{\Phi} \leq \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{1}{|B \cap \Omega|} \int_{B \cap \Omega} \frac{1}{\Phi^{-1}\left(y, \frac{1}{|B|}\right)} dy.$$

(3)

(3)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{|B \cap \Omega|} \int_{B \cap \Omega} \frac{1}{\Phi^{-1}\left(y, \frac{1}{|B \cap \Omega|}\right)} dy &\leq \int_{B \cap \Omega} (\Phi^*)^{-1}\left(y, \frac{1}{|B \cap \Omega|}\right) dy \\ &\leq \frac{2}{|B \cap \Omega|} \int_{B \cap \Omega} \frac{1}{\Phi^{-1}\left(y, \frac{1}{|B \cap \Omega|}\right)} dy. \end{aligned}$$

(4)

$$\begin{aligned} \beta \frac{1}{|B \cap \Omega|} \int_{B \cap \Omega} (\Phi^*)^{-1}\left(y, \frac{1}{|B|}\right) dy &\leq (\Phi^*)^{-1}\left(x, \frac{1}{|B|}\right) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{1}{|B \cap \Omega|} \int_{B \cap \Omega} (\Phi^*)^{-1}\left(y, \frac{1}{|B|}\right) dy. \end{aligned}$$

The usefulness of condition (A1) comes from the fact that it lets us control norms of characteristic functions of balls that are in $L^\Phi(\Omega)$.

Lemma

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and Φ be a MO function defined on Ω . Assume that Φ satisfies (A0) or (A1). Then for any compact set $K \subset \Omega$ we have $\chi_K \in L^\Phi(\Omega)$ and $\chi_K \in L^{\Phi^*}(\Omega)$.

Theorem

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and Φ be a MO function defined on Ω . Assume that Φ satisfies (A0) or (A1). Then $L^\Phi(\Omega) \subset L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$.

34 Density of C_c^∞ in $W^{k,\Phi}$

The problem of density of smooth functions in Musielak-Orlicz-Sobolev spaces turns out to be more subtle than that of Musielak-Orlicz spaces. In the context of MOS spaces we do not only need to be able to approximate functions in $L^\Phi(\Omega)$ but also we need to have control over the size of the derivatives of the approximants. In particular, the method that worked for approximating a function in $L^\Phi(\Omega)$ will not work for functions in $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$. It is based on approximating characteristic functions of compact sets which are not weakly differentiable, hence cannot belong to $W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$.

Recall, in order to smooth out a function, we will use the **standard mollifier**, which is the function $J : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ given by the formula

$$J(x) = Ce^{\frac{-1}{1-|x|^2}} \chi_{B(0,1)}(x),$$

where $C^{-1} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} e^{\frac{-1}{1-|x|^2}} \chi_{B(0,1)}(x) dx$. For any $r > 0$, set $J_{(r)}(x) := \frac{1}{r^d} J\left(\frac{1}{r}x\right)$. For any locally integrable f and any $r > 0$ we define

$$f_r(x) = (f * J_{(r)})(x).$$

Lemma

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and Φ be a MO function defined on Ω . Assume that Φ satisfies (A1). If $f \in L^\Phi(\Omega)$ then there exists a constant $C' > 1$ such that for any $x \in \Omega$ and $r > 0$ with $|B(x, r)| < \delta$, and for almost all $z \in B(x, r) \cap \Omega$, we have

$$|f_r(x)| \leq C' \Phi^{-1}\left(z, \frac{1}{|B(x, r)|}\right) \|f\|_\Phi.$$

Theorem

(*) Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and Φ be a MO function defined on Ω satisfying (A1) condition. For any $N \in \mathbb{N}$ let $f_0, \dots, f_N \in L^\Phi(\Omega)$ be such that $\text{esssupp} f_i \subset \Omega$ is compact, $f_i \neq 0$ a.e., for $i = 0, \dots, N$. Let β be the constant from the condition (A1) and C'' be the constant from Lemma above. There exists a sequence $\{r_n\}_{n=1}^\infty \subset (0, \infty)$ such that for every $i = 0, \dots, N$,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \Phi\left(x, \frac{\beta}{4C''} \frac{|f_i(x) - (f_i)_{r_n}(x)|}{\|f_i\|_\Phi}\right) dx = 0,$$

where $(f_i)_{r_n}(x) = (f_i * J_{(r_n)})(x)$ and $C'' = \frac{4C'}{\beta}$. In particular $\{(f_i)_{r_n}\}_{n=1}^\infty$ converges to f_i in modular for all $i = 0, \dots, N$.

We will also need the following approximation result in $E^\Phi(\Omega)$.

Theorem

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and Φ be a MO function defined on Ω . If Φ is locally integrable then $C_c^\infty(\Omega) \cap E^\Phi(\Omega)$ is dense in $E^\Phi(\Omega)$. In other words $\overline{C_c^\infty(\Omega) \cap E^\Phi(\Omega)} = E^\Phi(\Omega)$.

Now we have the tools to prove the concrete results in MOS spaces. The next Theorem and Corollary provide sufficient conditions to approximate compactly supported functions $f \in E^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ with smooth, compactly supported functions as long as the support of f is a subset of Ω . The only extra assumption put on Φ is condition (A1). Thus they generalize [Theorem 6.4.7 from Hasto book](#) where one uses assumptions (A0), (A1) and (A2) on Φ .

Theorem

(**) Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and Φ be a MO function locally integrable on Ω and satisfying the (A1) condition. Let β and C'' be the constants from condition (A1) and Theorem (*). Let $f \in E^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ be such that $\text{esssupp} f \subset \Omega$ is compact. Then there exists a sequence $\{r_m\}_{m=1}^\infty \subset (0, \infty)$ such that, for every multi-index α with $|\alpha| \leq k$,

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \Phi \left(x, \frac{\beta |\partial^\alpha f_{r_m}(x) - \partial^\alpha f(x)|}{12C'' \|f\|_{W^{k,\Phi}}} \right) dx = 0.$$

Corollary

Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be open and Φ be a MO function defined on Ω satisfying both (A1) and Δ_2 condition. For every compactly supported $f \in W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$ such that $\text{esssupp} f \subset \Omega$ there exists a sequence of smooth functions $\{u_n\}_{n=1}^\infty \subset C_C^\infty(\Omega)$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|f - u_n\|_{W^{k,\Phi}} = 0.$$

Proof.

By the fact that Φ satisfies Δ_2 condition and Theorem 6 (3) we have that $E^{k,\Phi}(\Omega) = W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$. For any $f \in W^{k,\Phi}(\Omega)$, by Theorem (**), there exists a sequence of positive numbers $\{r_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ such that for any multi-index α with $|\alpha| \leq k$ we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\Omega} \Phi \left(x, \frac{\beta |\partial^\alpha f_{r_n}(x) - \partial^\alpha f(x)|}{12C'' \|f\|_{W^{k,\Phi}}} \right) dx = 0.$$

Since Φ satisfies Δ_2 condition, we conclude that for any multi-index α with $|\alpha| \leq k$ we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\partial^\alpha (f - f_{r_n})\|_{\Phi} = 0.$$

In view of $\|f - f_{r_n}\|_{W^{k,\Phi}} = \sum_{|\alpha| \leq k} \|\partial^\alpha (f - f_{r_n})\|_{\Phi}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we get

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|f - f_{r_n}\|_{W^{k,\Phi}} = 0. \text{ Setting } u_n = f_{r_n}, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|f - u_n\|_{W^{k,\Phi}} = 0. \quad \square$$

Let $s : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow [0, 1]$, be a **smooth compactly supported function** such that

$$s(x) = 1 \quad \text{for } |x| \leq 1 \quad \text{and} \quad s(x) = 0 \quad \text{for } |x| > 2.$$

For $R > 0$ define $s_R(x) = s\left(\frac{x}{R}\right)$. For any $f \in L^0(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and $R > 0$ we define the **smooth cutoff** of f as

$$f_R(x) = f(x)s_R(x).$$

Theorem

For any $f \in W^{k,\Phi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $f_R = fs_R$ converges in modular in $W^{k,\Phi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ to f as $R \rightarrow \infty$, that is there is $\lambda > 0$,

$$I_\Phi(\lambda(f - f_R)) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as} \quad R \rightarrow \infty.$$

In the case of $\Omega = \mathbb{R}^d$ we can use Theorem (***) and the smooth cutoff functions to establish the modular density of compactly supported smooth functions in $E^{k,\Phi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$. In particular, if Φ satisfies Δ_2 condition we establish density of $C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ in $W^{k,\Phi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

Theorem

Let Φ be a MO function defined on \mathbb{R}^d satisfying (A1). Then for every $f \in E^{k,\Phi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ there exists a sequence $\{f_n\}_{n=1}^\infty \subset C_C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and a constant $\lambda' > 0$ such that for any multi-index α with $|\alpha| \leq k$ we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \Phi(x, \lambda' |\partial^\alpha (f_n(x) - f(x))|) dx = 0.$$

In particular if Φ satisfies Δ_2 condition then $\|f - f_n\|_\Phi = 0$, and so $C_C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is dense in $W^{k,\Phi}(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

Corollary

Let $\Phi(x, t) = t^{p(x)}$, $t \geq 0$, $p(x) \geq 1$, $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, be a variable exponent function satisfying log-Hölder condition. Then for every $f \in E^{k,p(\cdot)}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ there exists a sequence $\{f_n\}_{n=1}^\infty \subset C_C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and a constant $\lambda' > 0$ such that for any multi-index α with $|\alpha| \leq k$ we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \Phi(x, \lambda' |\partial^\alpha (f_n(x) - f(x))|) dx = 0.$$

In particular if Φ satisfies Δ_2 condition, that is the exponent $p(x)$ is essentially bounded on \mathbb{R}^d , then $C_C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is dense in $W^{k,p(\cdot)}(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

The above result is true for $L^1(\mathbb{R}^d)$; we did not use maximal operator in the proofs.

Density of restrictions of functions from $C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ to Ω in $W^{1,\phi}(\Omega)$.

For any $x = (x_1, \dots, x_d) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ we define $x' \in \mathbb{R}^{d-1}$ to be

$$x' = (x_1, \dots, x_{d-1}).$$

Moreover for $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ such that $x_d = 0$, we have that $x' = 0$ in \mathbb{R}^{d-1} . With a slight abuse of notation we write

$$x = (x', x_d).$$

Recall that for $y \in \mathbb{R}^d$, $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and $r > 0$, $Q(y, r)$ is a cube with center y and side length $2r$. For a fixed $d \in \mathbb{N}$ we will need both cubes in \mathbb{R}^d and in \mathbb{R}^{d-1} . For a fixed $(y', y_d) = y \in \mathbb{R}^d$ we denote the cube in \mathbb{R}^{d-1} , centered at y' and of side length $2r$ as $Q_{d-1}(y', r)$.

We will also need the notion of *rigid motion* on \mathbb{R}^d . A rigid motion on \mathbb{R}^d is the map $T : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ of the form

$$T = R + c,$$

where R is a rotation in \mathbb{R}^d and $c \in \mathbb{R}^d$. For a fixed rigid motion T and a point $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ we define the *local coordinates* of x as the vector y , where $y := T(x)$.

For $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and an open subset $U \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, by $C^m(U)$ we denote all complex valued m -times continuously differentiable functions defined on U .

Definition

Let U, V be open subsets of \mathbb{R}^d and $\mathcal{R} : U \rightarrow V$ be a map. For a fixed $m \in \mathbb{N}$ we say that \mathcal{R} belongs to $C^m(U, V)$, if for $i = 1, \dots, d$ there exist functions $\varrho_i \in C^m(U)$ such that for $x \in U$, $\mathcal{R}(x) = (\varrho_1(x), \dots, \varrho_d(x))$.

Now we can make a precise definition of a set with regular boundary.

Definition

Given an open set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ we say that boundary of Ω is of class C^1 if for every $x_0 \in \partial\Omega$ there exist an open neighborhood U of x_0 , a rigid motion T , a number $r > 0$ and $f \in C^1(Q_{d-1}(0, r))$ such that

$$T(x_0) = 0,$$

$$T(\Omega \cap U) = \{y \in Q(0, r) : y_d > f(y')\}.$$

Theorem

Let Ω be an open set in \mathbb{R}^d such that its boundary is of class C^1 . Let Φ be a MO function on Ω satisfying both (A1) and Δ_2 properties. Then the set of restrictions of functions from $C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^d)$ to Ω is dense in $W^{1,\Phi}(\Omega)$.

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Henryk Hudzik (1945–2019). With memories and appreciation.

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Henryk Hudzik was my friend and we wrote 8 joint papers in the years 1990–2004. So I feel obliged to tell about him and a little about his mathematics. First, I will present the history of Hudzik's life. I will also recall his scientific career with a doctorate in 1977, a habilitation in 1986 and a professorship from 1992. He worked at the University of Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań in the years 1972–2015. Hudzik's research interests include functional analysis, in particular: the theory of function spaces, Banach lattices, the geometry of Banach spaces and its applications, operator theory, metric fixed point theory. The number of his publications includes over 220 research papers, 3 chapters in monographs and several popular science and review papers. I will mention three of his most important papers, in my opinion.

In the years 1986–2020 I worked outside Poland, but we met many times in Poznań and other countries, which I will show in many joint photos.

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Henryk Hudzik (1945–2019).

With memories and appreciation

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Fig. 1. Henryk Hudzik

Why will I talk about Henryk Hudzik (briefly HH)?

Because he was my friend and we wrote 9 joint papers in the years
1990–2004.

**So I feel obliged to tell you about him and a little about
his mathematics.**

We met several times in Poznań and other countries, which I will show
on many joint photos.

A. Parents, youth, schools and university

Henryk Teodor Hudzik (1945–2019)

- was born on 16 March **1945** in Kelcin Hawel¹, Germany.
- died on 2 March **2019** in Poznań.

Fig. 2. Henryk Hudzik in 1972

A1. Parents and sisters

Marcin Hudzik (6 XI 1911 Mielcuchy – 1 V 1993 Mielcuchy) and
Jadwiga Hudzik née Pacyna (19 X 1914 Klon Zadki – 5 I 1958 Ostrzeszów).

Henryk's parents were deported to Germany to work in 1943, and he was born there in 1945.

In June 1945, the parents returned to Poland and settled in Mielcuchy, Ostrzeszów district and 143 km south-east of the regional capital Poznań.

His parents worked on a 5-hectare farm.

Henryk had 2 sisters:

- Barbara Danuta Hudzik, married name Wyrwas (born 1946).
- Wanda Hudzik, married name Bednarek (born 1953).

¹Should be Ketzin with official name Ketzin/Havel, town in Germany situated on the river Havel, 17 km northwest of Potsdam, and 40 km west of Berlin.

A2. Schools and university

1952–1958 Primary School in Mielcuchy

1958–1960 Two years break after the death of his mother in 1958
to help his father on the farm and in raising his two younger sisters

1960–1963 Basic Vocational School in Świebodzice.
He starts learning to become a carpenter

Fig. 3. Hudzik (first from the right) learned to be a furniture carpenter

1963–1967 Industrial and Pedagogical Technical Secondary School
for graduates of vocational schools in Łomża

Five more photos of Henryk from his school years:

Fig. 4. Hudzik, boy

Fig. 5. 20 IX 1963. School ID of Hudzik

Fig. 6. Singing Hudzik

Fig. 7. Hudzik with his school colleagues

Fig. 8. Hudzik's performance in a cabaret

1967: In those years in Poland, there was an entrance examination to be admitted to higher education. Entrance examination to the University of Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań included mathematics and Russian language in HH case.

Interesting fact – one of the tasks in mathematics was the following (Henryk solved it correctly). Solve the system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} x + xy + y = 19, \\ x^2y + xy^2 = 84. \end{cases}$$

1967–1972: University of Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań (UAM)

15 VI 1972: Master's examination (conducted in Polish).

Examiners: Włodzimierz Staś, Julian Musielak and Andrzej Alexiewicz

Questions: 1. Fréchet spaces, 2. Dual space, weak convergence, 3. Countably modular spaces, 4. Taking limits under the integral sign, 5. Fourier transform and convolution, 6. Quotient groups.

Master thesis: *Modular and Countably Modular Spaces* under supervision of J. Musielak.

Henryk Hudzik received his degree with honors in 1972.

Fig. 9. 7 Dec. 1972. Graduate Diploma in Mathematics, theoretical section

B. Private life 1972–2005

Wedding: 2 April 1972 with Halina Bożena Hudzik née Bachor
(3 II 1948–3 VIII 2001)

Fig. 10. Halina Bachor

Fig. 11. 2 IV 1972. Wedding photo

5 V 1980: daughter Anna Hudzik was born (married name Dankowska)

Fig. 12. Henryk with his wife and daughter

Anna's children (Henryk's grandchildren):

Jan Dankowski (born on 16 VI 2010),
Maria Dankowska (born on 12 I 2012).

Fig. 13. 2016. Henryk with grandson Jan

Fig. 14. Henryk with Anna and Maria

3 VIII 2001: After a 26-year battle with rheumatoid arthritis [reumatoidalne zapalenie stawów], Henryk's first wife died.

Fig. 15. Henryk with his second wife and grandson and granddaughter

5 XI 2005: Henryk married Maria Hudzik née Kaczmarek (born in 1956).
The wedding took place in Rogalin.

Fig. 16. Wedding ceremony

Fig. 17. Henryk with Maria

Fig. 18. Henryk with Maria in Rogalin

Hobbies and interests of HH: music, sports, gardening.

C. Scientific work and career

1 IX 1972 – 1 II 1974: assistant at the Institute of Mathematics of the University of Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań (abbreviated UAM)

1 II 1974 – 1 II 1977: PhD student, Doctoral Study at the Institute of Mathematics of Adam Mickiewicz University

• 18 II 1977: PhD thesis, *On generalized Orlicz–Sobolev spaces*, Adam Mickiewicz University, supervisor **Julian Musielak**

Referees: Tadeusz **Jędryka** (Bydgoszcz) and Aleksander **Waszak** (Poznań)

Public defense: 29 January 1977

Fig. 19. Doctoral diploma from 3 March 1978

Hudzik's doctoral thesis was written in 1976 and consisted of 114 pages.

He considered generalized Orlicz–Sobolev spaces

$$W_M^k(\Omega) = \{f \in L_M(\Omega) : D^\alpha f \in L_M(\Omega) \text{ for all multi-indices } \alpha, |\alpha| \leq k\},$$

where $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $L_M(\Omega)$ is a generalized Orlicz space generated by the continuous, convex N-function $M(t, u)$ with a parameter t .

Hudzik proved that this space is a Banach space and has some properties similar to classical Sobolev spaces $W_p^k(\Omega)$.

31 V **1977–1987**: Associate Professor at UAM (adiunkt in Polish).

24 May **1983** Orlicz’s 80th birthday in the Institute of Mathematics Polish Academy of Sciences, Branch in Poznań:

Fig. 20. Orlicz’s 80th birthday. *Photo by Lech Maligranda*

Fig. 21. Orlicz's 80th birthday. *Photo from Lech Maligranda's collection*

• 17 VI 1986: Habilitation: *Geometric and topological properties of Orlicz and Musielak–Orlicz spaces*, University of Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań.

Hudzik's scientific achievements at that time included 33 papers, 11 of which were part of his habilitation thesis.

The main goal of Hudzik's research was to determine the conditions under which Orlicz spaces of real (complex)-valued or vector-valued functions and their generalizations, often called Musielak–Orlicz spaces, have certain geometric properties. These properties concern the convexity of unit spheres in the considered spaces.

Hudzik systematically studied Orlicz and Musielak–Orlicz spaces (referred here as O.M.O. spaces), focusing on the following geometric properties: strict convexity, uniform convexity, uniform non-squareness, local uniform convexity, B-convexity (and more precisely the property “to be a uniformly non- $l_n^{(1)}$ space”) and other related geometric properties.

Referees: Lech **Drewnowski** (Poznań), Kazimierz **Goebel** (Lublin), Władysław **Orlicz** (Poznań), Kondagunta **Sundaresan** (Cleveland, Ohio).

Important conclusions from the review of Dr. Henryk Hudzik's habilitation thesis and the assessment of his scientific achievements (chronologically):

L. Drewnowski (21 December 1985):

Dr. Henryk Hudzik's habilitation thesis and all his scientific publications prove his independent creative contribution to functional analysis. (...) I consider the results obtained by him to be his important original contribution to the theory of the Banach space of measurable functions, also proving his ability to conduct independent systematic scientific research on well-selected and current issues.

K. Sundaesan (23 December 1985):

I consider that the entire work of Hudzik is interesting and important. The proofs and methods adopted in resolving the problems discussed in his papers are original and extremely nontrivial. His work has settled several problems that arise in the study of $O.M.O.$ spaces and which have not appeared in the literature in any form.

K. Goebel (10 April 1986):

It can undoubtedly be said that the candidate's mathematical talent is developing evenly and properly. (...) I have no doubt that Dr. Hudzik is a mature mathematician.

W. Orlicz (29 April 1986):

Dr. Henryk Hudzik's habilitation thesis and all his scientific publications prove his independent creative contribution to functional analysis. He also stated that Dr. Hudzik is an outstanding specialist in the geometry of Banach space and that his works are widely cited in the literature, and the results are interesting and difficult.

The habilitation lecture (16 May 1986): "Sobolev spaces" was assessed positively and the chairman of the meeting of the Council of the Faculty of Mathematics and Physics of the Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Dean Mirosław Krzyśko, ordered a vote to award Hudzik the degree of habilitated doctor of mathematical sciences in the field of mathematical analysis. It was unanimously supported by 31 votes.

Fig. 22. Habilitation diploma from 25 September 1987

- **1986:** Henryk Hudzik received the Stefan Banach Main Prize of the Polish Mathematical Society for 1986 for his scientific achievements.
- **1987–1990:** Position of Associated Professor at UAM (docent in Polish) and a half position at the Institute of Mathematics of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Branch in Poznań (1987–1989).
- **1987–2015:** head of the Department of the Theory of Function Spaces
- **1991–1996:** Position of Professor of the University of Adam Mickiewicz.

Fig. 23. 8 X 1991, Caracas, Plaza Venezuela

Fig. 24. 10 X 1991, Caracas, Sabana Grande

Fig. 25. 11 X 1991. Colonia Tovar – town of Venezuela in Aragua state.

It is located about 65 km west of Caracas. Colonia Tovar is famous for the fact that mostly people with German roots live here.

From the left: Hans Heinig, **Henryk Hudzik** and Lech Maligranda.

Photo from Lech Maligranda's collection

Fig. 26. 18 X 1991. IVIC=Instituto Venezolano de Investigaciones Cientificas
 [The Venezuelan Institute for Scientific Research] in Caracas,
 located near San Antonio de los Altos, a suburban town.
 From the left: Lech Maligranda, **Henryk Hudzik** and Carlos Finol.

Photo from Lech Maligranda's collection

- **1991–1994**: Procedure for obtaining the academic title of professor.
Referees: Julian Musielak (Poznań), Roman Ger (Katowice) and Stefan Rolewicz (Warszawa).
- 14 Jan. **1994**: HH obtained the academic **title of professor of mathematical sciences** (after some strange decisions in 1993).
 It was awarded to him by the President of Poland – Lech Wałęsa.
- **1993–1994**: visiting professorship at the University of Memphis, Memphis, TN, USA (20 VIII 1993–19 VIII 1994).

- **1995–2001**: HH was employed at UAM and also at the Institute of Mathematics of the **Poznań University of Technology**.

Fig. 27. Luleå, May 1996, Luleå University of Technology, Sweden.
 From the left: Mieczysław Mastyło, Anna Kamińska, **Henryk Hudzik**,
 Anna Klisińska and Lech Maligranda. *Photo from Lech Maligranda's collection*

- **1997–2015**: HH worked as a full professor (profesor zwyczajny in Polish).
- **1990–1993**: vice-dean of the Faculty of Mathematics and Physics at the Adam Mickiewicz University (student affairs).
- **2002–2005**: vice-dean of the Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics at the Adam Mickiewicz University (scientific affairs).
- **1975–2019**: Member of the **Polish Mathematical Society** (president of Poznań section 1989–1992).

Fig. 28. Poznań, September 1998, visit to Hudzik's house.
 From the left: Mikio Kato (Japan), LM, Patryk Maligranda, Bożena Maligranda,
Henryk Hudzik, Anna Hudzik-daughter of HH, and Keiko Kato

Fig. 29. Poznań, 15 March 2001, University of Adam Mickiewicz.
 Conversation with Hudzik after seminar

Fig. 30. Poznań, 17 March 2001, meeting after my lecture at UAM, “Type and cotype and convexity properties of certain Banach spaces”.

From the left: Witold Wnuk, Zbigniew Palka, Marek Nawrocki, Lech Drewnowski, **Henryk Hudzik** and Lech Maligranda

Fig. 31. Kitakyushu, 2 October 2003. Conference in Japan.

Conference “*Banach and Function Spaces*”, Kyushu Institute of Technology, 2–4 October 2003, Kitakyushu².

From the left: Thomas Kühn (Leipzig), **Henryk Hudzik** (Poznań), Fernando Cobos (Madrid), Luz M. Fernández-Cabrera (Madrid) and Lech Maligranda (Luleå). *Photo from Lech Maligranda’s collection*

²Together with Mikio Kato and Tomonari Suzuki (organizing since 2009) from Kitakyushu, we organized the “*Banach and Function Spaces*’ conference in Japan five times in 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015. The conference proceedings were published by Yokohama Publisher in the form of four books “*Banach and Function Spaces*” in years: 2004 (393 pp.), 2008 (467 pp.), 2011 (484 pp.), 2014 (456 pp.) and “*Banach and Function Spaces V*”, in the journal (Edited by M. Kato, L. Maligranda and T. Suzuki) “*Linear and Nonlinear Analysis*”, 2 (2016), no. 2, 175–327 and 3 (2017), no. 1, 1–148.

Fig. 32. Kitakyushu, 3 October 2003. Conference in Japan.

Conference “*Banach and Function Spaces*”, Kyushu Institute
of Technology, 2–4 October 2003, Kitakyushu.

First row from the left: Akihiko Miyachi (Tokyo), Thomas Kühn (Leipzig),
Luz M. Fernández-Cabrera (Madrid), Fernando Cobos (Madrid),
Henryk Hudzik (Poznań), Lech Maligranda (Luleå) and Mikio Kato (Kitakyushu).

Photo from Lech Maligranda's collection

● **22 IV 2005: scientific session on the occasion of the 60th anniversary of the birth of Professor Henryk Hudzik.**

It was prepared by the Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science of Adam Mickiewicz University and a group of the Professor's colleagues and students.

Scientific achievements were presented by professors: Julian Musielak, Mieczysław Mastyło, Ryszard Płuciennik, Marek Wiśła and lecture on the life and work of HH was given by Magdalena Jaroszevska.

Fig. 33. Poznań, 22 April 2005. 60th birthday of HH at UAM.

From the left: **Henryk Hudzik**, Wiesław Pleśniak, Mieczysław Mastyło and Julian Musielak

Fig. 34. Poznań, 22 April 2005. 60th birthday of HH at UAM.

From the left: Lech Drewnowski, Witold Wnuk and **Henryk Hudzik**

• **1 IX 2005–2019: HH worked in parallel with his employment at UAM in the State University of Applied Sciences in Płock** [Państwowa Wyższa Szkoła Zawodowa w Płocku].

It was a full-time job, and HH commuted by train from Poznań to Płock with a change in Kutno on Thursdays for the whole day. **It took 17 hours.** HH would get up at 4 a.m. and come back at 9 p.m. In Płock he had 6 hours of classes. **Hard work!!!**

- **2007–2014:** Editor in chief of mathematical journal *Commentationes Mathematicae*.
- Additionally, he was a member of the editorial board of 17 scientific journals.

Fig. 35. Chiang Mai, July 2007. Conference in Thailand – conference trip.

The 8th International Conference on Fixed Point Theory and Its Applications,
16–22 July 2007.

From the left: Lech Maligranda, Kazimierz Goebel and **Henryk Hudzik**

- HH received the Award of the Minister of Science and Higher Education three times (1978, 1981, 1986) and the Award of the Minister of National Education twice (1990, 1999).

Fig. 36. Harbin, July 2007. Conference in China.
*International Workshop on Banach Spaces, Operator Theory and Applications
to Nonlinear Analysis, 25–28 July 2007, Harbin*

Fig. 37. Harbin, July 2007. Conference in China.
From the left: Yunan Cui, **Henryk Hudzik**, Chen Shutao and Lech Maligranda

Fig. 38. Harbin, July 2007. Conference in China.
From the left: Mikio Kato, Lech Maligranda and **Henryk Hudzik**

Fig. 39. Saint Petersburg, September 2010. Conference in Russia.
“The International Conference Banach Spaces Geometry”, 5–12 September 2010.
From the left: Karol Leśnik, Radosław Kaczmarek, Agata Panfil, Aleksander Usachev,
Paweł Kolwicz, Ryszard Pluciennik and **Henryk Hudzik**

- 15 V 2013: HH was awarded the Knight's Cross of the Order of Polonia Restituta [Krzyż Kawalerski Orderu Odrodzenia Polski]

Fig. 40. Leiden, July 2013. Conference “*Positivity VII*”, 22–26 July 2013. Where is Hudzik?
Third from the right in the first row

Fig. 41. Leiden, July 2013. Conference “*Positivity VII*”.
From the left: Ryszard Pluciennik, **Henryk Hudzik** and Marek Wisła

D. PhD students of Henryk Hudzik

During his extensive scientific career, prof. Hudzik supervised 16 PhDs in mathematics, including 6 from outside Poland:

- 1. Ghassan **Alherk**, Syria (1991)
- 2. Małgorzata **Doman** (II 1994))
- 3. Zenon **Zbąszyniak** (XI 1994)
- 4. Yunan **Cui**, China 1 (1995)
- 5. Paweł **Foralewski** (1997)
- 6. Lifang **Liu**, China 2 (2001)
- 7. Wojciech **Kowalewski** (2001)
- 8. Agata **Narloch** (2002)
- 9. Yuwen **Wang**, China 3 (2003)
- 10. Karol **Właźlak** (2004)
- 11. Lucjan **Szymaszkiewicz** (V 2005)
- 12. Xinbo **Liu**, China 4 (XII 2005)
- 13. Alicja **Szymaszkiewicz** (I 2007)
- 14. Radosław **Kaczmarek** (IX 2007)
- 15. Hajfeng **Ma**, China 5 (2012)
- 16. Tadeusz **Chawziuk** (2018)

E. 12 conferences “Function Spaces”, 1986–2018

The International Conference on “Function Spaces” has a 38-year tradition. Each conference was devoted to various aspects of Theory of Function Spaces, Geometry of Banach Spaces, Operator Theory on Function Spaces, Interpolation Theory, Approximation Theory and Theory of Vector Measures.

The previous 12 conferences “Function Spaces” were held in:

- Poznań 6: $\overbrace{1986}^1, \overbrace{1989}^2, \overbrace{1992}^3, \overbrace{1998}^5, \overbrace{2003}^7, \overbrace{2012}^{10}$
- Zielona Góra 2: $\overbrace{1995}^4, \overbrace{2015}^{11}$
- Wrocław: $\overbrace{2001}^6$
- Będlewo – Banach Conference Center: $\overbrace{2006}^8$
- Kraków 2: $\overbrace{2009}^9, \overbrace{2018}^{12}$

J. Musielak wrote in 2015 about Hudzik’s participation in organizing conferences “Function Spaces” from the beginning:

For some time an idea had been brewing to make Poznań a venue for systematic international science conferences. (...) A deep involvement of Henryk Hudzik in the organizing activities is a key element here. Let me say a few words about “Function Spaces II”, which was held in late August and early September of 1989. Without the assistance and dedication of professor by then Henryk Hudzik and many other colleagues this conference could not possibly have taken place. It was held at a time of complete economic chaos accompanying the political transformation: Poland was just leaving the “socialist bloc” in Europe.

It will be interesting to see photos from several “Function Spaces” conferences, where Henryk Hudzik is visible.

Fig. 42. The First International Conference “Function Spaces”, Poznań, 25–30 August 1986. From the left: Wang Yuwen, Wang Tingfu, Wu Congxin, Julian Musielak, **Henryk Hudzik**, Helena Musielak, Ryszard Grzaślewicz and Liu Tiefu

Fig. 43. The Second International Conference “Function Spaces”, Poznań, 28 August–2 September, 1989. Henryk Hudzik is talking with Aleksander Pełczyński

Fig. 44. Poznań, 31 August 1989, "Function Spaces II".
From the left: **Henryk Hudzik**, Władysław Orlicz and Julian Musielak.
Photo by Lech Maligranda

Fig. 45. "Function Spaces VI", 3–8 September 2001, Wrocław.

Fig. 46. "Function Spaces VI", 3–8 September 2001, Wrocław.

Fig. 47. Poznań, 20 July 2003. Participants of the conference “The Władysław Orlicz Centenary Conference and Function Spaces VII”, 20–25 July 2009, Poznań.

Fig. 48. Poznań, 20 July 2003. Participants of the conference “The Władysław Orlicz Centenary Conference and Function Spaces VII”, 20–25 July 2009, Poznań.

From the left: N. Lindenstrauss, L. Drewnowski, J. Musielak, R. Pinkus, A. Pinkus, nn, D. Pallaschke, J. Lindenstrauss, J. Kurzweil, L.-E. Persson, B. Sims, L. Skrzypczak, J. Diestel, N. Kalton, A. Kamińska, L. Maligranda, **H. Hudzik**, F. Sukochev, P. Domański, B. Bojarski, S. Konyagin, H. König, F. Hernandez, B. Kashin, T. Iwaniec, J. Appell, C. Sbordone, A. Rozhdzestvensky, G. Bennett, Z. Ciesielski, A. Pelczyński, P. Wojtaszczyk, Z. Palka.

President of the Republic of Poland, Mr. Aleksander Kwaśniewski, has taken honorary patronage over “*The Władysław Orlicz Centenary Conference and Function Spaces VII*”. So 160 participants came to the conference. In gratitude, on 10 March 2004, the President received a Medal named after Władysław Orlicz at the Presidential Palace in Warsaw.

Fig. 49. Warszawa, 10 March 2004. Ceremony at the Presidential Palace in Warsaw. From the left: Julian Musielak, Lech Drewnowski, Aleksander Pelczyński, Zbigniew Ciesielski, Stanisław Janeczko, Barbara Labuda, Zbigniew Palka, Leszek Skrzypczak, President Aleksander Kwaśniewski, **Henryk Hudzik**, Stanisław Lorenc, Bolesław Szafirski and Ireneusz Kibiaczyk

After the award ceremony, there was a meeting with the President, during which the following topics were discussed: mathematics and science, youth and their education, relations with the European Mathematical Society.

Fig. 50. “Function Spaces VIII”, 3–7 July 2006, Będlewo.
Henryk Hudzik in first row, third from the left

Fig. 51. Organizers of the conference “Function Spaces IX”, 6–11 July 2009, Kraków.
From the left: Grzegorz Lewicki, Julian Musielak, Roman Szrednicki, **Henryk Hudzik**,
Marian Nowak and Leszek Skrzypczak

Fig. 52. 8 July 2009, excursion to the salt mine in Wieliczka connected with a conference dinner. From the left: Katsuo Matsuoka, Brailey Sims, Lech Maligranda, Narin Petrot, Rabian Wangkeeree, Suthep Suantai, **Henryk Hudzik**, Amnuay Kananthai and Ryszard Pluciennik

Fig. 53. “Function Spaces X”, 9–14 July 2012, Poznań.

Fig. 54. “Function Spaces X”, 9–14 July 2012, Poznań.

Fig. 55. “Function Spaces XI”, 6–10 July 2015, Zielona Góra.

Function Spaces XII, July 9-14, 2018, Kraków, Poland

Fig. 56. “Function Spaces XII”, 9–14 July 2018, Kraków.

Where is Hudzik?

He was at the conference but is not in the photo

- **2021** COVID = no conference.
- **2024** “*Function Spaces XIII*”, 8–12 July 2024, Poznań.

F. Research of Henryk Hudzik

Henryk Hudzik was the author or co-author of over 220 scientific papers published in mathematical journals, 3 chapters in monographs and several popular science and review papers.

His research interests included: functional analysis, in particular the theory of function spaces, Banach lattices, the geometry of Banach spaces and its applications, operator theory and metric fixed point theory.

- In MathSciNet (4 July 2024) Henryk Hudzik is cited
2469 times by 921 authors.

Top 5 most cited papers on MathSciNet (4 July 2024):

- [152] B. Wang and H. Hudzik, *The global Cauchy problem for the NLS and NLKG with small rough data*, J. Differential Equations 232 (2007), no. 1, 36–73.
- [97] H. Hudzik and L. Maligranda, *Some remarks on s -convex functions*, Aequationes Math. 48 (1994), no. 1, 100–111.
- [71] H. Hudzik, A. Kamińska and M. Mastyło, *Monotonicity and rotundity properties in Banach lattices*, Rocky Mountain J. Math. 30 (2000), no. 3, 933–950.
- [65] H. Hudzik and W. Kurc, *Monotonicity properties of Musielak–Orlicz spaces and dominated best approximation in Banach lattices*, J. Approx. Theory 95 (1998), no. 3, 353–368.
- [58] H. Hudzik and L. Maligranda, *Amemiya norm equals Orlicz norm in general*, Indag. Math. (N.S.) 11 (2000), no. 4, 573–585.

In my opinion, these are his three most important results in mathematics:

- **1. 1992:** H. Hudzik and T. R. Landes, *Characteristic of convexity of Köthe function spaces*, Math. Ann. 294 (1992), no. 1, 117–124 [cited 27 times].
- **2. 1985:** H. Hudzik, *Uniformly non- $l_n^{(1)}$ Orlicz spaces with Luxemburg norm*, Studia Math. 81 (1985), no. 3, 271–284 [cited 37 times].
- **3. 1976–1980:** early research (9 papers: 1976-3 papers, 1977, 1977/78-2 papers, 1978, 1979, 1980) of generalized Orlicz–Sobolev spaces (Musielak–Orlicz–Sobolev spaces) [cited $49+10+9+6+5+7+8+8+35=137$].

F1. Modulus of convexity and Köthe–Bochner spaces

Let X be a Banach space with $\dim X \geq 2$. Geometric properties of X are determined by the unit sphere S_X and the closed unit ball B_X .

X is said to be *uniformly non-square* if there exists $\delta > 0$ such that

$$\min\{\|x + y\|, \|x - y\|\} \leq 2(1 - \delta), \quad x, y \in S_X.$$

The *modulus of convexity* δ_X of X is a function $\delta_X: [0, 2] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ given by

$$\delta_X(\varepsilon) = \inf\left\{1 - \left\|\frac{x + y}{2}\right\| : x, y \in S_X, \|x - y\| \geq \varepsilon\right\}, \quad \varepsilon \in [0, 2].$$

It is well known that the function δ_X is continuous on $[0, 2)$ and nondecreasing on the interval $[0, 2]$, but it doesn't have to be convex (Liokumovich 1973). δ_X is increasing on the interval $[\varepsilon_0(X), 2]$, where

$$\varepsilon_0(X) = \inf\{\varepsilon \in (0, 2] : \delta_X(\varepsilon) > 0\}.$$

A Banach space X is called *uniformly convex* if $\delta_X(\varepsilon) > 0$ for all $0 < \varepsilon \leq 2$, i.e. $\varepsilon_0(X) = 0$.

A Banach space X is *uniformly non-square* if and only if $\varepsilon_0(X) < 2$.

Let E be a Banach function lattice on a measure space (Ω, Σ, μ) and let $E(X)$ be the Köthe–Bochner space of all strongly measurable functions $x: \Omega \rightarrow X$ with $[x](\cdot) := \|x(\cdot)\|$ and the norm $\|x\|_{E(X)} = \|[x]\|_E$.

M. M. Day (1941) proved that $L_p(X)$ is uniformly convex if and only if $1 < p < \infty$ and X is uniformly convex. Then, Halperin (1954) shows that the Köthe–Bochner space $E(X)$ is uniformly convex if both spaces E and X are uniformly convex.

Further, Smith and Turett (1980) proved that $L_p(X)$ is uniformly non-square if and only if $1 < p < \infty$ and X is uniformly non-square.

On the other hand, Dowling and Turett (1983) generalized these results to the formula

$$\varepsilon_0(L_p(X)) = \max\{\varepsilon_0(L_p), \varepsilon_0(X)\}.$$

Finally, Hudzik (1989) proved for the Orlicz–Bochner space $L_\Phi(X)$ over an infinite non-atomic measure space that

$$\varepsilon_0(L_\Phi(X)) = \max\{\varepsilon_0(L_\Phi), \varepsilon_0(X)\}$$

provided that Φ is a uniformly convex Orlicz function.

The remarkable result of Hudzik and Landes (1992) covers all of the above-mentioned results.

THEOREM 1 (Hudzik and Landes, 1992). *The characteristic of convexity of any Köthe–Bochner space $E(X)$ satisfies the following estimates*

$$\max\{\varepsilon_0(E), \varepsilon_0(X)\} \leq \varepsilon_0(E(X)) \leq \varepsilon_0(E) + \varepsilon_0(X) - \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_0(E) \varepsilon_0(X). \quad (1)$$

COROLLARY 1. (i) $E(X)$ is uniformly convex if and only if both E and X are uniformly convex.

(ii) $E(X)$ is uniformly non-square if both E and X are uniformly non-square.

F2. Uniformly non- $l_n^{(1)}$ and B-convex Banach spaces

A Banach space X is said to be *uniformly non- $l_n^{(1)}$* ($n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2$) if there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that for any elements $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in B_X$ and some choice of signs, we have

$$\|x_1 \pm x_2 \pm \dots \pm x_n\| \leq n(1 - \varepsilon).$$

Banach spaces which are uniformly non- $l_n^{(1)}$ for some $n \geq 2$ are called *B-convex spaces*.

This concept follows from the result of Beck (1962): the strong law of large numbers for random variables which take values in a Banach space X is valid if and only if space X is B-convex.

Hudzik gives some criteria for Orlicz spaces with the Luxemburg norm to be uniformly non- $l_n^{(1)}$.

THEOREM 2 (Hudzik, 1985). *Let Φ be an Orlicz function. The Orlicz space $L_\Phi(\mu)$ on a σ -finite measure space (Ω, Σ, μ) is uniformly non- $l_n^{(1)}$ if and only if the following conditions are satisfied:*

- (i) Φ satisfies the Δ_2 -condition and the following inequality for some $\sigma \in (0, 1)$

$$\Phi\left(\frac{u}{n}\right) \leq \frac{\sigma \Phi(u)}{n} \quad (2)$$

for every $u \geq 0$ if μ is a non-atomic and infinite measure.

- (ii) Φ is finite, satisfies the Δ_2^∞ -condition and inequality (2) for all $u \geq \Phi^{-1}(n/\mu(\Omega)) = \sup\{v \geq 0: \Phi(v) \leq n/\mu(\Omega)\}$, if μ is a non-atomic and finite measure.

- (iii) Φ satisfies the Δ_2^0 -condition and inequality (2) in some interval $[0, u_0]$, where $u_0 > 0$, if μ is purely atomic with a countably infinite number of atoms of measure 1 and $\Phi(c) = 1$ for $c > 0$.

F3. Musielak–Orlicz–Sobolev spaces

The first fields that attracted Henryk Hudzik was the theory of Sobolev and Orlicz–Sobolev spaces. His early papers deal with Musielak–Orlicz–Sobolev spaces.

These are pioneering papers in such research. 9 papers he published in years 1976–1980:

1976-3 papers, 1977-2 papers, 1978-2 papers, 1979, 1980.

Remark 1. Hudzik’s pioneering papers on Musielak–Orlicz–Sobolev spaces are noted in books:

I. D. V. Cruz-Urbe and A. Fiorenza, *Variable Lebesgue Spaces*, Birkhäuser/Springer, Heidelberg 2013, x+312 pp.

In Chapter 6 (pages 239–270), the variable Sobolev spaces $W^{k,p(\cdot)}$ are presented and **all 9 papers of Hudzik are cited.**

II. O. Méndez and J. Lang, *Analysis on Function Spaces of Musielak–Orlicz Type*, Monographs and Research Notes in Mathematics, Boca Raton 2019, xiii+260 pp.

In Chapter 3 (pages 161–179), entitled *Sobolev spaces of Musielak–Orlicz type* **we find Hudzik’s results and 5 his papers are cited.**

III. L. Diening, P. Harjulehto, P. Hästö and M. Růžička, *Lebesgue and Sobolev Spaces with Variable Exponents*, Lecture Notes in Mathematics 2017, Springer, Heidelberg 2011, x+509 pp.

In Chapter 8, “*Introduction to Sobolev Spaces*” (pages 247–314) are variable Sobolev spaces $W^{k,p(\cdot)}$ and Hudzik is not cited. **Strange !!!**

Could it be the influence of the behavior from Göttingen?

The great scientific center that was Göttingen in the period 1884–1933, had a strange habit that was inconsistent with the ethical principles of academic coexistence.

Richard Courant recalls unusual customs. In his opinion, over time, a strange system of educating young outstanding staff took over among mathematicians in Göttingen^{3,4}:

The Göttingen group was famous in this respect for its lack of responsibility. We used to call this process of learning something, forgetting the source, then doing it again and doing it better, and then publishing without properly citing the source, “nostrification.” This was one of the concepts of the Göttingen group^{3,4}.

Remark 2. A more complete discussion of Hudzik’s mathematical results was presented by M. Mastyło in publication [MM15].

[MM15] M. Mastyło and J. Musielak, *Henryk Hudzik – vita et opera*, Comment. Math. 55 (2015), no. 2, 45–78.

³R. Courant, *Wspomnienia z Getyngi* [Memories from Göttingen], „Wiadomości Matematyczne” 18 (1974), page 152.

⁴D. Ciesielska, L. Maligranda, J. Zwierzyńska, *W świątyni nauki, mekce matematyków. Studia i badania naukowe polskich matematyków, fizyków i astronomów na Uniwersytecie w Getyndze 1884-1933* [In the temple of science, the mecca of mathematicians. Studies and research of Polish mathematicians, physicists and astronomers at the University in Göttingen 1884–1933], Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN, Warszawa 2021, page 78.

G. My comments as a historian of mathematics

1. Musielak–Orlicz spaces or Orlicz–Nakano spaces?

If (Ω, Σ, μ) is a σ -finite measure space and $\varphi: \Omega \times [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is an *Orlicz function with a parameter* (called recently *Musielak–Orlicz function*), that is, a non-decreasing **convex** function in the first variable such that $\varphi(0, t) = 0$ and Σ -measurable in the second variable, then spaces $L^{\{\varphi\}} = L^{\{\varphi\}}(\Omega)$ defined by

$$L^{\{\varphi\}} = \{x \in L^0(\Omega) : \|x\|_{\{\varphi\}} = \inf\{\lambda > 0 : I_\varphi(x/\lambda) \leq 1\} < \infty\},$$

with a modular $I_\varphi(x) = \int_\Omega \varphi(|x(t)|, t) d\mu(t)$ were introduced by Hidegoro **Nakano** in 1950 in his book [Na50] as a generalization of Orlicz space (that is, when the function φ depends only on first variable $\varphi(u, t) = \varphi(u)$) and sometimes they have name (although they should have it permanently) *Orlicz–Nakano spaces* or *Nakano–Orlicz spaces*⁵.

They are also called the *Orlicz space with a parameter* or the *variable Orlicz spaces* (see [He61]).

The correct name of the Orlicz–Nakano space was used, for example, in the following papers: [Sh67], [LS68] and [Sh75].

[Na50] H. Nakano, *Modulated Semi-Ordered Linear Spaces*, Maruzen Co., Ltd., Tokyo, 1950.

[He61] S. Heckscher, *Variable Orlicz spaces*, *Indag. Math.* 23 (1961), 229–241.

[Sh67] I. V. Shragin, *The Amemiya norm in an Orlicz–Nakano space*, *Kishinev. Gos. Univ. Uchen. Zap.* 91 (1967), 91–102 (Russian).

[LS68] V. I. Levchenko and I. V. Shragin, *Nemychiĭ’s operator acting from the space of continuous functions into an Orlicz–Nakano space*, *Mat. Issled.* 3 (1968), vyp. 3 (9), 91–100 (Russian).

[Sh75] I. V. Shragin, *Some metric properties of Orlicz–Nakano spaces*, *Trudy Mosk. Inst. Khim. Mashin.* 64 (1975), 45–52 (Russian).

⁵More information can be found in the paper L. Maligranda, *Hidegoro Nakano (1909–1974) – on the centenary of his birth*, in: “Banach and Function Spaces III”, *Proc. of the Third Internat. Symp. on Banach and Function Spaces (ISBFS2009)* (14–17 Sept. 2009, Kitakyushu-Japan), Edited by M. Kato, L. Maligranda and T. Suzuki, Yokohama Publishers 2011, 99–171.

2. Historical remark about Luxemburg–Nakano norm.

W. Orlicz introduced in 1932 (when $\varphi \in \Delta_2^\infty$) and in 1936 (in general) Orlicz space $L^\varphi = L^\varphi(\Omega)$ when $\Omega = [a, b]$ and φ is so-called convex N-function, and the norm, which is currently called the *Orlicz norm*,

$$\|x\|_\varphi^0 = \sup\left\{\int_\Omega |x(t)y(t)| dt : \int_\Omega \varphi^*(|y(t)|) dt \leq 1\right\}, \quad (3)$$

where φ^* is a complementary function to φ given by formula

$$\varphi^*(v) = \sup_{u \geq 0} [uv - \varphi(u)].$$

He proved that the space L^φ with such norm (3) is a Banach space.

Only in the 1950s did Nakano (in 1950) and Luxemburg (in 1955) notice that we can have in the Orlicz space $L^\varphi(\Omega)$ another norm

$$\|x\|_\varphi = \inf\left\{\lambda > 0 : \int_\Omega \varphi\left(\frac{|x(t)|}{\lambda}\right) d\mu(t) \leq 1\right\}, \quad (4)$$

and these norms are equivalent since $\|x\|_\varphi \leq \|x\|_\varphi^0 \leq 2\|x\|_\varphi$.

Usually the norm (4) is called the *Luxemburg norm* (see [KR58]), but it should be called Nakano–Luxemburg or Luxemburg–Nakano norm in the Orlicz space $L^\varphi(\Omega)$ (see [Ma11, pp. 125–126]). Let us note that in 1950 it was also paper by Morse and Transue [MT50] where implicitly appeared norm (4).

[KR58] M. A. Krasnosel'skiĭ and Ja. B. Rutickiĭ, *Convex Functions and Orlicz Spaces*, Noordhoff, Groningen, 1961.

[Ma11] L. Maligranda, *Hidegoro Nakano (1909–1974) – on the centenary of his birth*, in: “Banach and Function Spaces III (ISBFS 2009, Kitakyushu 2009)”, Yokohama Publ., Yokohama 2011, 99–171.

[MT50] M. Morse and W. Transue, *Functionals F bilinear over the product $A \times B$ of two pseudo-normed vector spaces. II. Admissible spaces A* , Ann. of Math. (2), 51 (1950), 576–614.

3. What are Musielak–Orlicz spaces really?

The Orlicz spaces generated by positive functions φ (**not necessarily convex**) were investigated by Mazur and Orlicz [MO58] in 1958. They proved that for **positive non-decreasing functions** φ (**without any assumption about the convexity** of φ) the corresponding Orlicz spaces are F -spaces with the F -norm

$$|x|_{\varphi} = \inf\{\lambda > 0: I_{\varphi}(x/\lambda) \leq \lambda\}. \quad (5)$$

Then, in 1959, Musielak and Orlicz [MO59] extended this result to general modulars (not necessarily convex) and showed that modular spaces $X_{\rho} = \{x \in X: \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0^+} \rho(\lambda x) \rightarrow 0\}$ are F -spaces with the F -norm $|x|_{\rho} = \inf\{\lambda > 0: \rho(x/\lambda) \leq \lambda\}$, similar to Mazur–Orlicz F -norm (5). As important example Musielak–Orlicz had the Orlicz spaces with a parameter $L^{\{\varphi\}}$ generated by Orlicz function φ with a parameter (not necessarily convex in the first variable) and the corresponding modular $\rho_{\varphi}(x): = \int_{\Omega} \varphi(|x(t)|, t) d\mu(t)$.

These spaces began to be correctly called “**Musielak–Orlicz spaces**” by K. Urbanik in [Ur68], because he considered the case of not necessarily convex functions. A great influence on the further use of the name “Musielak–Orlicz spaces” (with not necessarily convex functions) had papers [Tu75], [Tu76], [Tu78] of P. Turpin from years 1974–1978. However, mathematicians incorrectly transferred the name also to the convex case. Currently, most mathematicians use the name Musielak–Orlicz spaces for these spaces (unfortunately, even in the convex case, i.e. in the case considered already by Nakano in 1950).

[MO58] S. Mazur and W. Orlicz, *On some classes of linear spaces*, *Studia Math.* 17 (1958), 97–119.

[MO59] J. Musielak and W. Orlicz, *On modular spaces*, *Studia Math.* 18 (1959), 49–65.

[Ur68] K. Urbanik, *Random measures and harmonizable sequences*, *Studia Math.* 31 (1968), 61–88.

[Tu75] P. Turpin, *Suites sommables dans certains espaces de fonctions mesurables*, *C. R. Acad. Sci. Paris Sér. A-B* 280 (1975), no. 6, A349–A352.

[Tu76] [Tu76] P. Turpin, *Conditions de bornitude et espaces de fonctions mesurables*, *Studia Math.* 56 (1976), no. 1, 69–91.

[Tu78] P. Turpin, *Fubini inequalities and bounded multiplier property in generalized modular spaces*, Special issue dedicated to Władysław Orlicz on the occasion of his seventy-fifth birthday, *Comment. Math. Special Issue* 1 (1978), 331–353.

H. HH as colleague and a friend

Henryk Hudzik was my friend and we wrote 9 joint papers in the years 1990–2004. Three most cited papers are the following;

- [97] H. Hudzik and L. Maligranda, *Some remarks on s -convex functions*, Aequationes Math. 48 (1994), no. 1, 100–111.
- [58] H. Hudzik and L. Maligranda, *Amemiya norm equals Orlicz norm in general*, Indag. Math. (N.S.) 11 (2000), no. 4, 573–585.
- [10] H. Hudzik and L. Maligranda, *An interpolation theorem in symmetric function F -spaces*, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. 110 (1990), no. 1, 89–96.

For Henryk, scientific work was the center of his interests, it was his passion, to which he devoted himself endlessly.

Henryk was an extremely hard-working man, very well organized, defending his beliefs, and at the same time very sensitive.

Henryk noticed problems in others and tried to help them as much as possible.

I will remember Professor Hudzik as an extremely open and kind person, ready to serve all those who need it. Just as a good person.

Henryk died on 2 March 2019 and was buried on 9 March 2019 at the parish cemetery in Suchy Las near Poznań.

Dear Henryk, we will miss you very much! Your support, your wise advice and your great kindness.

I'm glad I knew you and thank you very much for everything, Henryk!!!

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank Anna Hudzik (Dankowska) – daughter of HH, Maria Hudzik – second wife of HH for providing many family photos, and the Adam Mickiewicz University Archives, and in particular Mr. Dominik Pawlik for providing and copying many documents.

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That is all !

Thank you very much !

Dziękuję bardzo !

Convergence results for varying measures

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Some limit theorems of the type

$$\int_{\Omega} f_n dm_n \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} f dm$$

are presented for scalar, (vector), (multi)-valued sequences of m_n -integrable functions f_n . Conditions for the convergence of sequences of measures $(m_n)_n$ and of their integrals $(\int f_n dm_n)_n$ in a measurable space Ω are of interest in many areas of pure and applied mathematics such as statistics, transportation problems, interactive partial systems, neural networks and signal processing.

Sufficient conditions in order to obtain some kind of Vitali's convergence theorems for a sequence of (multi)functions $(f_n)_n$ integrable with respect to a sequence of measures $(m_n)_n$ are considered.

We consider the asymptotic properties of $(\int_{\Omega} f_n dm_n)_n$ with respect to varying measures, which are setwisely or vaguely convergent in an arbitrary measurable spaces.

Consequently, a continuous dependence result for a wide class of differential equations with many interesting applications, namely measure differential equations (including Stieltjes differential equations, generalized differential problems, impulsive differential equations with finitely or countably many impulses and also dynamic equations on time scales) is provided.

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Convergence results for varying measures

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XIII Function Space
Poznań, June 8-13 2024

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Convergence results for varying measures

Introduction

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 m_n & \& f_n & \longmapsto & \int_E f_n dm_n = \nu_n(E) \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 m & \& f & \longmapsto & \int_E f dm = \nu(E)
 \end{array}
 \quad \text{for every } E \in \mathcal{A}.$$

Valeria Marraffa

Convergence results for varying measures

Examples of areas of applications

- stochastic processes and statistic
- control and game theories
- transportation problems
- neural networks
- signal and image processing
- continuous dependance for measure differential inclusions and measure differential equations.

some references

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Theorem

Let $f, f_n : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be measurable functions and let m and $(m_n)_n$ be measures. Suppose $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} m_n(A) = m(A)$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} f_n(x) = f(x)$. If $|f_n(x)| \leq g_n(x)$ and $\overline{\lim}_n \int g_n dm_n \leq \int g dm < \infty$, where $g(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} g_n(x)$, then

$$\int f dm < \infty, \quad \lim_n \int f_n dm_n = \int f dm$$

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Notations

- (Ω, \mathcal{A}) measurable space
- $\mathcal{M}(\Omega)$ is the vector space of *finite real-valued measures* on (Ω, \mathcal{A})
- $|m|$ denotes the total variation of a measure m
- $(m_n)_n \subset \mathcal{M}(\Omega)$ is *setwise convergent* to $m \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega)$ ($m_n \xrightarrow{s} m$) if $\lim_n m_n(A) = m(A)$ for every $A \in \mathcal{A}$
- $(m_n)_n \subset \mathcal{M}(\Omega)$ *converges in total variation* to m ($m_n \xrightarrow{tv} m$) if $|m - m_n|(\Omega) \rightarrow 0$. Then $(m_n)_n$ is convergent to m uniformly on \mathcal{A} .
- simple functions are dense in the space of bounded measurable functions, so a sequence $(m_n)_n$ of measures setwise converges to m if and only if

$$\int_{\Omega} f dm_n \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} f dm, \quad \text{for all bounded measurable } f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}.$$

Notations

- $(m_n)_n$ is *uniformly absolutely continuous with respect to* m , ($m_n \ll_u m$) if for each $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $\delta > 0$ such that

$$(A \in \mathcal{A} \text{ and } m(A) < \delta) \implies \sup_n m_n(A) < \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

- $m_n \leq m$, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\implies m_n \ll_u m$
- If m is a finite signed measure, m^{\pm} denote its positive and negative parts

$$(m_n^{\pm} \xrightarrow{s} m^{\pm}) \quad \begin{matrix} \implies \\ \not\Leftarrow \end{matrix} \quad (m_n \xrightarrow{s} m)$$

Vitali's theorem for varying measures

Definition

Let $(m_n)_n$ be a sequence of measures.

(u.a.c.) $(f_n)_n : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ has *uniformly absolutely continuous (m_n) -integrals on Ω* , if $\forall \varepsilon > 0 \exists \delta > 0$ s. t. $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$(A \in \mathcal{A} \text{ and } m_n(A) < \delta) \implies \int_A |f_n| dm_n < \varepsilon. \quad (2)$$

(u.i.) $(f_n)_n : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is *uniformly (m_n) -integrable on Ω* , if

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow +\infty} \sup_n \int_{\{|f_n| > \alpha\}} |f_n| dm_n = 0. \quad (3)$$

Vitali's theorem for varying measures

Let $(m_n)_n$ be a bounded sequence of measures and $(f_n)_n$ be a sequence of real valued measurable functions on Ω . Then, the sequence $(f_n)_n$ is uniformly (m_n) -integrable on Ω if and only if it has uniformly absolutely continuous (m_n) -integrals and

$$\sup_n \int_{\Omega} |f_n| dm_n < +\infty. \quad (4)$$

Vitali's theorem for varying measures

Theorem

Let $f, f_n : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be measurable functions and let m and $(m_n)_n$ be measures. Suppose that

- (2.i) $(f_n)_n$ has u.a.c (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;
- (2.ii) $f_n(t) \rightarrow f(t)$, in m -measure, as $n \rightarrow \infty$;
- (2.iii) f has u.a.c. (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;
- (2.iv) $(m_n \xrightarrow{s} m)$.

Then, for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$,

$$\lim_n \int_A f_n dm_n = \int_A f dm. \quad (5)$$

The multivalued case for integrands

- X Banach space with dual X^* and B_{X^*} is the unit ball of X^*
- $c(X)$ is the collection of all nonempty closed convex subsets of X and $cwk(X)$ is the family of all weakly compact members of $c(X)$.
- $s(x^*, C) = \sup\{\langle x^*, x \rangle : x \in C\}$, for each x^* is the *support function* of C
- If $C, D \in cwk(X)$ $d_H(C, D) := \sup_{\|x^*\| \leq 1} |s(x^*, C) - s(x^*, D)|$ is the Hausdorff metric on the hyperspace $cwk(X)$

The multivalued case for integrands

- Any map $\Gamma : \Omega \rightarrow c(X)$ is called a *mulfunctor*
- Γ is said to be *scalarly measurable* if for every $x^* \in X^*$, the function $t \rightarrow s(x^*, \Gamma(t))$ is measurable
- Γ is said to be *scalarly integrable* if for each $x^* \in X^*$, the function $t \rightarrow s(x^*, \Gamma(t))$ is integrable
- Γ is said to be *Pettis integrable* in $ckw(X)$ with respect to a measure m if Γ is scalarly integrable with respect to m and for every $A \in \mathcal{A}$, there exists $M_\Gamma(A) \in cwk(X)$ such that

$$s(x^*, M_\Gamma(A)) = \int_A s(x^*, \Gamma) dm \text{ for all } x^* \in X^*.$$

$$\text{and } \int_A \Gamma dm := M_\Gamma(A)$$

The multivalued case for integrands

The sequence $(\Gamma_n)_n$ has uniformly absolutely continuous scalar (m_n) -integrals on Ω if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $\delta > 0$ such that for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $A \in \mathcal{A}$

$$m_n(A) < \delta \Rightarrow \sup \left\{ \int_A |s(x^*, \Gamma_n)| dm_n : \|x^*\| \leq 1 \right\} < \varepsilon. \quad (7)$$

If $\Gamma_n = \Gamma$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we obtain the uniformly absolutely continuous scalar (m_n) -integrability of Γ on Ω .

The multivalued case for integrands

Theorem

Let $\Gamma, \Gamma_n : \Omega \rightarrow \text{cwk}(X)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, be scalarly measurable multifunctions. Suppose that

- (3.j) the sequence $(\Gamma_n)_n$ has u.a.c. scalar (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;
- (3.jj) $s(x^*, \Gamma_n) \rightarrow s(x^*, \Gamma)$, in m -measure, for each $x^* \in X^*$;
- (3.jjj) Γ has u.a.c. scalar (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;
- (3.jv) $(m_n \xrightarrow{s} m)$;
- (3.v) each multifunction Γ_n is Pettis integrable with respect to m_n .

Then the multifunction Γ is Pettis integrable with respect to m in $\text{cwk}(X)$ and $\forall x^* \in X^*$ and $\forall A \in \mathcal{A}$

$$\lim_n s \left(x^*, \int_A \Gamma_n dm_n \right) = s \left(x^*, \int_A \Gamma dm \right).$$

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The multivalued case for integrands-steps of the proof

•

Theorem 2 $\implies \lim_n \int_A s(x^*, \Gamma_n) dm_n = \int_A s(x^*, \Gamma) dm.$

In order to prove that Γ is Pettis m -integrable

- $T_\Gamma : X^* \rightarrow L^1(m)$, $T_\Gamma(x^*) = s(x^*, \Gamma)$ is weakly compact
- Γ is determined by a WCG space $Y \subset X$

X weakly compact generated (briefly WCG) if it possesses a weakly compact subset K whose linear span is dense in X .

Since Γ_n is Pettis m_n -integrable, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $Y_n \subseteq X$ be a WCG space generated by a set $W_n \in \text{cwk}(B_{X^*})$ which m_n -determines Γ_n .

Let Y be the WCG space generated by $W := \sum 2^{-n} W_n$.

In order to prove that $s(y^*, \Gamma(t)) = 0$ m -a.e. on the set Ω . we use (*)

with $A = \Omega^+ := \{t : s(y^*, \Gamma(t)) \geq 0\}$ ($A = \Omega^- := \{t : s(y^*, \Gamma(t)) < 0\}$)

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The multivalued case for integrands

Let $\Gamma, \Gamma_n : \Omega \rightarrow \text{cwk}(X)$ be scalarly measurable multifunctions. We say that the sequence $(\Gamma_n)_n$ is scalarly equi-convergent in measure with respect to a sequence of measures $(m_n)_n$ to Γ if, for every $\delta > 0$,

$$\lim_n \sup_{\|x^*\| \leq 1} m_n\{t \in \Omega : |s(x^*, \Gamma_n(t)) - s(x^*, \Gamma(t))| > \delta\} = 0. \quad (8)$$

The multivalued case for integrands

Theorem

Let $\Gamma, \Gamma_n : \Omega \rightarrow \text{cwk}(X)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, be scalarly measurable multifunctions. If

- (10.j) the sequence $(\Gamma_n)_n$ has u.a.c. scalar (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;
 - (10.jj) the sequence $(\Gamma_n)_n$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, is scalarly equi-convergent in measure with respect to $(m_n)_n$ and m to Γ ;
 - (10.jjj) Γ has u.a.c. scalar (m_n) and m integrals;
 - (10.jv) $(m_n \xrightarrow{tv} m)$;
 - (10.v) each multifunction Γ_n is Pettis integrable with respect to m_n .
- Then Γ is Pettis integrable with respect to m in $\text{cwk}(X)$ and

$$\lim_n d_H(M_{\Gamma_n}(A), M_{\Gamma}(A)) = 0$$

uniformly in $A \in \mathcal{A}$

The vector case for integrands

$$\Gamma(t) = \{f(t)\}$$

Theorem

Let $f, f_n : \Omega \rightarrow X$ be scalarly measurable functions. Suppose that

- (5.j) $(f_n)_n$ has u.a.c. scalar (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;
- (5.jj) $x^* f_n(t) \rightarrow x^* f(t)$, in m -measure, for each $x^* \in X^*$;
- (5.jjj) f has u.a.c. scalar (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;
- (5.jv) $(m_n \xrightarrow{s} m)$;
- (5.v) each function f_n is Pettis integrable with respect to m_n .

Then f is Pettis integrable with respect to m and

$$\lim_n \int_{\Omega} f_n dm_n = \int_{\Omega} f dm,$$

weakly in X .

The vector case for integrands

and also..

Theorem

Let $f, f_n : \Omega \rightarrow X$ be measurable functions. If

- (6.i) $(f_n)_n$ has u.a.c. scalar (m_n) -integrals;
- (6.ii) $(f_n)_n$ is scalarly equi-convergent in measure to f ;
- (6.iii) f has u.a.c. scalar (m_n) and m integrals;
- (6.iv) $(m_n \xrightarrow{tv} m)$;
- (6.v) each function f_n is Pettis integrable with respect to m_n .

Then, f is Pettis-integrable with respect to m and

$$\lim_n \left\| \int_A f_n dm_n - \int_A f dm \right\| = 0$$

uniformly with respect to $A \in \mathcal{A}$.

The vector case for McShane integrable integrands

- (Ω, \mathcal{A}) be a compact Radon measure space with measure m and topology \mathcal{T}
- A *McShane partition* of Ω is a family $\{(A_i, t_i)\}_{i \leq p}$ such that A_1, \dots, A_p is a finite disjoint cover of Ω by elements of \mathcal{A} and $t_i \in \Omega, i = 1, \dots, p$
- A *gauge* Δ on Ω is a function $\Delta : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{T}$ such that $t \in \Delta(t)$ for every $t \in \Omega$

The vector case for McShane integrable integrands

- A McShane partition $\{(A_i, t_i)\}_{i \leq p}$ is *subordinated* to a gauge $\Delta(t)$ if $A_i \subset \Delta(t_i)$ for $i = 1, \dots, p$.
 $f : \Omega \rightarrow X$ is said to be *m-McShane integrable* on Ω with *m-(MS)-integral* $w \in X$ if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a gauge Δ such that for each partition $\{(A_i, t_i)\}_{i \leq p}$ subordinated to Δ , we have

$$\left\| \sum_{i=1}^p f(t_i)m(A_i) - w \right\| < \varepsilon. \quad (9)$$

$$w := (MS) \int_{\Omega} f dm$$

The vector case for McShane integrable integrands

The vector valued case was derived from the multivalued in the case of Pettis integrability.

In the case of the McShane integral it is possible to proceed in the same way. But, thanks to the Rådström embedding, for the McShane integral it is possible to deduce at once the multivalued case from the vector valued one.

The Rådström embedding is an additive, positively homogeneous and isometric map

$$i : cb(X) \rightarrow \ell_\infty(B_{X^*})$$

$$\Gamma_n \text{ McS - integrable} \implies i \circ \Gamma_n \text{ McS - integrable}$$

the assumptions for multifunctions can be translated for the corresponding $i \circ \Gamma'_n$ s allowing to get the convergence from the vector case.

In general the Rådström embedding of a Pettis integrable multifunction could be not Pettis integrable.

The vector case for McShane integrable integrands

- $f_n : \Omega \rightarrow X$ is (m_n) -*equi-integrable* on Ω , if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a gauge Δ such that for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\left\| \sum_{i=1}^p f_n(t_i) m_n(A_i) - (MS) \int_{\Omega} f_n dm_n \right\| < \varepsilon \quad (10)$$

for each partition $\{(A_i, t_i)\}_{i \leq p}$ subordinated to Δ .

The vector case for McShane integrable integrands

Theorem

Let m and $(m_n)_n$ be measures, let $f_n : \Omega \rightarrow X$ be m_n - (MS)-integrable functions, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and let $f : \Omega \rightarrow X$.

Suppose that

(7.i) the sequence $(f_n)_n$ is (m_n) -equi-integrable on Ω ;

(7.ii) $f_n(t) \rightarrow f(t)$, for all $t \in \Omega$;

(7.iii) $(m_n \xrightarrow{s} m)$.

Then, f is m -(MS)integrable and for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$,

$$\lim_n (MS) \int_A f_n dm_n = (MS) \int_A f dm. \quad (11)$$

Moreover if we substitute condition (7.iii) with the convergence in total variation $(m_n \xrightarrow{tv} m)$, then (11) holds uniformly in $A \in \mathcal{A}$.

The vector case for McShane integrable integrands

- A multifunction $\Gamma : \Omega \rightarrow cb(X)$ is m -McShane integrable on Ω , if there exists $\varphi_\Gamma \in cb(X)$ such that for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a gauge Δ on Ω such that for each partition $\{(A_i, t_i)\}_{i \leq p}$ of Ω subordinated to Δ , we have

$$d_H \left(\varphi_\Gamma, \sum_{i=1}^p \Gamma(t_i) m(A_i) \right) < \varepsilon. \quad (12)$$

The vector case for McShane integrable integrands

Theorem

Let m and $(m_n)_n$ be measures, let $\Gamma_n : \Omega \rightarrow cb(X)$ be m_n - (MS)-integrable multifunctions, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and let $\Gamma : \Omega \rightarrow cb(X)$. Suppose that

- (8.i) the sequence $(\Gamma_n)_n$ is (m_n) -equi-integrable on Ω ;
- (8.ii) $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_H(\Gamma_n(t), \Gamma(t)) = 0$, for each $t \in \Omega$;
- (8.iii) $(m_n \xrightarrow{s} m)$.

Then, Γ is m -(MS)integrable and for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$,

$$\lim_n (MS) \int_A \Gamma_n dm_n = (MS) \int_A \Gamma dm. \quad (13)$$

Moreover if we substitute condition (8.iii) with the convergence in total variation $(m_n \xrightarrow{tv} m)$, then (13) holds uniformly in $A \in \mathcal{A}$.

Topological case

Ω a locally compact Hausdorff space, \mathcal{B} be its Borel σ -algebra
 $\mathcal{F}(\Omega)$ indicates the class of all \mathcal{B} -measurable functions
 $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

Topological case

Let m and m_n be in $\mathcal{M}(\Omega)$.

- $(m_n)_n$ converges vaguely to m ($m_n \xrightarrow{v} m$) if

$$\int_{\Omega} g dm_n \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} g dm, \quad \text{for every } g \in C_0(\Omega).$$

- $(m_n)_n$ converges weakly to m ($m_n \xrightarrow{w} m$) if

$$\int_{\Omega} g dm_n \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} g dm, \quad \text{for every } g \in C_b(\Omega).$$

comparison

$$(m_n \xrightarrow{s} m) \quad \begin{matrix} \implies \\ \nLeftrightarrow \end{matrix} \quad (m_n \xrightarrow{w} m) \quad \begin{matrix} \implies \\ \nLeftrightarrow \end{matrix} \quad (m_n \xrightarrow{v} m)$$

- $m_n \leq m \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega)$ & $m_n \xrightarrow{v} m \implies m_n \xrightarrow{s} m$ and, for every $f \in L^1(m)$, for every $A \in \mathcal{B}$,

$$\lim_n \int_A f dm_n = \int_A f dm$$

- $m_n \xrightarrow{w} m \implies m_n(\Omega) \rightarrow m(\Omega)$
- $m_n := \delta_n \xrightarrow{v} m := 0, \quad m_n(\mathbb{R}) = 1 \not\rightarrow m(\mathbb{R}) = 0$
- L. Ma, *Sequential convergence on the space of Borel measures*, (2021), ArXiv 2102.05840, Doi:10.48550/arXiv.2102.05840.

some references: weakly and vague convergence

- Feinberg, E. A., Kasyanov, P. O. and Liang, Y., Fatou's Lemma in its classic form and Lebesgue's Convergence Theorems for varying measures with applications to MDPs, *Theory Prob. Appl.*, **65** (2), (2020), 270–291.
- O. Hernandez-Lerma, and J.B. Lasserre, Fatou's Lemma and Lebesgue's Convergence Theorem for measures, *J. Appl. Math. Stoch. Anal.*, **13** (2), (2000), 137–146.

Valeria Marraffa

Convergence results for varying measures

some references: weakly and vague convergence

previous results in the literature

- in [locally compact second countable and Hausdorff spaces](#), by **Serfozo**, for the vague and weak convergence respectively, when the sequence $(f_n)_n$ converges continuously to f . Under a domination condition in the first result while, in the second, the uniform (m_n) -integrability of the sequence $(f_n)_n$, with $f_n \geq 0$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, is required;
- in [locally compact separable metric spaces](#) by **Hernandez-Lerma** and **Lasserre**, obtaining a Fatou result and asking for the convergence of the sequence of measures an inequality of the $\liminf_n m_n$ on each Borelian set;
- in [metric spaces](#) by **Feinberg**, **Kasyanov** and **Liang**, where the authors obtained a dominated convergence result for sequences of equicontinuous functions $(f_n)_n$ satisfying the uniform (m_n) -integrability.

Valeria Marraffa

Convergence results for varying measures

Topological case

Ω is a locally compact Hausdorff space

- **Portmanteau on an arbitrary completely regular space**

Let $m, m_n \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega)$ with m Radon and $\lim_n m_n(\Omega) = m(\Omega)$. Then f.a.e.:

- $(m_n)_n$ is vaguely convergent to m ;
- for any closed set $F \subset \Omega$, $\limsup_n m_n(F) \leq m(F)$.

- **Uryson's Lemma**

If K is compact and $U \supset K$ is open in a locally compact Ω , then

$\exists f : \Omega \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f \in C_c(\Omega)$, such that $\chi_K \leq f \leq \chi_U$.

Topological case

Theorem

Let m and m_n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, be measures in $\mathcal{M}(\Omega)$, with m Radon. Let $f, f_n \in \mathcal{F}(\Omega)$. Suppose that

(9.i) $f_n(t) \rightarrow f(t)$, m -a.e.;

(9.ii) $f \in C(\Omega)$;

(9.iii) $(f_n)_n$ and f have u.a.c. (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;

(9.iv) $(m_n \xrightarrow{v} m)$ and $m_n \ll_u m$.

Then $f \in L^1(m)$ and

$$\lim_n \int_A f_n dm_n = \int_A f dm \quad \text{for every } A \in \mathcal{B}. \quad (14)$$

Topological case- steps of the proof

comparison with the case of setwise convergence:

- we get thesis for Ω (Urysohn's Lemma & vaguely convergence)
- we obtain it for an arbitrary compact set ($m_n \ll_u m$ & $(f_n)_n$ has uniformly absolutely continuous (m_n) -integrals on Ω)
- we pass to arbitrary Borelian sets (previous steps & m Radon)

Valeria Marraffa

Convergence results for varying measures

Topological case

Theorem

Let $\Gamma, \Gamma_n, n \in \mathbb{N}$, be scalarly measurable multifunctions. Moreover let $m, m_n \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega)$, m Radon. Suppose that

(10.j) $(\Gamma_n)_n$ and Γ have u.a.c. scalar (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;

(10.jj) $s(x^*, \Gamma_n) \rightarrow s(x^*, \Gamma)$ m -a.e. for each $x^* \in X^*$;

(10.jjj) Γ is scalar continuous;

(10.jv) $m_n \xrightarrow{v} m, m_n \ll_u m$;

(10.v) each multifunction Γ_n is Pettis m_n -integrable.

Then the multifunction Γ is Pettis m -integrable in $cwk(X)$ and

$$\lim_n s\left(x^*, \int_A \Gamma_n dm_n\right) = s\left(x^*, \int_A \Gamma dm\right), \quad (15)$$

for every $x^* \in X^*$ and for every $A \in \mathcal{B}$.

Valeria Marraffa

Convergence results for varying measures

Topological case

As an immediate consequence of the previous theorem we have a result for the vector case:

Corollary

Let $g, g_n : \Omega \rightarrow X$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, be scalarly measurable functions. Moreover let $m, m_n \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, m Radon. Suppose that

- (2.j) $(g_n)_n$ and g have scalarly u.a.c. (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;
- (2.jj) $g_n \rightarrow g$ scalarly m -a.e.;
- (2.jjj) g is scalar continuous;
- (2.jv) $m_n \xrightarrow{v} m$, $m_n \ll_u m$;
- (2.v) each g_n is Pettis m_n -integrable.

Then g is Pettis m -integrable in X and

$$\lim_n x^* \left(\int_A g_n dm_n \right) = x^* \left(\int_A g dm \right),$$

The multivalued case for integrands

If we assume by hypothesis

$$\lim_n \int_A s(x^*, \Gamma_n) dm_n = \int_A s(x^*, \Gamma) dm.$$

we can remove the assumption on Ω and the convergence of the sequence $(m_n)_n$ and we can obtain the following result in a general measure space without any topology.

Topological case

Theorem

Let Ω be a measure space on a σ -algebra \mathcal{A} and let Γ be scalarly continuous, Γ_n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, be Pettis m_n -integrable multifunctions. Moreover let $m, m_n \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega)$. Suppose that

(11.j) $(\Gamma_n)_n$ have scalarly u.a.c. (m_n) -integrals on Ω ;

(11.jj) $m_n \ll_u m$;

(11.jjj) for every $A \in \mathcal{A}$ and for every $x^* \in X^*$ it is

$$\lim_n \int_A s(x^*, \Gamma_n) dm_n = \int_A s(x^*, \Gamma) dm.$$

Then the multifunction Γ is Pettis m -integrable.

Topological case

Corollary

Let Ω be a measure space on a σ -algebra \mathcal{A} and let g be scalarly continuous, $g_n : \Omega \rightarrow X$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, be Pettis m_n -integrable functions. Moreover let $m, m_n \in \mathcal{M}(\Omega)$. Suppose that

(3.j) $(g_n)_n$ have scalarly u.a.c. (m_n) -integrals;

(3.jj) $m_n \ll_u m$;

(3.jjj) for every $A \in \mathcal{A}$ and for every $x^* \in X^*$ it is

$$\lim_n \int_A x^* g_n dm_n = \int_A x^* g dm.$$

Then the function g is Pettis m -integrable.

Convergence results for measures satisfying convexity conditions

We will consider limit theorems of the following type

$$\int_{\Omega} f \, dm_n \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} f \, dm$$

in the case in which the sequence of measures $(m_n)_n$ satisfies a convexity condition.

It is known that if $(m_n)_n$ is a sequence of measures converging setwise to a set function m , then m is a measure if one of the following holds:

- 1) $(m_n)_n$ is an increasing sequence;
- 2) (Vitali-Hahn-Saks) m is finite-valued.

Convergence results for measures satisfying convexity conditions

If we substitute the monotonicity condition by one of the following inequalities of Copson type,

$$m_{n+k}(A) \geq \sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j m_{n+k-j}(A), \quad \text{for all } n \geq 1, A \in \mathcal{A}, \quad (16)$$

or

$$m_{n+k}(A) \leq \sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j m_{n+k-j}(A), \quad \text{for all } n \geq 1, A \in \mathcal{A}, \quad (17)$$

where k is a fixed positive integer, the coefficients α_j are strictly positive and $\sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j = 1$, we still obtain that m is a measure.

Convergence results for measures satisfying convexity conditions

Theorem

Let $(m_n)_n$ be a sequence in $\mathcal{M}(\Omega)$ converging setwisely to a set function $m : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. If (16) holds then m is a measure.

Application to measure differential equations

We apply previously obtained convergence result in order to get a continuous dependence feature of a measure differential equation

$$dx(t) = f(t, x(t))dm, \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad (18)$$

where $\Omega = [0, 1]$ and \mathcal{B} is its Borel σ -algebra, $m \in \mathcal{M}([0, 1])$ and $f : [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$.

A function $x : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ is a solution of this problem if

$$x(t) = x_0 + \int_{[0,t)} f(s, x(s))dm(s) \quad \text{for every } t \in [0, 1]$$

Application to measure differential equations

Theorem

Let $f : [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ satisfy:

- i) for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, $f(\cdot, x)$ is measurable;
- ii) $f(\cdot, x_0)$ is Lebesgue-integrable w.r.t. m ;
- iii) there exists a map $L : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ Lebesgue-integrable with respect to m such that

$$\|f(t, x) - f(t, y)\| \leq L(t)\|x - y\|, \quad \text{for } m\text{-a.e. } t \in [0, 1], \quad x, y \in \mathbb{R}^d.$$

Then (18) has a unique solution on $[0, 1]$.

Application to measure differential equations

Theorem

Let $f : [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ satisfy:

- i), ii), iii)
- iv) there exists a map $M : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ Lebesgue-integrable with respect to m such that

$$\|f(t, x)\| \leq M(t), \quad \text{for all } t \in [0, 1], \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^d.$$

Let $(m_n)_n$ be a sequence in $\mathcal{M}([0, 1])$ setwise convergent to $m \in \mathcal{M}([0, 1])$ and satisfying (16).

Then the sequence $(x_n)_n$ of solutions of the measure differential problems

$$dx(t) = f(t, x(t))dm_n, \quad x(0) = x_0 \quad (19)$$

converges uniformly on $[0, 1]$ to the solution x of (18).

THANKS

THANK YOU

Multilinear fractional integrals: boundedness criteria and sharp estimates

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Necessary and sufficient conditions for the trace inequality of multilinear fractional integral operators from a product of Lebesgue/ Morrey spaces to a Lebesgue/ Morrey space will be presented. Sharp Olsen-type estimates in the multilinear setting will also be discussed. Similar problems for one-sided fractional integral operator are studied as well.

The talk is based on the papers [1-5]

References

- [1] L. Grafakos and A. Meskhi, *On sharp Olsen's and trace inequalities for multilinear fractional integrals*, Potential Analysis, 59(2023), 1039-1050, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11118-022-09991-y>.
- [2] G. Imerlishvili, A. Meskhi and Q. Xue, *Multilinear Fefferman-Stein type inequality and its generalizations*, Trans. A. Razmadze Math. Inst. 174 (2020), no. 1, 83-92.
- [3] V. Kokilashvili, M. Mastilo and A. Meskhi, *On the Boundedness of Multilinear Fractional Integral Operators*, J. Geometric Anal. 30 (2020), 667-679, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12220-019-00159-6>.
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- [5] A. Meskhi, *Boundedness weighted criteria for multilinear Riemann-Liouville integral operators*, Trans. A. Razmadze Math. Inst. 177 (2023), No. 1, 147-148.

Multilinear Fractional Integrals: Boundedness Criteria and Sharp Estimates

ALEXANDER MESKHI
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Introduction

Our aim is:

- ▶ to discuss sharp Olsen's inequality

$$\|g(I_\alpha f)\|_X \leq C \|g\|_E \|f\|_F, \quad (*)$$

where I_α is the Riesz potential operator, X , E and F are Morrey spaces. Under sharpness we mean that the Morrey norm $\|g\|_E$ in (*) can not be replaced by the smaller Morrey norm;

- ▶ to derive such an optimal inequality (0.1) for multilinear fractional integrals $\mathcal{I}_\alpha(f_1, \dots, f_m)$;
- ▶ to give necessary and sufficient condition on a weight v guaranteeing the trace inequality

$$\|\mathcal{I}_\alpha(f_1, \dots, f_m)\|_{E(V)} \leq C \prod_{j=1}^m \|f_j\|_{E_j},$$

where $E(V)$, is a weighted Morrey space, E_j , $j = 1, \dots, m$ are unweighted (classical) Morrey spaces;

Introduction

- ▶ to present necessary and sufficient condition on a measure μ guaranteeing the multilinear inequality

$$\|T_{\gamma,\mu}^m(f_1, \dots, f_m)\|_{E(\mu)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{E_k(\mu)},$$

for multilinear fractional integral operator $T_{\gamma,\mu}^m$ defined with respect to a measure μ , where $E(\mu)$, $E_k(\mu)$, $k = 1, \dots, m$ are Lebesgue/Lorentz spaces defined with respect to μ ;

- ▶ to present necessary and sufficient conditions on a weight function v defined on \mathbb{R}_+ governing the inequality

$$\|R_\alpha^{(m)}(f_1, \dots, f_m)\|_{L_v^q(\mathbb{R}_+)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{L^{p_k}(\mathbb{R}_+)}$$

for the multilinear one-sided multilinear fractional integral operator $R_\alpha^{(m)}$.

Introduction

The talk is based on the papers:

- ▶ L. Grafakos and A. Meskhi, On sharp Olsen's and trace inequalities for multilinear fractional integrals, *Potential Analysis*, **59** (2023), 1039-1050, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11118-022-09991-y>.
- ▶ V. Kokilashvili, M. Mastylo and A. Meskhi, On the Boundedness of Multilinear Fractional Integral Operators, *J. Geometric Anal.* **30**(2020), 667-679, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12220-019-00159-6>.
- ▶ A. Meskhi, Boundedness weighted criteria for multilinear Riemann-Liouville integral operators, *Trans. A. Razmadze Math. Inst.* **177** (2023), No. 1, 147–148.
- ▶ A. Meskhi and L. Natelashvili, Boundedness Criteria for Linear and Multilinear Fractional Integrals in Lorentz Spaces, *Trans. A. Razmadze Math. Inst.* **178**(2024), No. 2.

Olsen's inequality

In the literature Classical Olsen's inequality is called the following bilinear inequality:

$$\|g(I_\alpha f)\|_X \leq C \|g\|_E \|f\|_F, \quad (0.1)$$

where X , E and F are Morrey spaces (generally speaking, different) and I_α is the Riesz potential (fractional integral) operator:

$$I_\alpha(f)(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{f(y)}{|x-y|^{n-\alpha}} dy, \quad 0 < \alpha < n, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Introduction

Inequalities of type (0.1) play an important role in the study of perturbed Schrödinger equation (see Olsen, 1995).

We refer to the papers by Y. Sawano, S. Sugano, and H. Tanaka (2011) for subsequent improvements of Olsen's original inequality and applications.

Perturbed Schrödinger equation

This inequality comes from the estimate of the appropriate norm of the solution of

$$\Delta u(x) + V(x)u(x) = 0, \quad u(x) \Big|_{\partial\Omega} = 1, \quad (0.2)$$

where $\Omega = \{x : x \in \mathbb{R}^3, |x| < R\}$.

Perturbed Schrödinger equation

Classical Morrey space M_q^p , $1 \leq p \leq q < \infty$ is defined with respect to the norm:

$$\|f\|_{M_q^p} = \sup_Q |Q|^{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_Q |f(x)|^p dx \right)^{1/p}.$$

If $p = q$, then we have the classical Lebesgue space L^p .

Morrey spaces play an important role in relation to regularity problems of solutions of partial differential equations. They describe the integrability more precisely than Lebesgue spaces. These spaces were introduced by Ch. Morrey in 1938.

These spaces play also important role in Harmonic Analysis and PDEs (see e.g. Recent monograph by G. Di Fazio, D.I. Hakim, Y. Sawano, 2020, and references therein).

Olsen studied the problem when V is in the Morrey space $M_{3/2}^p$, which turned out to be right space for this problem.

Perturbed Schrödinger equation

In the proof of the theorem it is important to use the sharp estimate for the mapping

$$V(\cdot) \mapsto V(\cdot) \int_{\Omega} \frac{V(y)}{|\cdot - y|} dy$$

in Morrey spaces.

We are interested, generally speaking, in a variant of sharp (multilinear) Olsen type inequality:

$$\|g \mathcal{I}_{\alpha}(f_1, \dots, f_m)\|_{L_r^q} \leq C \|g\|_{L_{\ell}^q} \prod_{j=1}^m \|f_j\|_{L_{s_j}^{p_j}}$$

for multilinear fractional integrals:

$$\mathcal{I}_{\alpha}(\vec{f})(x) = \int_{(\mathbb{R}^n)^m} \frac{f_1(y_1) \cdots f_m(y_m)}{(|x - y_1| + \cdots + |x - y_m|)^{mn - \alpha}} d\vec{y}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^n,$$

where L_r^q , L_{ℓ}^q , $L_{s_j}^{p_j}$, $j = 1, \dots, m$, are Morrey spaces.

From the latter inequality it follows necessary and sufficient condition on weights function V for which the inequality

$$\|\mathcal{I}_\alpha(f_1, \dots, f_m)\|_{L^q_r(V)} \leq C \prod_{j=1}^m \|f_j\|_{L^{p_j}_{s_j}}$$

holds.

We also derive a characterization of the trace inequality

$$\|B_\alpha(f_1, f_2)\|_{L^q(d\mu)} \leq C \prod_{j=1}^2 \|f_j\|_{L^{p_j}_{s_j}},$$

in terms of a Borel measure μ , where B_α is another type bilinear fractional integral operator given by the formula

$$B_\alpha(f_1, f_2)(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{f_1(x+t)f_2(x-t)}{|t|^{n-\alpha}} dt, \quad 0 < \alpha < n,$$

Results are new even in the linear case, i.e. when $m = 1$.

Fractional Integrals

Let $0 < \alpha < n$. The fractional integral operator

$$I_\alpha(f)(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{f(y)}{|x-y|^{n-\alpha}} dy, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^n,$$

plays a fundamental role in Harmonic Analysis; it also finds applications in PDEs, such as in the theory of Sobolev embeddings, for instance see Maz'ya (1984).

A variant of this operator is the bilinear fractional integral operator

$$B_\alpha(f_1, f_2)(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{f_1(x+t)f_2(x-t)}{|t|^{n-\alpha}} dt, \quad 0 < \alpha < n,$$

introduced Grafakos 1992 (see also J.-G. Bak, 1992). Mapping properties of this operator were obtained by Kenig and Stein (1999) and Grafakos and Kalton (2001).

Multilinear Fractional Integrals

The operator B_α maps $L^{p_1}(\mathbb{R}^n) \times L^{p_2}(\mathbb{R}^n)$ to $L^q(\mathbb{R}^n)$ exactly when

$$\frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{p_1} + \frac{1}{p_2} - \frac{\alpha}{n}.$$

A very natural intermediate operator between $(I_{\alpha_1} f_1)(I_{\alpha_2} f_2)$ and $B_{\alpha_1+\alpha_2}(f_1, f_2)$ is

$$\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\vec{f})(x) = \int_{(\mathbb{R}^n)^m} \frac{f_1(y_1) \cdots f_m(y_m)}{(|x-y_1| + \cdots + |x-y_m|)^{mn-\alpha}} d\vec{y}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^n,$$

(expressed in its multilinear form) where $0 < \alpha < nm$, $\vec{f} := (f_1, \dots, f_m)$, $\vec{y} := (y_1, \dots, y_m)$, $d\vec{y} = dy_1 \cdots dy_m$.

Grand Lebesgue spaces

For the multilinear fractional operator \mathcal{I}_α : Moen (2009) obtained:
(i) one-weight criteria under vector Muckenhoupt-Wheeden condition;
(ii) "power bump" conditions for the two-weight inequalities.

Various type of weighted multilinear problems for these operators in Lebesgue spaces were studied by many authors (see e.g. the papers by K. Moen, G. Pradolini, X. Chen and Q. Xue, Y. Sawano, E. Nakai, V. Kokilashvili, M. Mastyło and A. Meskhi., Y. Shi and X. Tao, Q. He and D. Yan etc etc).

Morrey Spaces

Let $1 \leq q \leq r < \infty$ and let μ be a Borel measure on \mathbb{R}^n . We denote by $L_r^q(d\mu)$ the Morrey space of all measurable functions f on \mathbb{R}^n such that

$$\|f\|_{L_r^q(\mu)} := \sup_{Q \in \mathcal{Q}} \frac{1}{|Q|^{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{r}}} \left(\int_Q |f(x)|^q d\mu(x) \right)^{1/q} < \infty. \quad (0.3)$$

If V is a locally integrable a.e. positive function on \mathbb{R}^n , i.e. a weight on \mathbb{R}^n , then we denote $L_r^q(\mu)$ by $L_r^q(V)$.

If $V \equiv 1$, then we have unweighted Morrey space L_r^q .

For $q = r$, L_r^q is the classical Lebesgue space L^q .

The following emdeddings are immediate:

$$L_r^p \subset L_r^q, \quad 1 \leq q \leq p < \infty.$$

Fractional Integrals in Morrey Spaces: Known Results

Proposition A. (Spanne, unpublished) Let $0 < \alpha < n$, $1 < p_0 \leq s_0 < \infty$, $1 < q_0 \leq r_0 < \infty$. Suppose that $\frac{1}{s_0} - \frac{1}{r_0} = \frac{1}{p_0} - \frac{1}{q_0} = \frac{\alpha}{n}$. Then I_α is bounded from $L_{s_0}^{p_0}$ to $L_{r_0}^{q_0}$.

Proposition B. (Adams, 1975) Let $0 < \alpha < n$, $1 < p_0 \leq s_0 < \infty$, $1 < q_0 \leq r_0 < \infty$. Suppose that $\frac{1}{r_0} = \frac{1}{s_0} - \frac{\alpha}{n}$, $\frac{q_0}{r_0} = \frac{p_0}{s_0}$. Then I_α is bounded from $L_{s_0}^{p_0}$ to $L_{r_0}^{q_0}$.

In the unweighted case the following multilinear result is also known.

Fractional Integrals in Morrey Spaces: Known Results

Proposition C. (Tang) Let $0 < \alpha < mn$, $1 < q \leq r < \infty$, $1 < p_i \leq s_i < \infty$, $i = 1, \dots, m$ be such that

$$\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{r} = \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{q} = \frac{\alpha}{n},$$

where p and s are defined by

$$\frac{1}{p} := \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{1}{p_i}, \quad \frac{1}{s} := \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{1}{s_i}, \quad m \geq 2. \quad (0.4)$$

Then there exists a positive constant C such that for all $f_j \in L_{s_j}^{p_j}$, $j = 1, \dots, m$, we have

$$\|\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\vec{f})\|_{L_r^q} \leq C \prod_{j=1}^m \|f_j\|_{L_{s_j}^{p_j}}.$$

Main Results. Olsen Multilinear Inequality

One of the main our results reads as follows:

Theorem

Let $1 < q \leq r < \infty$, $1 < p_i \leq s_i < \infty$, $i = 1, \dots, m$, $1 < p < q$, $0 < \alpha < \frac{n}{s}$. Let $\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{r} = \frac{\alpha}{n} - \frac{1}{\ell}$, where $\frac{1}{s} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{s_j}$, $\frac{1}{p} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{p_j}$. Then there exists a positive constant C depending only on $n, \alpha, q, r, p_i, s_i, i = 1, \dots, m$, such that for all $f_j \in L_{s_j}^{p_j}$, $j = 1, \dots, m$, inequality

$$\|g \mathcal{I}_\alpha(\vec{f})\|_{L_r^q} \leq C \|g\|_{L_\ell^q} \prod_{j=1}^m \|f_j\|_{L_{s_j}^{p_j}},$$

holds. Moreover, this estimate is optimal in the sense that the space L_ℓ^q in the norm $\|g\|_{L_\ell^q}$ can not be replaced by the larger one.

Main Results. Olsen Multilinear Inequality

Corollary

Let $1 < q \leq r < \infty$, $1 < p \leq s < \infty$, $1 < p < q$ and $0 < \alpha < \frac{n}{s}$. Let $\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{r} = \frac{\alpha}{n} - \frac{1}{\ell}$. Then there is a positive constant C depending only on n, α, q, r, p, s such that for all $f \in L_s^p$ and $g \in L_\ell^q$ we have

$$\|g I_\alpha(f)\|_{L_r^q} \leq C \|g\|_{L_\ell^q} \|f\|_{L_s^p}$$

Moreover, this estimate is optimal in the sense that the space L_ℓ^q in the norm $\|g\|_{L_\ell^q}$ can not be replaced by the larger one.

Trace inequality criteria

Theorem

Let $1 < q \leq r < \infty$, $1 < p_i \leq s_i < \infty$, $i = 1, \dots, m$, $1 < p < q$, $0 < \alpha < \frac{n}{s}$. Let $\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{r}$, where $\frac{1}{s} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{s_j}$, $\frac{1}{p} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{p_j}$. Suppose that V is a weight function on \mathbb{R}^n . Then the inequality

$$\|\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\vec{f})\|_{L_r^q(V)} \leq C \prod_{j=1}^m \|f_j\|_{L_{s_j}^{p_j}}. \quad (0.5)$$

holds if and only if

$$[V]_{\alpha,p,q} := \sup_{Q \in \mathcal{Q}} \left(\int_Q V(x) dx \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} |Q|^{\frac{\alpha}{n} - \frac{1}{p}} < \infty \quad (0.6)$$

is satisfied.

Moreover, under either assumption, we have the norm equivalence

$$\|\mathcal{I}_\alpha\| \approx [V]_{\alpha,p,q}.$$

Trace inequality criteria

- ▶ Linear case in Lebesgue spaces, D. Adams, em *Studia Math.*, 1972.
- ▶ Linear case in Morrey space: Eridani, V. Kokilashvili and A.Meskhi, *Expo Math.* 2009.
- ▶ Multilinear case in Lebesgue Spaces: V. Kokilashvili, M. Mastyło and A.Meskhi, *Nonlinear Anal.* 2014.

Main Results. Olsen's inequality for B_α

We also have a result for the bilinear fractional integral operator

$$B_\alpha: B_\alpha(f_1, f_2)(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{f_1(x+t)f_2(x-t)}{|t|^{n-\alpha}} dt, \quad 0 < \alpha < n,$$

Theorem

Let $1 < q \leq r$, $1 < p_i \leq s_i < \infty$, $i = 1, 2$. Let $1 < p < q < \infty$ and $0 < \alpha < \min\{\frac{1}{s_1}, \frac{1}{s_2}\}$, $\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{r} = \frac{\alpha}{n} - \frac{1}{\ell}$, where $\frac{1}{p} = \frac{1}{p_1} + \frac{1}{p_2}$, $\frac{1}{s} = \frac{1}{s_1} + \frac{1}{s_2}$. Then there is a positive constant C depending only on $n, \alpha, q, r, p_1, p_2, s_1, s_2$ such that for all $f_1, f_2, g \geq 0$ we have

$$\|g B_\alpha(f_1, f_2)\|_{L_r^q} \leq C \|g\|_{L_\ell^q} \|f_1\|_{L_{s_1}^{p_1}} \|f_2\|_{L_{s_2}^{p_2}}. \quad (0.7)$$

Main Results. Generalization of the Adams Trace Inequality

Theorem

Let $1 < q \leq r$, $1 < p_i \leq s_i < \infty$, $i = 1, 2$, and let $1 < p < q < \infty$. Let $0 < \alpha < \min\{\frac{1}{s_1}, \frac{1}{s_2}\}$, $\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{r}$, where $\frac{1}{p} = \frac{1}{p_1} + \frac{1}{p_2}$, $\frac{1}{s} = \frac{1}{s_1} + \frac{1}{s_2}$. Then there is a positive constant C depending on $n, \alpha, q, r, p_1, p_2, s_1, s_2$ such that for all $f_1, f_2 \geq 0$,

$$\|B_\alpha(f_1, f_2)\|_{L_r^q(d\mu)} \leq C[\mu] \|f_1\|_{L_{s_1}^{p_1}} \|f_2\|_{L_{s_2}^{p_2}}, \quad (0.8)$$

holds, where $[\mu]$ is defined by:

$$[\mu] := \sup_Q (\mu(Q))^{\frac{1}{q}} |Q|^{\frac{\alpha}{n} - \frac{1}{p}}.$$

Multilinear Potentials With Measure

Let (X, d, μ) be a quasi-metric measure space. Let

$$T_{\gamma, \mu}^m(\vec{f})(x) = \int_{X^m} \frac{f_1(y_1) \cdots f_m(y_m) d\mu(\vec{y})}{(d(x, y_1) + \cdots + d(x, y_m))^{m-\gamma}}, \quad 0 < \gamma < m, \quad x \in X,$$

where $\vec{f} = (f_1, \dots, f_m)$, $d\mu(\vec{y}) = d\mu(y_1) \cdots d\mu(y_m)$.

Problem: To give a complete characterization of measure μ for which $T_{\gamma, \mu}^m$ is bounded from $\prod_{j=1}^m E_j(\mu, X)$ to $E(\mu, X)$, where $E_j(\mu, X)$ and $E(\mu, X)$ are generally speaking, Lorentz spaces defined on (X, d, μ) .

Linear case: $m = 1$

Linear fractional integral operator:

$$T_{\gamma, \mu}(g)(x) = \int_X \frac{g(y)}{d(x, y)^{1-\gamma}} d\mu(y) \quad 0 < \gamma < 1, \quad x \in X.$$

- ▶ A complete characterization of a measure μ guaranteeing the boundedness of the fractional integral operator $T_{\gamma, \mu}$ from $L^{r, s}(\mu, X)$ to $L^{p, q}(\mu, X)$.
- ▶ Characterization of the Sobolev-type inequality in Lorentz spaces. In particular, criteria for

$$\|T_{\gamma, \mu}(g)\|_{L^{p, q}(\mu, X)} \leq \|g\|_{L^{r, s}(\mu, X)}, \quad p = \frac{r}{1 - \gamma r}. \quad (0.9)$$

History of this problem:

Lebesgue spaces:

- ▶ Linear case, Euclidean spaces: V. Kokilashvili, 1988.
- ▶ Linear case, general QMMS: V. Kokilashvili and A. M., *Fract. Calc. Appl. Anal.* 2001
- ▶ Linear case when q is a Sobolev Exponent of p : J. García-Cureva and E. Gatto, *Studia Math.*, 2004.
- ▶ Multilinear setting: V. Kokilashvili, M. Mastyo and A. Meskhi, *J. Geom. Anal.* 2020.

Multilinear Potentials With Measure

Let (X, d, μ) be a topological space with a quasi-metric d and a complete measure μ . Let κ be a triangle inequality constant for d , i.e., $d(x, y) \leq \kappa(d(x, z) + d(z, y))$ for all $x, y, z \in X$. We will assume that the class of compactly supported continuous functions is dense in $L^1(\mu, X)$.

In the sequel we assume that all the balls $B(x, R)$ with center x and radius R are μ -measurable with finite measure, and that for every neighborhood V of $x \in X$, there exists $R > 0$ such that $B(x, R) \subset V$.

We say that the measure μ is Ahlfors upper β -regular if there is a positive constant c such that

$$\mu(B(x, R)) \leq cR^\beta \quad (0.10)$$

for all $x \in X$ and $R > 0$.

Multilinear Potentials With Measure

Let f be a μ -measurable function on X and let $1 \leq p, s \leq \infty$. We say that f belongs to the Lorentz space $L^{p,s}(\mu, X)$ if

$$\|f\|_{L^{p,s}(\mu, X)} = \begin{cases} \left(s \int_0^\infty (\mu\{x \in X : |f(x)| > \tau\})^{s/p} \tau^{s-1} d\tau \right)^{1/s}, & \text{if } s < \infty, \\ \sup_{s>0} s (\mu\{x \in X : |f(x)| > s\})^{1/p}, & \text{if } s = \infty \end{cases}$$

is finite. It is easy to see that $L^{p,p}(\mu, X)$ coincides with the Lebesgue space $L^p(\mu, X)$ with measure μ .

Multilinear Potentials With Measure

Denote by f_μ^* a weighted non-increasing rearrangement of f with respect to the measure μ . Then by integration by parts it can be checked that:

$$\|f\|_{L^{p,s}(\mu)} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{s}{p} \int_0^\infty \left(t^{1/p} f_\mu^*(t) \right)^s \frac{dt}{t} \right)^{1/s}, & \text{if } s < \infty, \\ \sup_{t>0} \{ t^{1/p} f_\mu^*(t) \}, & \text{if } s = \infty, \end{cases}$$

Multilinear Potentials With Measure

Now we formulate our main statements.

Theorem

Let (X, d, μ) be a quasi-metric measure space, $0 < \gamma < m$, $1 < r_j, s_j < \infty$, $j = 1, \dots, m$. We set $\frac{1}{r} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{r_j}$ and $\frac{1}{s} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{s_j}$. Suppose that $1 < r < p < \infty$ and q be such that $\frac{r}{p} = \frac{s}{q}$. Then the following statements are equivalent:

(i)

$$\|T_{\gamma, \mu}^m(\vec{f})\|_{L^p(\mu, X)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{L^{r_k}(\mu, X)};$$

(ii)

$$\|T_{\gamma, \mu}^m(\vec{f})\|_{L^{p, q}(\mu, X)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{L^{r_k, s_k}(\mu, X)};$$

(iii) μ is Ahlfors upper β -regular with $\beta = \frac{rp(m-\gamma)}{rpm+r-p}$.

Sobolev-type inequality

This statement implies the following statement.

Theorem

Let (X, d, μ) be a quasi-metric measure space, $0 < \gamma < 1/r$, and let $1 < r_j, s_j < \infty$, $j = 1, \dots, m$. We set $\frac{1}{r} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{r_j}$ and $\frac{1}{s} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{s_j}$. Suppose that $1 < r < \frac{1}{\gamma}$, and $\frac{1}{p} = \frac{1}{r} - \gamma$. Let q be such that $\frac{r}{p} = \frac{s}{q}$. Then the following statements are equivalent:

(i)

$$\|T_{\gamma, \mu}^m(\vec{f})\|_{L^p(\mu, X)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{L^{r_k}(\mu, X)};$$

(ii)

$$\|T_{\gamma, \mu}^m(\vec{f})\|_{L^{p, q}(\mu, X)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{L^{r_k, s_k}(\mu, X)};$$

(iii) μ is Ahlfors upper 1-regular.

Fractional integral operator in \mathbb{R}^n

Let us recall multilinear fractional integral in \mathbb{R}^n :

$$\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\vec{f})(x) = \int_{(\mathbb{R}^n)^m} \frac{f_1(y_1) \cdots f_m(y_m)}{(|x - y_1| + \cdots + |x - y_m|)^{mn-\alpha}} d\vec{y}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Then as a corollary we have the following statements:

Fractional integral operator in \mathbb{R}^n

Theorem

Let $0 < \alpha < mn$, and let $1 < r_j, s_j < \infty$, $j = 1, \dots, m$. Let μ be a Beorel measure on \mathbb{R}^n . We set $\frac{1}{r} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{r_j}$ and $\frac{1}{s} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{s_j}$.

Suppose that $1 < r < \frac{n}{\alpha}$, and $\frac{1}{p} = \frac{1}{r} - \frac{\alpha}{n}$. Let q be such that $\frac{r}{p} = \frac{s}{q}$. Then the following statements are equivalent:

(i)

$$\|\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\vec{f})\|_{L^p(\mu, \mathbb{R}^n)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{L^{r_k}(\mu, \mathbb{R}^n)};$$

(ii)

$$\|\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\vec{f})\|_{L^{p,q}(\mu, \mathbb{R}^n)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{L^{r_k, s_k}(\mu, \mathbb{R}^n)};$$

(iii) μ is Ahlfors upper β_n -regular, where $\beta_n = \frac{rp(mn-\alpha)}{rpm+r-p}$.

Sobolev-type inequality

This statement implies the following statement.

Theorem

Let μ be a Beorel measure on \mathbb{R}^n . $0 < \alpha < n/r$, and let $1 < r_j, s_j < \infty, j = 1, \dots, m$. We set $\frac{1}{r} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{r_j}$ and $\frac{1}{s} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{s_j}$. Suppose that $1 < r < \frac{n}{\alpha}$, and $\frac{1}{p} = \frac{1}{r} - \frac{\alpha}{n}$. Let q be such that $\frac{r}{p} = \frac{s}{q}$. Then the following statements are equivalent:

(i)

$$\|\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\vec{f})\|_{L^p(\mu, \mathbb{R}^n)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{L^{r_k}(\mu, \mathbb{R}^n)};$$

(ii)

$$\|\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\vec{f})\|_{L^{p,q}(\mu, \mathbb{R}^n)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{L^{r_k, s_k}(\mu, \mathbb{R}^n)};$$

(iii) μ is Ahlfors upper n -regular.

Boundedness in Modified Morrey spaces

Let k be a constant such that $k > \kappa_1$. Suppose that $0 < \lambda < 1$, $1 < p < \infty$. We say that a locally integrable function f on X belongs to the modified Morrey space $L^{p,\lambda}(X, \mu)$ defined with respect to measure μ if

$$\|f\|_{L^{p,\lambda}(X, \mu)} := \sup_B \left(\frac{1}{\mu(B)^\lambda} \int_B |f(x)|^p d\mu(x) \right)^{1/p}.$$

If $\lambda = 0$, then this is classical Lebesgue space defined with respect to measure μ .

Boundedness in Modified Morrey spaces

Morrey spaces on non-homogeneous spaces:

- ▶ Y. Sawano and H. Tanaka, *Acta Math. Sinica*, 2005.
- ▶ Y. Sawano, *Nonlinear Diff. Equ. Appl.*, 2008.

Boundedness in Modified Morrey spaces

Theorem

Let $1 < p_j < q < \infty$, for each $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, and let $0 < \gamma < 1$.

Suppose that σ_j are numbers such that

$0 < \sigma_j < \frac{p_j}{m} \left[m + \frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{p} \right] + 1$ for each $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$. Then the condition that a measure μ is upper Ahlfors β -regular guarantees the boundedness of $T_{\gamma, \mu}$ from $L^{p_1, \sigma_1}(X, \mu) \times \dots \times L^{p_m, \sigma_m}(X, \mu)$ to $L^{q, \lambda}(X, \mu)$, where $\lambda = \eta q$ with $\eta = \sum_{j=1}^m \sigma_j / p_j$.

Multilinear one-sided fractional integrals

Let us denote by R_α multilinear Riemann-Liouville integral operator:

$$R_\alpha^{(m)}(f_1, \dots, f_m)(x) = \int_{(0,x)^m} \frac{f_1(x-t_1) \cdots f_m(x-t_m)}{(t_1 + \cdots + t_m)^{m-\alpha}} dt_1 \cdots dt_m, \quad x > 0,$$

which is a one-sided variant of

$$\mathcal{I}_\gamma(f_1, \dots, f_m)(x) = \int_{(\mathbb{R}^n)^m} \frac{f_1(y_1) \cdots f_m(y_m)}{(|x-y_1| + \cdots + |x-y_m|)^{mn-\gamma}} dy_1 \cdots dy_m,$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $0 < \gamma < nm$.

See also Z. W. Fu, Sh. L. Gong, Sh. Z. Lu and W. Yuan, *Forum Mathematicum*, 2015, for $R_\alpha^{(m)}$.

If $m = 1$, we denote $R_\alpha^{(m)}$ by R_α .

Multilinear one-sided fractional integrals

Taking $\alpha = m$ we have multilinear Hardy operator $H^{(m)} := R_\alpha^{(m)}$:

$$H^{(m)}(f_1, \dots, f_m)(x) = \int_0^x \cdots \int_0^x f_1(t_1) \cdots f_m(t_m) dt_1 \cdots dt_m, \quad x > 0.$$

(see M. I. Aguilar Castro, P. Ortega Salvador and C. Ramires Torreblan, *J. Math. Ana. Appl.* 2012.)

The two-weight problem

- ▶ The two-weight problem for H : B. Muckenhoupt (1972), J. Bradley (1978), V. Kokilashvili (1979).
- ▶ The two-weight problem for R_α , $\alpha > 1$ (without singularity), V. Stepanov, 1989 (see also the monographs B. Opic and A. Kufner, *Longman Sci. and Tech., Harlow*; 1990; A. Kufner and L. E. Persson, 2000).
- ▶ The two-weight problem for R_α in the case of singularity $0 < \alpha < 1$ is still open unlike the case of one-sided fractional operators on \mathbb{R} (see M. Lorente, 1997, and monograph D. E. Edmunds, V. Kokilashvili and A. Meskhi, *Kluwer*, 2002 and references therein).
- ▶ A complete characterization of a weight v guaranteeing the boundedness of R_α from L^p to L^q_v was given by A. Meskhi *Georgian Math. J.* (1998) and independently by D. Prokhorov, *J. London Math. Soc.*, 2001.
- ▶ Two-weight criteria for $H^{(m)}$ in the bilinear case were derived by M. I. Aguilar Canstro, P. Ortega Salvador and C. Ramires Torreblan, *J. Math. Ana. Appl.* 2012.

Multilinear Riemann-Liouville operator

Theorem

Let $1 < \min\{p_1, \dots, p_m\} \leq \max\{p_1, \dots, p_m\} \leq q < \infty$ and let $\alpha > 1/p$, where p is defined by $\frac{1}{p} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{p_j}$. Then the inequality

$$\|R_\alpha^{(m)}(f_1, \dots, f_m)\|_{L^q_v(\mathbb{R}_+)} \leq C \prod_{k=1}^m \|f_k\|_{L^{p_k}(\mathbb{R}_+)}, \quad f_k \in L^{p_k}(\mathbb{R}_+), \quad k = 1, \dots, m,$$

holds if and only if

$$\sup_k \left(\int_{2^k}^{2^{k+1}} v(x) dx \right)^{1/q} 2^{k(\alpha-1/p)} < \infty. \quad (0.11)$$

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Thank you!

Non-linear variants of factorization theorems for operators on Banach function spaces

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This talk explores several approaches aimed at extending classical factorization results for linear operators to nonlinear ones. These classical results are building blocks of the current theory of (linear) operators on Banach function spaces. We will present some results on two relevant classes of nonlinear maps: multilinear maps and Lipschitz maps. From a technical point of view, our results could be understood in terms of what kind of separation argument is used to obtain factorization theorems: summability inequalities for operators (involving Pietsch-type theorems and Pisier-type theorems), Maurey-Rosenthal factorizations through various classical function spaces characterized by geometric lattice inequalities, and Nikishin-type results involving some notion of type for domain spaces. The most fruitful class of function spaces we have used are Orlicz spaces and some variants and generalizations of these spaces, such as Marcinkiewicz spaces. Our goal is to provide an overview of the state of the art of factorization techniques concerning nonlinear operators on Banach function spaces.

Non-linear variants of factorization theorems for operators on Banach function spaces

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This talk explores several approaches aimed at extending classical factorization results for linear operators to nonlinear ones. We focus on two relevant classes of nonlinear maps: multilinear maps and Lipschitz maps. Our results could be understood in terms of what kind of separation argument is used to obtain factorization theorems:

- ▶ summability inequalities: Pietsch-type theorems, dominated operators,
- ▶ lattice geometric inequalities: Maurey-Rosenthal factorization, Pisier-type theorems, and
- ▶ measure inequalities: Nikishin-type results.

Our goal is to provide an overview of the state of the art on factorization of nonlinear operators that we have studied in recent years, together with Prof. M. Mastyło.

Part 1. Ideals of multilinear mappings via Orlicz spaces

φ -summing and φ -semi-integral multilinear operators

φ -dominated multilinear operators

Part 2. Lipschitz (q, p) -summing operators

(q, p) -summing operators on $C(K)$ -spaces

Pisier's result for Lipschitz maps

Part 3. Nikishin theorem for Lipschitz operators

- ▶ New summability properties of multilinear operators related to Orlicz norms: φ -summing, φ -semi-integral and φ -dominated multilinear maps generated by Orlicz functions.
- ▶ A variant of **Pietsch's domination theorem** for φ -summing operators, providing also a characterization of φ -dominated operators in terms of factorizations.
- ▶ Vector-valued inequalities associated to these maps, which are applied to obtain general variants of multiple summing operators.

- ▶ Motivated by various applications and generalizations of the concept of absolutely p -summing operators (defined using ℓ_p -type norms), different classes has been defined (examples: (E, F) -summing operators,...).
- ▶ The study of a class of linear operators based on Orlicz space norms was initiated several years ago. For example, Geiss introduced Orlicz spaces L_{φ_q} with an exponential function φ_q , given by $\varphi_q(t) = \exp(t^q) - 1$ for all $t \geq 0$ with $q \in [1, \infty)$, with an exponential function φ_q , given by $\varphi_q(t) = \exp(t^q) - 1$ for all $t \geq 0$ with $q \in [1, \infty)$, for proving the required inequalities.

Operators on martingales, Φ -summing operators, and the contraction principle, Probab. Math. Statist. 18, no. 1, 2045, Acta Univ. Wratislav. 149–171 (1998)

- ▶ On the other hand, the ideal structure of **multilinear** operators acting between Banach spaces has been investigated intensively in recent years. Applications.
- ▶ New definitions of classes of multilinear operators based on **summability properties and integral dominations provided by Orlicz space norms**. Multilinear variants of the main linear results?
- ▶ Linear results are related to summability properties and integral dominations involving L^p -type norms. We consider the more general Orlicz variant of these notions.

A **Banach ideal of multilinear mappings** \mathcal{I} is a class of continuous multilinear operators between Banach spaces such that for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and Banach spaces X_1, \dots, X_n, Y , the associated component

$$\mathcal{I}(X_1, \dots, X_n; Y) := \mathcal{L}(X_1, \dots, X_n; Y) \cap \mathcal{I},$$

satisfies :

- (i) $\mathcal{I}(X_1, \dots, X_n; Y)$ is a linear subspace of $\mathcal{L}(X_1, \dots, X_n; Y)$ containing the n -linear mappings of finite type, and
- (ii) if $A \in \mathcal{I}(X_1, \dots, X_n; Y)$ and $u_j \in \mathcal{L}(G_j; X_j)$ for each $1 \leq j \leq n$, and $v \in \mathcal{L}(Y; H)$, then $v \circ A \circ (u_1, \dots, u_n)$ belongs to $\mathcal{I}(G_1, \dots, G_n; H)$ and

$$\|v \circ A \circ (u_1, \dots, u_n)\|_{\mathcal{I}} \leq \|v\| \|A\|_{\mathcal{I}} \|u_1\| \cdots \|u_n\|,$$

where $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{I}}$ is given by a rule for defining the ideal norm.

- ▶ **Orlicz spaces.** Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu)$ be a measure space and let $\varphi: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ be an *Orlicz function* (that is, a convex increasing and continuous positive function with $\varphi(0) = 0$).
- ▶ The Orlicz space $L_\varphi(\mu)$ (L_φ for short) on a measure space $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu)$ is defined to be the space of $f \in L^0(\mu)$ such that $\int_\Omega \varphi(\lambda|f|) d\mu < \infty$ for some $\lambda > 0$ and is equipped with the Luxemburg norm given by

$$\|x\|_{L_\varphi} := \inf \left\{ \varepsilon > 0; \int_\Omega \varphi\left(\frac{|f|}{\varepsilon}\right) d\mu \leq 1 \right\}.$$

If Ω is a finite or countable set and $\mathcal{A} = 2^\Omega$, we write $\ell_\varphi(\mu)$.

We denote by $\ell_\varphi^m(\nu)$ the m -dimensional Orlicz sequence space over the probability measure space $([m], 2^{[m]}, \nu)$, $([m] := \{1, \dots, m\})$ and $\nu(\{j\}) = \nu_j$ for each $j \in [m]$, endowed with the norm

$$\|\xi\|_{\ell_\varphi^m(\nu)} := \inf \left\{ \lambda > 0; \sum_{j=1}^m \varphi(|\xi_j|/\lambda) \nu_j \leq 1 \right\}, \quad \xi = \{\xi_j\}_{j=1}^m.$$

An n -linear operator $T: X_1 \times \dots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **φ -summing** if there exists a constant $C > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \left\{ \|T(x_j^1, \dots, x_j^n)\|_Y \right\}_{j=1}^m \right\|_{\ell_\varphi^m(\nu)} \\ & \leq C \sup_{(x_j^*)_{j=1}^n \in B_{X_1^*} \times \dots \times B_{X_n^*}} \left\| \left\{ \langle x_j^1, x_1^* \rangle \cdots \langle x_j^n, x_n^* \rangle \right\}_{j=1}^m \right\|_{\ell_\varphi^m(\nu)} \end{aligned}$$

for every m -dimensional Orlicz space $\ell_\varphi^m(\nu)$ and for all $x_j^i \in X_i$, $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $1 \leq j \leq m$. We denote by $\mathcal{L}_\varphi(X_1, \dots, X_n; Y)$ the space of all φ -summing n -linear operators from $X_1 \times \dots \times X_n$ into Y . It is a Banach space endowed with the norm $\pi_\varphi(T)$.

Below, \odot denotes the pointwise product of functions.

Theorem

Let φ be a normalized Orlicz function (i.e., $\varphi(1) = 1$) and let $T: X_1 \times \cdots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ be a φ -summing multilinear operator with $\pi_\varphi(T) \leq M$. If, for each $1 \leq j \leq n$, $J_j: X_j \rightarrow C(K_j)$ is an isometric embedding of a Banach space X_j into $C(K_j)$, then there exists a regular Borel probability measure μ on the product $K_1 \times \cdots \times K_n$ such that, for all $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in X_1 \times \cdots \times X_n$,

$$\|T(x_1, \dots, x_n)\|_Y \leq M \left\| \odot (J_1(x_1), \dots, J_n(x_n)) \right\|_{L_\varphi(\mu)}.$$

We write $k_X: X \rightarrow C(B_{X^*})$ for the canonical embedding.

Theorem

Let φ be a normalized Orlicz function. Suppose that $T: X_1 \times \cdots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ is a φ -summing multilinear operator with $\pi_\varphi(T) \leq C$. Then there exists a regular Borel probability measure μ on $B_{X_1^*} \times \cdots \times B_{X_n^*}$ equipped with the product of the weak* topologies so that for every $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in X_1 \times \cdots \times X_n$,

$$\|T(x_1, \dots, x_n)\|_Y \leq C \left\| \odot (k_{X_1}(x_1), \dots, k_{X_n}(x_n)) \right\|_{L_\varphi(\mu)}.$$

This result motivates the following definition.

A multilinear operator $T: X_1 \times \cdots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ is said to be $F(\mu)$ -**semi-integral** whenever there exist a constant $C > 0$, a measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(B_{X_1^*} \times \cdots \times B_{X_n^*})$ and a Banach lattice $F(\mu)$ in $L^0(B_{X_1^*} \times \cdots \times B_{X_n^*})$ s.t. for every $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in X_1 \times \cdots \times X_n$,

$$\|T(x_1, \dots, x_n)\|_Y \leq C \|\odot(k_{X_1}(x_1), \dots, k_{X_n}(x_n))\|_{F(\mu)}.$$

The infimum of the constant C for which the inequality holds is denoted by $\pi_{si, F}(T)$.

We write φ -**semi-integral** instead of $F(\mu)$ -semi-integral if $F(\mu) = L_\varphi(\mu)$.

Corollary

Let φ be a normalized Orlicz function. If $T: X_1 \times \cdots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ is a φ -summing multilinear operator, then T is φ -semi-integral with $\pi_{si, \varphi}(T) \leq \pi_\varphi(T)$.

Weakly sequentially continuous operators between Banach spaces are those that carry weakly convergent sequences to norm convergent sequences.

Proposition

Suppose that $T: X_1 \times \cdots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ is a weakly sequentially continuous multilinear operator. If for each j with $1 \leq j \leq n$, $\{x_k^j\}_k$ is a weakly Cauchy sequence in X_j , then $\{T(x_k^1, \dots, x_k^n)\}_k$ is a norm convergent sequence in Y .

Corollary

Suppose that each Banach space X_1, \dots, X_n does not contain isomorphic copy of ℓ_1 . Then every weakly sequentially continuous multilinear operator $T: X_1 \times \dots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ is compact.

Theorem

The following statements are true for a φ -summing multilinear operator $T: X_1 \times \dots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$.

- (i) T is a weakly sequentially continuous operator;
- (ii) If each Banach space X_1, \dots, X_n does not contain an isomorphic copy of ℓ_1 , then T is compact.

Let us give a fundamental example of a φ -semi-integral multilinear operator.

Lemma

Let φ be an Orlicz function and let K_1, \dots, K_n be compact Hausdorff spaces. Then for every Borel probability measure on $K_1 \times \dots \times K_n$ the multilinear operator

$$\odot: C(K_1) \times \dots \times C(K_n) \rightarrow L_\varphi(K_1 \times \dots \times K_n, \mu)$$

is φ -semi-integral with $\pi_{si, \varphi}(\odot) \leq 1$.

We say that φ is **C-supermultiplicative** if $\varphi(Cuv) \geq \varphi(u)\varphi(v)$ for all $u, v > 0$ and some $C > 0$.

A vector-valued estimate for φ -semi-integral multilinear operators.

Theorem

$T: X_1 \times \dots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ φ -semi-integral, $\pi_{si,\varphi}(T) \leq M$, φ C -supermultiplicative Orlicz function, $(\Omega_j, \Sigma_j, \nu_j)$ σ -finite. $L_\varphi(\nu)$ is an Orlicz space in $L^0(\Omega_1 \times \dots \times \Omega_n, \nu)$ with $\nu = \nu_1 \times \dots \times \nu_n$.

Then :

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \| T(f_1(\cdot), \dots, f_n(\cdot)) \|_Y \right\|_{L_\varphi(\nu)} \\ & \leq C M \sup_{(x_1^*, \dots, x_n^*) \in B_{X_1^*} \times \dots \times B_{X_n^*}} \| \langle f_1(\cdot), x_1^* \rangle \cdots \langle f_n(\cdot), x_n^* \rangle \|_{L_\varphi(\nu)} \end{aligned}$$

for $(f_1, \dots, f_n) \in L^0(\nu_1, X_1) \times \dots \times L^0(\nu_n, X_n)$.

Corollary

Let φ be a C -supermultiplicative Orlicz function at ∞ for some $C > 0$. Then a multilinear operator $T: X_1 \times \dots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ is φ -summing if and only if T is φ -semi-integral.

Theorem

Let φ be a normalized Orlicz function which is **1-supermultiplicative**. The following statements are equivalent for a multilinear operator $T: X_1 \times \dots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$.

- (i) T is φ -summing with $\pi_\varphi(T) \leq C$;
- (ii) T is φ -semi-integral with $\pi_{si,\varphi}(T) \leq C$;
- (iii) For every (equivalently, for some) isometric embeddings $J_j: X_j \rightarrow C(K_j)$ for each $1 \leq j \leq n$ there exist a Borel probability measure μ on the product $K_1 \times \dots \times K_n$ of compact Hausdorff spaces and a constant $C > 0$ such that, for all $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in X_1 \times \dots \times X_n$,

$$\| T(x_1, \dots, x_n) \|_Y \leq C \| \odot (J_1(x_1), \dots, J_n(x_n)) \|_{L_\varphi(\mu)}.$$

φ -dominated operators

For a given Orlicz function φ , a multilinear operator $T: X_1 \times \dots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ is said to be φ -dominated if there is a constant C and Borel probability measures μ_j on $B_{X_j^*}$ endowed with the weak* topology for each $1 \leq j \leq n$ such that for all $x_1 \in X_1, \dots, x_n \in X_n$, we have

$$\|T(x_1, \dots, x_n)\|_Y \leq C \|\langle x_1, \cdot \rangle\|_{L_\varphi(\mu_1)} \cdots \|\langle x_n, \cdot \rangle\|_{L_\varphi(\mu_n)}.$$

Theorem

Let $T: X_1 \times \dots \times X_n \rightarrow Y$ be a multilinear map. Then the following statements are equivalent.

- (i) T is φ -dominated;

- (ii) T admits a factorization:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X_1 \times \dots \times X_n & \xrightarrow{T} & Y \\ \downarrow i_1 \times \dots \times i_n & \nearrow \hat{T} & \\ S_1 \times \dots \times S_n & & \end{array}$$

\hat{T} multilinear, S_1, \dots, S_n the usual subs. of $C(B_{X_j^*})$ with the Orlicz norms $\|\cdot\|_{L_\varphi(\mu_j)}$ and i_j are the maps $X_j \ni x_j \mapsto \langle x_j, \cdot \rangle$;

- (iii) T admits a factorization:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X_1 \times \dots \times X_n & \xrightarrow{T} & Y \\ \downarrow u_1 \times \dots \times u_n & \nearrow \hat{T} & \\ E_1 \times \dots \times E_n & & \end{array}$$

where E_1, \dots, E_n are Banach spaces and u_1, \dots, u_n are φ semi-integral linear operators.

Lemma

Let $1 \leq p < \infty$ and let φ be an Orlicz function. Define ϕ by $\phi(t) = \varphi(t^{1/p})$ for all $t \geq 0$, and suppose that ϕ is also an Orlicz function. Then every p -summing operator $T: X \rightarrow Y$ between Banach spaces is also φ -summing with $\pi_\varphi(T) \leq \pi_p(T)$, and so it is φ semi-integral.

Corollary

Let φ be an Orlicz function and let $1 \leq p < \infty$. Suppose that the function ϕ given by $\phi(t) = \varphi(t^{1/p})$ for all $t \geq 0$ is equivalent to an Orlicz function. Assume that $u_j: X_j \rightarrow Y_j$ is a p -summing operator between Banach spaces for each $1 \leq j \leq n$. Then, for every multilinear operator $S: Y_1 \times \cdots \times Y_n \rightarrow Z$, $T = S \circ (u_1, \dots, u_n)$ is a φ -dominated multilinear operator.

- ▶ p -summing Lipschitz operators. The main results extending the linear case are known.
- ▶ Variants of (q, p) -summability for Lipschitz operators for $q \neq p$ acting between metric spaces will be explained.
- ▶ Pisier's classical work on (q, p) -summability. We will focus on Lipschitz operators from $C(K)$ -spaces to metric spaces. As in the linear case, the key result is an integral domination involving Lipschitz-type inequalities for Lipschitz operators, which is shown to be equivalent to $(q, 1)$ -summability for maps under certain requirements.

Domination theorems—as the one that characterizes p -summing operators—are the keystone for many of these results. Pietsch's and Pisier's factorization theorems are two of them, probably the most relevant ones in terms of applications

The formal study of the class of **absolutely p -summing linear operators** began in 1967 with the seminal work of Pietsch, and they have become an important tool for the study of summability in Banach spaces. The notion of **(q, p) -summing operator**, due to Mityagin and Pełczyński completes the previous one, and is also fundamental in the theory of Banach operator ideals.

Starting point: Farmer, J., and Johnson, W.

Lipschitz p -summing operators.

PAMS, 137(9), (2009) 2989-2995.

- ▶ They introduced the concept of **Lipschitz p -summing map** between metric spaces.
- ▶ They proved a Pietsch domination-factorization theorem for these maps.
- ▶ They showed that this is an extension of the linear concept and that the Lipschitz p -summing norm coincides with the classical p -summing norm.

Consider two metric spaces (M, ρ) and (D, d) . A map $T : M \rightarrow D$ is **Lipschitz** if there is a constant $K > 0$ such that

$$d(T(x), T(y)) \leq K\rho(x, y), \quad x, y \in M.$$

Let (M, d) be a pointed metric space, that is, a metric space equipped with a distinguished point 0 . We denote by $M^\# := Lip_0(M)$ the **Banach space of real-valued Lipschitz functions** $f : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $f(0) = 0$ equipped with the norm

$$\|f\|_{M^\#} := \sup \left\{ \frac{|f(x) - f(y)|}{d(x, y)}; x, y \in X, x \neq y \right\}.$$

A Lipschitz map $\Psi : M \rightarrow N$ is said to be **Lipschitz (q, p) -summing** ($1 \leq p \leq q < \infty$) if there is a constant $C > 0$ such that, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and for all finite sets $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}, \{y_1, \dots, y_n\}$ in M ,

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n d_N(\Psi x_k, \Psi y_k)^q \right)^{1/q} \leq C \sup_{f \in B_{M^\#}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |f(x_k) - f(y_k)|^p \right)^{1/p}.$$

The smallest such constant C is $\pi_{q,p}^L(\Psi)$, and the space of all Lipschitz (q, p) -summing maps from M into N is denoted by $\Pi_{q,p}^L(M, N)$.

In the case $p = q$, we recover the space $\Pi_p^L(M, N)$ of **Lipschitz p -summing maps** introduced by Farmer and Johnson.

This is not the only definition of (q, p) -summing map that can be done. Other approaches have been developed, as the one given in 2009 by Johnson and Schechtman in the paper

“Diamond graphs and super-reflexivity”. Journal of Topology and Analysis, 1(02), pp.177-189.

If $F : (M, d) \rightarrow (N, \rho)$, it is said to be **Lipschitz (p, r) -summing** if for $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n) \in M \times M$ and positive scalars c'_i 's,

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^n c_i^p \rho(F(x_i), F(y_i))^p \right)^{1/p} \leq K \sup_{f \in B_{M^\#}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n c_i^r |f(x_i) - f(y_i)|^r \right)^{1/r}.$$

They prove that with this definition, if $p > 1$ then every Lipschitz map is Lipschitz $(p, 1)$ -summing.

Let E be a Banach lattice and (N, d_N) a metric space. Given $1 \leq p \leq q < \infty$, a Lipschitz map $\Psi : E \rightarrow N$ is called **Lipschitz (q, p) -concave** if, for any choice of finitely many elements $x_1, y_1, \dots, x_n, y_n$ in E , one has

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n d_N(\Psi_{x_k}, \Psi_{y_k})^q \right)^{1/q} \leq C \left\| \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k - y_k|^p \right)^{1/p} \right\|_E.$$

The least constant C that satisfies the above estimate is denoted by $K_{q,p}^L(\Psi)$.

Main reference in the linear case: **Pisier's theorem**

It states that if a linear operator $T: C(K) \rightarrow Y$ is $(q, 1)$ -summing, where Y is a Banach space, then there exist a Radon probability measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(K)$ and a constant $\gamma \leq q^{1/q}$ such that

$$\|Tf\|_Y \leq \gamma \pi_{q,1}(T) \|f\|_{q,1}, \quad f \in C(K).$$

Here $L_{q,1}(\mu)$ denotes the Lorentz space over (K, μ) equipped with the **quasi**-norm

$$\|f\|_{q,1} := \int_0^\infty \mu(|f| > t)^{1/q} dt = \frac{1}{q} \int_0^\infty s^{1/q-1} f^*(s) ds,$$

where f^* denotes the decreasing rearrangement of $|f|$.

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Pisier's result for Lipschitz maps

Part 3. Nikishin theorem for Lipschitz operators

Let (M, d_M) and (N, d_N) be metric spaces and let $W \subset B_{M^\#}$ be a compact subset with respect to the topology of the pointwise convergence on M .

A Lipschitz map $\Psi: M \rightarrow N$ is said to be (q, p) - W -summing ($1 \leq p \leq q < \infty$) if there is a constant $C > 0$ such that, for each n and for all choices of finite sets $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ and $\{y_1, \dots, y_n\}$ in M , one has

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n d_N(\Psi x_k, \Psi y_k)^q \right)^{1/q} \leq C \sup_{f \in W} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |f(x_k) - f(y_k)|^p \right)^{1/p}.$$

If M Banach space, $W = B_{M^*}$, Ψ is Lipschitz (q, p) -summing if

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n d_N(\Psi x_k, \Psi y_k)^q \right)^{1/q} \leq C \sup_{x^* \in B_{M^*}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x^*(x_k - y_k)|^p \right)^{1/p}$$

The smallest such constant is denoted by $\pi_{q,p}^{(*)}(\Psi)$.

Examples. X, Y be Banach spaces, M, N metric spaces. Then :

- ▶ If $1 \leq p \leq q < \infty$, then a linear operator $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is Lipschitz (q, p) - B_{X^*} -summing if and only if it is (q, p) -summing in the classical sense.
- ▶ If $S: X \rightarrow Y$ is a linear operator and $\Psi: Y \rightarrow M$ is a Lipschitz (q, p) - B_{Y^*} -summing map, then $\Psi S: X \rightarrow M$ is Lipschitz (q, p) - B_{X^*} -summing with

$$\pi_{q,p}^{(*)}(\Psi S) \leq \pi_{q,p}^{(*)}(\Psi) \|S\|.$$

- ▶ If $\Phi: X \rightarrow M$ is a Lipschitz (q, p) - B_{X^*} -summing map and $\Psi: M \rightarrow N$ is Lipschitz, then $\Psi \Phi: X \rightarrow N$ is Lipschitz (q, p) - B_{X^*} -summing with

$$\pi_{q,p}^{(*)}(\Psi \Phi) \leq \pi_{q,p}^{(*)}(\Phi) \text{Lip}(\Psi).$$

- ▶ If X is a rearrangement invariant space on the Lebesgue measure space $[0, 1]$, with fundamental function $\phi_X(t) = t^{1/q}$ for all $t \in [0, 1]$, then the inclusion map

$$\text{id}: C(K) \rightarrow X$$

is $(q, 1)$ -summing, since the inclusion $\text{id}: C(K) \rightarrow L_{q,1}(\mu)$ is $(q, 1)$ -summing and the inclusion $L_{q,1}(\mu) \hookrightarrow X$ is continuous.

- ▶ If a Banach space Y has **finite cotype q** , then every Lipschitz map $\Psi: X \rightarrow Y$ is Lipschitz $(q, 1)$ -summing (that is, Lipschitz $(q, 1)$ - B_{X^*} -summing).

Let us turn our attention to the case of maps acting in $C(K)$ -spaces.

$\Psi: C(K) \rightarrow (N, d_N)$ is **Lipschitz (q, p) - $B_{C(K)^*}$ -summing** whenever there is a positive constant γ such that, for any choice of finitely many functions $f_1, g_1, \dots, f_n, g_n$ in $C(K)$ one has

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n d_N(\Psi f_k, \Psi g_k)^q \right)^{1/q} \leq \gamma \left\| \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |f_k - g_k|^p \right)^{1/p} \right\|_\infty.$$

Thus Ψ is Lipschitz (q, p) - $B_{C(K)^*}$ -summing **if and only if** Ψ is Lipschitz (q, p) -concave, and the constants $\pi_{q,p}^{(*)}$ and $K_{q,p}^L$ coincide.

The analysis of the proof of **Pisier's result** shows that for every $q \in [1, \infty)$ there is a constant $\gamma(q) \leq q$ such that the following statement about a linear operator T from $C(K)$ to a Banach space Y are equivalent:

- (i) $T: C(K) \rightarrow Y$ is $(q, 1)$ -concave;
- (ii) There exists a probability measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(K)$ such that

$$\|Tf\|^q \leq \gamma(q) \pi_{q,1}(T) \int_K |f| d\mu, \quad f \in C(K), \|f\|_\infty = 1;$$

- (iii) There exists a probability measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(K)$ such that

$$\|Tf - Tg\|^q \leq \gamma(q) \pi_{q,1}(T) \int_K |f - g| d\mu,$$

for $f, g \in C(K), \|f - g\|_\infty = 1$.

In the linear case, the implications from (ii) and (iii) to (i) are direct; we will see that this is not the case for Lipschitz maps. Also, for a linear operator proving (i) \Rightarrow (ii) requires an elaborate argument; and the statements (ii) and (iii) are obviously equivalent. In fact, for the case of Lipschitz maps the implication (i) \Rightarrow (ii) is not true in general, as the following lemma shows.

Lemma

Let X be an infinite-dimensional Banach space and suppose K is an infinite compact Hausdorff space. Then, for every $q \in [1, \infty)$ there exists a Lipschitz $(q, 1)$ -concave map $\Psi: C(K) \rightarrow X$, for which there is not a probability Borel measure μ on K such that for some $C > 0$ one has

$$\|\Psi f\|_X^q \leq C \int_K |f| d\mu, \quad \|f\|_\infty = 1.$$

However, we can always generate examples...use this!

Lemma

Let (M, d) be a metric space and let $\Psi: C(K) \rightarrow (M, d)$ be a mapping. Suppose that there exists a probability measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(K)$ and a constant $\gamma > 0$ such that, for some $q \in [1, \infty)$ one has

$$d(\Psi f, \Psi g)^q \leq \gamma \int_K |f - g| d\mu, \quad f, g \in C(K), \quad \|f - g\|_\infty = 1.$$

Then, for every metric ρ on M which satisfies that for $f, g \in C(K)$,

$$\rho(\Psi f, \Psi g) \leq \|f - g\|_\infty \cdot d\left(\Psi\left(\frac{f}{\|f - g\|_\infty}\right), \Psi\left(\frac{g}{\|f - g\|_\infty}\right)\right),$$

we have that the map $\Psi: C(K) \rightarrow (M, \rho)$ is $(q, 1)$ -concave. In particular, it is a Lipschitz map which satisfies the above integral domination formula, with the same q too.

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Part 2. Lipschitz (q, p) -summing operators

(q, p) -summing operators on $C(K)$ -spaces

Pisier's result for Lipschitz maps

Part 3. Nikishin theorem for Lipschitz operators

Main definitions

○ A function $\varphi \in C(K)^\#$ is said to be **subadditive** if, for every choice of f_1, \dots, f_n in $C(K)$, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \varphi(|f_k|) \leq \varphi\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |f_k|\right).$$

A function $\varphi \in W$ is called **superadditive** whenever $-\varphi$ is subadditive.

○ A subset $W \subset B_{C(K)^\#}$ is said to be **$C(K)$ -metric attaining** for a Lipschitz map $\Psi : C(K) \rightarrow (N, d_N)$ if, for every $f, g \in C(K)$ there is an element $\varphi_{f,g} \in W$ such that the following two conditions are satisfied

$$\varphi_{f,g}(1) = d_N(\Psi f, \Psi g)$$

and

$$|\varphi_{f,g}(h)| \leq d_N(\Psi(fh), \Psi(gh)), \quad h \in C(K).$$

○ A Lipschitz map $\Psi : C(K) \rightarrow M$ is **sub-homogeneous** whenever

$$d(\Psi(\lambda f), \Psi(\lambda g)) \leq \lambda d(\Psi f, \Psi g), \quad f, g \in C(K), \lambda \in (0, 1).$$

Pisier's theorem for Lipschitz (q, p) -summing maps

Theorem

Let $1 \leq p < q < \infty$, let (M, d) be a metric space and let $\Psi: C(K) \rightarrow (M, d)$ be a *Lipschitz sub-homogeneous (q, p) -concave* map with $K_{q,p}^L(T) = 1$. Suppose that $W \subset C(K)^\#$ is a τ_p -compact subset that contains a $C(K)$ -metric attaining set of subadditive (and monotone in the case $p > 1$) functions for the map Ψ . Then there exists a Borel measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(K)$ such that

$$d(\Psi f, \Psi g)^q \leq q \int_W \frac{\varphi(|f - g|^p)}{\varphi(1)} d\mu(\varphi) \leq q \| |f - g|^p \|_\infty,$$

for all $f, g \in C(K)$, $\|f - g\|_\infty \leq 1$.

Corollary

$1 < q < \infty$. (M, d) metric space, and $W \subset C(K)^\#$ is a τ_p -compact and $C(K)$ -metric attaining set for a Lipschitz sub-homogeneous map $\Psi: C(K) \rightarrow (M, d)$. Consider :

- (i) W contains subadditive functions and Ψ is $(q, 1)$ -concave with $K_{q,1}^L(\Psi) = 1$;
- (ii) There exists a positive constant γ and a Borel measure μ on W such that, for all $f, g \in C(K)$ with $\|f - g\|_\infty \leq 1$ one has

$$d(\Psi f, \Psi g)^q \leq \gamma \int_W \frac{\varphi(f - g)}{\varphi(1)} d\mu(\varphi) \leq \gamma \|f - g\|_\infty;$$

- (iii) The condition (ii) holds with W containing superadditive functions.

Then (i) implies (ii), and

(iii) implies that, for all $f_1, g_1, \dots, f_n, g_n \in C(K)$ with $\left\| \sum_{k=1}^n |f_k - g_k| \right\|_\infty \leq 1$ one has

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n d(\Psi f_k, \Psi g_k)^q \right)^{1/q} \leq \gamma \left\| \sum_{k=1}^n |f_k - g_k| \right\|_\infty.$$

Part 1. Ideals of multilinear mappings via Orlicz spaces

φ -summing and φ -semi-integral multilinear operators

φ -dominated multilinear operators

Part 2. Lipschitz (q, p) -summing operators

(q, p) -summing operators on $C(K)$ -spaces

Pisier's result for Lipschitz maps

Part 3. Nikishin theorem for Lipschitz operators

We consider the set Φ of all functions $\varphi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ that are increasing, continuous, unbounded and such that $\varphi(0) = 0$. Recall that a convex function $\varphi \in \Phi$ is called an *Orlicz function*. For a map φ in Φ , we denote by $L_{\varphi, \infty}(\mu)$ the **weak Marcinkiewicz space** of all $f \in L^0(\mu)$ such that

$$\|f\|_{\varphi, \infty} := \sup_{\lambda > 0} \lambda \varphi(\mu_f(\lambda)) < \infty,$$

where $\mu_f(\lambda) := \mu(\{\omega \in \Omega; |f(\omega)| > \lambda\})$ for all $\lambda > 0$.

- ▶ If $\varphi \in \Phi$ satisfies that there exists $C \geq 1$ such that $\varphi(2t) \leq C\varphi(t)$ for all $t \in (0, \mu(\Omega))$, then $(L_{\varphi, \infty}, \|\cdot\|_{\varphi, \infty})$ is a quasi-Banach lattice over $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu)$.
- ▶ If $0 < p < \infty$ and $\phi(t) = t^{1/p}$ for all $t \geq 0$, then we recover the weak L^p -Marcinkiewicz space denoted by $L_{p, \infty}$.
- ▶ A quasi-Banach space X is of type p for $1 \leq p \leq 2$ if there is a constant C such that for any finite sequence $(x_j)_j$ in X ,

$$\left(\int_0^1 \left\| \sum_j r_j(t)x_j \right\|_X^2 dt \right)^{1/2} \leq C \left\| (\|x_j\|_X)_j \right\|_{\ell_p},$$

where $(r_j)_j$ are the Rademacher functions. The least C is $T_p(X)$.

Nikishin factorization

If X is a Banach space of type p ($1 \leq p < 2$) and $T: X \rightarrow L^0(\mu)$ is a continuous linear operator, then for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there is a set E with $\mu(E) \geq 1 - \varepsilon$ and such that the operator S given by

$$Sx := 1_E T x, \quad x \in X$$

is bounded from X into $L_{p,\infty}(\mu)$, where 1_E denotes the indicator function of E .

Nikishin's theorem for functions from quasi-metric spaces into $L^0(\mu)$ involving Marcinkiewicz spaces instead of the weak L_p -spaces

Quasi-metric space (X, d) , measure space $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu)$, function $\varphi \in \Phi$. A mapping $T: X \rightarrow L^0(\mu)$ **factors strongly through $L_{\varphi,\infty}(\mu)$** if there exists a function $g \in L^0(\mu)$ such that for all $x, y \in X$ one has

$$\varphi\left(\mu\left(\left\{\omega \in \Omega : \left|\frac{T x(\omega) - T y(\omega)}{g(\omega)}\right| > \lambda\right\}\right)\right) \leq \frac{d(x, y)}{\lambda}, \quad \lambda > 0.$$

For short, $\|(Tx - Ty)/g\|_{\varphi,\infty} \leq d(x, y)$. This is equivalent to the following factorization diagram

Recall that if $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu)$ is a measure space and $\varphi \in \Phi$, we write $L_\varphi(\mu)$ for the *Orlicz space* of all $f \in L^0(\mu)$ such that for some $\lambda > 0$,

$$\rho_\varphi(\lambda f) := \int_\Omega \varphi(\lambda|f|) d\mu < \infty.$$

F -space with the F -norm $\|f\|_\varphi := \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \rho_\varphi(f/\varepsilon) \leq \varepsilon\}$.

We consider only such $\varphi \in \Phi$ for which the functional

$$\|f\|_\varphi := \inf\{\varepsilon > 0 : \rho_\varphi(f/\varepsilon) \leq 1\}, \quad f \in L_\varphi$$

is a quasi-norm on L_φ . We write $\widehat{\Phi}$ for the set of all such functions $\varphi \in \Phi$. $\|\cdot\|_\varphi$ is a norm on L_φ if φ is an Orlicz function.

A function $\varphi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ satisfies the Δ_2 -condition ($\varphi \in \Delta_2$ for short), if $\sup_{t>0} \varphi(2t)/\varphi(t) < \infty$. For $\varphi \in \Delta_2$, we define the function $s_\varphi: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ by

$$s_\varphi(t) := \sup_{u>0} \frac{\varphi(tu)}{\varphi(u)}, \quad t > 0.$$

If $\varphi \in \widehat{\Phi} \cap \Delta_2$ satisfies $s_\varphi(t) \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow 0$, then we write $\varphi \in \Phi_0$. If $\varphi \in \Phi \cap \Delta_2$ is an Orlicz function, then for all $t \in (0, 1]$ one has $s_\varphi(t) \leq t$ and so $\varphi \in \Phi_0$.

Theorem

Let (X, d) be a quasi-metric space and let $T: X \rightarrow L^0(\mu)$ be a mapping. Let us assume that $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu)$ is a probability measure space and $\varphi \in \Phi_0$. Then the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) T factors strongly through $L_{\varphi^{-1}, \infty}(\mu)$.
- (ii) There is a function $C: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ with $C(\lambda) \rightarrow 0$ as $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ such that, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and for all real positive scalars $(\alpha_j)_{j=1}^n$ and all finite sequences $(x_j)_{j=1}^n, (y_j)_{j=1}^n$ in X , one has

$$\mu\left(\left\{\omega \in \Omega : \sup_{1 \leq j \leq n} \alpha_j |Tx_j(\omega) - Ty_j(\omega)| \geq \lambda \|(\alpha_j d(x_j, y_j))_{j=1}^n\|_{\ell_\varphi^n}\right\}\right) \leq C(\lambda)$$

- (iii) For every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exist a constant $C_\varepsilon > 0$ and a set $E_\varepsilon \in \mathcal{A}$ with $\mu(\Omega \setminus E_\varepsilon) < \varepsilon$ such that

$$\|1_{E_\varepsilon}(Tx - Ty)\|_{\varphi^{-1}, \infty} \leq C_\varepsilon d(x, y), \quad x, y \in X.$$

- ▶ This result gives a characterization of the factorization through weak Marcinkiewicz spaces for a special class of non-linear maps.
- ▶ A generalization of the notion Rademacher type p involving functions $\varphi \in \Phi_0$ for quasi-Banach spaces is needed.
- ▶ Recall that if X is a quasi-Banach space, then an operator $T: X \rightarrow L^0(\mu)$ is called sublinear if for all $x, y \in X$ and scalars λ ,
 - (a) $|T(x + y)| \leq |Tx| + |Ty|$,
 - (b) $|T(\lambda x)| = |\lambda| |Tx|$.

Corollary

Let X be a quasi-Banach space and let $T: X \rightarrow L^0(\mu)$ be a sublinear operator. Let us assume that μ is a probability measure and $\varphi \in \Phi_0$. Then the following statements are equivalent:

- (a) $|T|$ factors strongly through $L_{\varphi^{-1}, \infty}(\mu)$.
- (b) There is a function $C: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ with $C(\lambda) \rightarrow 0$ as $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ such that, for any finite sequence $(x_j)_j$ in X , one has

$$\mu\left(\left\{\omega \in \Omega : \sup_j |Tx_j(\omega)| \geq \lambda \|(\|x_j\|_X)_j\|_{\ell_\varphi}\right\}\right) \leq C(\lambda).$$

A quasi-Banach space X is of type φ for if there is a constant C such that for any finite sequence $(x_j)_j$ in X ,

$$\left(\int_0^1 \left\|\sum_j r_j(t)x_j\right\|_X^2 dt\right)^{1/2} \leq C \|(\|x_j\|_X)_j\|_{\ell_\varphi},$$

where $(r_j)_j$ are the Rademacher functions. The least C is $T_\varphi(X)$.

Proposition Let X is a quasi-Banach space of type φ with $\varphi \in \Phi_0$ and let $T: X \rightarrow L^0(\mu)$ be a sublinear operator that is continuous at zero. Then there exists a function $C: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ such that $C(\lambda) \rightarrow 0$ as $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ and

$$\mu\left(\left\{\sup_j |Tx_j| > \lambda\right\}\right) \leq 2 T_\varphi(X)^2 \lambda^{-1} + 2 C(\sqrt{\lambda}), \quad \lambda > 0,$$

for all finite sequences $(x_j)_j$ in X satisfying $\sum_j \varphi(\|x_j\|_X) \leq 1$.

Corollary

Let X be a quasi-Banach space of type φ with $\varphi \in \Phi_0$. Then every sublinear continuous operator $T: X \rightarrow L^0(\mu)$ factors strongly through $L_{\varphi^{-1}, \infty}(\mu)$.

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THANKS FOR YOUR ATTENTION!!

We define the "distribution function" $\mu_f : [0, \infty] \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ by the rule $\mu_f(s) = \mu\{x \in E : |f(x)| > s\}$.

We can now define the "decreasing rearrangement" of f as the function $f^* : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty]$

defined as $f^*(t) = \inf\{s \in [0, \infty] : \mu_f(s) \leq t\}$.

Professor Julian Musielak, an outstanding member of the Poznań School of Mathematics

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Professor Julian Musielak was a person whose achievements to develop of mathematical investigations and the Poznań School of Mathematics were important, essential, valuable, inspired, numerous and varied. His scientific interests concerned many problems related to functional analysis, approximations and expansions, harmonic analysis on Euclidean spaces, sequences, series, summability, measure and integration, real functions, history and biography. At the end of fifties of twentieth century Julian Musielak, together with Władysław Orlicz, initiated investigations of spaces of measurable functions called later one Musielak-Orlicz spaces $L^\psi(S, \Sigma, \mu)$ (they generalized Nakano's ideas considering nonconvex functions ψ). During his sixty years of activity, he published over two hundred papers including monographs and textbooks (looking at Mathematical Reviews you can see, that they have been cited 1.695 times – data from the end of May 2024). Having so broad knowledge Professor Musielak was able to take care about many pupils preparing their Ph.D. theses devoted to various topics (he was a supervisor of thirty six dissertations). Professor Musielak had a lot of international relations and he was a desirable collaborator in research made by other mathematicians (twenty five is a number of his co-authors). He was also a fan of traveling. Towards the end of his life he described trips in extensive memories, where he also told the events of his life. The main aim of the lecture is to show how unique Professor Musielak was.

**Professor Julian Musielak, an outstanding member
of the Poznań School of Mathematics**

by Witold Wnuk

Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science

Adam Mickiewicz University

Our talk is closely related to a lecture devoted to Henryk Hudzik, excellently prepared by Professor Lech Maligranda. Main aim of the talk is to present, in short, a life and work of Professor Julian Musielak who was Henryk's master, teacher, friend and an initiator, in 1986, of the Function Spaces conference series. We will start with several remarks about scientific life in Poznań before Julian Musielak started his mathematical studies.

Poland lost its independence in 1795. The western part of the country was annexed, two years earlier, to the Kingdom of Prussia. The so called Grand Duchy of Poznań became a part of the Kingdom of Prussia, and later on, from 1871 a part of the German Empire, until the end of 1918, when the Polish state was reborn. In January 1857 the Poznań Society for Advancement of Art and Sciences was established. The aim of the Society was to protect and further develop the sciences and endangered culture of the Polish nation in Prussia, where there was no possibility to create Polish university. The Society continues its activities to this day. Members of the Society were among the most involved in the creation of the University in Poznań, which took place on 7 May 1919, half a year after Poland regained independence. Mathematics was present at the university from the very beginning, but the departments were led by professors from outside Poznań, where there was a lack of native, local staff. Many mathematicians working at the University of Poznań studied at prestigious universities in Paris, Göttingen, Freiburg, Berlin and others. This lecture is not good place to say about achievements of mathematicians from Poznań obtained before the second World War, but it is worth to recall at least four people. The first was Władysław Ślebodziński. His early works have already been noticed and he became the famous expert in differential geometry, widely known as the author of the "Lie derivative" notion. After the Second World War, having spent over two years in Nazi concentration camps, Ślebodziński moved to Wrocław. Later on differential geometry was not developed in Poznań.

It is impossible to pass over silence achievements of three young Polish mathematicians, graduates of the University in Poznań: Marian

Rejewski, Jerzy Rózeki, Henryk Zygalski. After short course in cryptography organized for volunteers graduated in mathematics and spoke fluent German, they started to work in Cipher Bureau of the General Staff of Polish Army. Using completely new, mathematical methods, the first of all from the permutation theory, they needed only four months, from September to December 1932, to break German military ciphers created by Enigma machine (“enigma”, in Greek, means “riddle”). The Enigma machine was considered so secure that it was used to encipher the most top-secret messages. The Enigma has an electromechanical rotor mechanism that scrambles the letters of the alphabet. Poles were able to read military messages prior to and into the war. British and French intelligence services were unable to break the German codes until the summer of 1939. From 26 till 27 July 1939, the Poles initiated French and British military intelligence representatives into the Polish Enigma-decryption techniques and equipment, including such Polish inventions as Zygalski’s sheets and the cryptologic bomb as well as a Polish-reconstructed Enigma (the devices were soon delivered to Allies). The fundamental works of Polish code-breakers significantly contributed to later success of Alan Turing’s team at Bletchley Park (during World War II, the estate housed the Government Code and Cypher School, which regularly penetrated the secret communications of the Axis Powers). Adam Mickiewicz University Press published in 2011 Marian Rejewski’s memories (full title of the book is *Memories of my work at the Cipher Bureau of the General Staff Second Department 1930–1945*). In this book Rejewski described the process of breaking the Enigma cipher.

Professor Julian Musielak was born on 7th November 1928 in Poznań. His parents, Antoni and Halina, née Maeusel, were public administration officials and Julian was their only child. He attended a private primary school and had a carefree first period of childhood. During holidays, he visited various parts of Poland with his parents and retained his passion for traveling until adulthood. A situation changed dramatically during the Nazi occupation. Antoni, the father, as a reserve officer, was mobilized at the beginning of the war and his war fate took him to Hungary, where he stayed in an internment camp. Julian, together with his mother, were evicted from subsequent apartments and placed in flats of an increasingly lower standard. Schools were unavailable to Polish youth, but the mother took care of her son’s education by engaging private tutors. Julian also liked to spend time reading books and textbooks. From the age of fourteen, Polish children, unlike German children, were sent to work. Obligatory. Julian worked in the State Archives and later on as a postman. Thanks to his diligence,

talents and home education, he finished secondary school in two years (1945–1946) and got secondary school certificate, Polish substitute of British General Certificate of Education Advanced Level. He entered the University in Poznań immediately after graduating from secondary school and started to study mathematics. He achieved excellent results confirmed by high exam grades. He was interested not only in mathematics, but also chose subjects in physics, philosophy and logic. He had great teachers: Szczepan Szczeniowski (physicist) and Kazimierz Ajdukiewicz (philosopher and logician). Contact with Władysław Orlicz and Andrzej Alexiewicz had a huge influence on the development of the young mathematics enthusiast, which cannot be overestimated. Orlicz, a member of the legendary Lwów School of Mathematics, introduced functional analysis to Poznań, educated a large group of young research workers. Orlicz had extremely extensive, wide knowledge and he was able to effectively help people interested in areas of mathematics other than functional analysis. Over time, dynamic groups were created, which made research in discrete mathematics, algebra, number theory, differential equations, statistics, logic, game theory and other branches of maths. People began to talk about the Poznań School of Mathematics founded by Orlicz.

Julian Musielak started his academic career very early. Already as a third-year student, he got the position of deputy assistant. He was promoted to assistant and senior assistant in two-year intervals. In the period 1953–1963 he was additionally employed at the Institute of Mathematics, Polish Academy of Sciences. On 11th October 1951 Musielak defended his Master Thesis *On generalized almost periodic Besicovitch functions* and several years later, on 2nd April 1958, he received his doctor degree presenting the thesis *On absolute convergence of Fourier series of almost periodic functions and periodic functions of several variables*. Clearly Orlicz was the supervisor (Musielaak was the fourth Orlicz's Ph.D. student). It took him only four years to prepare the habilitation. On 9th of June 1962 Julian Musielak presented a set of publications entitled *On some spaces of functions and distributions* accepted by the Council of the Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry. Julian Musielak was constantly expanding his scientific achievements, a number of published paper constantly increased. It led him to the awarding of the title of extraordinary professor on 5th April 1971. Finally, on 21 May 1980, he received the highest academic title - the title of full professor.

Professor Musielak began his publishing activity in 1955. As far as we know the paper *On the estimation of the norm of the n -linear symmetric operation* (Studia Mathematica 15 (1955), 29-30, coauthor:

Józef Kopeć) was his first publication. Mathematical Reviews registered 145 Musielak's papers, but their true number is 214: 138 papers, 3 monographs, 13 textbooks, 34 surveys and educational articles, 26 others. According to the AMS classification Professor Musielak published papers in nine branches: 46-Functional analysis, 41-Approximation and expansions, 47-Operator theory, 42-Harmonic analysis, 01-History and biography, 40-Sequences, series, summability, 28-Measure and integration, 26-Real functions, 45-Integral equations. His results were cited 1716 times in 1400 publications. The group of his co-authors counts 25 researches.

It is worth to recall Musielak's three monographs: *Modular Spaces* (in Polish), Adam Mickiewicz University Press 1978, 136 pp., *Orlicz Spaces and Modular Spaces*, Lecture Notes in Mathematics vol 1034, Springer-Verlag 1983, *Nonlinear Integral Operators and Applications*, De Gruyter Series in Nonlinear Analysis and Applications 9, Walter de Gruyter, Berlin 2003, xii+201 pp. (co-authors: C. Bardaro, G. Vinti).

Professor Musielak wrote dozen textbooks. The best known are: *Introduction to Mathematics* (= *Introduction to Set Theory*), in Polish, (Polish Scientific Publishers 1970, 127 pp.), *Introduction to Functional Analysis*, in Polish, (Polish Scientific Publishers, first edition 1976, 315 pp, second edition 1989, 369 pp.) and three volumes of *Mathematical Analysis*. The first volume, published in 1993, was written together with Helena Musielak, Julian's wife, second and third in cooperation with Professor's pupils Magdalena Jarszewska and Leszek Skrzypczak.

Starting his scientific activity Musielak was interested in Fourier series related to various orthogonal systems, not only trigonometric and Haar systems. He investigated expansions of almost periodic functions and periodic functions of several variables. This topic was popular in fifties and the first half of sixties of twentieth century because at that time the problem concerning the almost everywhere convergence of Fourier series was still open. As we know a positive answer was established by Carleson, for square-integrable functions, in 1966. While participating in one of the conferences, Musielak met there not only Antoni Zygmund and Marshall H. Stone, but also an outstanding Indian mathematician Komaravolu Chandrasekharan, who was a professor at ETH Zürich, worked in the Institute for Advanced Study, Princeton, and in the School of Mathematics of the Tata Institute of Fundamental Research in Bombay (from 1995 Mumbai). Chandrasekharan spoke on multiple Fourier series. This topic was a part of Musielak Ph.D. Thesis, and so young Polish mathematician was able to competently participate in the discussion after the lecture. The lecturer liked the remarks

and comments, and offered him a one-year scholarship at the Tata Institute, which was realized from June 1958 to April 1959. In Bombay Musielak listened Kiyoshi Itô's (= Itô integral, stochastic analysis) lectures and started cooperating with Serbian mathematician, Ranko Bojanić, an expert in approximation theory, a student of Jovan Karamata. During the stay in Bombay Musielak analyzed deeply p -integrable distributions investigated by Laurent Schwartz, and found a path leading to a generalization – to φ -integrable distributions, where φ is an Orlicz function. This type of distributions was included in Musielak's habilitation. Contacts with Bojanić were in progress during several succeeding years, and Musielak was invited, as a visiting professor, to the University of Notre Dame, South Bend, Indiana, where he spent a period from 1 September 1962 till 31 August 1963.

Modular spaces form very important part of Musielak's achievements. The notions of a modular and a modular space were introduced by Hidegorô Nakano in fortieth of twenty century. He was the author of the monograph *Modulated Semi-Ordered Linear Spaces* (1950) presenting properties of such spaces. Nakano considered so called convex modulars ϱ , i.e., functionals on, for simplicity, real vector spaces X , $\varrho: X \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ satisfying the following conditions:

- ($\rho 1$) $\varrho(x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = 0$.
- ($\rho 2$) $\varrho(x) = \varrho(-x)$.
- ($\rho 3$) $\varrho(\alpha x + \beta y) \leq \alpha \varrho(x) + \beta \varrho(y)$ whenever $\alpha + \beta = 1$.

A modular space X_ϱ generated by ϱ is a (linear) subspace of X consisting of elements with the property $\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \varrho(rx) = 0$. Clearly, every norm is a simple example of a modular. We have to add, that usually Nakano, and members of his school, considered modulars on vector lattices L , i.e., L are real vector spaces equipped with a partial order \leq (= reflexive, antisymmetric, transitive relation) compatible with the algebraic structure, what means $x \leq y \Rightarrow x + z \leq y + z$, $0 \leq x, 0 \leq r \in \mathbb{R} \Rightarrow 0 \leq rx$, and $\sup\{x, y\} = x \vee y$ exists for all $x, y \in L$. Considering modulars on vector lattices Japanese mathematicians assumed, very often, that additionally a modular is monotone

- ($\rho 4$) $|x| \leq |y| \Rightarrow \varrho(x) \leq \varrho(y)$ where $|x| = \sup\{x, -x\}$.

and has the Fatou property

- ($\rho 5$) $0 \leq x_n \uparrow x \Rightarrow \varrho(x_n) \uparrow \varrho(x)$.

Every modular defines a norm on X_ϱ : $\|x\|_\varrho = \inf\{\lambda > 0 : \varrho(\frac{x}{\lambda}) \leq 1\}$. Nakano indicated very important example of modular spaces - spaces today known as Musielak–Orlicz spaces. Namely, let (S, Σ, μ)

be a measure space (suppose, for simplicity, that μ is σ -finite), and let $\psi: [0, \infty) \times S \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ be such that:

- (ψ 1) $\psi(r, s) = 0$ iff $r = 0$.
- (ψ 2) $\psi(\cdot, s)$ is convex and right continuous at 0 for every s .
- (ψ 3) $\psi(r, \cdot)$ is measurable for every r .

Then ψ defines an integral modular on the space $L^0(\mu)$ of (real valued) Σ -measurable functions:

$$(*) \quad I_\psi(f) = \int_S \psi(|f(s)|, s) d\mu.$$

This integral modular generates the modular space

$$\begin{aligned} L_{I_\psi} &= \{f \in L^0(\mu) : \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} I_\psi(rf) = 0\} \\ &= L^\psi(\mu) = \{f \in L^0(\mu) : \exists_{r_f > 0} \int_S \psi(|rf(s)|, s) d\mu < \infty\} \end{aligned}$$

Musielak and Orlicz in their fundamental paper *On modular spaces* (Studia Math. 18 (1959), 49–65) weakened the definition of a modular, assuming that, instead of condition (ρ 3) there holds

$$(\rho 3') \quad \varrho(\alpha x + \beta y) \leq \varrho(x) + \varrho(y) \text{ whenever } \alpha + \beta = 1.$$

Now every F -norm $q: X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a modular (let us recall, that q has to satisfy the following conditions: $q(x) = 0$ iff $x = 0$, $q(rx) \leq q(x)$ for $|r| \leq 1$, $q(x + y) \leq q(x) + q(y)$, $\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} q(rx) = 0$). New modular defines an F -norm q_ϱ on X_ϱ by the formula

$$q_\varrho(x) = \inf\{\lambda > 0 : \varrho\left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right) \leq \lambda\},$$

and so a modular space became a metrizable topological vector space. Replacing the convexity condition (ψ 2) by

$$(\psi 2') \quad \psi(\cdot, s) \text{ is continuous and nondecreasing for every } s,$$

we obtain broader class of Musielak–Orlicz spaces. An integral modular has the Fatou property (ρ 5), it is monotone (property (ρ 4)), and moreover orthogonally additive, i.e., $I_\psi(f+g) = I_\psi(f) + I_\psi(g)$ whenever the supports of the functions are almost disjoint: $\mu(\text{supp } f \cap \text{supp } g) = 0$. In other words, f and g are orthogonal, infimum of their modules is equal to zero: $|f| \wedge |g| = 0$.

It turns out that a vector lattice L_ρ with a monotone, orthogonally additive modular having Fatou property is isomodular to some order dense sublattice in a Musielak–Orlicz space, i.e., there exist: a Musielak–Orlicz space $L^\psi(\mu)$, an order dense vector sublattice $L \subset L_\rho$, a linear homeomorphism $T: L_\rho \rightarrow L$ preserving partial order such that $I_\psi(Tx) = \varrho(x)$.

Musielak–Orlicz spaces belong to objects investigated by huge number of mathematicians. The function $\psi(r, s) = r^{p(s)}$ ($p(s) > 0$) generates so-called Nakano space, also known as variable Lebesgue space. Looking for papers devoted to this particular case of Musielak–Orlicz spaces we will see, that Mathematical Reviews shows us 3353 results. Among them the monograph *Variable Lebesgue Spaces* by D. V. Cruz-Uribe, A. Fiorenza (D. V. Cruz-Uribe, A. Fiorenza, Variable Lebesgue Spaces, Birkhäuser, Springer, Heidelberg 2013, 312 pp.). L^ψ spaces are applied in many different branches of mathematics: partial differential equations (see the book *Partial Differential Equations in Anisotropic Musielak–Orlicz Spaces*, Iwona Chlebicka, Piotr Gwiazda, Agnieszka Świerczewska-Gwiazda, Aneta Wróblewska-Kamińska Springer Monographs in Mathematics 2021, 389 pp.), nonlinear integral operators, probability, stochastic integrals, calculus of variations, infinitely divisible processes, mathematical physics and so on. In the mathematical literature we can find spaces derived from Musielak spaces such as Musielak–Orlicz–Hardy spaces Musielak–Orlicz–Sobolev–Hajlasz spaces, Besicovich–Musiela–Orlicz spaces. After Professor Musielak’s death Leszek Skrzypczak and Anna Kamińska published, in Polish, a commemorative article in *Wiadomości Matematyczne* (vol. 56 issue 2 (2020), 491–506). There you can find very valuable and interesting survey concerning Professor Musielak’s achievements, especially these related to Musielak–Orlicz spaces.

Throughout the whole period of his scientific activity, he maintained very extensive and constantly expanding international scientific contacts, primarily with German mathematicians Paul L. Butzer, Heinz König, Karl Zeller, Diethard Pallaschke, Jürgen Batt, Susanne Dierolf. Many times visited universities in Aachen, Tübingen, Karlsruhe, Trier, Munich, Saarbrücken. He stayed longer in some German research centers, e.g. Halle (15 September–15 December 1972) or Kiel (1 May–31 July 1989). He was a guest at the Universidad Complutense in Madrid several times, visited the University of Science and Technology in Harbin (China). Cooperation with researchers from the Università degli Studi di Perugia was particularly lasting and fruitful. Thanks to subsidies from Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Italian National Research Council) and Komitet Badań Naukowych (Polish State Committee for Scientific Research) as well as support of the Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science it became possible to create a research team whose activities in the years 1993–2001 gave several publications and mentioned before monograph *Nonlinear Integral Operators and Applications*.

Professor Musielak was awarded many times for his achievements: he received the Minister of Higher Education Awards three times (1964, 1969, 1975), the First Degree Award of the Minister of Science, Higher Education and Technology three times (1981, 1984, 1988), the Science Award of the City of Poznań (2004), academic medal *Palmae Universitatis Posnaniensis* (2006) and, the first of all honorary doctoral degree (doctor honoris causa) from the University of Zielona Góra. Additionally, he was awarded the Knight's Cross and Officer's Cross of the Order of Polonia Restituta (1973, 2011).

He acted for the mathematical community as the president of the Poznań Branch of the Polish Mathematical Society, later a member of the Management Board, vice-president and president of the Polish Mathematical Society (1991–1993). He received the rarely awarded the dignity of an honorary member of the Polish Mathematical Society (2000).

From the mid-1970s, he took on the responsibility of managing the department and the whole university. He was deputy dean of the Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry (academic years 1975/76–1977/78), deputy dean of the Faculty of Mathematics and Physics (term 1978/79–1980/81) and dean of the Faculty of Mathematics and Physics (1981–1984). On 1 September 1984, he took up the position of vice-rector for foreign cooperation. The Minister of Science, Higher Education and Technology did not respect the will of the academic community, which democratically elected the rector's team, and led to the termination of his term of office on 30 November 1985. Musielak's last managerial position was the director of the Institute of Mathematics (1991–1993). During this time, together with his collaborators, he prepared the transformation of the Institute of Mathematics into the Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, which took place on 1 September 1993.

For many years he was the editor-in-chief of the journals *Functiones and Approximatio*, *Commentationes Mathematicae* and an editor of *Mathematica Japonica*.

Musielak made a great contribution to the education of young scientific staff promoting 36 Ph.D. students. For decades he conducted seminars for Ph.D. students and employees of the Department of the Theory of Real Functions, which he headed. The seminar was a real scientific school. He was always very devoted to his younger colleagues and students, generously distributing countless inspiring suggestions and tips that had an invaluable impact on their development and subsequent achievements. He never spared them time, was always available to them, willing to discuss, explain, help, support and advise. He was

a genuine scientific supervisor who was able to encourage systematic work not through constant inspections, but his inexhaustible kindness and enormous authority among his students meant that it was inappropriate to come for the next meeting without showing at least a little progress in their current investigations. Musielak's attitude to his pupils was very democratic, he treated them as partners.

His lectures were always clear, lively, interesting, rich with examples, perfectly prepared. Professor Musielak was able to convey very extensive material. For example, he included the basics of measure theory and Lebesgue integrals into a course of mathematical analysis. He always lectured without notes. He rarely looked at the cheat sheet, which was the size of a tram ticket.

Musielak had a very cheerful character, he liked to joke and was kind to people. He maintained high moral principles under all circumstances.

Musielak officially retired in July 2006. He left very extensive, three-volume memoirs, which he handed over to the Faculty authorities in 2010.

What concerns his private life, Professor Musielak married Helena, née Perdziak, in 1953. The couple had three daughters and two sons.

Julian Musielak after almost ninety-two years of a busy life, ended it on 11 October 2020.

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On maximal projection constants

Beata Deręgowska

CT

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Let X be a Banach space over \mathbb{K} , where $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{C}$. Let $Y \subset X$ be a subspace. By $\mathcal{P}(X, Y)$ denote the set of all linear and continuous projections from X onto Y , recalling that an operator $P: X \rightarrow Y$ is called a *projection* onto Y if $P|_Y = Id_Y$. We define the *relative projection constant* of subspace Y of space X by

$$\lambda(Y, X) := \inf\{\|P\| : P \in \mathcal{P}(X, Y)\}.$$

Now we can define the *absolute projection constant* of Y by

$$\lambda(Y) := \sup\{\lambda(Y, X) : Y \subset X\}.$$

The ultimate goal of researchers in this area is to determine the exact value of *maximal absolute projection constant*, which is defined by

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m) := \sup\{\lambda(Y) : \dim(Y) = m\}.$$

In 1994, H. König and N. Tomczak-Jaegermann stated the following estimation.

Theorem (stated in [3]; proved in [1]) *Let $m > 1$ then*

$$\text{i) } \lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(m) \leq \frac{2}{m+1} \left(1 + \frac{m-1}{2} \sqrt{m+2}\right)$$

$$\text{ii) } \lambda_{\mathbb{C}}(m) \leq \frac{1}{m} \left(1 + (m-1)\sqrt{m+1}\right).$$

Unfortunately, their proof is based on an erroneous lemma, as was pointed out in [2]. In this talk, we will present the correct proof of the latter. Moreover relying on this result we provide the exact values of $\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m)$ in cases where the maximal equiangular tight frame exists in \mathbb{K}^m .

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ON MAXIMAL PROJECTION CONSTANTS

Beata Deregowska

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July 8, 2024

BASIC DEFINITIONS

Let X be a Banach space over \mathbb{K} (where $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{C}$) and let $Y \subset X$ be a finite-dimensional subspace. Let $\mathcal{P}(X, Y)$ denote the set of all linear and continuous projections from X onto Y , recalling that an operator $P: X \rightarrow Y$ is called a **projection** onto Y if $P|_Y = \text{Id}_Y$.

We define the **relative projection constant** of Y by

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(Y, X) := \inf\{\|P\| : P \in \mathcal{P}(X, Y)\}$$

and the **maximal relative projection constant** by

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) := \sup\{\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(Y_m, \ell_{\infty}^N) : Y_m \text{ is an } m\text{-dimensional subspace of } \ell_{\infty}^N\}, \quad (1)$$

and finally the **maximal absolute projection constant**, by

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m) := \sup\{\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) : N \geq m\}.$$

Theorem 1 (Chalmers and Lewicki, 2009, Foucart and Skrzypek, 2017)

For integers $N \geq m$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) &= \max \left\{ \sum_{i,j=1}^n t_i t_j |U^* U|_{ij} : t \in \mathbb{R}_+^N, \|t\|_2 = 1, U \in \mathbb{K}^{m \times N}, UU^* = I_m \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^\downarrow(TAT) : T = \text{diag}(t), t \in \mathbb{R}_+^N, \|t\|_2 = 1, A \in \mathcal{A}_N \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

where:

$\lambda_1^\downarrow(M) \geq \lambda_2^\downarrow(M) \geq \dots \geq \lambda_N^\downarrow(M)$ eigenvalues of a self-adjoint matrix $M \in \mathbb{K}^{N \times N}$.

$\mathcal{A}_n = \{A \in \mathbb{K}^{N \times N} : A_{ii} = 1, |A_{ij}| = 1\}$

2 / 11

Definition 1 (Foucart and Skrzypek, 2017)

For $N \geq m$ we define a quasimaximal relative projection constant by

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) &:= \max \left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i,j=1}^m |U^* U|_{ij} : U \in \mathbb{K}^{m \times N}, UU^* = I_m \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^\downarrow(A) : A \in \mathcal{A}_N \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

and the quasimaximal absolute projection constant by

$$\mu_{\mathbb{K}}(m) = \sup \{ \mu_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) : N \geq m \}.$$

Theorem 2 (Basso, 2019, B.D. and Lewandowska, 2023)

For integer m , we have

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m) = \mu_{\mathbb{K}}(m)$$

3 / 11

PROOF

It is enough to show that $\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) \leq \mu_{\mathbb{K}}(m)$. We choose $U_0 \in \mathbb{K}^{m \times N}$ and $t^0 \in \mathbb{R}_+^n$ that realize $\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N)$. Next we define the function

$$f : \mathbb{R}_+^N \ni t \mapsto \sum_{i,j=1}^N t_i t_j |U_0^* U_0|_{ij}.$$

Since f is a continuous function, for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $t^\varepsilon \in \mathbb{Q}_+^N$ such that $\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) = f(t^0) \leq f(t^\varepsilon) + \varepsilon$ and $\|t_0 - t^\varepsilon\| \leq \varepsilon$. Taking the common denominator, we know that there exists $q, n_1, \dots, n_N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $t^\varepsilon = \frac{1}{q}(n_1, \dots, n_N)$. Put $\tilde{N} = n_1^2 + \dots + n_N^2$. Let u_i denote the i -th column of the matrix U_0 . Now we consider the matrix $U_\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times \tilde{N}}$ defined, in block notation, by

$$U_\varepsilon := \left[\frac{1}{n_1} u_1 \mathbb{1}_{n_1}^\top \mid \dots \mid \frac{1}{n_N} u_N \mathbb{1}_{n_N}^\top \right].$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} U_\varepsilon U_\varepsilon^* &= \frac{1}{n_1^2} u_1 \mathbb{1}_{n_1}^\top \mathbb{1}_{n_1} u_1^* + \dots + \frac{1}{n_N^2} u_N \mathbb{1}_{n_N}^\top \mathbb{1}_{n_N} u_N^* = u_1 u_1^* + \dots + u_N u_N^* \\ &= U_0 U_0^* = I_m. \end{aligned}$$

4 / 11

In turn,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\tilde{N}} \sum_{i,j=1}^{\tilde{N}} |U_\varepsilon^* U_\varepsilon|_{ij} &= \frac{1}{\tilde{N}} \sum_{i,j=1}^N \left| \left\langle \frac{1}{n_i} u_i, \frac{1}{n_j} u_j \right\rangle \right| n_i^2 n_j^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{\|t^\varepsilon\|^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^N |\langle u_i, u_j \rangle| \frac{n_i n_j}{q} = \frac{f(t^\varepsilon)}{\|t^\varepsilon\|^2} \\ &= \frac{\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) - \varepsilon}{(1 + \varepsilon)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

5 / 11

EQUIANGULAR TIGHT FRAMES

A system of unit (i.e., l_2 -normalized) vectors (u_1, \dots, u_n) in \mathbb{K}^m is called **equiangular** if there is a constant $c \geq 0$ such that

$$|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle| = c \quad \text{for all } i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, i \neq j.$$

It is called a **tight frame** if

$$UU^* = \frac{n}{m} I_m,$$

where U is the matrix with columns u_1, \dots, u_n .

The system (u_1, \dots, u_n) of unit vectors is called an **equiangular tight frame (ETF)** if it is both an equiangular and a tight frame.

6 / 11

Theorem 3 (König et al., 1983, Foucart and Skrzypek, 2017)

For integers $N \geq m$, the maximal relative projection constant $\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N)$ is upper bounded by

$$\delta_{m,N} := \frac{m}{N} \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{(N-1)(N-m)}{m}} \right).$$

Moreover, the following properties are equivalent:

- i) There is an equiangular tight frame consisting of N vectors in \mathbb{K}^m ,
- ii) $\mu_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) = \frac{m}{N} \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{(N-1)(N-m)}{m}} \right)$,
- iii) $\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) = \frac{m}{N} \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{(N-1)(N-m)}{m}} \right)$.

7 / 11

Theorem 4 (König and Tomczak-Jaegermann, 1994, B.D. and Lewandowska, 2023)

Let $m > 1$ then

$$\text{i) } \lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(m) \leq \delta_{m, \frac{m(m+1)}{2}} = \frac{2}{m+1} \left(1 + \frac{m-1}{2} \sqrt{m+2}\right)$$

$$\text{ii) } \lambda_{\mathbb{C}}(m) \leq \delta_{m, m^2} = \frac{1}{m} \left(1 + (m-1) \sqrt{m+1}\right).$$

Furthermore, the inequality becomes an equality if there exists a maximal ETF in \mathbb{K}^m .

8 / 11

SKETCH OF THE PROOF

Combining the Cauchy - Schwarz inequality and $\text{tr}(AA^*) \geq \frac{(\text{tr}(A))^2}{\text{rk}(A)}$ (see e.g. Bernstein, 2018) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{(|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle| - \varphi \|u_i\| \|u_j\|)^2}{\|u_i\| \|u_j\|} &= \sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{(|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle|^2 - \varphi^2 \|u_i\|^2 \|u_j\|^2)^2}{\|u_i\| \|u_j\| (|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle| + \varphi \|u_i\| \|u_j\|)^2} \\ &\geq \sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{(|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle|^2 - \varphi^2 \|u_i\|^2 \|u_j\|^2)^2}{(1 + \varphi)^2 \|u_i\|^3 \|u_j\|^3} = \sum_{i,j=1}^N \left(\frac{G_{ij}}{1 + \varphi} - \frac{\varphi^2}{1 + \varphi} \|u_i\|^{\frac{1}{2}} \|u_j\|^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)^2 \\ &\geq \frac{1}{\text{rk}(G)} \left((1 - \varphi) \sum_{i=1}^N \|u_i\| \right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

Squaring the addends of the left-sided sum and rearranging the latter inequality gives

$$2\varphi \sum_{i,j=1}^N |U^* U|_{ij} \leq \sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle|^2}{\|u_i\| \|u_j\|} + \left(\varphi^2 - \frac{(1 - \varphi)^2}{\text{rk}(G)} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \|u_i\| \right)^2. \quad (2)$$

9 / 11

Theorem 5

- ▶ $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(2) = \frac{4}{3}$. (the Grünbaum conjecture, Chalmers and Lewicki, 2010, Basso, 2019)
- ▶ $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(3) = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$;
- ▶ $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(7) = \frac{5}{2}$;
- ▶ $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(23) = \frac{14}{3}$.

Theorem 6

In complex case, exact expressions for maximal ETFs have been found for all dimensions from $m = 2$ up to $m = 53$ and in some higher dimensions as large as 5779, for 115 values of m in all,

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{C}}(m) = \frac{1}{m} \left(1 + (m-1)\sqrt{m+1} \right).$$

Conjecture 1

For every $m \geq 1$

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{C}}(m) = \frac{1}{m} \left(1 + (m-1)\sqrt{m+1} \right).$$

10 / 11

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11 / 11

The spaces Ces_∞ and ces_∞ are not isometric, yet still isomorphic

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CT

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Recall that the **Cesàro function space** Ces_∞ is defined as the collection of all measurable functions f such that the norm $\|f\|_{Ces_\infty} := \sup_{x>0} \frac{1}{x} \int_0^x |f(t)| dt$ is finite. The sequence counterpart of this construction, called the **Cesàro sequence space** ces_∞ , is understood as the collection of all sequences $x = \{x_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ such that the norm $\|x\|_{ces_\infty} := \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|$ is finite.

From the perspective of the remarkable result due to Aleksander Pełczyński [4], later complemented by Denny Leung [3], it is completely natural to ask whether the spaces Ces_∞ and ces_∞ are isomorphic. In fact, this question was asked by Astashkin and Maligranda in [2] (precisely, see Problem 1 ibidem) and finally answered positively by Astashkin, Leśnik and Maligranda in (Theorem 5.1)[1]. The goal of this talk is to provide a completely different proof of this fact. We will also show that although isomorphic, the spaces Ces_∞ and ces_∞ are not isometric.

This talk is based on a joint work with Jakub Tomaszewski titled "Rethinking the isomorphism between Ces_∞ and ces_∞ " (at the time of writing this text, it is still a work in progress).

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Prologue
 On Astashkin and Maligranda's question
 Blocking technique, after Grosse-Erdmann
 Three key observations
 The proof
 Some remarks
 Fin

The spaces Ces_{∞} and ces_{∞} are not isometric, yet still isomorphic

Function Spaces 13

Tomasz Kiwerski

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Poznań, 2024

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Tomasz Kiwerski
 Prologue
 On Astashkin and Maligranda's question
 Blocking technique, after Grosse-Erdmann
 Three key observations
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 Some remarks
 Fin

The spaces Ces_{∞} and ces_{∞} are not isometric, yet still isomorph

Contents

- 1 Prologue
- 2 On Astashkin and Maligranda's question
- 3 Blocking technique, after Grosse-Erdmann
- 4 Three key observations
- 5 The proof
- 6 Some remarks

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Tomasz Kiwerski

The spaces Ces_{∞} and ces_{∞} are not isometric, yet still isomorph

Prologue On Astashkin and Maligranda's question Blocking technique, after Grosse-Erdmann Three key observations The proof Some remarks Fin	
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T. Kiwerski and J. Tomaszewski
Rethinking the isomorphism between Ces_∞ and ces_∞
 work in progress...

Tomasz Kiwerski Prologue On Astashkin and Maligranda's question Blocking technique, after Grosse-Erdmann Three key observations The proof Some remarks Fin	The spaces Ces_∞ and ces_∞ are not isometric, yet still isomorph
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$$1 < p \leq \infty$$

$I = (0, 1)$ or $I = (0, \infty)$ with the usual Lebesgue measure

$$\|f\|_{Ces_p(I)} = \left(\int_I \left[\frac{1}{x} \int_0^x |f(t)| dt \right]^p \right)^{1/p} \quad (1)$$

$$\|f\|_{Ces_p(I)} = \|\text{Average } f\|_{L_p(I)} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Average } f(x) = \frac{1}{x} \int_0^x |f(t)| dt \quad (3)$$

Tomasz Kiwerski	The spaces Ces_∞ and ces_∞ are not isometric, yet still isomorph
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$$1 < p \leq \infty$$

$$\|x\|_{ces_p} = \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i| \right]^p \right)^{1/p} \quad (4)$$

$$\|x\|_{ces_p} = \|\text{Average } x\|_{\ell_p} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Average } x(n) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i| \quad (6)$$

Qualitative version of discrete Hardy's inequality

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i| \right)^p \leq C(p) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |x_n|^p \quad (7)$$

Operator theoretic version of Hardy's inequality

$$\text{Average: } \ell_p \rightarrow \ell_p \text{ is bounded} \quad (8)$$

Inclusion theorem

$$\ell_p \hookrightarrow ces_p \quad (9)$$

Optimal domain point of view

$$\text{Average: } ces_p \rightarrow \ell_p \text{ is bounded and } \ell_p \subsetneq ces_p \quad (10)$$

- S. V. Astashkin and L. Maligranda
Structure of Cesàro function spaces
Indag. Math. (2009)

Are the spaces Ces_∞ and ces_∞ isomorphic?

- A. Pełczyński
On the isomorphism of the spaces m and M
Bull. Acad. Polon. Sci. Sér. Sci. Math. Astr. Phys. (1958)

The spaces L_∞ and ℓ_∞ are isomorphic

- S. V. Astashkin, K. Leśnik and L. Maligranda
Isomorphic structure of Cesàro and Tandori spaces
Canad. J. Math. (2017)

The spaces Ces_∞ and ces_∞ are isomorphic!

A very superficial idea of proof

Find a **complemented** subspace of ces_∞ isomorphic to $L_1(0, 1)$...
but without using Hagler and Stegall's result (~ 1973)...
in tandem with Andrzej Alexiewicz duality result (~ 1957).
Use the **blocking technique** due to Grosse-Erdmann (~ 1998).
The rest is just Pełczyński's decomposition method (~ 1958).

K.-G. Grosse-Erdmann

The Blocking Technique, Weighted Mean Operators and Hardy's Inequality

Lecture Notes in Math. (1998)

$$\|f\|_{Ces_p(I)} \asymp \left(\sum_{j \in \mathbb{J}} 2^{j(1-p)} \left[\int_{2^n}^{2^{n+1}} |f(t)| dt \right]^p \right)^{1/p} \quad (11)$$

Here, $\mathbb{J} = \mathbb{Z}$ if $I = (0, \infty)$ and $\mathbb{J} = \mathbb{Z}_- = \{\dots, -2, -1\}$ if $I = (0, 1)$

$$\|x\|_{ces_p} \asymp \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} 2^{j(1-p)} \left[\sum_{k=2^j}^{2^{j+1}-1} |x_k| \right]^p \right)^{1/p} \quad (12)$$

$$Ces_p(I) \approx \left(\bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{J}} L_1(2^n, 2^{n+1}) \right)_{\ell_p} \approx \left(\bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{N}} L_1(0, 1) \right)_{\ell_p} \quad (13)$$

$$ces_p \approx \left(\bigoplus_{n=0}^{\infty} \ell_1^{2^n} \right)_{\ell_p} \approx \left(\bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} \ell_1^n \right)_{\ell_p} \quad (14)$$

T. Kiwerski and J. Tomaszewski

Arithmetic, interpolation and factorization of amalgams

Preprint available on ArXiv.org (2024)

★ Both spaces $Ces_\infty(0, \infty)$ and $Ces_\infty(0, 1)$ are isomorphic

★★ The spaces Ces_∞ and ces_∞ are **not** isomorphic to any $L_\infty(\mu)$

Why?

$L_\infty(\mu)$ are Grothendieck spaces, that is, every weakly* convergent sequences in $L_\infty(\mu)^*$ converges weakly.

However, Ces_∞ and ces_∞ have a complemented subspaces isomorphic to ℓ_1 ...

and ℓ_1 is **not** a Grothendieck space.

★★★ The space $(\bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} X)_{\ell_\infty}$ is isomorphic to $\mathfrak{L}(\ell_1, X)$

Why?

Given a mapping $T: \ell_1 \rightarrow X$ just set $\Phi: T \rightsquigarrow \{T(e_n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$

Remark

In particular, if X is just a scalar field, say \mathbb{F} , then

$$\left(\bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} \mathbb{F}\right)_{\ell_\infty} \approx \ell_\infty \approx (\ell_1)^* \approx \mathfrak{L}(\ell_1, \mathbb{F})$$

$$\begin{aligned} Ces_\infty(I) &\approx \left(\bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} L_1(0, 1) \right)_{\ell_\infty} \quad (\text{by blocking technique}) \\ &\approx \mathfrak{L}(\ell_1, L_1(0, 1)) \quad (\text{using } \star\star\star) \\ &\approx \mathfrak{L}(L_\infty(0, 1), \ell_\infty) \quad (\text{since } \mathfrak{L}(X, Y) \approx \mathfrak{L}(Y^*, X^*)) \\ &\approx \mathfrak{L}(\ell_\infty, \ell_\infty) \quad (\text{in view of Pełczyński's result}) \\ &\approx \mathfrak{L}(\ell_1, \ell_1) \quad (\text{again, since } \mathfrak{L}(X, Y) \approx \mathfrak{L}(Y^*, X^*)) \\ &\approx \left(\bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} \ell_1 \right)_{\ell_\infty} \quad (\text{again, using } \star\star\star) \\ &\approx \left(\bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} \ell_1^n \right)_{\ell_\infty} \quad (\text{this is folklore}) \\ &\approx ces_\infty \quad (\text{again, by blocking technique}) \end{aligned}$$

Remark 1

The spaces Ces_∞ and ces_∞ are **not** isometric

Remark 2

The space Ces_∞ is isomorphic to $(\bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} Z)_{\ell_\infty}$, where Z is a **separable** \mathcal{L}_1 -space...

Remark 3

...meanwhile, Ces_∞ is also isomorphic to $(\bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} \mathcal{M}(0, 1))_{\ell_\infty}$

Remark 4

The space ces_∞ has a [strongly] unique isometric predual

Problem 1

How to describe the dual of $(\bigoplus_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n)_{\ell_{\infty}}$?

$$\ell_{\infty}(X)^* \approx ba(X^*) \quad (15)$$

Problem 2

Does the space Ces_{∞} has a unique isometric predual?

Problem 3

What is the Banach–Mazur distance between Ces_{∞} and ces_{∞} ?

Thank you for your attention!

Geometric properties of noncommutative Orlicz spaces with p -Amemiya norms in the context of metric and Brègman projections

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CT

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Combining known characterisations of several geometric properties of Orlicz spaces with p -Amemiya norms with the results translating between the geometric properties of commutative and noncommutative rearrangement invariant spaces (cf. [4] for a review), we obtain the corresponding geometric characteristics of noncommutative Orlicz spaces with p -Amemiya norms. Next, we use them for:

- 1) the characterisation of strictly convex and reflexive (commutative and noncommutative) Orlicz spaces with p -Amemiya norms, as well as commutative and noncommutative Orlicz-Lorentz spaces with Amemiya and Morse-Transue-Nakano norms, by the norm-to-norm continuity of metric projections (substantially generalising the result of Wáng and Chén [8];
- 2) providing sufficient conditions for the (norm-to-norm, uniform, and Lipschitz-Hölder) continuity of (left and right) Brègman projections, as well as for the existence of monoids of (left and right) Brègman strongly quasi-nonexpansive operators (including Brègman resolvents of monotone operators), for a large family of the Vainberg-Brègman relative entropies over reflexive Banach spaces determined by the integrals Ψ_φ of strictly increasing ϕ -functions φ , with concrete examples specified using the above results on the Orlicz space geometry;
- 3) establishing sufficient conditions for q -uniform convexity and r -uniform Fréchet differentiability of a family of nonassociative Orlicz spaces (over type II_1 JBW-algebras) with the Morse-Transue-Nakano norm, determined by the family of Orlicz functions given by positive univariate monomials; from this we derive the continuity properties of metric and Brègman projections over these spaces (these are the first new results on nonassociative Orlicz spaces since their introduction by Tadzhibaev [6]).

Ad rem 2): Under generalisation from Hilbert spaces to Banach spaces $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$, metric projections lose several properties that are crucial for their applications (such as: pythagorean and cosine theorems, monotonicity and nonexpansivity, and strong convergence of iterated projections). However, under replacement of the metric distance by the Vainberg-Brègman relative entropy, $D_\Psi(x, y) := \Psi(x) - \Psi(y) - (\Psi'(y))(x - y)$ [7,3] (where Ψ is a proper, convex, lower semicontinuous function on X , with Gateaux derivative Ψ'), these properties hold for reflexive Banach spaces (for suitable conditions on Ψ), while coinciding with metric setting in Hilbert spaces (cf.: [1] for the main ideas with $\Psi = \frac{1}{2} \|\cdot\|_X^2$; [5] for a review with any Ψ). Yet, so far, the availability of concrete functions Ψ , satisfying all relevant conditions, has been very limited.

Talks

We use Orlicz space theory for the analogies underlying the study of $\Psi = \Psi_\varphi$, and as a source of examples of $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ differentiating between various properties of Ψ_φ . (While the geometric properties of Orlicz spaces are characterised by the properties of the Young functions $\Phi(u) = \int_0^u dt f(t)$, the geometric properties of $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ are characterised [2,9] by the properties of $\Psi_\varphi(x) := \int_0^{\|x\|_X} dt \varphi(t)$, where $\varphi : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is strictly increasing, continuous, $\varphi(0) = 0$, and $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(t) = \infty$.)

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Geometric properties of noncommutative Orlicz spaces with ρ -Amemiya norms in the context of metric and Vaĭnberg–Kachurovskĭĭ–Brègman projections

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Function Spaces XIII

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Three main ideas underlying the results presented in this talk

1. Deep analogy between the “internal” characterisation of the properties of an Orlicz space $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \mathcal{S}})$ by the properties of an Orlicz/Young function Φ and the “external” characterisation of the properties of a Banach space $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ by the properties of an Asplund Ψ_φ function.
2. The latter properties provide sufficient conditions to determine the properties of nonlinear projections generated by the Vaĭnberg–Kachurovskĭĭ–Brègman information D_{Ψ_φ} .

Orlicz space	Banach space
$\Phi(u) = \int_0^u dt \phi(t)$ $\Phi^Y(v) := \sup\{u v - \Phi(u) : u \geq 0\}$ $\underbrace{\Phi \in \dots \iff \ \cdot\ _{\Phi, \mathcal{S}} \in \dots}_{\text{characterisation of norm geometry}}$ \vdots $\underbrace{\Phi(u) + \Phi^Y(v) - uv \geq 0}_{\Rightarrow \text{Rogers–Hölder inequality}}$	$\Psi_\varphi(x) = \int_0^{\ x\ _X} dt \varphi(t)$ $\Psi_\varphi^F(y) := \sup\{\llbracket x, y \rrbracket_{X \times X^*} - \Psi_\varphi(x) : x \in X\}$ $\underbrace{\Psi_\varphi \in \dots \iff \ \cdot\ _X \in \dots}_{\text{characterisation of norm geometry}}$ \vdots $\underbrace{\Psi_\varphi(x) - \Psi_\varphi^F(y) - \llbracket x, y \rrbracket_{X \times X^*} \geq 0}_{\iff : D_{\Psi_\varphi}(x, y) \geq 0}$ <p style="text-align: center;">VKB information</p>

3. The bijective relationship between the geometric properties of norms of commutative and noncommutative rearrangement invariant spaces, $(E(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{E(\mathcal{X}, \mu)}) \xleftrightarrow{(\cdot)^T} (E(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{E(\mathcal{N}, \tau)})$, allows to extend the above analogy (and results that follow) to the noncommutative setting.

I. Spaces

Orlicz spaces with p -Amemiya norms:

- $(\mathcal{X}, \mu) :=$ a countably finite, complete measure space.
- we will denote: $\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$ (resp., $\| \cdot \|_1; \| \cdot \|_\infty$)
 $:= (\mathcal{X}, \mu)$ is atomic and infinite (resp., nonatomic and finite; nonatomic and infinite).
- $\Phi : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ is **Young** := $\Phi(0) = 0$, $\Phi \not\equiv 0$, $\exists u > 0$ $\Phi(u) < \infty$, Φ is convex on the domain of its finiteness, and left continuous on $]0, \infty[$. [Zaanen'49](#)
- $\Phi \in \mathcal{N} :=$ Φ is Young, finite, $\Phi(x) = 0$ iff $x = 0$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow +0} \frac{\Phi(x)}{x} = 0$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Phi(x)}{x} = \infty$.
- $\mathbb{R} \ni y \mapsto \Phi^Y(y) := \sup\{x|y| - \Phi(x) : x \geq 0\} \in [0, \infty]$. [Young'1912'26](#), [Birnbaum-Orlicz'31](#)
- a modular := $I_\Phi(f) := \int_{\mathcal{X}} \mu(\chi) \Phi(f(\chi))$.
- an Orlicz space := $L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu) := \{x \in L_0(\mathcal{X}, \mu) : \exists \lambda > 0 I_\Phi(\lambda x) < \infty\}$.
- $\|x\|_\Phi^O := \sup\{\int \mu|x y| : y \in L_{\Phi^Y}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), I_{\Phi^Y}(y) \leq 1\}$. [Orlicz'32](#)
- $\|x\|_\Phi := \inf\{\lambda > 0 : I_\Phi(\frac{x}{\lambda}) \leq 1\}$. [Morse-Transue'50](#), [Nakano'50](#)
- $\|x\|_{\Phi, p} := \inf_{k > 0} \{\frac{1}{k} s_p(I_\Phi(kx))\}$, $s_\infty(t) := \lim_{p \rightarrow \infty} (1 + t^p)^{1/p} = \max\{1, t\}$, $p = \infty$: [Orlicz'61](#)
 $s_{p \in [1, \infty[}(t) := (1 + t^p)^{1/p}$. $p = 1$: [Amemiya'54](#); $p \in]1, \infty[$: [Hudzik-Maligranda'00](#)
- $\|\cdot\|_\Phi = \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \infty}$. [Orlicz'61](#)
- $\|\cdot\|_\Phi^O = \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, 1}$. [Shragin'67](#), [Hudzik-Maligranda'00](#)

Orlicz–Lorentz spaces and rearrangement invariant Banach spaces:

- $\text{chr}_Z :=$ the characteristic function of the set Z .
 - a **rearrangement** :=
 $L_0(\mathcal{X}, \mu) \ni f \mapsto f^\mu(t) := \inf\{s \geq 0 : \int \mu \text{chr}_{\{x \in \mathcal{X} : |f(x)| > s\}} \leq t\} \in [0, \infty]^{[0, \infty]}$.
Hardy–Littlewood'30.
 - a Banach space $(E(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{E(\mathcal{X}, \mu)})$ with $E(\mathcal{X}, \mu) \subseteq L_0(\mathcal{X}, \mu)$ is **rearrangement invariant** := $(f \in E(\mathcal{X}, \mu), g \in L_0(\mathcal{X}, \mu), |g|^\mu(t) \leq |f|^\mu(t) \forall t \in [0, \infty]) \Rightarrow (g \in E(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|g\|_{E(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \leq \|f\|_{E(\mathcal{X}, \mu)})$. (Lorentz'51,...) Seměnov'64, Kreřn–Petunin–Seměnov'78
-
- $\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \text{let } w : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \text{ nonincreasing, } w \not\equiv 0 \\ I_{\Phi, w}(x) := \sum_{i=1}^\infty w_i \Phi(x^\mu(i)). \end{cases}$
 - $\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) \in \{\text{II}_1, \text{II}_\infty\} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \text{let } w : [0, \mu(\mathcal{X})] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \text{ nonincreasing, locally integrable w.r.t. } (\mathbb{R}^+, dt), w \not\equiv 0 \\ I_{\Phi, w}(x) := \int_{[0, \mu(\mathcal{X})]} dt w(t) \Phi(x^\mu(t)). \end{cases}$
 - $\|x\|_{\Phi, w} := \inf\{\lambda > 0 : I_{\Phi, w}(x/\lambda) \leq 1\}$.
 - $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w})$: Nakamura'70: $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$, $\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) = \text{II}_1$; Maligranda'85: Φ finite nondegenerate, $\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) \in \{\text{II}_1, \text{II}_\infty\}$; Yáo–Chéng–Sòng'92: Young $\Phi \in \Delta_2^0$, $\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$;
for $\Phi = (\cdot)^p$: Lorentz'50: $L_{p, q}$; Lorentz'51, Halperin'53: $L_{p, w}$
 - $\|x\|_{\Phi, w}^A := \inf_{k > 0} \{1 + I_{\Phi, w}(kx)\}$. Wu–Rěn'99
-
- examples of r.i.B.s.: $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p})$, $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w})$, $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A)$.

Noncommutative integration:

- $\mathcal{N} :=$ a **von Neumann algebra** on a Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} :=$ von Neumann'29, Sakai'56
 - ▶ a (noncommutative) algebra over \mathbb{C} with unit \mathbb{I} ,
 - ▶ with $*$ operation s.t. $(xy)^* = y^*x^*$, $(x + y)^* = x^* + y^*$, $(x^*)^* = x$, $(\lambda x)^* = \lambda^*x^*$,
 - ▶ that is also a Banach space,
 - ▶ with $\cdot, +, *$ continuous in the norm topology (implied by the condition $\|x^*x\| = \|x\|^2$),
 - ▶ s.t. there exists a Banach space \mathcal{N}_* satisfying the Banach space duality: $(\mathcal{N}_*)^* \cong \mathcal{N}$.
- $\tau : \mathcal{N}^+ \rightarrow [0, \infty] :=$ a **faithful, normal, semifinite trace** on \mathcal{N} : von Neumann'29
 - ▶ $\tau(0) = 0$, $\tau(x + y) = \tau(x) + \tau(y)$, $\lambda > 0 \Rightarrow \tau(\lambda x) = \lambda\tau(x)$,
 - ▶ $\forall x \in \mathcal{N}^+ \exists \mathcal{N}^+ \setminus \{0\} \ni y \leq x \tau(y) < +\infty$,
 - ▶ $\tau(\sup \mathcal{F}) = \sup_{x \in \mathcal{F}} \tau(x) \forall$ directed filters $\mathcal{F} \subseteq \mathcal{N}^+$,
 - ▶ $\tau(x^*x) = 0 \Rightarrow x = 0 \forall x \in \mathcal{N}$,
 - ▶ $\tau(u^*xu) = \tau(x) \forall$ unitary $u \in \mathcal{N}$.
- $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}} : \iff \mathcal{N} = \mathfrak{B}(\mathcal{H})$, \mathcal{H} is separable, and $\dim(\mathcal{H}) = \infty$;
 $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \text{II}_1 : \iff \tau(\mathbb{I}) < \infty$ and $\mathcal{N} \subsetneq \mathfrak{B}(\mathcal{H})$;
 $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \text{II}_\infty : \iff \tau(\mathbb{I}) = \infty$ and $\mathcal{N} \subsetneq \mathfrak{B}(\mathcal{H})$. Murray–von Neumann'36
- Let $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$. $x : \mathcal{Y} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ is called **(\mathcal{N}, τ) -measurable** iff
 - 0) x is closed, densely defined, linear;
 - 1) $u_x \in \mathcal{N}$, $E^{|x|}(\lambda) \in \mathcal{N} \forall \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$, where: $x = u_x|x|$, $|x| = \int_{\mathbb{R}^+} E^{|x|}(\lambda)|\lambda|$ (i.e. a unique polar decomposition & a unique spectral decomposition);
 - 2) $\exists \lambda \geq 0 \tau(\mathbb{I} - E^{|x|}(\lambda)) < \infty$. Nelson'74, Yeadon'75
- $\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) :=$ a set of all (\mathcal{N}, τ) -measurable operators on \mathcal{H} .

Noncommutative rearrangement invariant Banach spaces:

- a **noncommutative rearrangement** :=
 $\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \ni x \mapsto x^\tau(t) := \inf\{s \geq 0 : \tau(\mathbb{I} - E^{|x|}(s)) \leq t\} \in [0, \infty]^{[0, \infty[}$
Grothendieck'55, Ovchinnikov'70, Yeadon'75
- a **noncommutative r.i.B.s.** := a Banach space $(E(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{E(\mathcal{N}, \tau)})$ with
 $E(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \subseteq \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{N}, \tau)$ s.t. $(f \in E(\mathcal{N}, \tau), g \in \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{N}, \tau),$
 $|g|^\tau(t) \leq |f|^\tau(t) \forall t \in [0, \infty[) \Rightarrow (g \in E(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|g\|_{E(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \leq \|f\|_{E(\mathcal{N}, \tau)}).$
Ovchinnikov'70, Yeadon'80, Medzhitov'87
- **Theorem:** Yeadon'80, Sukochev'86, Dodds–Dodds–de Pagter'89, Chilin–Sukochev'90, Kalton–Sukochev'08
 If $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu),$
 $(E(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{E(\mathcal{X}, \mu)})$ is r.i.B.s.,
 $E(\mathcal{N}, \tau) := \{x \in \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) : x^\tau \in E(\mathcal{X}, \mu)\},$
 $\|\cdot\|_{E(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} := \|(\cdot)^\tau\|_{E(\mathcal{X}, \mu)},$
 then: $(E(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{E(\mathcal{N}, \tau)})$ is n.r.i.B.s.

Noncommutative Orlicz and Orlicz–Lorentz spaces (I):

- $l_\Phi(x) := \tau(\Phi(x)) = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \Phi(x^\tau(i)) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}} \\ \int_{[0, \tau(\mathbb{I})[} dt \Phi(x^\tau(t)) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\text{II}_1, \text{II}_\infty\} \end{cases}$
 $\forall x \in \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{N}, \tau).$
- $L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau) := \{x \in \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) : \exists \lambda > 0 \ l_\Phi(\lambda x) < \infty\}.$
- $\|x\|_\Phi := \inf\{\lambda > 0 : l_\Phi(\frac{x}{\lambda}) \leq 1\}.$ $l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: Rao'71, II_1 : Tadzhibaev'86
- $\|x\|_{\Phi}^{\tilde{O}} := \sup\{|\tau(xy)| : y \in \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \tau(\Phi^Y(|y|)) \leq 1\}.$ II_1 : Muratov'78
- $\|x\|_{\Phi}^{\tilde{\sim}} := \sup\{|\tau(xy)| : L_{\Phi^Y}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|y\|_{\Phi^Y}^{\tilde{O}} \leq 1\}.$ II_1 : Muratov'78
- $\|x\|_{\Phi}^{\tilde{O}} := \sup\{\tau(|xy|) : y \in \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \tau(\Phi^Y(|y|)) \leq 1\}.$ $\text{II}_1, \text{II}_\infty$: Kunze'90
- $\|x\|_{\Phi, p} := \inf_{k>0} \{\frac{1}{k} s_p(l_\Phi(kx))\}.$ RPK'23
- $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w})$: Hán'13
 $(L_{p, q}; l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}})$: Triebel'67, $(L_{p, q}; \{\text{II}_1, \text{II}_\infty\})$: Peetre–Sparr'75, Kosaki'81, $L_{1, w}$: Ovchinnikov'71, $L_{p, w}$: Ciach'83
- $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A)$: RPK'23

Noncommutative Orlicz and Orlicz–Lorentz spaces (II):

- Let:

- ▶ $\Phi \in \Delta_2^0 := \lim_{u \rightarrow +0} \frac{\Phi(2u)}{\Phi(u)} < \infty$; Birnbaum–Orlicz'31
- ▶ $\Phi \in \Delta_2^\infty := \limsup_{u \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Phi(2u)}{\Phi(u)} < \infty$; Birnbaum–Orlicz'30
- ▶ $\Phi \in \Delta_2 := \sup_{u > 0} \frac{\Phi(2u)}{\Phi(u)} < \infty$ ($\iff \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap \Delta_2^\infty$); Burkil'28
- ▶ $\Phi \in \Delta_2^{\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} :=$
 $\Phi \in \Delta_2^0$ (resp., Δ_2^∞ ; Δ_2) if $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$ (resp., II_1 ; II_∞).

- **Theorem:** RPK'23

- 1) $(\Phi, \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^\infty, \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = II_1, \mathcal{N}$ has a commutative von Neumann subalgebra) $\Rightarrow (\|\cdot\|_\Phi^{\tilde{O}} = \|\cdot\|_\Phi^O, (L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_\Phi) \cong (L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\tilde{\Phi}}^{\tilde{O}}))$.
- 2) $\Phi \in \Delta_2^{\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \Rightarrow (L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_\Phi)^* \cong (L_{\Phi^Y}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi^Y}^O)$.
- 3) $\Phi, \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^{\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \Rightarrow (L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_\Phi^O)^* \cong (L_{\Phi^Y}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi^Y})$.
- 4) $\Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^{\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \Rightarrow \|\cdot\|_\Phi^O = \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, 1}$.
- 5) $(\Phi \in \Delta_2^{\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau)}, \Phi$ finite, Φ not linear on $[0, \infty[$, $\gamma \in]0, 1[$) $\Rightarrow (L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, 1/\gamma})^* \cong (L_{\Phi^Y}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi^Y, 1/(1-\gamma)})$.

II. Geometry of spaces

Geometric properties of Banach spaces $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$:

- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{R} := X \ni x \mapsto \llbracket x, \cdot \rrbracket_{X \times X^*} \in X^{**}$ is an isometric isomorphism. [Hahn'27](#)
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{SC} := \forall x, y \in S(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$
 $x \neq y \Rightarrow \|x + y\|_X < 2$. [Kreĭn'38](#); equiv.: [Fréchet'25](#), [Clarkson'36](#)
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{LUC} := \forall \varepsilon_1 > 0 \forall x \in S(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \exists \varepsilon_2 > 0 \forall y \in S(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$
 $\|x - y\|_X \geq \varepsilon_1 \Rightarrow \|x + y\|_X \leq 2(1 - \varepsilon_2)$. [Lovaglia'55](#)
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UC} := \forall \varepsilon_1 > 0 \forall \varepsilon_2 > 0 \forall x, y \in S(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$
 $\|x - y\|_X \geq \varepsilon_1 \Rightarrow \|x + y\|_X \leq 2(1 - \varepsilon_2)$. [Clarkson'36](#)
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{RRS} := \forall \{x_n \in X : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ (x_n is convergent to $x \in X$ in weak topology, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n\|_X = \|x\|_X$) $\Rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x\|_X = 0$.
[I_p: Radon'1913](#), [L_p\(\$\mathcal{X}, \mu\$ \): Riesz'29](#), $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$: [Shmul'yan'39](#)
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{G} := \|\cdot\|_X$ is Gateaux differentiable on $S(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$. [Mazur'33](#)
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{F} := \|\cdot\|_X$ is Fréchet differentiable on $S(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$. [Mazur'33](#)
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UF} := \forall \varepsilon_1 > 0 \exists \varepsilon_2 \forall x, y \in S(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$
 $\|x - y\|_X \leq \varepsilon_1 \Rightarrow \|x + y\|_X \geq 2(1 - \varepsilon_2 \|x - y\|_X)$. [Day'44](#); equiv.: [Shmul'yan'40](#), [Nakano'51](#)
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UC}_{r \in [2, \infty[} := \exists \lambda > 0 \forall x, y \in X$
 $\|x + y\|_X^r + \|x - y\|_X^r \geq 2(\|x\|_X^r + \|\lambda^{-1}y\|_X^r)$.
[Assouad'75](#); equiv.: [Woyczyński'75](#), $r=2$: [Lindenstrauss'63](#)
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UF}_{r \in [1, 2]} := \exists \lambda > 0 \forall x, y \in X$ $\|x + y\|_X^r + \|x - y\|_X^r \leq 2(\|x\|_X^r + \|\lambda y\|_X^r)$.
[Assouad'75](#); equiv.: [Hoffmann-Jørgensen'74](#), $p = 2$: [Lindenstrauss'63](#)

Characterisation of geometry of $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}$ by the properties of Φ :

Each property has a priori $3 \times 3 = 9$ different cases of $(\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), p)$:

- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p} \in \mathbf{SC}$: $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, 1)$: [Cuĭ-Hudzik-Nowak-Płuciennik'99](#); $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, [1, \infty[)$: [Lĭ-Cuĭ'22](#);
 $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, \infty)$: [Kamińska'81](#); $(\|I_1, \infty, [1, \infty[)$: [Cuĭ-Duàn-Hudzik-Wiśta'08](#).
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p} \in \mathbf{LUC}$: $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, 1)$: [Cuĭ-Hudzik-Nowak-Płuciennik'99](#); $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, [1, \infty[)$:
[Chéng-Duàn-Zuō'15](#) $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$; $(\{I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, \|I_1, I_{\infty}\}, \infty)$: [Kamińska'84](#); $(\|I_1, 1)$: [Chén'86](#) $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$;
 $(\|I_1, [1, \infty[)$: [Duàn-Zuō-Cuĭ'14](#) $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$; $(\|I_{\infty}, 1)$: [Níng'10](#) $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$; $(\|I_{\infty}, [1, \infty[)$: [\[?\]](#).
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p} \in \mathbf{RRS}$: $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, 1)$: [Cuĭ-Hudzik-Nowak-Płuciennik'99](#); $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, [1, \infty[)$: [Zhào-Cuĭ'21](#);
 $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, \infty)$: [Hudzik-Pallaschke'97](#); $(\|I_1, 1)$: [Cuĭ-Zhào'22](#); $(\|I_1, [1, \infty[)$: [\[?\]](#); $(\|I_1, \infty)$:
[Medzhitov-Sukochev'92](#), [Wáng-Cuĭ'98](#); $(\|I_{\infty}, [1, \infty[)$: [\[?\]](#); $(\|I_{\infty}, \infty)$: [Wáng-Cuĭ-Zhāng'98](#).
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p} \in \mathbf{UC}$: $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, 1)$: [Táo'86](#) $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$; $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, [1, \infty[)$: [\[?\]](#); $(\{I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, \|I_1, I_{\infty}\}, \infty)$:
[Kamińska'82](#); $(\|I_1, I_{\infty}, 1)$: [Milnes'57](#); $(\{\|I_1, I_{\infty}\}, [1, \infty[)$: [Kaczmarek'18](#).
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p} \in \mathbf{G}$: $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, 1)$: [Cuĭ-Hudzik-Nowak-Płuciennik'99](#) \cup [Lĭ-Cuĭ-Wiśta'23](#); $(I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, [1, \infty[)$:
[Lĭ-Cuĭ-Wiśta'23](#); $(\{I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, \|I_1, I_{\infty}\}, \infty)$: [Grząślewicz-Hudzik'92](#); $(\{\|I_1, I_{\infty}\}, 1)$: [Vigelis'11](#);
 $(\|I_1, [1, \infty[)$: [Lĭ-Cuĭ-Wiśta'21](#); $(\|I_{\infty}, [1, \infty[)$: [\[?\]](#).
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p} \in \mathbf{R}$ & $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p} \in \mathbf{OC}$: $(\{I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, \|I_1, I_{\infty}\}, \{1, \infty\})$: [Luxemburg'55](#);
 $(\{I_{\infty}^{\text{s.f.}}, \|I_1, I_{\infty}\}, [1, \infty[)$: follows from equivalence of $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}$ and $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi}$.

Known results on UC_s and UF_r of $\|\cdot\|_\Phi$:

- Φ finite, nondegenerate, $\Phi(1) = 1$, $u \mapsto \Phi(u^{1/2})$ convex, $\Phi \in \Delta_2$ (resp., Δ_2^0) and $\frac{1}{\gamma} := \sup_{t>0} \frac{t\Phi'_+(t)}{\Phi(t)}$ (resp., $\sup_{t \in]0,1]} \frac{t\Phi'_+(t)}{\Phi(t)}$) for $\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) \in \{\|1, \|_\infty\}$ (resp., $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$)
 $\Rightarrow (L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_\Phi) \in \mathbf{UC}_{1/\gamma}$. Hudzik'91
- Φ is an inverse of $u \mapsto (\Phi_0^{-1}(u))^{1-2\gamma} u^\gamma$, $\gamma \in]0, \frac{1}{2}]$, $\Phi_0 \in \mathbb{N}$, $\|\cdot\| \in \{\|\cdot\|_\Phi, \|\cdot\|_\Phi^O\}$
 $\Rightarrow (L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|) \in \mathbf{UC}_{1/\gamma} \cap \mathbf{UF}_{1/(1-\gamma)}$. Ren'97
- Φ finite, nondegenerate, $\Phi(1) = 1$, $1 < r \leq 2 \leq s < \infty$, $u \mapsto \Phi(u^{1/r})$ convex, $u \mapsto \Phi(u^{1/s})$ concave, $\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) \in \{\|1, \|_\infty\}$
 $\Rightarrow (L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_\Phi) \in \mathbf{UC}_s \cap \mathbf{UF}_r$. Hao-Kamińska-Tomczak-Jaegermann'06
- no characterisation results (so far).
- no results for $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p \in]1, \infty[}$ (so far).

Charact. of geometry of $\{\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}, \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A\}$ by the properties of $\{\Phi, w\}$:

- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w} \in \mathbf{SC}$: $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: Cerd-Hudzik-Kamińska-Mastyło'98; $\{\|1, \|_\infty\}$: Kamińska'90.
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A \in \mathbf{SC}$: $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: Ning'10 $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$; $\|1$: W-Ren'99 $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$; $\|_\infty$: Chn'09 $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$.
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w} \in \mathbf{RRS}$: $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: Hudzik-Kowalewski-Lewicki'06; $\{\|1, \|_\infty\}$: [??].
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A \in \mathbf{RRS}$: $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: Cu-Foralewski-Hudzik-Kaczmarek'21; $\{\|1, \|_\infty\}$: [??].
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w} \in \mathbf{LUC}$: $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: Cerd-Hudzik-Kamińska-Mastyło'98; $\|1$: Hudzik-Kamińska-Mastyło'97, W-Ren'97; $\|_\infty$: Hudzik-Kamińska-Mastyło'97.
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A \in \mathbf{LUC}$: $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: M'11 $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$; $\|1$: [??]; $\|_\infty$: Ning'10 $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$.
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w} \in \mathbf{UC}$: $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: Cerd-Hudzik-Kamińska-Mastyło'98; $\{\|1, \|_\infty\}$: Kamińska'91.
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A \in \mathbf{UC}$: $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: Ning'10 $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$; $\|1$: Chn'09 $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$; $\|_\infty$: Wng-Chn'12 $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$.
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w} \in \mathbf{R}$: $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: Yo-Chng-Sng'92; $\{\|1, \|_\infty\}$: Ln-Sn'95.
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w} \in \mathbf{OC}$: $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$: Yo-Chng-Sng'92.
- $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A \in \mathbf{OC}$: $\{\|1, \|_\infty\}$: Foralewski-Koczak'23.
- the rest of \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{OC} cases follows from the equivalence of $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}$ with $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A$.

Transfer of geometric properties between r.i.B.s. and n.r.i.B.s.:

- Let $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu)$, $(E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} := (E(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{E(\mathcal{X}, \mu)})$ be r.i.B.s., $(E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} := (\{x \in \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) : x^\tau \in E(\mathcal{X}, \mu)\}, \|\cdot\|_{E(\mathcal{X}, \mu)}^\tau)$.
- $(E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{SC} \iff (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{SC}$. Arazy'81, Chilin–Krygin–Sukochev'92, Czerwińska–Kamińska'17
- $(E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{RRS} \iff (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{RRS}$. Arazy'81, Chilin–Dodds–Sukochev'97
- $(E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{LUC} \iff (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{LUC}$. Krygin–Sukochev–Chilin'91, Chilin–Krygin–Sukochev'92
- $(E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{UC} \iff (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{UC}$. Krygin–Sukochev–Chilin'91, Chilin–Krygin–Sukochev'92
- $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \mathbf{I}_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{OC})$
 $\Rightarrow ((E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{G} \iff (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{G});$ Arazy'81
 $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\mathbf{II}_1, \mathbf{II}_\infty\}, (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{OC}, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} x^\mu(t) = 0 \forall x \in (E(\mathcal{X}, \mu))^\times)$
 $\Rightarrow ((E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{G} \iff (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{G})$. Czerwińska–Kamińska–Kubiak'12
- $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \mathbf{I}_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{R}) \Leftrightarrow (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{R};$ Arazy'81
 $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \mathbf{II}_1 \Rightarrow ((E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{R} \iff (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{R});$ Sukochev'87
 $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \mathbf{II}_\infty, (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{OC}) \Rightarrow$
 $((E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{R} \iff (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{R})$. Dodds–Dodds'95
- $(E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{UC}_q \Leftrightarrow (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{UC}_q$. Tomczak–Jaegermann'84, Xü'89
- $(E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{X}, \mu)} \in \mathbf{UF}_q \Leftrightarrow (E, \|\cdot\|)_{(\mathcal{N}, \tau)} \in \mathbf{UF}_q$. Tomczak–Jaegermann'84, Xü'89

Ψ_φ :

- $\varphi : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is called a **gauge** $:= \varphi$ is strictly increasing, continuous, $\varphi(0) = 0$, $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(t) = \infty$. Matuszewska'60 (without strictly increasing), Beurling–Livingston'62
- For any Banach space $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$, a **duality map** $:= j_\varphi : X \ni x \mapsto \{y \in X^* : \llbracket x, y \rrbracket_{X \times X^*} = \|x\|_X \|y\|_{X^*}, \|y\|_{X^*} = \varphi(\|x\|_X)\} \subseteq X^*$. Beurling–Livingston'62
- a **subdifferential** $:= \partial\Psi(x) := \{y \in X^* : \Psi(z) - \Psi(x) \geq \llbracket z - x, y \rrbracket_{X \times X^*} \forall z \in X\}$. Rockafellar'63, Moreau'63, Minty'64
- if Ψ is Gateaux differentiable at x , then $\partial\Psi(x) = \{\mathcal{D}^G\Psi(x)\}$, where $\mathcal{D}^G\Psi(x) :=$ a Gateaux derivative of Ψ at x .
- $X \ni x \mapsto \Psi_\varphi(x) := \int_0^{\|x\|_X} dt \varphi(t) \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Asplund'67
- **Theorem:** Asplund'67
 $j_\varphi(x) = \partial\Psi_\varphi(x) \forall x \in X \setminus \{0\}$,
 $j_\varphi(0) = 0$.

Charact. of geometry of Banach spaces by the geometry of Ψ_φ :

- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{SC} \iff \Psi_\varphi$ is strictly convex on X . Zălinescu'83
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{LUC} \iff \Psi_\varphi$ is uniformly convex at each $x \in X$. Zălinescu'83
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UC} \iff \Psi_\varphi$ is uniformly convex on bounded subsets of X .
Zălinescu'83
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{G} \iff \Psi_\varphi$ is Gateaux differentiable on X . Zălinescu'83
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{F} \iff \Psi_\varphi$ is Fréchet differentiable on X . Zălinescu'02
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UF} \iff \Psi_\varphi$ is uniformly Fréchet diff. on bounded subsets of X .
Zălinescu'02
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UC}_r \iff \Psi_\varphi$ with $\varphi(t) = rt^{r-1}$ is uniformly convex on X . Xu'91
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UF}_r \iff \Psi_\varphi$ with $\varphi(t) = rt^{r-1}$ is uniformly Fréchet diff. on X .
Shioji'94
- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{R} \iff \partial\Psi_\varphi$ is surjective on X . de Figueiredo'67

Characterisation of the geometry of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p})$ (I):

Theorem: RPK'21-'23

If

$\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) = \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{1^{\text{s.f.}}, 1, \infty\}$,

Φ is semi-Young ($:=$ Young without left-semicontinuity on $]0, \infty[$),

φ is a gauge,

$\Psi_\varphi : L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$,

$a_\Phi := \sup\{u \geq 0 : \Phi(u) = 0\}$,

$b_\Phi := \sup\{u \geq 0 : \Phi(u) < \infty\}$,

$\Phi^\vee(t) := \sup\{u \geq 0 : \Phi(u) \leq t\}$,

Φ'_+ (resp., Φ'_-) := right (resp., left) derivative of Φ ,

$\Phi \in C^1(I) := \Phi'_+$ is continuous on $I \subseteq \mathbb{R}$,

$\Phi \in \mathbf{SC}(I) := (u \neq v \Rightarrow \Phi(\frac{u+v}{2}) < \frac{1}{2}(\Phi(u) + \Phi(v))) \forall u, v \in I \subseteq \mathbb{R}$,

$\Phi \in \mathbf{UC}(I) := \forall a \in]0, 1[\exists \delta(a) \in]0, 1[\forall u \in I \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

$\Phi(\frac{u+au}{2}) \leq \frac{1}{2}(1 - \delta(a))(\Phi(u) + \Phi(au))$,

$\mathbf{UC} := \mathbf{UC}(\mathbb{R})$,

$\mathbf{UC}^\infty := \mathbf{UC}([u_0, \infty[)$ for some $u_0 > 0$,

$\varpi_\Phi(\lambda) := \sup\{t > 0 : \Phi^\vee(\Phi'_+(t)) \leq \lambda\}$,

$\varpi_{\Phi, p}(\lambda) := \sup\{t > 0 : 2^p(\Phi(t))^{p-1}\Phi^\vee(\Phi'_+(t)) \leq \lambda\}$,

$p = 1^{\mathbf{O}} := \{\text{either } \|\cdot\|_\Phi^{\mathbf{O}} \text{ is used instead of } \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, 1}, \text{ or } \Phi^\vee \in \Delta_2^{\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau)}\}$,

then:

Characterisation of the geometry of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p})$ (II):

1) if $p \in \{1^0\} \cup]1, \infty]$, and the following conditions are jointly satisfied:

- Φ is Young if not $((\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$ and $p = 1^0$) or $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\|1_1, \|_\infty\}$ and $p = \infty$));
- $(\Phi$ is Young or $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Phi(x)}{x} = \infty)$ if $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\|1_1, \|_\infty\}$ and $p = \infty$);

then:

Ψ_φ is strictly convex \iff

$(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \in \mathbf{SC} \iff$

$(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \in \mathbf{SC} \iff$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Phi \in \text{SC}([0, \varpi_\Phi(1)]), a_\Phi = 0, \exists u > 0 \Phi^{\mathbf{Y}}(\Phi'_+(u)) \geq \frac{1}{2} & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = 1^0 \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap \text{SC}([0, \Phi^\vee(\frac{1}{2})]), \exists u > 0 \Phi(u) = 1 & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = \infty \\ \Phi \in \text{SC}([0, \varpi_{\Phi, p}(1)]), a_\Phi = 0, \exists u > 0 \Phi^{\mathbf{Y}}(\Phi'_+(u)) > \frac{1}{2} & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p \in]1, \infty[\\ \Phi \in \text{SC}([0, b_\Phi]), \lim_{u \rightarrow \infty} \Phi^{\mathbf{Y}}(\Phi'_+(u)) = \infty, \\ \sup\{u \geq 0 : \Phi^{\mathbf{Y}}(\Phi'_+(u))\mu(\mathcal{X}) < 1\} \leq b_\Phi & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\|1_1, \|_\infty\}, p = 1^0 \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^\infty \cap \text{SC}([0, b_\Phi]) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|1_1, p = \infty \\ \Phi \in \text{SC}([0, b_\Phi]) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\|1_1, \|_\infty\}, p \in]1, \infty[\\ \Phi \in \Delta_2 \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|_\infty, p = \infty; \end{array} \right.$$

Characterisation of the geometry of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p})$ (III):

2) if $p \in [1, \infty]$ and the following conditions are jointly satisfied:

- $\Phi \in \mathbf{N}$ if $(p = 1$ and $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\|1_1, \|_\infty\})$ or $(p \in]1, \infty[$ and $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, \|1_1\})$;
- $b_\Phi = \infty$ if $p = \infty$;
- $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|_\infty$ and $p \in]1, \infty[)$ does not hold;

then:

Ψ_φ is uniformly convex at each $x \in L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \iff$

$(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \in \mathbf{LUC} \iff$

$(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \in \mathbf{LUC} \iff$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap \text{SC}([0, \varpi_\Phi(1)]), \Phi^{\mathbf{Y}} \in \Delta_2^0, \\ \exists u > 0 \Phi^{\mathbf{Y}}(\Phi'_+(u)) \geq \frac{1}{2} & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = 1 \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \text{ and either } \Phi \in \text{SC}([0, \Phi^\vee(1)]) \\ \text{or } (\Phi \in \text{SC}([0, \Phi^\vee(\frac{1}{2})]) \text{ and } \Phi^{\mathbf{Y}} \in \Delta_2^0) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = \infty \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap \text{SC}([0, \varpi_{\Phi, p}(1)]), \Phi^{\mathbf{Y}} \in \Delta_2^0 & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p \in]1, \infty[\\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^\infty \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}), \Phi^{\mathbf{Y}} \in \Delta_2^\infty & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|1_1, p \in [1, \infty[\\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^\infty \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|1_1, p = \infty \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2 \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}), \Phi^{\mathbf{Y}} \in \Delta_2 & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|_\infty, p = 1 \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2 \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|_\infty, p = \infty; \end{array} \right.$$

Characterisation of the geometry of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p})$ (IV):

3) if $p \in [1, \infty]$ and the following conditions are jointly satisfied:

- a) $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$ if $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$ and $p = 1)$;
- b) $b_\Phi = \infty$ if $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, l_1\}$ and $p = \infty)$;
- c) Φ is Young if $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{l_1, l_\infty\}$ and $p \in [1, \infty[)$;
- d) $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$ and $p \in]1, \infty[)$ does not hold;

then:

Ψ_φ is uniformly convex on bounded subsets of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \iff$

$(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \in \mathbf{UC} \iff$

$(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \in \mathbf{UC} \iff$

$$\begin{cases} \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap \text{UC}([0, \varpi_\Phi(1)]) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = 1 \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap \text{UC}([0, \Phi^\vee(\frac{1}{2})]) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = \infty \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^\infty \cap \text{UC}^\infty \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_1, p \in [1, \infty] \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2 \cap \text{UC} & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty, p \in [1, \infty]; \end{cases}$$

Characterisation of the geometry of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p})$ (V):

4) if $p \in \{1^0\} \cup]1, \infty]$ and the following conditions are jointly satisfied:

- a) $(b_\Phi = \infty$ and $\lim_{u \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Phi(u)}{u} = \infty)$ if either $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, l_1\}$ and $p \in]1, \infty[)$ or $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_1$ and $p = 1^0)$;
- b) $(\Phi$ is Young, $a_\Phi = 0$, $\exists u > 0 \Phi(u) = 1)$ if $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$ and $p = \infty)$;
- c) $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$ if $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_1$ and $p = \infty)$;
- d) $b_\Phi = \infty$ if $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty$ and $p \in \{1^0, \infty\})$;
- e) $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty$ and $p \in]1, \infty[)$ does not hold;

then:

$(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \in \mathbf{RRS} \iff$

$(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \in \mathbf{RRS} \iff$

$$\begin{cases} \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p \in \{1^0\} \cup]1, \infty] \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^\infty \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_1, p \in \{1^0\} \cup]1, \infty] \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2 \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty, p \in \{1^0, \infty\}; \end{cases}$$

Characterisation of the geometry of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p})$ (VI):

- 5) if $p \in \{1^0\} \cup]1, \infty]$ for $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$, or $p \in [1, \infty]$ for $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\|1_1, \|_\infty\}$, and the following conditions are jointly satisfied:
- $(b_\Phi < \infty, \Phi(b_\Phi) < \infty) \Rightarrow \Phi'_-(b_\Phi) < \infty$ if $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = \infty)$;
 - $\Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^\infty$ (resp., Δ_2) if $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|1_1$ (resp., $\|_\infty$);
 - Φ is lower semicontinuous if $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\|1_1, \|_\infty\}$ and $p = 1^0$) and it is Young in all other cases;
 - $(\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|_\infty$ and $p \in]1, \infty[)$ does not hold;

then:

Ψ_φ is Gateaux differentiable on $L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \iff$

$(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \in \mathbf{G} \iff (L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \in \mathbf{G} \iff$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap C^1([0, \varpi_\Phi(\frac{1}{2})[), \lim_{t \rightarrow +0} \frac{\Phi(t)}{t} = 0 & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = 1^0 \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap C^1([0, \varpi_{\Phi, p}(1)[), \lim_{t \rightarrow +0} \frac{\Phi(t)}{t} = 0 & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p \in]1, \infty[\\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap C^1([0, \Phi^V(1)[), \Phi(b_\Phi) \geq 1 & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = \infty \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^\infty \cap C^1(\mathbb{R}) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|1_1, p \in \{1, \infty\} \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^\infty \cap C^1(\mathbb{R}), \lim_{t \rightarrow +0} \frac{\Phi(t)}{t} = 0 & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|1_1, p \in]1, \infty[\\ \Phi \in \Delta_2 \cap C^1(\mathbb{R}) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|_\infty, p \in \{1, \infty\}. \end{array} \right.$$

We have also the analogous sets of results for $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w})$ and $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A)$.

III. Nonlinear projections

Metric projections in Banach and Orlicz spaces

- Let $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ be a Banach space, $\emptyset \neq C \subseteq X$.
- **metric projection** $:= \mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|_X}}(x) := \arg \inf_{y \in C} \{\|x - y\|_X\} \subseteq X$.
- a set C is **Chebyshev** $:= \mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|_X}}$ is a function on $X \iff \forall x \in X \mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|_X}}(x) = \{*\}$. Efimov–Stechkin'58
- if C is closed and convex, then:
 $\mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|_X}}$ is a function on $X \iff (X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC}$. Klee'61
- if C is closed and convex, and $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC} \cap \mathbf{RRS}$,
then $\mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|_X}}$ is norm-to-norm continuous. Fán–Glicksberg'58

- **Theorem:** Wáng–Chén'86
if (\mathcal{X}, μ) is nonatomic, $\Phi \in \mathbf{N}$, C is closed and convex, then **equivalent** are:
 - 1) $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_\Phi) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC}$;
 - 2) $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_\Phi^{\circ}) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC}$;
 - 3) $\mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|_\Phi}}$ is norm-to-norm continuous;
 - 4) $\mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|_\Phi^{\circ}}}$ is norm-to-norm continuous.
- if (\mathcal{X}, μ) is nonatomic, Φ is finite, then:
 $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_\Phi) \in \mathbf{SC} \iff (L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_\Phi) \in \mathbf{LUC}$. Kamińska'84
- if (\mathcal{X}, μ) is nonatomic, Φ is finite and nondegenerate, then:
 $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}) \in \mathbf{SC} \iff (L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}) \in \mathbf{LUC}$.
Hudzik–Kamińska–Mastyło'97

Charact. of norm continuity of $\mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|}}$ on Orlicz spaces (I)

Theorem: RPK'23

Let $\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) = \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, \|\cdot\|_1, \|\cdot\|_\infty\}$, $p \in [1, \infty]$,
with an exclusion of $(\|\cdot\|_\infty,]1, \infty[)$ case.

Let φ be a gauge, $\Psi_\varphi : (L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

Let $\emptyset \neq M \subseteq L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu)$ and $\emptyset \neq K \subseteq L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau)$ be convex and closed in the topology of respective $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}$.

$$\text{Let } \begin{cases} a_\Phi = 0, \exists u > 0 \Phi(u) = 1 & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = \infty \\ b_\Phi = \infty, \lim_{u \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Phi(u)}{u} = \infty & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p \in]1, \infty[\\ \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \Phi^\Psi(\Phi'_+(t)) = \infty, & \\ \sup\{u \geq 0 : \Phi^\Psi(\Phi'_+(u))\mu(\mathcal{X}) < 1\} \leq b_\Phi & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\|\cdot\|_1, \|\cdot\|_\infty\}, p = 1 \\ \Phi \in \mathbf{N} & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|\cdot\|_1, p = \infty \\ b_\Phi = \infty, \lim_{u \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Phi(u)}{u} = \infty & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|\cdot\|_1, p \in]1, \infty[\\ b_\Phi = \infty & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|\cdot\|_\infty, p = \infty. \end{cases}$$

Charact. of norm continuity of $\mathfrak{R}_C^{d\|\cdot\|}$ on Orlicz spaces (II)

Consider the statements:

- 1) $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho}) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC}$;
- 2) $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho}) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC}$;
- 3) $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho}) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC} \cap \mathbf{RRS}$;
- 4) $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho}) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC} \cap \mathbf{RRS}$;
- 5) M is Chebyshev;
- 6) K is Chebyshev;
- 7) $\mathfrak{R}_M^{d\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho}}$ is norm-to-norm continuous on $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho})$;
- 8) $\mathfrak{R}_K^{d\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho}}$ is norm-to-norm continuous on $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho})$;
- 9) Ψ_φ is strictly convex and $\text{ran}(\mathfrak{D}^G \Psi_\varphi) = L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau)$.

Then:

- (i) if $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\|1, \|_\infty\}$ and $(\Phi \in \Delta_2$ if $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|_\infty$), then: **1) iff ... iff 9)**
 iff **10)** := $\begin{cases} \Phi \in \Delta_2^\infty \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}), \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^\infty & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|1, \rho \in [1, \infty] \\ \Phi \in \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}), \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2 & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|_\infty, \rho \in \{1, \infty\}; \end{cases}$

- (ii) if $\widetilde{\text{type}}(\mathcal{N}) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$ then:

Charact. of norm continuity of $\mathfrak{R}_C^{d\|\cdot\|}$ on Orlicz–Lorentz spaces (I)

Theorem: RPK'23

Let $\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu) = \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, \|1, \|_\infty\}$, $\rho \in [1, \infty]$, $\|\cdot\| \in \{\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}, \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^A\}$.

Let φ be a gauge, $\Psi_\varphi : (L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

Let $\emptyset \neq M \subseteq L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu)$ and $\emptyset \neq K \subseteq L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau)$ be convex and closed in the topology of respective $\|\cdot\|$.

Consider the statements:

- 1) $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC}$;
- 2) $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC}$;
- 3) $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC} \cap \mathbf{RRS}$;
- 4) $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC} \cap \mathbf{RRS}$;
- 5) M is Chebyshev;
- 6) K is Chebyshev;
- 7) $\mathfrak{R}_M^{d\|\cdot\|}$ is norm-to-norm continuous on $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|)$;
- 8) $\mathfrak{R}_K^{d\|\cdot\|}$ is norm-to-norm continuous on $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \mu), \|\cdot\|)$;
- 9) Ψ_φ is strictly convex and $\text{ran}(\mathfrak{D}^G \Psi_\varphi) = L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau)$.

Then:

- (i) if $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{\|1, \|_\infty\}$ and $\|\cdot\| = \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}$, Φ is finite and nondegenerate, $\int_0^1 dt w(t) = 1$, and $(\Phi \in \Delta_2$ and $\int_0^\infty dt w(t) = \infty$) if $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|_\infty$), then **1) iff ... iff 9) iff**
 $\begin{cases} \Phi \in \Delta_2^\infty \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}), \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^\infty, w(t) > 0 \forall t \in [0, \tau(\mathbb{I})[& : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|1 \\ \Phi \in \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}), \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2, w(t) > 0 \forall t \in \mathbb{R}^+ & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = \|_\infty; \end{cases}$

Charact. of norm continuity of $\mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|}}$ on Orlicz–Lorentz spaces (II)

(ii) if $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$, $\|\cdot\| = \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}$, Φ is finite and nondegenerate, $w(t) > 0$ $\forall i \in \mathbb{N}$, $\sum_{i=1}^\infty w(i) = \infty$, $w(1) = 1$, $\Phi \in \Delta_2^0$, then:

where $10^\circ) := \Phi \in \text{SC}[0, \Phi^{-1}(\frac{1}{w(1)+w(2)})]$, $\Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^0$;

(iii) if $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = II_\infty$, $\|\cdot\| = \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^\Delta$, $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$, $\int_0^1 dt w(t) = 1$, $\Phi \in \Delta_2$, and $\int_0^\infty dt w(t) = \infty$, then 1), 2), 5), 6), 9) are equivalent with $10')$:= $\Phi \in \text{SC}(\mathbb{R})$, $\Phi^Y \in \Delta_2$.

If, additionally, $\exists k > 1 \exists x_0 > 0 \forall x > x_0 \int_0^{2x} dt w(t) \geq k \int_0^x dt w(t)$, then $10')$ is also equivalent with 3), 4), 7), 8);

(iv) if $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$, $\|\cdot\| = \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^\Delta$, $\Phi \in \mathbb{N}$, $w(i) > 0 \forall i \in \mathbb{N}$, $\sum_{i=1}^\infty w(i) = \infty$, $w(1) = 1$, $\Phi \in \Delta_2^0$, then the above diagram of implications holds, under replacement of $10^\circ)$ by: $\Phi \in \text{SC}[0, \varpi(\frac{1}{w(1)})]$, $\Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^0$.

Charact. of norm continuity of $\mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|}}$ on L_Φ & $L_{\Phi, w}$ spaces: proof

Components of the proof:

- 1) Characterisations of the geometry of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p \in [1, \infty]})$, $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w})$, $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^\Delta)$.
- 2) Theorems on transfer of geometric properties between r.i.B.s. and n.r.i.B.s.
- 3) Theorem: [Vlasov'81](#)
For any Banach space $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$,
 $\mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|}^X}$ is norm-to-norm continuous $\iff (X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC} \cap \mathbf{RRS}$.

Note:

The above characterisation of the norm-to-norm continuity of $\mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|}}$ is new also in the commutative case, beyond the original range of the Wáng–Chén theorem.

The Vaĭnberg–Kachurovskĭĭ–Brègman information:

- Let $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{R}$, let $\Psi : X \rightarrow]-\infty, \infty]$ be convex, lower semicontinuous, Gateaux differentiable on $\text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi)) \neq \emptyset$, $\text{efd}(\Psi) := \{x \in X : \Psi(x) \neq \infty\}$.
 - **Vaĭnberg–Kachurovskĭĭ–Brègman information** $:= D_\Psi(y, x) := \begin{cases} \Psi(y) - \Psi(x) - \llbracket y - x, \mathfrak{D}^G \Psi(x) \rrbracket_{X \times X^*} & : (y, x) \in X \times \text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi)) \\ \infty & : y \in X, x \notin \text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi)). \end{cases}$
- Vaĭnberg'65, Kachurovskĭĭ'66, Brègman'66, Al'ber–Butnariu'97
- $D_\Psi(x, y) \geq 0 \ \forall x, y \in X$.
 - $(D_\Psi(x, y) = 0 \text{ iff } x = y) \iff \Psi$ is strictly convex. Butnariu–lusem'00

Cosine theorem:

Pythagorean theorem: $c^2 = a^2 + b^2$ is a special case of the cosine theorem:

- Eúkleidos'~–300

$$\overline{AB}^2 = \overline{AC}^2 + \overline{CB}^2 + 2(\overline{AC})(\overline{CD}),$$

- Al Kāshĭr'1427

$$\overline{AB}^2 = \overline{AC}^2 + \overline{CB}^2 - 2(\overline{AC})(\overline{CB}) \cos \gamma.$$

- In cartesian (\mathbb{R}^n) and Hilbert (\mathcal{H}) spaces:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\vec{AB}\|^2 &= \|\vec{AC}\|^2 + \|\vec{CB}\|^2 - 2 \langle \vec{AC}, \vec{CB} \rangle, \\ \|z - x\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 &= \|z - y\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 + \|y - x\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 - 2 \langle z - y, x - y \rangle_{\mathcal{H}}. \end{aligned}$$

- $\Psi(x) = \frac{1}{2} \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2 \Rightarrow D_\Psi(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} \|x - y\|_{\mathcal{H}}^2$.
 - D_Ψ provides a direct generalisation of the cosine theorem: Chen–Teboulle'93
- $$D_\Psi(z, x) = D_\Psi(z, y) + D_\Psi(y, x) - \llbracket z - y, \mathfrak{D}^G \Psi(x) - \mathfrak{D}^G \Psi(y) \rrbracket_{X \times X^*}.$$
- What is the corresponding generalisation of the pythagorean theorem?

The Vaĭnberg–Kachurovskĭĭ–Brègman projection (I):

- Let $\emptyset \neq C \subseteq X$.
 - left VKB projection := $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_C^{D_\Psi}(x) := \arg \inf_{z \in C} \{D_\Psi(z, x)\}$. Brègman'66
 - right VKB projection := $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_C^{D_\Psi}(x) := \arg \inf_{z \in C} \{D_\Psi(x, z)\}$.
Amari–Nagaoka'93, Bauschke–Noll'02
 - if $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ is a Hilbert space, then $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_C^{D_\Psi} = \mathfrak{P}_C^{d_{\|\cdot\|_X}} = \overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_C^{D_\Psi}$.
-
- $X^* \ni y \mapsto \Psi^F(y) := \sup_{x \in X} \{\langle x, y \rangle_{X \times X^*} - \Psi(x)\}$. Mandelbrojt'39, Fenchel'49, Moreau'62
 - $\Psi : X \rightarrow]-\infty, \infty]$ is Euler–Legendre :=
 Ψ is convex, lower semicontinuous, Gateaux differentiable on $\text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi)) \neq \emptyset$,
 Ψ^F is Gateaux differentiable on $\text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi^F)) \neq \emptyset$,
 $\partial \Psi(x) \neq \emptyset$ iff $x \in \text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi)) \forall x \in \text{efd}(\Psi)$,
 $\partial \Psi^F(x) \neq \emptyset$ iff $x \in \text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi^F)) \forall x \in \text{efd}(\Psi^F)$.
 Bauschke–Borwein–Combettes'01; \mathbb{R}^n : Rockafellar'63

The Vaĭnberg–Kachurovskĭĭ–Brègman projection (II):

- Theorem: Brègman'66, Bauschke–Borwein–Combettes'03
 if Ψ is Euler–Legendre, $\emptyset \neq Q \subseteq \text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi))$ is convex and closed, then:
 - $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_Q^{D_\Psi}$ is a function on $\text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi))$;
 - $D_\Psi(y, x) \geq D_\Psi(y, z) + D_\Psi(z, x) \forall (y, x) \in Q \times \text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi))$
 $\iff z = \overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_Q^{D_\Psi}(x)$;
 - ' \geq ' turns into '=' if Q is affine.
- Theorem: Martín-Marquez–Reich–Sabach'12, RPK'21
 Ψ is Euler–Legendre, $\emptyset \neq K \subseteq \text{int}(\text{efd}(\Psi))$, $\mathfrak{D}^G \Psi(K)$ is convex and closed \implies
 - $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_\Psi}$ is a function on X ;
 - $D_\Psi(x, y) \geq D_\Psi(x, z) + D_\Psi(z, y) \forall (x, y) \in X \times K \iff z = \overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_\Psi}(x)$;
 - ' \geq ' turns into '=' if $\mathfrak{D}^G \Psi(K)$ is affine.

Pythagoreanity, and continuity, of $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{\Psi_\varphi}$ and $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{\Psi_\varphi}$ (I):

- **Theorem:** RPK'21

Let $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ be any Banach space.

Then $\Psi_\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is Euler–Legendre iff $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{SC} \cap \mathbf{G}$.

- **Theorem:** RPK'21–23, with an exception of 3).(i) by Schuster–Kaltenbach–Hofmann–Kazimierski'12

1) For any gauge φ , $\emptyset \neq K \subseteq X$, if $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC} \cap \mathbf{G}$, then:

- (i) if K is convex and closed, then $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$ is a function on X , and $\forall x \in X \forall z \in K$
 $z = \overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}(x) \iff D_{\Psi_\varphi}(y, z) + D_{\Psi_\varphi}(z, x) \leq D_{\Psi_\varphi}(y, x) \forall y \in K;$
- (ii) if $\mathfrak{D}^G \Psi_\varphi(K)$ is convex and closed, then $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$ is a function on X , and $\forall x \in X \forall z \in K$
 $z = \overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}(x) \iff D_{\Psi_\varphi}(x, z) + D_{\Psi_\varphi}(z, y) \leq D_{\Psi_\varphi}(x, y) \forall y \in K.$

2) For any gauge φ , $\emptyset \neq K \subseteq X$, if $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC} \cap \mathbf{F} \cap \mathbf{RRS}$, then:

- (i) if K is convex and closed, then $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$ is norm-to-norm continuous on X ;
- (ii) if $\mathfrak{D}^G \Psi_\varphi(K)$ is convex and closed, then $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$ is norm-to-norm continuous on X .

Pythagoreanity, and continuity, of $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{\Psi_\varphi}$ and $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{\Psi_\varphi}$ (II):

3) If $\beta \in]0, 1[$, $r \in]1, 2]$, $\varphi_{1,\beta}(t) := t^{1/\beta-1}$, $\emptyset \neq K \subseteq X$, then:

- (i) if $\beta \in]0, \frac{1}{2}]$, $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UC}_{1/\beta} \cap \mathbf{UF}$, K is convex and closed, then $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_{\varphi_{1,\beta}}}}$ is uniformly continuous on bounded subsets of X ;
- (ii) if $\beta \in]0, \frac{1}{2}]$, $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UC}_{1/\beta} \cap \mathbf{UF}_r$, K is convex, closed, and bounded, then $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_{\varphi_{1,\beta}}}}$ is $\beta(r-1)$ -Lipschitz–Hölder continuous on bounded subsets of X ;
- (iii) if $\beta \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1[$, $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UC} \cap \mathbf{UF}_{1/\beta}$, $\mathfrak{D}^G \Psi_{\varphi_{1,\beta}}$ is convex and closed, then $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_{\varphi_{1,\beta}}}}$ is uniformly continuous on bounded subsets of X ;
- (iv) if $\beta \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1[$, $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \in \mathbf{UC}_{r/(r-1)} \cap \mathbf{UF}_{1/\beta}$, $\mathfrak{D}^G \Psi_{\varphi_{1,\beta}}(K)$ is convex, closed, and bounded, then $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_{\varphi_{1,\beta}}}}$ is $\frac{(1-\beta)^2}{\beta}(r-1)^2$ -Lipschitz–Hölder continuous on bounded and convex subsets of X .

Pythagoreanity & continuity of $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{\Psi_\varphi}$ & $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{\Psi_\varphi}$ on $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p})$ (I):

Theorem: RPK'21-'23

Let $\text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) \in \{l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, l_1, l_\infty\}$ and $p \in [1, \infty]$, let φ be a gauge,
 let $\emptyset \neq K \subseteq L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau)$ be convex and closed in the topology of $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p}$,
 let $\emptyset \neq C \subseteq L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau)$, let $\mathfrak{D}^G \Psi_\varphi(C)$ be convex and closed in the topology of
 $\|\cdot\|_{\Phi^Y, p/(p-1)}$. Then:

(i) if

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap \text{SC}([0, \varpi_\Phi(1)]), \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^0 \cap \text{SC}([0, (\Phi^Y)^\vee(\frac{1}{2})]), \\ \exists u > 0 \Phi^Y(u) = 1, \exists u > 0 \Phi^Y(\Phi'_+(u)) \geq \frac{1}{2} & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = 1 \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap \text{SC}([0, \Phi^{-1}(\frac{1}{2})]), \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^0 \cap \text{SC}([0, \varpi_{\Phi^Y}(1)]), \\ \exists u > 0 \Phi((\Phi^Y)'_+(u)) \geq \frac{1}{2} & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p = \infty \\ \Phi \in \Delta_2^0 \cap C^1([0, \varpi_{\Phi, p}(1)]), \\ \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^0 \cap C^1([0, \varpi_{\Phi^Y, p/(p-1)}(1)]) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p \in]1, \infty[\\ \Phi, \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2^\infty \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_1, p \in [1, \infty] \\ \Phi, \Phi^Y \in \Delta_2 \cap \text{SC}(\mathbb{R}) & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty, p \in [1, \infty] \end{array} \right.$$

then:

- 1) $D_{\Psi_\varphi}(x, y) = 0 \iff x = y \forall x, y \in L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau)$;
- 2) $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$ and $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_C^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$ are functions on $L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau)$;
- 3) D_{Ψ_φ} satisfies left and right generalised pythagorean theorem on $L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau)$;

Pythagoreanity & continuity of $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{\Psi_\varphi}$ & $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{\Psi_\varphi}$ on $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p})$ (II):

(ii) under the same conditions as above, with an additional assumption of

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \lim_{u \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Phi(u)}{u} = \infty & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}, p \in]1, \infty[\\ \Phi \in \Delta_2 \cap \text{UC}, \Phi^Y \in \text{UC} & : \text{type}(\mathcal{N}, \tau) = l_\infty, p \in]1, \infty[\end{array} \right.$$

$\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$ and $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_C^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$ are norm-to-norm continuous on $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, p})$;

(iii) if $p = \infty$, $\varphi(t) = \varphi_{1, \gamma}(t) := t^{1/\gamma-1}$ with $\gamma \in]0, 1[$,

and one of the following (inequivalent) conditions holds:

- a) $1 < r \leq 2 \leq s < \infty$, Φ is finite and nondegenerate, $\Phi(1) = 1$,
 $u \mapsto \Phi(u^{1/r})$ is convex, $u \mapsto \Phi(u^{1/s})$ is concave;
- b) Φ is an inverse of $u \mapsto (\Phi_0^{-1}(u))^{1-2\beta} u^\beta$, $\beta \in]0, \frac{1}{2}[$, $\Phi_0 \in \mathbb{N}$, $s := \frac{1}{\beta}$,
 $r := \frac{1}{1-\beta}$;

then:

Pythagoreanity & continuity of $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{\Psi_\varphi}$ & $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{\Psi_\varphi}$ on $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho})$ (III):

- 1) $\mathfrak{P}_K^{d\|\cdot\|_\Phi}$ is uniformly continuous on bounded subsets of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_\Phi)$, and $\frac{r}{s}$ -Lipschitz–Hölder continuous on bounded neighbourhoods of K ;
- 2) $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi 1, 1/s}}$ is uniformly continuous on bounded subsets of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_\Phi)$;
- 3) $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_C^{D_{\Psi_\varphi 1, 1/r}}$ is uniformly continuous on bounded subsets of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_\Phi)$;
- 4) if K bounded, then $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi 1, 1/s}}$ is $\frac{1}{s}(r-1)$ -Lipschitz–Hölder continuous on bounded subsets of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_\Phi)$;
- 5) if $\mathfrak{D}^G \Psi_{\varphi 1, 1/r}(C)$ is bounded, then $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_C^{D_{\Psi_\varphi 1, 1/r}}$ is $\frac{(r-1)^2}{r(s-1)} \min\{\frac{1}{r-1}, \frac{1}{s-1}\}$ -Lipschitz–Hölder continuous on bounded and convex subsets of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_\Phi)$.

Proof:

Follows from the results presented earlier, except of (iii).1), that uses additionally a theorem of [Adzhiev'09](#).

Summary of results

- 1) Banach space duality for $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_\Phi)$, $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_\Phi^O)$, as well as $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho})$, and establishing their relationship with Muratov's variants.
- 2) Characterisation of geometric properties of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho})$, $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w})$, $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^\Delta)$ using geometry transfer theorems for r.i.B.s.
- 3) Characterisation of norm-to-norm continuity of metric projection $\mathfrak{P}_C^{d\|\cdot\|}$ on $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho})$, $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w})$, $(L_{\Phi, w}(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, w}^\Delta)$ by $\mathbf{R} \cap \mathbf{SC}$. (This result is new also in the commutative cases, beyond the range of the Wáng–Chén theorem.)
- 4) Characterisation of Euler–Legendre Ψ_φ on any Banach space $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ by $\mathbf{SC} \cap \mathbf{G}$.
- 5) Sufficient conditions for left and right pythagorean theorems for D_{Ψ_φ} , and for {norm-to-norm, uniform, Lipschitz–Hölder} continuity of $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$ and $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$, on $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ in terms of geometric properties of $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$.
- 6) Sufficient conditions for left and right pythagorean theorems for D_{Ψ_φ} , and for {norm-to-norm, uniform, Lipschitz–Hölder} continuity of $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$ and $\overrightarrow{\mathfrak{P}}_K^{D_{\Psi_\varphi}}$, on $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{N}, \tau), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho})$ in terms of the properties of Φ . (This result is new also in the commutative case.)

Open problems (which would improve generality of the above results):

- Missing (or limited to $\Phi \in \mathbf{N}$) characterisations of a few geometric properties of $(L_\Phi(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \|\cdot\|_{\Phi, \rho})$ in some particular cases of $(\text{type}(\mathcal{X}, \mu), \rho)$.
- Missing equivalences in n.r.i.B.s. transfer of \mathbf{R} for type $I_\infty^{\text{s.f.}}$, and of \mathbf{UC}_r for any type.

On the value of the fifth maximal projection constant

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CT

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Let X be a Banach space over \mathbb{K} , where $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{C}$. Let $Y \subset X$ be a subspace. By $\mathcal{P}(X, Y)$ denote the set of all linear and continuous projections from X onto Y , recalling that an operator $P: X \rightarrow Y$ is called a *projection* onto Y if $P|_Y = Id_Y$. We define the *relative projection constant* of a subspace Y of a space X by

$$\lambda(Y, X) := \inf\{\|P\| : P \in \mathcal{P}(X, Y)\}.$$

Now we can define the *absolute projection constant* of Y by

$$\lambda(Y) := \sup\{\lambda(Y, X) : Y \subset X\}.$$

The ultimate goal of researchers in this area is to determine the exact value of *maximal absolute projection constant*, which is defined by

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m) := \sup\{\lambda(Y) : \dim(Y) = m\}.$$

In 1960, B.Grünbaum conjectured that $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(2) = \frac{4}{3}$ (see [6]), and only in 2010, B. Chalmers and G. Lewicki proved it (see [2]) and that was the only known nontrivial case. Recently, we have provided exact values of $\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m)$ in cases where the maximal equiangular tight frame exists in \mathbb{K}^m . There are numerous examples of complex maximal ETFs, for example, for $m \in \{1, \dots, 17, 19, 24, 28, 35, 48\}$ (see, e.g., [5]). In fact, it is conjectured that there is a complex maximal ETF in every dimension (Zauner's conjecture [7]). Unlike in the complex case, real maximal ETFs seem to be rare objects. The only known cases are for m equal to 2, 3, 7 and 23. A lot of the community believes that these are all real cases where maximal ETFs exist. In other cases, the determination of the constant $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(m)$ seems to be difficult. Numerical experiments conducted by B. L. Chalmers (and unfortunately unpublished) suggest that $\lambda(5) \approx 2.06919$. In this talk, relying on a new construction of certain mutually unbiased equiangular tight frames, we will provide the lower bound for $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(5)$ and present some arguments that it may be its true value.

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ON THE VALUE OF THE FIFTH MAXIMAL PROJECTION CONSTANT

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July 8, 2024

BASIC DEFINITIONS

WHY PROJECTION CONSTANTS ARE CALLED PROJECTION CONSTANTS

Let X be a Banach space over \mathbb{K} (where $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{C}$) and let $Y \subset X$ be a finite-dimensional subspace. Let $\mathcal{P}(X, Y)$ denote the set of all linear and continuous projections from X onto Y , recalling that an operator $P: X \rightarrow Y$ is called a **projection** onto Y if $P|_Y = \text{Id}_Y$.

We define the **relative projection constant** of Y by

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(Y, X) := \inf\{\|P\| : P \in \mathcal{P}(X, Y)\}$$

and the **absolute projection constant** of Y by

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(Y) := \sup\{\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(Y, X) : Y \subset X\}, \quad (1)$$

and finally the **maximal absolute projection constant**, by

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m) := \sup\{\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(Y) : \dim(Y) = m\}.$$

Theorem 1 (Wojtaszczyk, 1991,Chalmers and Lewicki, 2009,Foucart and Skrzypek, 2017)

For integer m

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m) = \sup\{\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, n) \mid n \geq m\},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, n) &= \max \left\{ \sum_{i,j=1}^n t_i t_j |U^* U|_{ij} : t \in \mathbb{R}^n, \|t\|_2 = 1, U \in \mathbb{K}^{m \times n}, UU^* = I_m \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^\downarrow(TAT) : T = \text{diag}(t), t \in \mathbb{R}^n, \|t\|_2 = 1, A \in \mathcal{A}_n \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2 (Kadec-Snohar Inequality)

For any $m \geq 1$

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m) \leq \sqrt{m}.$$

2 / 15

Theorem 1 (Wojtaszczyk, 1991,Chalmers and Lewicki, 2009,Foucart and Skrzypek, 2017)

For integer m

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m) = \sup\{\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, n) \mid n \geq m\},$$

where

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, n) = \max \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^\downarrow(TAT) : T = \text{diag}(t), t \in \mathbb{R}^n, \|t\|_2 = 1, A \in \mathcal{A}_n \right\}.$$

Theorem 3 (Basso, 2019,Deregowska and B.L., 2023)

For integer m

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m) = \sup\{\mu_{\mathbb{K}}(m, n) \mid n \geq m\},$$

where

$$\mu_{\mathbb{K}}(m, n) := \max \left\{ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i,j=1}^n |U^* U|_{ij} : U \in \mathbb{K}^{m \times n}, UU^* = I_m \right\} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^m \lambda_k^\downarrow(A) : A \in \mathcal{A}_n \right\}.$$

$\lambda_1^\downarrow(M) \geq \lambda_2^\downarrow(M) \geq \dots \geq \lambda_n^\downarrow(M)$ eigenvalues of a self-adjoint matrix $M \in \mathbb{K}^{n \times n}$.

$\mathcal{A}_n = \{A \in \mathbb{K}^{n \times n} : A_{ii} = 1, |A_{ij}| = 1\}$

3 / 15

EQUIANGULAR TIGHT FRAMES

A system of unit (i.e., l_2 -normalized) vectors (u_1, \dots, u_n) in \mathbb{K}^m is called **equiangular** if there is a constant $c \geq 0$ such that

$$|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle| = c \quad \text{for all } i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, i \neq j.$$

It is called a **tight frame** if

$$UU^* = \frac{n}{m} I_m,$$

where U is the matrix with columns u_1, \dots, u_n .

The system (u_1, \dots, u_n) of unit vectors is called an **equiangular tight frame (ETF)** if it is both an equiangular and a tight frame. Then

$$|\langle v_i, v_j \rangle| = \sqrt{\frac{n-m}{m(n-1)}} \quad \text{for all } i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, i \neq j.$$

and the cardinality n cannot exceed $\frac{m(m+1)}{2}$ in the real case and m^2 in the complex case. An ETF that realizes this upper bound is called **the maximal ETF**.

4 / 15

EQUIANGULAR TIGHT FRAMES

Theorem 4 (König et al., 1983, Foucart and Skrzypek, 2017)

For integers $N \geq m$, the maximal relative projection constant $\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N)$ is upper bounded by

$$\delta_{m,N} := \frac{m}{N} \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{(N-1)(N-m)}{m}} \right).$$

Moreover, the following properties are equivalent:

- i) There is an equiangular tight frame consisting of N vectors in \mathbb{K}^m ,
- ii) $\mu_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) = \frac{m}{N} \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{(N-1)(N-m)}{m}} \right)$,
- iii) $\lambda_{\mathbb{K}}(m, N) = \frac{m}{N} \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{(N-1)(N-m)}{m}} \right)$.

5 / 15

EQUIANGULAR TIGHT FRAMES

Theorem 5 (König and Tomczak-Jaegermann, 1994, Deregowska and B.L., 2023)

Let $m > 1$ then

$$i) \lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(m) \leq \delta_{m, \frac{m(m+1)}{2}} = \frac{2}{m+1} \left(1 + \frac{m-1}{2} \sqrt{m+2}\right)$$

$$ii) \lambda_{\mathbb{C}}(m) \leq \delta_{m, m^2} = \frac{1}{m} \left(1 + (m-1) \sqrt{m+1}\right).$$

Furthermore, the inequality becomes an equality if there exists a maximal ETF in \mathbb{K}^m .

Theorem 6 (The real case)

- ▶ $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(2) = \frac{4}{3}$. (the Grünbaum conjecture, Chalmers and Lewicki, 2010, Basso, 2019)
- ▶ $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(3) = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$;
- ▶ $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(7) = \frac{5}{2}$;
- ▶ $\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(23) = \frac{14}{3}$.

Conjecture 1 (Zauner's conjecture, Zauner, 1999)

For every $m \geq 1$

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{C}}(m) = \frac{1}{m} \left(1 + (m-1) \sqrt{m+1}\right).$$

6 / 15

MUTUALLY UNBIASED TIGHT FRAMES

Definition 1 (Fickus and Mayo, 2020, Deregowska et al., 2022)

Two equiangular tight frames (v_1, \dots, v_k) and (w_1, \dots, w_l) for \mathbb{R}^m are mutually unbiased if there exists $c \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$|\langle v_i, w_j \rangle| = c \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, k\} \text{ and } j \in \{1, \dots, l\}.$$

Lemma 1

The constant c appearing in the definition of mutually unbiased equiangular tight frames for \mathbb{R}^n necessarily satisfies

$$c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{m}}.$$

Theorem 7 (Deregowska et al., 2022)

If mutually unbiased equiangular tight frames (v_1, \dots, v_k) and (w_1, \dots, w_l) for \mathbb{R}^m exist, then the maximal relative projection constant $\lambda(m, k+l)$ is bounded below as

$$\lambda(m, k+l) \geq \frac{m - \delta_{m,k} \delta_{m,l}}{2\sqrt{m} - \delta_{m,k} - \delta_{m,l}}.$$

7 / 15

MUTUALLY UNBIASED TIGHT FRAMES

Theorem 8

For any integer $s \geq 2$, there are mutually unbiased equiangular tight frames (v_1, \dots, v_k) and (w_1, \dots, w_l) for \mathbb{R}^m , where

$$k = 2^{s-1}(2^s - 1), \quad l = 2^{s-1}(2^s + 1), \quad m = \frac{2^{2s} - 1}{3}.$$

Theorem 9 (and Conjecture)

The fifth absolute projection constant satisfies

$$\lambda(5) \geq \lambda(5, 16) \geq \frac{5}{59}(11 + 6\sqrt{5}) \approx 2.06919,$$

and it is expected that the latter is indeed the true value of $\lambda(5)$.

8 / 15

SPHERICAL (t, t) -DESIGNS

Suppose that $U = (u_j)_{j=1}^N$ are unit vectors in \mathbb{K}^m , and $(w_j)_{j=1}^N \in \mathbb{R}^N$ satisfy $w_j \geq 0$ and $\sum_{j=1}^N w_j = 1$. Then (U, w) is called a **weighted (spherical) (t, t) -design** if

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^N w_i w_j |\langle u_i, u_j \rangle|^{2t} = c_t(m, \mathbb{K}),$$

where

$$c_t(m, \mathbb{R}) = \frac{1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdots (2t-1)}{m(m+2) \cdots (m+2(t-1))}, \quad c_t(m, \mathbb{C}) = \frac{1}{\binom{m+t-1}{t}}$$

Theorem 10 (Waldron, 2017)

Let $U = (u_j)_{j=1}^N$ be a sequence of unit vectors in \mathbb{K}^m , and $(w_j)_{j=1}^N$ be nonnegative weights, i.e., $w_j \geq 0$, $\sum_{j=1}^N w_j = 1$. Then

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^N w_i w_j |\langle u_i, u_j \rangle|^{2t} \geq c_t(m, \mathbb{K}), \quad (2)$$

with equality if and only if (U, w) is a weighted (t, t) -design

9 / 15

SPHERICAL (t, t) -DESIGNS

A KEY STEP IN THE PROOF OF THEOREM 4

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{i,j=1}^N t_i t_j \frac{(|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle| - \varphi \|u_i\| \|u_j\|)^2}{\|u_i\| \|u_j\|} &= \sum_{i,j=1}^N t_i t_j \frac{(|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle|^2 - \varphi^2 \|u_i\|^2 \|u_j\|^2)^2}{\|u_i\| \|u_j\| (|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle| + \varphi \|u_i\| \|u_j\|)^2} \\
 &\geq \sum_{i,j=1}^N t_i t_j \frac{(|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle|^2 - \varphi^2 \|u_i\|^2 \|u_j\|^2)^2}{(1 + \varphi)^2 \|u_i\|^3 \|u_j\|^3} = \frac{1}{(1 + \varphi)^2} \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^N \left\langle \frac{u_i}{\|u_i\|}, \frac{u_j}{\|u_j\|} \right\rangle \right)^4 \|t_i u_i\| \|t_j u_j\| \\
 &\quad - 2\varphi^2 \sum_{i,j=1}^N t_i t_j \frac{|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle|^2}{\|u_i\| \|u_j\|} + \varphi^4 \sum_{i,j=1}^N t_i t_j \|u_i\| \|u_j\| \geq \frac{1}{(1 + \varphi)^2} \left(c_2(m, \mathbb{K}) \left(\sum_{i=1}^N t_i \|u_i\| \right)^2 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - 2\varphi^2 \sum_{i,j=1}^N t_i t_j \frac{|\langle u_i, u_j \rangle|^2}{\|u_i\| \|u_j\|} + \varphi^4 \left(\sum_{i=1}^N t_i \|u_i\| \right)^2 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

10 / 15

SPHERICAL (t, t) -DESIGNS

Theorem 11

Every maximal ETF is a $(2, 2)$ -design.

Theorem 12 (Waldron, 2018)

Let n be a number of vectors in a weighted spherical (t, t) -design then

$$n \geq \binom{m-1+t}{t}.$$

In the real case, maximal ETFs consist of $\frac{m(m+1)}{2}$ vectors. Hence, they are $(2, 2)$ -design with the smallest possible number of vectors.

Theorem 13 (Waldron, 2018)

Let n be a number of vectors in a real weighted spherical (t, t) -design then

$$n \leq \binom{m-1+2t}{2t}.$$

11 / 15

SPHERICAL (t, t) -DESIGNS

WITH A MINIMAL NUMBER OF VECTORS

Table 1

The minimum numbers n_w and n_e of vectors in a weighted and in a equal-norm spherical (t, t) -design for \mathbb{R}^d (spherical half-design of order $2t$) as calculated numerically.

t	d	n_w	n_e	Comments	
1	d	d	d	orthonormal bases in \mathbb{R}^d	(Example 1.3)
t	2	$t+1$	$t+1$	equally spaced lines in \mathbb{R}^2	(Example 3.2)
2	3	6	6	equiangular lines in \mathbb{R}^3	(Example 3.3)
2	4	11	12	no structure	§5, ST 28, Table 4
2	5	16	20	Example 3.5	no structure
2	6	22	24	group structure	work in progress
2	7	28	28	equiangular lines in \mathbb{R}^7	(Example 3.3)
2	8	45	>45	no structure	
3	3	11	16	no structure	possible group structure
3	4	23	>23	group structure	
3	5	41	>41	group structure	
4	3	16	25	Example 3.6	no structure
4	4	43	>43	work in progress	
5	3	24	35	no structure	no structure
Other known real (t, t) -designs with a small number of vectors					
2	6		27	§5, ST 35, Table 5	
Other known optimal real (t, t) -designs					
2	23		276	equiangular lines in \mathbb{R}^{23}	(Example 3.3)
3	8		120	§5, ST 37, Table 5	(due to [21])
3	23		2300	tight spherical design	
5	4	60	60	§5, ST 30, Table 4	(Example 3.4)
5	24		98280	tight spherical design	
t	d		$\binom{d-1+t}{t}$	tight spherical $(2t+1)$ -designs	

Hughes and Waldron, 2021

12 / 15

SPHERICAL (t, t) -DESIGNS

WITH A MINIMAL NUMBER OF VECTORS

Conjecture 2

Let $U \in \mathbb{R}^m$ be a weighted $(2, 2)$ -design with a minimal number of vectors. If $\text{sgn}(U^T U) \in \mathcal{A}_n$, then $\lambda_m(\text{sgn}(U^T U)) = \lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(m, n) = \lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(m)$.

Conjecture 3

Let m be an integer, then there exists $n \in \left[\binom{m+1}{2} : \binom{m+3}{4} \right]$ such that

$$\lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(m, n) = \lambda_{\mathbb{R}}(m).$$

13 / 15

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14 / 15

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15 / 15

Seminormwise approximation by matrix means of Fourier series

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CT

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Let $X = L^p$ or $X = C$, where L^p ($1 \leq p \leq \infty$) [C] be the class of all 2π -periodic real-valued functions, integrable in the Lebesgue sense with p -th power when $p \geq 1$ and essentially bounded when $p = \infty$ [continuous] over $Q = [-\pi, \pi]$ with the usual norm.

For a seminorm P , we define the following seminormed space:

$$(X, P) = \{f \in X : P(f) < \infty\},$$

with the property that $f(\cdot + h) \in (X, P)$ for any $h \in \mathbb{R}$ and the following conditions:

1. for any $h \in \mathbb{R}$

$$P(f(\cdot + h)) = P(f(\cdot)),$$

2. if $|f(x)| \leq |g(x)|$ for every $x \in [-\pi, \pi]$, then

$$P(f) \leq P(g).$$

Consider the trigonometric Fourier series Sf with the partial sums $S_k f$ and its transformation

$$T_{n,A}f(x) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_{n,k} S_k f(x)$$

by a matrix $A := (a_{n,k})_{0 \leq n, k < \infty} = (a_{n,k})$ of regular summability method.

The main aim of this paper is to estimate the seminormwise deviation: $P(T_{n,A}f - f)$ depending on the following r, s -th differences (higher forward differences):

$$A_{\mu,\nu}^{r,s}(b.) = A_{\mu,\nu}^{r,s}\left(\frac{a_{n,\cdot}}{b.}\right) = \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} b_k \left| \Delta_r^s \left(\frac{a_{n,k}}{b_k} \right) \right|,$$

where $\Delta_r^0(a_{n,k}) = a_{n,k}$, $\Delta_r^1(a_{n,k}) = a_{n,k} - a_{n,k+r}$ and $\Delta_r^s(a_{n,k}) = \Delta_r^1(\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n,k}))$,

for $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\mu, \nu, k, n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, with positive nondecreasing sequence (b_k) .

As a measure of the such deviation we will use the classical modulus of continuity of f in the spaces (X, P) defined by the formula

$$\omega f(\delta)_P = \sup_{0 \leq t \leq \delta} P(\varphi_x(t)),$$

where

$$\varphi_x(t) = f(x+t) + f(x-t) - 2f(x).$$

P. Chandra in [1] and [2] estimated the deviation $T_{n,A}^{text} f - f$ in sup-norm, when $(a_{n,k})$ is a monotonic sequences with respect to k . Many years later, L. Leindler [6] replaced the monotonic sequences with rest bounded variation sequences. More general results were obtained by B. Wei and D. Yu in [7] and Xh. Z. Krasniqi in [3], [4] and [5].

In our theorems and corollaries we will formulate the very general conditions for the method of summability, with application of r -th differences of higher orders, and for the moduli of continuity obtaining the best degrees of approximation.

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Seminormwise approximation by matrix means of Fourier series under some conditions with r -th differences of higher orders

Włodzimierz Lenski*, Bogdan Szal

Abstract

In this paper several results pertaining to the approximation of seminormed functions by general means of partial sums of their Fourier series under the conditions on the entries of considered matrices are formulated in terms of r -th differences of higher orders. As a measure of approximation the suitable modulus of continuity of considered function is used. Some earlier results in generalized and improved forms are presented as corollary.

Key words: Rate of approximation, approximation in seminorm,

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification: 42A24

1 Introduction

Let $X = L^p$ or $X = C$, where L^p ($1 \leq p \leq \infty$) [C] be the class of all 2π -periodic real-valued functions, integrable in the Lebesgue sense with p -th power when $p \geq 1$ and essentially bounded when $p = \infty$ [continuous] over $Q = [-\pi, \pi]$ with the norm

$$\|f\|_{L^p} : = \|f(\cdot)\|_{L^p} = \begin{cases} \left(\int_Q |f(t)|^p dt \right)^{1/p} & \text{when } 1 \leq p < \infty, \\ \operatorname{ess\,sup}_{t \in Q} |f(t)| & \text{when } p = \infty, \end{cases}$$
$$\|f\|_C : = \|f(\cdot)\|_C = \sup_{t \in Q} |f(t)|.$$

For a seminorm P , we define the following seminormed space:

$$(X, P) = \{f \in X : P(f) < \infty\},$$

with the property that $f(\cdot + h) \in (X, P)$ for any $h \in \mathbb{R}$.

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In this paper we will consider the seminorms P satisfying, for all $f, g \in (X, P)$, the following conditions:

1. for any $h \in \mathbb{R}$

$$P(f(\cdot + h)) = P(f(\cdot)), \quad (1)$$
2. if $|f(x)| \leq |g(x)|$ for every $x \in [-\pi, \pi]$, then
$$P(f) \leq P(g). \quad (2)$$

Consider the trigonometric Fourier series

$$Sf(x) := \frac{a_0(f)}{2} + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} (a_{\nu}(f) \cos \nu x + b_{\nu}(f) \sin \nu x)$$

with the partial sums $S_k f$.

If $A := (a_{n,k})_{0 \leq n, k < \infty} = (a_{n,k})$ is an infinite matrix of real numbers such that

$$a_{n,k} \geq 0 \text{ when } k, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_{n,k} = 0 \text{ for every } k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

and

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_{n,k} = 1 \text{ for every } n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \text{ whence } \lim_{k \rightarrow 0} a_{n,k} = 0$$

or $A_0 := (a_{n,k}^{\circ})_{0 \leq k \leq n < \infty} = (a_{n,k}^{\circ})$, where

$$a_{n,k}^{\circ} \geq 0 \text{ when } k \leq n \text{ and } a_{n,k}^{\circ} = 0 \text{ when } k > n,$$

then

$$T_{n,A} f(x) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_{n,k} S_k f(x) \text{ or } T_{n,A_0} f(x) := \sum_{k=0}^n a_{n,k}^{\circ} S_k f(x) \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, \dots).$$

The main aim of this paper is to estimate the seminormwise deviation: $P(T_{n,A} f - f)$ depending on the following r, s -th differences (higher r -th order, forward differences with the spacing r):

$$A_{\mu,\nu}^{r,s}(b) = A_{\mu,\nu}^{r,s} \left(\frac{a_{n,\cdot}}{b} \right) = \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} \left| b_k \Delta_r^s \left(\frac{a_{n,k}}{b_k} \right) \right|, \quad A_{\mu,\nu}^{r,s} = A_{\mu,\nu}^{r,s}(1)$$

and $(b_k) \subset \mathbb{R}_+$ increases, where $\Delta_r^0(a_{n,k}) = a_{n,k}$, $\Delta_r^1(a_{n,k}) = a_{n,k} - a_{n,k+r}$
and $\Delta_r^s(a_{n,k}) = \Delta_r^1(\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n,k}))$,

for $m, r, s \in \mathbb{N}$. It is easily to see that if $r_1, r_2 \in \mathbb{N}$, $r_1 \mid r_2$, then there exists $\rho \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $r_2 = \rho r_1$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} A_{\mu, \nu}^{r_2, s}(b) &= \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} \left| b_k \Delta_{r_2}^s \left(\frac{a_{n, k}}{b_k} \right) \right| = \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} \left| b_k \sum_{i=0}^{\rho-1} \Delta_{r_1}^s \left(\frac{a_{n, k+ir_1}}{b_{k+ir_1}} \right) \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} b_k \sum_{i=0}^{\rho-1} \left| \Delta_{r_1}^s \left(\frac{a_{n, k+ir_1}}{b_{k+ir_1}} \right) \right| \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\rho-1} \sum_{k=\mu+ir_1}^{\nu+ir_1} b_{k-ir_1} \left| \Delta_{r_1}^s \left(\frac{a_{n, k}}{b_k} \right) \right| \leq \rho \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} \left| b_k \Delta_{r_1}^s \left(\frac{a_{n, k}}{b_k} \right) \right| = \rho A_{\mu, \nu}^{r_1, s}(b) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} A_{\mu, \nu}^{r, s} &= \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^s(a_{n, k})| = \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r(\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k}))| \\ &\leq \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k})| + \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k+r})| \\ &= \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k})| + \sum_{k=\mu+r}^{\nu+r} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k})| \\ &\leq 2 \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k})| = 2A_{\mu, \nu}^{r, s-1} \end{aligned}$$

as well as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^s(a_{n, k})| &= \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r(\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k}))| \\ &\geq \left| \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k})| - \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k+r})| \right| \\ &= \left| \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k})| - \sum_{k=\mu+r}^{\nu+r} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k})| \right| \\ &= \left| \sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n, k})| \right|, \end{aligned}$$

in case $a_{n, k} = 0$ for $k > \nu$ or when $\nu = \infty$

As a measure of the such deviation we will use the classical modulus of continuity of f in the spaces (X, P) defined by the formula

$$\omega f(\delta)_P = \sup_{0 \leq t \leq \delta} P(\varphi(t)),$$

where

$$\varphi_x(t) = f(x+t) + f(x-t) - 2f(x).$$

We will also consider a function ω of modulus of continuity type, i.e. a nondecreasing continuous function having the following properties:

$\omega(0) = 0$, $\omega(\delta_1 + \delta_2) \leq \omega(\delta_1) + \omega(\delta_2)$ for any $0 \leq \delta_1 \leq \delta_2 \leq \delta_1 + \delta_2$. Let additionally a function of modulus of continuity type ω satisfies condition

$$\int_u^\beta t^{-2}\omega(t) dt = O(H(u)) \text{ when } u \in [0, \beta], \quad (3)$$

with $H(u) \geq 0$, such that

$$\int_0^u H(t) dt = O(uH(u)) \text{ when } u \in [0, \beta]. \quad (4)$$

Finally let

$$(X, P)(\omega) = \{f \in (X, P) : \omega f(\delta)_P = O(\omega(\delta)) \text{ when } \delta \geq 0\}.$$

P. Chandra in [1] and [2] [Acta Math. Hungar. 52 (1988) 199-205 and 62 (1993) 21-23] estimated the deviation $T_{n, A_0} f - f$ in sup-norm, when $(a_{n, k}^\circ)$ is a monotonic sequences with respect to k . Many years later, L. Leindler [6] [Annales Univ. Sci. Budapest., Sect. Comp. 29 (2008) 93-99] replaced the monotonic sequences with rest bounded variation sequences. More general results were obtained by B. Wei and D. Yu in [12] [Math. Commun. 17 (2012) 211{219] and Xh. Z. Krasniqi in [3], [4] and [5].

In our theorems and corollaries we will formulate the very general conditions for the method of summability, with application of r -th differences of higher orders, and for the moduli of continuity obtaining the best degrees of approximation.

2 Statement of the results

Our main results will be formulated depending on the considered matrix.

We begin with differences of the first order.

Theorem 1 *Let $f \in (X, P)$, $k, m, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and $r \in \mathbb{N}$. If the matrix $A = (a_{n, k})$ satisfies the condition*

$$A_{m, \infty}^{r, 1}(b) = \sum_{k=m}^{\infty} b_k \left| \Delta_r^1 \left(\frac{a_{n, k}}{b_k} \right) \right| = \sum_{k=m}^{\infty} b_k \left| \frac{a_{n, k}}{b_k} - \frac{a_{n, k+r}}{b_{k+r}} \right| = O(a_{n, m}) \quad (5)$$

with an increasing sequence (b_k) of positive numbers such that

$$\frac{b_{k+r} - b_k}{b_{k+r}} = O\left(\frac{1}{k+1}\right) \text{ and } \frac{b_{k+2r} - 2b_{k+r} + b_k}{b_{k+2r}} = O\left(\frac{1}{(k+1)^2}\right) \quad (6)$$

holds, then

$$P(T_{n,A}f - f) = O(1) \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{r} a_{n,0}} \frac{\omega f(t)_P}{t} dt + O(a_{n,0}) \int_{\frac{\pi}{r} a_{n,0}}^{\frac{\pi}{r}} \frac{\omega f(t)_P}{t^2} dt.$$

Theorem 2 Let $f \in (X, P)$, $k, m, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and $r \in \mathbb{N}$. If the matrix $A = (a_{n,k})$ satisfy conditions:

$$A_{m,\infty}^{r,1}(b) = \sum_{k=m}^{\infty} b_k \left| \Delta_r^1 \left(\frac{a_{n,k}}{b_k} \right) \right| = \sum_{k=m}^{\infty} b_k \left| \frac{a_{n,k}}{b_k} - \frac{a_{n,k+r}}{b_{k+r}} \right| = O\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right) \quad (7)$$

with an increasing sequence (b_k) of positive numbers such that (6) holds, and

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_{n,k} (k+1) = O(n+1), \quad (8)$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} P(T_{n,A}f - f) &= O(1) \left[\omega f \left(\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right)_P + \frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \int_{\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)}}^{\frac{\pi}{r}} \frac{\omega f(t)_P}{t^2} dt \right] \\ &= O(1) \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{k=0}^n \omega f \left(\frac{\pi}{r(k+1)} \right)_P. \end{aligned}$$

Now we consider the differences of higher orders.

Theorem 3 Let $f \in (X, P)$ and $k, \mu, \nu, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$. If the matrix $A = (a_{n,k})$ satisfies

$$A_{\mu,\nu}^{r,s} = \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^s(a_{n,k})| = O\left(\frac{a_n(\mu,\nu)}{(\mu+1)^{s-1}}\right), \quad (9)$$

where $a_n(\mu,\nu) = \max_{\mu \leq k \leq \nu} a_{n,k}$, and additionally, for $2 \leq \eta \leq s-1$,

$$\sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} |\Delta_r^{s-\eta}(a_{n,k})| = O(\mu^{\eta-1}) \sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(a_{n,k})|, \quad (10)$$

then

$$P(T_{n,A}f - f) = O(1) \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{r} a_n} \frac{\omega f(t)_P}{t} dt + O(a_n) \int_{\frac{\pi}{r} a_n}^{\frac{\pi}{r}} \frac{\omega f(t)_P}{t^2} dt,$$

where $a_n = a_n(0, \infty) = \max_{0 \leq k \leq \infty} a_{n,k}$.

Theorem 4 Let $f \in (X, P)$ and $k, \mu, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$. If the matrix $A = (a_{n,k})$ satisfy

$$A_{\mu,\infty}^{r,s} = \sum_{k=\mu}^{\infty} |\Delta_r^s(a_{n,k})| = O\left(\frac{1}{(\mu+1)^{s-1}(n+1)}\right), \quad (11)$$

(10) for $1 \leq \eta \leq s$, and (8), then

$$\begin{aligned} P(T_{n,\Lambda}f - f) &= O(1) \left[\omega f \left(\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right)_P + \frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \int_{\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)}}^{\frac{\pi}{r}} \frac{\omega f(t)_P}{t^2} dt \right] \\ &= O(1) \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{k=0}^n \omega f \left(\frac{\pi}{r(k+1)} \right)_P. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we present results with the helpful function H .

Theorem 5 Let $k, \mu, \nu, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $r \in \mathbb{N}$, $f \in (X, P)(\omega)$ and ω satisfy (3). If the matrix $A = (a_{n,k})$ satisfies (5) with an increasing sequence (b_k) of positive numbers such that (6) holds, then

$$P(T_{n,\Lambda}f - f) = O(\omega(a_n) + a_n) H(a_n),$$

If additionally $H(u) \geq 0$, such that (4) holds, then

$$P(T_{n,\Lambda}f - f) = O(a_n) H(a_n).$$

Theorem 6 Let $m, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $r \in \mathbb{N}$, $f \in (X, P)(\omega)$ and ω satisfy (3). If the matrix A satisfy (8), (7) with an increasing sequence (b_k) of positive numbers such that (6) holds, then

$$P(T_{n,\Lambda}f - f) = O \left(\omega \left(\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right) + \frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right) H \left(\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right).$$

If additionally $H(u) \geq 0$, such that (4) holds, then

$$P(T_{n,\Lambda}f - f) = O \left(\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right) H \left(\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right).$$

Theorem 7 Let $k, \mu, \nu, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$, $f \in (X, P)(\omega)$ and ω satisfy (3). If the matrix $A = (a_{n,k})$ satisfy (9) and (10) for $2 \leq \eta \leq s-1$, then

$$P(T_{n,\Lambda}f - f) = O(\omega(a_n) + a_n) H(a_n),$$

If additionally $H(u) \geq 0$, such that (4) holds, then

$$P(T_{n,\Lambda}f - f) = O(a_n) H(a_n).$$

Theorem 8 Let $m, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$, $f \in (X, P)(\omega)$ and ω satisfy (3). If the matrix A satisfy (8), (11) and (10) for $1 \leq \eta \leq s$, then

$$P(T_{n,\Lambda}f - f) = O \left(\omega \left(\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right) + \frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right) H \left(\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right).$$

If additionally $H(u) \geq 0$, such that (4) holds, then

$$P(T_{n,\Lambda}f - f) = O \left(\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right) H \left(\frac{\pi}{r(n+1)} \right).$$

We can give yet a corollary.

Corollary 9 *If we take $r = s = 1$, then in the case of matrix A_0 and $f \in (X, P)$ with $X = C$ and $P(f) = \|f\|_C$ our theorems lead to the essentially better results than that of Xh. Z. Krasniqi and consequently to the results of L. Leindler and P. Chandra.*

3 Auxiliary results

We begin this section by some notations from [10]. Let for $r = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$

$$D_{k,r}(t) = \frac{\sin \frac{(2k+r)t}{2}}{2 \sin \frac{rt}{2}}, \quad \tilde{D}_{k,r}(t) = \frac{\cos \frac{(2k+r)t}{2}}{2 \sin \frac{rt}{2}}.$$

In the proofs we will need the following results and remarks.

Remark 10 *We can observe that entries of every lower triangular matrix A_0 always satisfy the condition (8)*

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_{n,k}^{\circ} (k+1) \equiv \sum_{k=0}^n a_{n,k}^{\circ} (k+1) \leq \sum_{k=0}^n a_{n,k}^{\circ} (n+1) = n+1.$$

Remark 11 *Assumption (5) implies the relation $a_{n,l} = O(a_{n,k})$ with $k \leq l$, but assumption (??) implies the relation $a_{n,k} = O(a_{n,n})$ with $k \leq n$.*

Lemma 12 *(see [13]) If $0 < |t| \leq \pi/2$, then*

$$|D_{k,1}(t)| \leq \frac{\pi}{2|t|}, \quad |\tilde{D}_{k,1}(t)| \leq \frac{\pi}{2|t|}$$

and for any real t we have

$$|D_{k,1}(t)| \leq k+1.$$

Lemma 13 *If $r \in \mathbb{N}$, $l \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $(b_k) \subset \mathbb{R}_+$, $(c_k) \subset \mathbb{R}$, then for all nonnegative integers $\nu \geq \mu$ and $x \neq \frac{2l\pi}{r}$*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} c_k \frac{\cos kx}{\sin kx} &= \pm \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} \Delta_r^1 \left(\frac{c_k}{b_k} \right) b_k \frac{D_{k,r}(x)}{\tilde{D}_{k,r}(x)} \\ &\mp \left(\sum_{k=\mu+1}^{\nu+r} - \sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} \right) c_k \frac{D_{k,-r}(x)}{\tilde{D}_{k,-r}(x)} \mp \sum_{k=\mu+r}^{\nu+r} c_k \frac{[b_{k-r} - b_k]}{b_k} \frac{D_{k,-r}(x)}{\tilde{D}_{k,-r}(x)}. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The special case with $b_k = 1$ it was proved by the second author in [10] and [11].

Lemma 14 If $r \in \mathbb{N}$, $l \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $(h_k) \subset \mathbb{R}$, $(f_k) \subset \mathbb{R}_+$, then for all nonnegative integers $\nu \geq \mu$ and $x \neq \frac{2l\pi}{r}$

$$2 \sin^2 \frac{rx}{2} \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} h_k \frac{D_{k,r}(x)}{\tilde{D}_{k,r}(x)} = \mp \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} \Delta_r^1 \left(\frac{h_k}{f_k} \right) f_k \frac{\cos(k+r)x}{\sin kx} \\ \pm \left(\sum_{k=\mu+r}^{\nu+r} - \sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} \right) h_k \frac{\cos kx}{\sin(k-r)x} \pm \sum_{k=\mu+r}^{\nu+r} h_k \frac{[f_{k-r} - f_k]}{f_k} \frac{\cos kx}{\sin(k-r)x}.$$

Now, we can present the main estimates used in the proofs of our theorems with $s = 1$.

Lemma 15 If $m, n, r \in \mathbb{N}$, $l \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $(c_k), (b_k) \subset \mathbb{R}_+$, then for $t \neq \frac{2l\pi}{r}$, $t \in (0, \pi)$ and $m \leq n$,

$$\left| \sum_{k=m}^n c_k \frac{D_{k,1}(t)}{\tilde{D}_{k,1}(t)} \right| = \frac{O(1)}{\sin \frac{t}{2} |\sin \frac{rt}{2}|} \left[\sum_{k=m}^n \left| \Delta_r^1 \left(\frac{c_k}{b_k} \right) \right| b_k + \left(\sum_{k=n+1}^{n+r} + \sum_{k=m}^{m+r-1} \right) c_k \right] \\ + \frac{O(1)}{\sin \frac{t}{2} \sin^2 \frac{rx}{2}} \sum_{k=m+r}^{n+r} \left| \Delta_r^1 \left(\frac{c_k}{b_k} \right) \right| |b_{k-r} - b_k| \\ + \frac{O(1)}{\sin \frac{t}{2} \sin^2 \frac{rx}{2}} \left[\left(\sum_{k=n+r+1}^{n+2r} - \sum_{k=m+r}^{m+2r-1} \right) c_k \frac{|b_{k-r} - b_k|}{b_k} \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{k=m+2r}^{n+2r} c_k \frac{|b_k - 2b_{k-r} + b_{k-2r}|}{b_k} \right].$$

Lemma 16 If $m, n, r \in \mathbb{N}$, $l \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $(c_k) \subset \mathbb{R}_+$ and

$$\sum_{k=m}^{\infty} \left| \Delta_r^1 \left(\frac{c_k}{b_k} \right) \right| b_k = O(c_m) \quad (13)$$

holds with an increasing sequence (b_k) of positive numbers such that (6) holds, then

$$\left| \sum_{k=0}^n c_k \frac{D_{k,1}(t)}{\tilde{D}_{k,1}(t)} \right| = \frac{O(1)}{\sin \frac{t}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\tau} c_k + \frac{O(c_{\tau})}{\sin \frac{t}{2} |\sin \frac{rt}{2}|} + \frac{O(1)}{2(\tau+1) \sin \frac{t}{2} \sin^2 \frac{rt}{2}} c_{\tau+2r}$$

for $t \neq \frac{2l\pi}{r}$, $t \in (0, \pi)$ and $\tau \leq n$, but if additionally $\tau = \left\lfloor \frac{\pi}{|\sin \frac{rt}{2}|} \right\rfloor$, then

$$\left| \sum_{k=0}^n c_k \frac{D_{k,1}(t)}{\tilde{D}_{k,1}(t)} \right| = \frac{O(1)}{\sin \frac{t}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\tau} c_k + \frac{O(c_{\tau})}{\sin \frac{t}{2} |\sin \frac{rt}{2}|} = \frac{O(c_0)}{\sin \frac{t}{2} |\sin \frac{rt}{2}|}.$$

Lemma 17 If $n, r \in \mathbb{N}$, $l \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $(c_k) \subset \mathbb{R}_+$ with $c_k = 0$ for $k > n$ and

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left| \Delta_r^1 \left(\frac{c_k}{b_k} \right) \right| b_k = O(c_n) \quad (14)$$

holds with an increasing sequence (b_k) of positive numbers such that (6) holds, then

$$\left| \sum_{k=0}^n c_k \frac{D_{k,1}(t)}{\tilde{D}_{k,1}(t)} \right| = \frac{O(c_n)}{\sin \frac{t}{2} \left| \sin \frac{rt}{2} \right|},$$

for $\tau \leq n$, where $\tau = \left\lceil \frac{\pi}{\left| \sin \frac{rt}{2} \right|} \right\rceil$, $t \in (0, \pi)$ and $t \neq \frac{2l\pi}{r}$.

Next, we present the main estimates used in the proofs of our theorems with $s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Lemma 18 If $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$, $l \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $(c_k) \subset \mathbb{C}$, then for all nonnegative integers $\nu \geq \mu$ and $t \neq \frac{2l\pi}{r}$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} c_k \frac{\cos kx}{\sin^s kx} &= \frac{1}{\sin^s \frac{rx}{2}} \left[\sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} \Delta_r^s(c_k) \Gamma_k(x) + \left(\sum_{k=\nu+1}^{\nu+r} - \sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} \right) \Delta_r^{s-1}(c_k) \Lambda_k(x) \right] \\ &+ \frac{1}{\sin^{s-1} \frac{rx}{2}} \left(\sum_{k=\nu+1}^{\nu+r} - \sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} \right) \Delta_r^{s-2}(c_k) \Psi_k(x) + \dots \\ &+ \frac{1}{\sin^2 \frac{rx}{2}} \left(\sum_{k=\nu+1}^{\nu+r} - \sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} \right) \Delta_r^1(c_k) \Theta_k(x) \\ &+ \frac{1}{\sin \frac{rx}{2}} \left(\sum_{k=\nu+1}^{\nu+r} - \sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} \right) \Delta_r^0(c_k) \Xi_k(x), \end{aligned}$$

where $\Gamma_k, \Lambda_k, \dots, \Theta_k$ and Ξ_k are some bounded functions.

Lemma 19 Let $\mu, \nu, n, r, s \in \mathbb{N}$, $l \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $(c_k) \subset \mathbb{R}_+$. If $c(\mu, \nu) = \min_{\mu \leq k < \nu} c_k$, $t \neq \frac{2l\pi}{r}$,

$$\sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^s(c_k)| = O\left(\frac{c(\mu, \nu)}{(\mu+1)^{s-1}} \right) \quad (15)$$

and

$$\sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} |\Delta_r^{s-\eta}(c_k)| = O(\mu^{\eta-1}) \sum_{k=\mu}^{\mu+r-1} |\Delta_r^{s-1}(c_k)| \quad (16)$$

for $2 \leq \eta \leq s - 1$, where $\Delta_r^1(c_k) = c_k - c_{k+r}$ and $\Delta_r^s(c_k) = \Delta_r^1(\Delta_r^{s-1}(c_k))$, then

$$\left| \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} c_k \frac{D_{k,1}(t)}{\tilde{D}_{k,1}(t)} \right| = \frac{O(c(\mu, \nu))}{\sin \frac{t}{2} \left| \sin \frac{rt}{2} \right|},$$

with $c_k = 0$ for $k > \nu$ or when $\nu = \infty$

Lemma 20 Let $\mu, \nu, n, r, s \in \mathbb{N}, l \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $(c_k) \subset \mathbb{R}_+$. If $c(\mu, \nu) = \min_{\mu \leq k < \nu} c_k$, $t \neq \frac{2l\pi}{r}$,

$$\sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} |\Delta_r^s(c_k)| = O\left(\frac{1}{(\mu+1)^{s-1}} \frac{1}{\nu+1}\right) \quad (17)$$

and (16) for $1 \leq \eta \leq s$ hold, where $\Delta_r(c_k) = c_k - c_{k+r}$ and $\Delta_r^s(c_k) = \Delta_r(\Delta_r^{s-1}(c_k))$, then

$$\left| \sum_{k=\mu}^{\nu} c_k \frac{D_{k,1}(t)}{\tilde{D}_{k,1}(t)} \right| = \frac{O(1)}{\sin \frac{t}{2} \left| \sin \frac{rt}{2} \right|} \frac{1}{\nu+1},$$

with $c_k = 0$ for $k > \nu$ or when $\nu = \infty$

We need the following very general lemma yet.

Lemma 21 (see [8]) Let $f \in (L^p, P)$ with $1 \leq p < \infty$ and $K \in (C, P)$. If the seminorm P satisfies conditions (1) and (2), then

$$P\left(\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(\cdot+t)K(t) dt\right) \leq P(f) \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} |K(t)| dt.$$

Remark 22 The above Lemma 21 will also be true for $f \in (C, P)$ and thus for $f \in (X^p, P)$ because $(C, P) \subset (L^p, P)$ for $1 \leq p < \infty$.

We additionally present three slight changed conditions (3) and (4).

Lemma 23 [7, 2, 9] If (3) and (4) hold, then, for $c \geq 1$ and $\beta \geq \alpha \geq 0$,

$$\int_{\alpha}^{\beta} t^{-1} \omega(t) dt = O((\beta - \alpha) H(c(\beta - \alpha))) .$$

Lemma 24 [9] If (3) and (4) hold, then, for $b \geq 1$ and $\beta \geq \alpha > 0$,

$$\int_{\alpha}^{\beta} t^{-2} \omega(t) dt = O(H(b\alpha)) .$$

Lemma 25 If (3) and (4) hold, then

$$\int_0^u \omega(t) dt = O(u^2 H(cu)) \text{ when } c \geq 1 \text{ and } u > 0.$$

Finally, we present very useful property of the modulus of continuity and two remark yet.

Lemma 26 [13] *A function ω of modulus of continuity type on the interval $[0, 2\pi]$ satisfies the following condition*

$$\delta_2^{-1}\omega(\delta_2) \leq 2\delta_1^{-1}\omega(\delta_1) \text{ for } \delta_2 \geq \delta_1 > 0.$$

Remark 27 *Analysing the proofs of our theorems we can observe that the condition (10) is superfluous when $s \leq 2$.*

Remark 28 *We note that instead of (3) and (4) one can use Bari-Stechkin conditions*

$$u \int_u^\beta t^{-2}\omega(t) dt = O(\omega(u)) \text{ when } u \in [0, \beta],$$

$$\int_0^u t^{-1}\omega(t) dt = O(\omega(u)) \text{ when } u \in [0, \beta]$$

Then all our results are true for $t^{-1}\omega(t)$ instead of $H(t)$.

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Joint backward extensions of weighted shifts on directed trees

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Weighted shifts on ℓ^2 are well known in operator theory and serve as an important class of examples. In [1], the concept was generalised to *weighted shifts on directed trees*, where we replace the linear order of coordinates by a more involved graph structure. The study of backward extension is about whether a given family of weighted shifts on directed trees can be extended to a weighted shift on a single tree, preserving some operator-theoretic property. Among the considered properties are subnormality, power hyponormality and complete hyperexpansivity. In the case of the first two classes the existence of joint backward extension for a family does not depend neither on the additional structure of an enveloping tree nor on any interrelation between the given operators.

The results come from my PhD dissertation written under the supervision of prof. Jan Stochel and were also published in [2,3].

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Joint backward extensions of weighted shifts on directed trees

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Function Spaces XIII, Poznań 2024

1 / 14

Classical weighted shifts

Weighted shift operator

Given a sequence $\alpha = \{\alpha_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ we define the weighted shift operator W_{α} in ℓ^2 by the formula

$$W_{\alpha}e_n = \alpha_n e_{n+1}, \quad n \geq 0.$$

Backward extension

Given a weighted shift operator W_{α} with weights $\alpha = \{\alpha_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we ask whether there exist numbers $\{\alpha_{-j}\}_{j=1}^k$ such that the weighted shift $W_{\tilde{\alpha}}$ with weights $\tilde{\alpha} = \{\alpha_{n-k}\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ has certain property (e.g. subnormality).

2 / 14

Directed trees

\mathcal{T} a directed tree
 ω root of the tree
 $\text{Chi}(v)$ children of the vertex v

V set of vertices
 $p(v)$ parent of the vertex v
 $\text{Chi}^{(k)}(v)$ k -th children of the vertex v

$$v \in \text{Chi}^{(k)}(u) \implies p^k(v) = u \quad V = \{\omega\} \sqcup \bigsqcup_{v \in V} \text{Chi}(v)$$

3 / 14

Weighted shifts on directed trees

Define $e_v(v) = 1$, $e_v|_{V \setminus \{v\}} \equiv 0$ for $v \in V$. Then $\{e_v\}_{v \in V}$ is the standard orthonormal basis of $\ell^2(V)$.

Weighted shift on a directed tree

Let \mathcal{T} be a directed tree and V be its set of vertices. Given a system of complex weights $\lambda = \{\lambda_v\}_{v \in V}$, the weighted shift S_λ on \mathcal{T} with weights λ is an operator in $\ell^2(V)$ determined by the formula

$$S_\lambda e_v = \sum_{u \in \text{Chi}(v)} \lambda_u e_u, \quad v \in V.$$

Note that the weights are assigned to the *target* vertices. In particular the weight in the root (λ_ω) is irrelevant.

The weighted shift is called *proper* if $\lambda_v \neq 0$ for all $v \in V \setminus \{\omega\}$.

We will focus on bounded weighted shifts. The equivalent condition for boundedness is that $\sup\{\sum_{u \in \text{Chi}(v)} |\lambda_u|^2 : v \in V\} < \infty$.

4 / 14

“Simple” backward extension

Let \mathcal{C} be a class of operators (e.g. subnormal, completely hyperexpansive etc.).

We say that a weighted shift S_λ on a directed tree \mathcal{T} with the root ω_0 admits a \mathcal{C} k -step backward extension if there exist non-zero weights $\lambda'_{\omega_0}, \dots, \lambda'_{\omega_{k-1}}$ such that the weighted shift $S_{\lambda'}$ on $\mathcal{T}_{(k)}$ (the tree obtained from \mathcal{T} by adding k ancestors to the root) belongs to class \mathcal{C} and $S_{\lambda'}|_{\ell^2(V)} = S_\lambda$.

It is also useful to say that S_λ “admits a \mathcal{C} 0-step backward extension” whenever S_λ belongs to \mathcal{C} .

5 / 14

Proposition

For the following classes of bounded weighted shifts every member admits a k -step backward extension within the class for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

- all bounded,
- contractive,
- bounded from below,
- isometric,
- scalar multiples of isometries,
- non-zero hyponormal ($\|Tf\| \geq \|T^*f\|$ for every vector f).

Proposition (Jabłoński-Jung-Stochel)

Every proper and quasinormal ($T^*TT = TT^*T$) weighted shift on a directed tree is a scalar multiple of isometry.

6 / 14

A rooted sum of directed trees

Rooted sum

The **rooted sum** of a family $\{\mathcal{T}_j : j \in J\}$ of rooted directed trees is the directed tree $\bigsqcup_{j \in J} \mathcal{T}_j$ with root ω containing each of \mathcal{T}_j 's and such that

$$\text{Chi}(\omega) = \{\omega_j : j \in J\},$$

where ω_j stands for the root of \mathcal{T}_j for $j \in J$.

7 / 14

Joint backward extension property

$$k = 2, \quad J = \{1, 2, 3\}$$

An extension on the rooted sum of the family admits k -step backward ext.

Every weighted shift in the family admits $(k + 1)$ -step backward ext.

8 / 14

Joint backward extension property

Sketch of definition

We say that the class \mathcal{C} has the **joint backward extension property** if the following statement is true.

For every $k \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ there exists a constant $c_k > 0$ such that for any non-empty at most countable family $\{S_j\}_{j \in J}$ of bounded proper weighted shifts on rooted directed trees \mathcal{T}_j , the following conditions are equivalent:

- 1 there exists a system $\{\lambda_{\omega_j}\}_{j \in J} \subseteq \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$ for which the weighted shift S_λ on $\sqcup_{j \in J} \mathcal{T}_j$ such that $S_{\lambda_{\omega_j}} = S_j$ for $j \in J$, is bounded and admits a \mathcal{C} k -step backward extension,
- 2 the system $\{\lambda_{\omega_j}\}_{j \in J}$ above can be chosen so that additionally $\|S_\lambda\| \leq c_k \sup\{\|S_j\| : j \in J\}$,
- 3 S_j admits a \mathcal{C} $(k+1)$ -step backward extension for each $j \in J$ and $\sup\{\|S_j\| : j \in J\} < \infty$.

9 / 14

The existence of weights for gray vertices such that the resulting weighted shift belongs to the class \mathcal{C} does not depend on the choice of particular structure of first k “levels” of the tree.

10 / 14

Formal statement

Theorem

Let \mathcal{C} be a class satisfying JBEP, \mathcal{T} be a leafless directed tree with the root ω and $k \geq 1$. Assume that weights $\{\lambda_v\}_{v \in W_k} \subseteq \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$ are given, where

$$W_k := \bigcup_{v \in \text{Chi}^{(k)}(\omega)} \text{Des}^\circ(v).$$

Then the following conditions are equivalent

- ① there exist $\{\lambda_v\}_{v \in V \setminus W_k} \subseteq \mathbb{C}$ such that the weighted shift S_λ with weights $\lambda = \{\lambda_v\}_{v \in V}$ is bounded proper and belongs to \mathcal{C} ,
- ② the set $\text{Chi}^{(k)}(\omega)$ is at most countable, the weighted shift $S_{\lambda_{\vec{v}}}$ is bounded proper and admits a \mathcal{C} k -step backward extension for every $v \in \text{Chi}^{(k)}(\omega)$, and $\sup\{\|S_{\lambda_{\vec{v}}}\| : v \in \text{Chi}^{(k)}(\omega)\} < \infty$.

11 / 14

Classes satisfying JBEP

Theorem

The following classes of bounded weighted shifts have the joint backward extension property:

- bounded,
- contractive,
- expansive,
- isometric,
- hyponormal,
- power hyponormal (T^n is hyponormal for all $n \geq 1$)
- subnormal (admitting an extension $N \supset T$ satisfying $N^*N = NN^*$).

12 / 14

Classes failing to satisfy JBEP

Theorem

The following classes of bounded weighted shifts have been proven to have **no** joint backward extension property:

- operators bounded from below,
- scalar multiples of isometries (in particular quasinormal weighted shifts),
- completely hyperexpansive ($\sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} T^{*j} T^j \leq 0$ for $n \geq 1$).

In the picture squares of the weights are provided. For $\alpha \in (0, \frac{1}{k})$, the whole weighted shift admits a completely hyperexpansive k -step backward extension.

13 / 14

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14 / 14

Interpolation theory of Down spaces over general measure spaces

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We consider a measure space together with a totally ordered subset of its sigma algebra called an ordered core. Recently, this construction was used in the context of Hardy inequalities, giving a uniform treatment of many different types of Hardy operators.

We will begin by introducing a definition of monotone functions compatible with the ordered core. This allows us to extend the down space construction, a variant of the Köthe dual restricted to positive decreasing functions, to all measure spaces. We will look at their associate spaces and their relationship with a suitable version of the least decreasing majorant construction in this more general setting. We will discuss the interpolation structure of these spaces and find strong similarities to the real line case; the down spaces corresponding to L^1 and L^∞ form an exact Calderón couple and as a consequence, we can describe all their exact interpolation spaces in terms of the K -functional. We will also show an analogous result for the dual couple.

This talk is based on joint work with Gord Sinnamon in [1].

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Interpolation theory of Down spaces over general measure spaces

Function Spaces XIII

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1 / 12

Introduction

Let $f : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be measurable, consider its **level function** f° and its **least decreasing majorant** \tilde{f} . Satisfying $f(t) \leq \tilde{f}(t)$ and $\int_0^x f \leq \int_0^x f^\circ$.

For h **decreasing**: If $f \leq h$ then $\tilde{f} \leq h$. If $\int_0^x f \leq \int_0^x h$ then $\int_0^x f^\circ \leq \int_0^x h$.

Applications: Describe the associate spaces of abstract Lorentz spaces [Kamińska, Raynauld 2019], study weighted Hardy inequalities [Sinnamon, Stepanov 1996], boundedness of the Fourier transform in Lorentz spaces [Rastegari, Sinnamon 2016], facilitate interpolation of Cesaro spaces [Leśnik, Maligranda 2016].

Goal: Extend these constructions and function spaces to general measure spaces not requiring an order.

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2 / 12

Monotone functions

Let (U, Σ, μ) be a σ -finite measure space. **We assume no order.**

Definition: An **ordered core** is a totally ordered subset \mathcal{A} of Σ (If $A, B \in \mathcal{A}$ then $A \subseteq B$ or $B \subseteq A$), containing \emptyset and satisfying $\mu(E) < \infty$ for all $E \in \mathcal{A}$ and $\cup \mathcal{A} = \cup_n E_n$ for some $\{E_n\} \in \mathcal{A}$.

Definition: A positive $\sigma(\mathcal{A})$ -measurable function is **core-decreasing** if

- 1.
2. f is constant in each **gap**

if $x \in E$ and $y \notin E$, $f(x) \geq f(y)$

$$\forall E \in \mathcal{A}$$

Examples

Every core contains \emptyset .

1. Let $U = [0, \infty)$, μ the Lebesgue measure. The **core** $\mathcal{A} = \{[0, x] : x > 0\}$. Note $\sigma(\mathcal{A})$ is the Borel σ -algebra. f is **core decreasing** if for each $E = [0, t]$, $x \in [0, t]$ and $y \notin [0, t]$ then $f(y) \leq f(x)$.
2. Let $U = [0, \infty)$, μ the Lebesgue measure. The **core** $\mathcal{A} = \{[0, n] : n \in \mathbb{N}^+\}$. Now $\sigma(\mathcal{A})$ is strictly smaller than the Borel σ -algebra. f is **core decreasing** if $x < y$ implies $f(y) \leq f(x)$ and f is **constant on each set** $(n - 1, n]$.
3. Let $U = \mathbb{R}^d$, μ satisfying $\mu(B[0; r]) < \infty$ for each $r > 0$. The **core** $\mathcal{A} = \{B[0; r] : r > 0\}$. Again $\sigma(\mathcal{A})$ is strictly smaller than the Borel σ -algebra. f is **core decreasing** if it is radially decreasing
4. Let (U, Σ, μ) be σ -finite and fix $\varphi : U \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ satisfying for all $r > 0$, $\mu(\{y : |\varphi(y)| > r\}) < \infty$. The **core** $\mathcal{A} = \{\{y : |\varphi(y)| > r\} : r > 0\}$. f is **core decreasing** if $f(x) \leq f(y) \iff |\varphi(x)| \leq |\varphi(y)|$.

Induced measure on the half line

Consider the a larger vector space.

$$L^1_{\text{Loc}, \mathcal{A}} = \left\{ f \text{ measurable} : \int_A |f| d\mu < \infty \text{ for all } A \in \mathcal{A} \right\}$$

Every ordered core induces a Borel measure λ on $[0, \infty)$ and maps R, Q :

New results: Level function and least core decreasing majorant

We use the maps R, Q to define the level function in general measure spaces.

$$L(\Sigma) \xrightarrow{||} L^+(\Sigma) \xrightarrow{R} L^+(\mathcal{B}) \xrightarrow{o} L^\downarrow(\mathcal{B}) \xrightarrow{Q} L^\downarrow(\mathcal{A})$$

$$f \xrightarrow{||} |f| \xrightarrow{R} R|f| \xrightarrow{o} (R|f|)^o \xrightarrow{Q} Q(R|f|)^o$$

The 'lifting' approach does not work for the least decreasing majorant, for instance, $|f| \leq Q(\widetilde{R|f|})$ might fail.

Lemma [S.-Sinnamon 2024]

Every Σ -measurable function g has a least core decreasing majorant, denoted \widetilde{g} , which is unique up to μ almost everywhere equality. If $g_n \in L^+(\Sigma)$ and $g_n \uparrow g$ μ -a.e., then $\widetilde{g}_n \uparrow \widetilde{g}$ μ -a.e.

Rearrangement invariant spaces

For a measurable function $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with mild conditions on the level sets, there exists a nonincreasing function $f^* : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$. Such that $\int_E |f| d\mu \leq \int_0^{\mu(E)} f^*(x) dx$ and $\|f\|_{L^p_\mu} = \|f^*\|_{L^p_\mu}$ for $p \in [1, \infty]$.

[Luxemburg 1967]

A function space X (on (U, μ)) is **universally rearrangement invariant (u.r.i.)** if $\|f\|_X = \|f^*\|_X$ for a function space Y (on $([0, \infty), dx)$).

Down spaces with respect to an ordered core

Let (U, Σ, μ) be σ -finite and \mathcal{A} be an ordered core.

Definition: The **down space** of a u.r.i space X is denoted by X_\downarrow and has the norm

$$\|f\|_{X_\downarrow} = \sup \left\{ \int_U |f| g d\mu : \|g\|_{X'} \leq 1, \text{ and } g \text{ is core decreasing} \right\}.$$

By restricting the supremum we have $X \subseteq X'' \subseteq X_\downarrow$. Examples: $L^1_{\mu\downarrow} = L^1_\mu$ and $L^\infty_\mu \subset L^\infty_{\mu\downarrow}$.

Definition: The space \tilde{X} has the norm

$$\|f\|_{\tilde{X}} = \|\tilde{f}\|_X.$$

Since $|f| \leq \tilde{f}$, we have $\tilde{X} \subseteq X$. Examples: $\tilde{L}^1_\mu \subset L^1_\mu$ and $L^\infty_\mu = \tilde{L}^\infty_\mu$.

Theorem [S.-Sinnamon 2024]

For X u.r.i over (U, μ) and core \mathcal{A} : $\|f\|_{X_\downarrow} = \|f^o\|_X$ and $(X_\downarrow)' = \tilde{X}'$.

Interpolation

Remarkable Property: For any linear operator

$$T : L_\mu^1 + L_\mu^\infty \rightarrow L_\mu^1 + L_\mu^\infty$$

such that $T|_{L_\mu^1} : L_\mu^1 \rightarrow L_\mu^1$ and $T|_{L_\mu^\infty} : L_\mu^\infty \rightarrow L_\mu^\infty$ are bounded

Then:

$T(L_\mu^p) \subseteq L_\mu^p$ and $T|_{L_\mu^p}$ is bounded with an estimate for the norm.

Question: Describe all the spaces Y such that

$$L_\mu^1 \cap L_\mu^\infty \subseteq Y \subseteq L_\mu^1 + L_\mu^\infty$$

and $T(Y) \subseteq Y$ and $T|_Y$ is bounded.

Solved: Calderón (1966), the spaces Y are precisely the u.r.i spaces.

Our project: Describe all the spaces Y such that

$$L_\mu^1 \cap (L_\mu^\infty)^\downarrow \subseteq Y \subseteq L_\mu^1 + (L_\mu^\infty)^\downarrow$$

and $T(Y) \subseteq Y$ and $T|_Y$ is bounded. The special case when $U = [0, \infty)$ was worked in [Mastylo, Sinnamon 2017].

Interpolation of down spaces

A tool to create such spaces is the K -functional:

$$K(x, t, X_1, X_2) = \inf \{ \|x_1\|_{X_1} + t\|x_2\|_{X_2} : x = x_1 + x_2 \}.$$

Theorem (K-functional) [S.-Sinnamon 2024]

$$K(f, t, L_\mu^1, (L_\mu^\infty)^\downarrow) = \int_0^t (f^\circ)^*$$

Theorem (Exact Calderón couples) [S.-Sinnamon 2024]

If $f, g \in L_\mu^1 + (L_\mu^\infty)^\downarrow$ and $\int_0^t (f^\circ)^* \leq \int_0^t (g^\circ)^*$ for all $t > 0$ then there exists an admissible contraction $T : L_\mu^1 + (L_\mu^\infty)^\downarrow$ such that $Tg = f$.

An analogous result holds for the dual couple.

Corollary

Z is an interpolation space of $(L_\mu^1, (L_\mu^\infty)^\downarrow)$ if and only if $Z = X^\downarrow$ for some rearrangement invariant space X .

Calderón couples, conclusion

We have a complete description of the interpolation spaces for the couples $(L_\mu^1, (L_\mu^\infty)^\downarrow)$ and $(\widetilde{L}_\mu^1, L_\mu^\infty)$, in terms of the rearrangement invariant spaces

References:

1. Santacruz Hidalgo, A., and Sinnamon, G. **Core decreasing functions.** Journal of Functional Analysis, 187(2024)

Thank you!

Bochner representable operators on variable exponent Lebesgue spaces**Juliusz Stochmal**

CT

Kazimierz Wielki University in Bydgoszcz, Poland, e-mail: j.stochmal@ukw.edu.pl

Let $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ denote a variable exponent Lebesgue space and X be a Banach space. We discuss when a bounded linear operator $T : L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow X$ is Bochner representable, that is, there exists a unique function $g \in L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega, X)$ such that

$$T(u) = \int_{\Omega} u(t)g(t) d\mu, \text{ for all } u \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega),$$

where $\frac{1}{p(t)} + \frac{1}{p^*(t)} = 1$ μ -a.e. As an application, we study the compactness property of these operators.

Bochner representable operators on variable exponent Lebesgue spaces

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Function spaces XIII

In memory of Henryk Hudzik and Julian Musielak
Poznań, Poland, July 8-12, 2024

1 / 20

Introduction

- Integral representation of bounded linear operators on Lebesgue spaces with respect to the vector measures - Phillips (1940), Dinculeanu (1967).
- Bochner representable operators on Lebesgue spaces - Dinculeanu (1966, 1973), Chaney (1971), Wong (1971) (see [DU, Chapter IV.4.]).
- Bochner representable operators on Orlicz spaces - Uhl [U], Nowak and Oelke [NO].

 [DU] Diestel, J. and J.J. Uhl, *Vector Measures*, Amer. Math. Soc., Math. Surveys 15, Providence, RI, 1977.

 [NO] Nowak, M. and A. Oelke, *Linear operators on non-locally convex Orlicz spaces*, Banach Center Publications, vol. 79, no.1 (2008), 157–165.

 [U] Uhl, J.J., *On a class of operators on Orlicz spaces*, *Studia Math.*, 40 (1971), 17–22.

2 / 20

Introduction

Let

- (Ω, Σ, μ) be a finite measure space
- $L^0(\Omega)$ be the space of μ -equivalence classes of all measurable real functions
- $\mathcal{P}(\Omega)$ denote the set of all μ -measurable functions $p : \Omega \rightarrow (1, \infty)$.

Definition

Given $p \in \mathcal{P}(\Omega)$, the **variable exponent Lebesgue space** $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ is defined by

$$L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) := \{u \in L^0(\Omega) : \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(\lambda u) < \infty \text{ for some } \lambda > 0\},$$

where

$$\varrho_{p(\cdot)}(u) := \int_{\Omega} |u(t)|^{p(t)} d\mu.$$

Then $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, equipped with the associated Luxemburg–Nakano norm $\|\cdot\|_{p(\cdot)}$,

$$\|u\|_{p(\cdot)} := \inf\{\lambda > 0 : \varrho_{p(\cdot)}(u/\lambda) \leq 1\} \text{ for } u \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega),$$

is a Banach function space.

3 / 20

Introduction

Let us put

- $p_- := \text{ess inf}\{p(t) : t \in \Omega\}$
- $p_+ := \text{ess sup}\{p(t) : t \in \Omega\}$.

By p^* we denote the conjugate function of p , i.e., p^* is a μ -measurable function such that $\frac{1}{p(t)} + \frac{1}{p^*(t)} = 1$ μ -a.e.

4 / 20

Introduction

Proposition ([CF], [DHHR])

If $p \in \mathcal{P}(\Omega)$ and $p_+ < \infty$, then

- (1) $(L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega), \|\cdot\|_{p(\cdot)})$ is an order continuous Banach function space.
- (2) The set $S(\Sigma)$ of all real simple functions on Ω is dense in $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$.
- (3) The Banach dual $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)^*$ of $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ is given by

$$L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)^* = \{\Phi_v : v \in L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega)\},$$

where $\Phi_v(u) := \int_{\Omega} u(t)v(t) d\mu$ for $u \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$.

[CF] Cruz-Uribe D.V. and A. Fiorenza, *Variable Lebesgue Spaces: Foundations and Harmonic Analysis*, Birkhäuser, Basel, 2013.

[DHHR] Diening, L., P. Harjulehto, P. Hästö and M. Ružička, *Lebesgue and Sobolev Spaces with Variable Exponents*, Lecture Notes in Math., vol. 2017, Springer, Heidelberg, 2011.

5 / 20

Introduction

- (4) $L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ coincides with the Köthe dual $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)'$ of $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, that is,

$$L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega) = \left\{ v \in L^0(\Omega) : \int_{\Omega} |u(t)v(t)| d\mu < \infty \text{ for all } u \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \right\}.$$

6 / 20

Introduction

Theorem (Hölder's inequality) [CF, Theorem 2.26]

Let $p \in \mathcal{P}(\Omega)$. Then for $u \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$ and $v \in L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega)$, we have $uv \in L^1(\Omega)$ and

$$\int_{\Omega} |u(t)v(t)| \, d\mu \leq K_{p(\cdot)} \|u\|_{p(\cdot)} \|v\|_{p^*(\cdot)},$$

where $1 \leq K_{p(\cdot)} \leq 2$.

7 / 20

Introduction

Denote by $L^0(\Omega, X)$ the space of μ -equivalence classes of all X -valued strongly measurable functions defined on Ω . For $p \in \mathcal{P}(\Omega)$, let $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega, X)$ denote the **variable exponent Bochner–Lebesgue space**, that is,

$$L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega, X) := \{f \in L^0(\Omega, X) : \|f(\cdot)\|_X \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)\}.$$

Then $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega, X)$, equipped with the norm

$$\|f\|_{L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega, X)} := \left\| \|f(\cdot)\|_X \right\|_{p(\cdot)} \quad \text{for } f \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega, X),$$

is a Banach space.

8 / 20

Bochner representable operators on $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$

Definition

A bounded linear operator $T : L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow X$ is called **Bochner representable** if there exists a unique function $g \in L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega, X)$ such that

$$T(u) = \int_{\Omega} u(t)g(t) d\mu, \text{ for all } u \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega).$$

9 / 20

Bochner representable operators on $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$

For a bounded linear operator $T : L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow X$, let $m_T : \Sigma \rightarrow X$ be a vector measure defined by

$$m_T(A) := T(\mathbb{1}_A) \text{ for } A \in \Sigma.$$

Since T is bounded, in view of [CF, Corollary 2.23], we get

$$\|m_T(A)\|_X = \|T(\mathbb{1}_A)\|_X \leq \|T\| \|\mathbb{1}_A\|_{p(\cdot)} \leq \|T\| \max \left\{ \mu(A)^{\frac{1}{p_+}}, \mu(A)^{\frac{1}{p_-}} \right\},$$

so m_T is μ -absolutely continuous and countably additive.

10 / 20

Bochner representable operators on $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$

Following [DU, Definition 7, p. 110], define

$$\|T\|_{p(\cdot)} := \sup \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n \|\alpha_i T(\mathbb{1}_{A_i})\|_X : s = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \mathbb{1}_{A_i} \in \mathcal{S}(\Sigma), \|s\|_{p(\cdot)} \leq 1 \right\}.$$

Lemma

Assume that $p \in \mathcal{P}(\Omega)$ and X has the Radon–Nikodym property with respect to μ . If $\|T\|_{p(\cdot)} < \infty$, then

- (i) m_T has bounded variation and there exists a unique function $g \in L^1(\Omega, X)$ such that for all $A \in \Sigma$,

$$m_T(A) = \int_A g(t) d\mu \quad \text{and} \quad |m_T|(A) = \int_A \|g(t)\|_X d\mu;$$

- (ii)

$$\|T\|_{p(\cdot)} = \sup \left\{ \int_{\Omega} |s(t)| \|g(t)\|_X d\mu : s \in \mathcal{S}(\Sigma), \|s\|_{p(\cdot)} \leq 1 \right\}.$$

11 / 20

Bochner representable operators on $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$

Theorem

Assume that $p \in \mathcal{P}(\Omega)$ with $p_+ < \infty$ and X has the Radon–Nikodym property with respect to μ . For a bounded linear operator $T : L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow X$ the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) $\|T\|_{p(\cdot)} < \infty$.
 (ii) T is Bochner representable, that is, there exists a unique function $g \in L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega, X)$ such that

$$T(u) = \int_{\Omega} u(t)g(t) d\mu, \quad \text{for all } u \in L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega).$$

In this case, $\|g\|_{L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega, X)} \leq \|T\|_{p(\cdot)} \leq K_{p(\cdot)} \|g\|_{L^{p^*(\cdot)}(\Omega, X)}$.

12 / 20

Bochner representable operators on $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega)$

Corollary

Suppose that $1 < p_- \leq p_+ < \infty$ and X has the Radon–Nikodym property with respect to μ . Then every bounded linear operator $T : L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow X$ with $\|T\|_{p(\cdot)} < \infty$ is compact.

13 / 20

Open problem

What is a characterization of a Bochner representable operator $T : L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow X$ in terms of m_T ?

14 / 20

Open problem

Let $1 < p < \infty$ and $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{p^*} = 1$.

Definition [DU, p. 115]

The p^* -**variation** of a vector measure $m : \Sigma \rightarrow X$ is defined by

$$\|m\|_{p^*} = \sup_{\pi} \left\{ \sum_{A \in \pi} \frac{\|m(A)\|^{p^*}}{\mu(A)^{p^*-1}} \right\}^{1/p^*}$$

where the supremum is taken over all finite Σ -partitions π of Ω . The convention $0/0 = 0$ is observed here.

Theorem [DU, p. 119]

Assume that X has the Radon–Nikodym property with respect to μ . For a bounded linear operator $T : L^p(\Omega) \rightarrow X$ the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) T is Bochner representable.
- (ii) m_T has a bounded p^* -variation.

15 / 20

Open problem

Let $V_{p^*}(\mu, X^*)$ be the space of all vector measures $m : \Sigma \rightarrow X^*$ with $\|m\|_{p^*} < \infty$.

Theorem [DU, p. 115]

For a linear functional $\Phi : L^p(\Omega, X) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) Φ is continuous.
- (ii) There exists a vector measure $m \in V_{p^*}(\mu, X^*)$ such that

$$\Phi(f) = \int_{\Omega} f \, dm \quad \text{for } f \in L^p(\Omega, X).$$

16 / 20

Open problem

Now, consider $([a, b], \mathcal{B}o, |\cdot|)$. By $p \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{B}o)$ denote the subset of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{B}o)$ such that the Hardy–Littlewood maximal operator is bounded on $L^{p(\cdot)}([a, b])$.

For $A \in \mathcal{B}o$ define p_A by

$$\frac{1}{p_A} = \frac{1}{|A|} \int_A \frac{1}{p(t)} dt.$$

Definition [CGR, Definition 12]

The $p^*(\cdot)$ -**variation** of a vector measure $m : \mathcal{B}o \rightarrow X$ is defined by

$$\varrho_{p^*(\cdot)}(m) = \sup_{\pi} \sum_{Q \in \pi} \frac{\|m(Q)\|^{p_Q^*}}{|Q|^{p_Q^*-1}}$$

where the supremum is taken over all finite partitions π of $[a, b]$ by any kind of disjoint non-degenerate intervals.

[CGR] Castillo R.E., O.M. Guzmán and H. Rafeiro, *Linear functionals on variable exponent Bochner–Lebesgue spaces*, Rend. Lincei Mat. Appl., 30 (2019), 583–597.

17 / 20

Open problem

By $V_{p^*(\cdot)}(|\cdot|, X^*)$ denote the space of vector measure $m : \mathcal{B}o \rightarrow X^*$ with bounded $p^*(\cdot)$ -variation.

Theorem [CGR, Theorem 21]

Let $p, p^* \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{B}o)$. For a linear functional $\Phi : L^{p(\cdot)}([a, b], X) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) Φ is continuous.
- (ii) There exists a vector measure $m \in V_{p^*(\cdot)}(|\cdot|, X^*)$ such that

$$\Phi(f) = \int_a^b f dm \text{ for } f \in L^{p(\cdot)}([a, b], X).$$

18 / 20

Open problem

What is a characterization of a Bochner representable operator $T : L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega) \rightarrow X$ in terms of m_T ?

14 / 20

References

Thank you for your attention!

20 / 20

Discrete Wiener-Hopf operators on Orlicz sequence spaces

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CT

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One of the main questions one can ask about a bounded linear operator on a Banach space is whether the operator is invertible. Sometimes this question can be very difficult to answer. A weaker form of this question is whether the operator is invertible modulo the ideal of all compact operators. Operators with this property are called Fredholm operators.

The aim of this work is to develop the Fredholm theory of discrete Wiener-Hopf operators with symbols which are periodic distributions. We concentrate on discrete Wiener-hopf operators acting on the Orlicz sequence spaces [2], which are far reaching generalizations of the Lebesgue sequence spaces. We try to extend the results for classical ℓ^p spaces [1] to the setting of Orlicz sequence spaces.

We extend the classical Brown-Halmos, Hartman-Wintner and Coburn theorems for discrete Wiener-Hopf operators to the setting of Orlicz spaces. Further, we give necessary and sufficient conditions for their Fredholmness if the symbols are continuous multipliers or, more generally, belong to the Douglas-type algebra $C_{\Phi} + H_{\Phi}^{\infty}$.

References

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- [2] Maligranda L., *Orlicz spaces and interpolation*, Vol.5, Seminários de Matemática [Seminars in Mathematics], Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Departamento de Matemática, Campinas (1989).

DISCRETE WIENER-HOPF OPERATORS ON ORLICZ SEQUENCE SPACES

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INTRODUCTION

In this project, we will concentrate our attention on Fredholmness (bounded linear operators with dimensions of kernel and cokernel are finite and a closed image) and invertibility of discrete Wiener-Hopf operators acting on Orlicz sequence spaces, extending results for classical ℓ^p -spaces.

YOUNG'S FUNCTION

DEFINITION

Let $\phi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ be increasing and left-continuous with $\phi(0) = 0$. Suppose that ϕ is neither identically zero nor identically infinite on $(0, \infty)$. Then the function Φ defined by

$$\Phi(s) := \int_0^s \phi(u) du, \quad s \geq 0,$$

is said to be a *Young's function*.

COMPLEMENTARY YOUNG'S FUNCTION

Let Φ be a Young's function as described earlier. Let

$$\psi(v) = \inf\{u : \phi(u) \geq v\}$$

for $v \geq 0$. Then the function

$$\Psi(t) := \int_0^t \psi(v) dv, \quad t \geq 0,$$

is called the *complementary Young's function* of Φ .

It is easily seen that if Ψ is complementary to Φ , then Φ is complementary to Ψ .

EXAMPLE

Let $1 < p < \infty$ and $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$.

Define $\phi(u) = u^{p-1}$. Then we have,

$$\Phi(x) = \int_0^x u^{p-1} du = \frac{x^p}{p}.$$

By definition,

$$\begin{aligned}\psi(v) &= \inf\{u : \phi(u) \geq v\} \\ &= \inf\{u : u^{p-1} \geq v\} \\ &= \inf\{u : u \geq v^{1/(p-1)} = v^{q-1}\} = v^{q-1}.\end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\Psi(x) = \int_0^x v^{q-1} dv = \frac{x^q}{q}.$$

Navigation icons: back, forward, search, etc.

ORLICZ SPACE WITH LUXEMBURG NORM

Introduced by W. Orlicz in 1932

$\mathbb{I} \in \{\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{Z}_+\}$

DEFINITION

Let Φ be a Young's function. The *Orlicz sequence space* $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{I})$ consists of all complex-valued sequences $x = (x_j)_{j \in \mathbb{I}}$ such that

$$M_\Phi(x/\lambda) = \sum_{j \in \mathbb{I}} \Phi\left(\frac{|x_j|}{\lambda}\right) < \infty$$

for some $\lambda = \lambda(x) > 0$.

Banach space with respect to the *Luxemburg norm*

$$\|x\|_{\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{I})} := \inf\{\lambda > 0 : M_\Phi(x/\lambda) \leq 1\}.$$

Navigation icons: back, forward, search, etc.

\mathcal{N} -FUNCTIONS

Now we will restrict ourselves to the following class of functions.

Let \mathcal{N} denote the class of all functions $\Phi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ which are nondecreasing, continuous, convex, $\Phi(0) = 0$ and

$$\lim_{u \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{\Phi(u)}{u} = 0, \quad \lim_{u \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Phi(u)}{u} = \infty.$$

A function $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ is called an \mathcal{N} -function.

δ_2 -CONDITION

A function $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ is said to satisfy δ_2 -condition if

$$\limsup_{u \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Phi(2u)}{\Phi(u)} < \infty.$$

Let $\ell^0(\mathbb{I})$ denotes the set of all complex sequences with finite support.

LEMMA

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ satisfies the δ_2 -condition. Then $\ell^0(\mathbb{I})$ is dense in $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{I})$.

WHY IS THE δ_2 -CONDITION IMPORTANT?

THEOREM

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$. The following conditions are equivalent:

- (I) Φ satisfies the δ_2 -condition.
- (II) $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{I})$ is separable.

THEOREM

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$. The following conditions are equivalent:

- (I) Both Φ and Ψ satisfy the δ_2 -condition.
- (II) $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{I})$ is reflexive.

INDICES OF ORLICZ SPACE

For $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$, we define,

$$\alpha_\Phi = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln \left(\liminf_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{\Phi(\lambda t)}{\Phi(t)} \right)}{\ln \lambda}$$

and

$$\beta_\Phi = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln \left(\limsup_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{\Phi(\lambda t)}{\Phi(t)} \right)}{\ln \lambda}.$$

α_Φ and β_Φ are called indices of Orlicz space or Matuszewska-Orlicz indices and $1 \leq \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi \leq \infty$.

EXAMPLE

Let $\Phi(x) = x^p, p > 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_\Phi &= \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln \left(\liminf_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{\Phi(\lambda t)}{\Phi(t)} \right)}{\ln \lambda} \\ &= \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln \left(\liminf_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{\lambda^p t^p}{t^p} \right)}{\ln \lambda} \\ &= \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln \lambda^p}{\ln \lambda} \\ &= \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{p \ln \lambda}{\ln \lambda} = p.\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $\beta_\Phi = p$.

PROPERTIES OF MATUSZEWSKA-ORLICZ INDICES

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$. Then,

- 1 The Orlicz sequence space $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{I})$ is separable if and only if $\beta_\Phi < \infty$.
- 2 The Orlicz sequence space $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{I})$ is reflexive if and only if $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$.
- 3 If Φ^{-1} is the inverse of Φ , then

$$\alpha_{\Phi^{-1}} = \frac{1}{\beta_\Phi} \text{ and } \beta_{\Phi^{-1}} = \frac{1}{\alpha_\Phi}.$$

- 4 $\frac{1}{\alpha_\Phi} + \frac{1}{\beta_\Psi} = \frac{1}{\alpha_\Psi} + \frac{1}{\beta_\Phi} = 1$.

The study of Wiener-Hopf integral operators

$$(Tf)(x) = \int_0^\infty a(x-y)f(y) dy, \quad x > 0,$$

was started by N. Wiener and E. Hopf in 1931.

Discrete Wiener-Hopf operators arise naturally as discretizations of their integral counterparts:

$$(Tf)_j = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_{j-k} f_k; \quad j \in \mathbb{Z}_+$$

where $(a_k)_{k \in \mathbb{Z}}$ is the Fourier coefficient sequence of a .

PERIODIC DISTRIBUTIONS

Periodic test functions \mathcal{P} : smooth functions from \mathbb{R} to \mathbb{C} that are 2π -periodic.

Periodic distribution: continuous linear functional on the space \mathcal{P} ,

$$F : \mathcal{P} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$$

such that

$$\begin{aligned} F(au) &= aF(u) & a \in \mathbb{C}, u \in \mathcal{P}; \\ F(u+v) &= F(u) + F(v) & u, v \in \mathcal{P}; \\ F(u_n) &\rightarrow F(u) & \text{if } u_n \rightarrow u \text{ in } \mathcal{P}. \end{aligned}$$

Let \mathcal{P}' be the set of all periodic distributions.

For $F \in \mathcal{P}'$ the n th **Fourier coefficient** ($n \in \mathbb{Z}$) is defined by

$$F_n = F(f_{-n}), \quad f_n(x) = \exp(inx).$$

THE SET OF MULTIPLIERS

For $a \in \mathcal{P}'$ and $\varphi \in \ell^0(\mathbb{Z})$ define the convolution $a * \varphi$ as the sequence

$$(a * \varphi)_j = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} a_{j-k} \varphi_k, \quad j \in \mathbb{Z},$$

where $(a_j)_{j \in \mathbb{Z}}$ is the sequence of Fourier coefficients of a .

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ and M^Φ denote the collection of all $a \in \mathcal{P}'$ for which $a * \varphi \in \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z})$ whenever $\varphi \in \ell^0(\mathbb{Z})$ and

$$\|a\|_{M^\Phi} := \sup \left\{ \frac{\|a * \varphi\|_{\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z})}}{\|\varphi\|_{\ell^0(\mathbb{Z})}} : \varphi \in \ell^0(\mathbb{Z}), \varphi \neq 0 \right\} < \infty.$$

LAURENT OPERATORS

DEFINITION

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ satisfy the δ_2 -condition. Then $\ell^0(\mathbb{Z})$ is dense in $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z})$. Hence, if $a \in M^\Phi$ then the operator

$$\ell^0(\mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}), \quad \varphi \mapsto a * \varphi$$

extends to a bounded operator

$$L(a) : \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}), \quad \varphi \mapsto a * \varphi,$$

which is referred to as the *Laurent operator* with symbol a .

MATRIX OF LAURENT OPERATORS

That is, the matrix of $L(a)$ is doubly-infinite and constant along diagonals.

$$L(a) = \begin{pmatrix} \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots \\ \ddots & a_0 & a_{-1} & a_{-2} & a_{-3} & a_{-4} & \ddots \\ \ddots & a_1 & a_0 & a_{-1} & a_{-2} & a_{-3} & \ddots \\ \ddots & a_2 & a_1 & a_0 & a_{-1} & a_{-2} & \ddots \\ \ddots & a_3 & a_2 & a_1 & a_0 & a_{-1} & \ddots \\ \ddots & a_4 & a_3 & a_2 & a_1 & a_0 & \ddots \\ \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots \end{pmatrix}.$$

For $\varphi \in \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{I})$ and $\psi \in \ell^\Psi(\mathbb{I})$, put

$$(\varphi, \psi) = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{I}} \varphi_n \overline{\psi_n}.$$

THEOREM (S.T. 2023)

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ satisfy the δ_2 -condition. Suppose $A \in \mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}))$ and

$$(Ae_j, e_k) = a_{k-j}, \quad j, k \in \mathbb{Z},$$

for some sequence $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$ of complex numbers. Then there is an $a \in M^\Phi$ such that $A = L(a)$ and $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$ is the Fourier coefficient sequence of a .

THE BANACH ALGEBRA M^Φ

- ① Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ satisfies the δ_2 -condition. If $a \in W$, where W is the Wiener algebra, then $a \in M^\Phi$ and

$$\|a\|_{M^\Phi} \leq \|a\|_W.$$

- ② Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. If $a \in L^\infty$ is of bounded variation, then $a \in M^\Phi$ and

$$\|a\|_{M^\Phi} \leq k(\|a\|_{L^\infty} + V(a)),$$

where k is a constant independent of a and $V(a)$ denotes the total variation of a .

- ③ Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. If $a \in M^\Phi$, then $a \in L^\infty$ and

$$\|a\|_{L^\infty} \leq \|a\|_{M^\Phi}.$$

- ④ Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. Then M^Φ is a Banach algebra with respect to the norm

$$\|a\|_{M^\Phi} = \|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}))}.$$

OUTLINE OF THE PROOF

- ① Let Φ and Ψ be complementary Young's functions. If T is a linear operator bounded on $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{I})$ and $\ell^\Psi(\mathbb{I})$, then T is bounded on $\ell^2(\mathbb{I})$ and

$$\|T\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^2(\mathbb{I}))} \leq 2 \|T\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{I}))}^{1/2} \|T\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Psi(\mathbb{I}))}^{1/2}.$$

- ② Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. If $a \in M^\Phi$, then $a \in M^\Psi$ and

$$\|a\|_{M^\Psi} \leq 2 \|a\|_{M^\Phi}.$$

- ③ This implies that

$$\|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}))} \leq 2 \|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}))}^{1/2} \|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Psi(\mathbb{Z}))}^{1/2} < \infty.$$

- ④ The Laurent operator $L(a)$ generates a bounded operator on $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z})$ if and only if $a \in L^\infty(\mathbb{T})$. Hence,

$$M^\Phi \subset L^\infty.$$

- ⑤ Norm inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} \|a\|_{L^\infty} &= \|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}))} \\ &\leq 2 \|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}))}^{1/2} \|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Psi(\mathbb{Z}))}^{1/2} \\ &\leq 2 \|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}))}^{1/2} \left(2 \|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}))} \right)^{1/2} \\ &= 2\sqrt{2} \|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}))} = 2\sqrt{2} \|a\|_{M^\Phi}. \end{aligned}$$

⑥ Applying equation to a^n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|a^n\|_{L^\infty} &\leq 2\sqrt{2}\|a^n\|_{M^\Phi}. \\ &\Downarrow \\ \|a\|_{L^\infty}^n &\leq 2\sqrt{2}\|a\|_{M^\Phi}^n \\ &\Downarrow \\ \|a\|_{L^\infty} &\leq (2\sqrt{2})^{1/n}\|a\|_{M^\Phi} \\ &\Downarrow (\text{as } n \rightarrow \infty), \\ \|a\|_{L^\infty} &\leq \|a\|_{M^\Phi}. \end{aligned}$$

DISCRETE WIENER-HOPF OPERATORS

Let P denotes the discrete Riesz projection of $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z})$ onto $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+)$ given by

$$(Pf)_j = \begin{cases} f_j, & \text{if } j \in \mathbb{Z}_+, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

For every $\varphi \in \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+)$, there exists a $\tilde{\varphi} \in \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z})$ such that

$$\tilde{\varphi}_n = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_+, \\ \varphi_n, & \text{if } n \in \mathbb{Z}_+. \end{cases}$$

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ satisfy the δ_2 -condition. Then $\ell^0(\mathbb{Z}_+)$ is dense in $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+)$. If $a \in M^\Phi$, then the operator

$$\ell^0(\mathbb{Z}_+) \rightarrow \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+), \quad \varphi \mapsto P(a * \tilde{\varphi})$$

extends to a bounded operator $T(a)$ on $\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+)$ given by

$$T(a) : \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+) \rightarrow \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+), \quad \varphi \mapsto P(a * \tilde{\varphi})$$

where $\tilde{\varphi} \in \ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z})$.

... AND THEIR MATRICES

$$T(a) = \begin{pmatrix} a_0 & a_{-1} & a_{-2} & a_{-3} & a_{-4} & \ddots \\ a_1 & a_0 & a_{-1} & a_{-2} & a_{-3} & \ddots \\ a_2 & a_1 & a_0 & a_{-1} & a_{-2} & \ddots \\ a_3 & a_2 & a_1 & a_0 & a_{-1} & \ddots \\ a_4 & a_3 & a_2 & a_1 & a_0 & \ddots \\ \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots \end{pmatrix}.$$

BROWN-HALMOS THEOREM

L^2 - Brown and Halmos (1963)

ℓ^p - Böttcher and Silbermann (1990)

THEOREM (S.T. 2023)

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ satisfy the δ_2 -condition. Suppose $A \in \mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+))$ and there is a sequence $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$ of complex numbers such that

$$(Ae_j, e_k) = a_{k-j}, \quad j, k \in \mathbb{Z}_+.$$

Then there exists an $a \in M^\Phi$ such that $A = T(a)$ and $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$ is the Fourier coefficient sequence of a . Moreover,

$$\|T(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+))} = \|L(a)\|_{\mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}))} = \|a\|_{M^\Phi}.$$

FREDHOLM OPERATORS

Let X be Banach spaces and let $A \in \mathcal{B}(X)$. The operator A is called a Fredholm operator if $\text{Im } A$ is closed in X and

$$\dim \text{Ker } A < \infty \text{ and } \dim X / \text{Im } A < \infty.$$

The collection of all Fredholm operators on X is denoted by $\Phi(X)$.

The index of A is defined as

$$\text{Ind } A = \dim \text{Ker } A - \dim X / \text{Im } A.$$

Navigation icons: back, forward, search, etc.

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JULY 11, 2024

27 / 34

HARTMAN-WINTNER THEOREM

The *essential range* $\mathcal{R}(a)$ of a function $a \in L^\infty$ is the spectrum of a considered as an element of the C^* -algebra L^∞ .

For $a \in M^\Phi$, let

$$\text{sp}_{M^\Phi} a = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : a - \lambda I \text{ is not invertible in } M^\Phi\}.$$

For $A \in \mathcal{B}(X)$, let

$$\text{sp}_{\Phi(X)} A = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : A - \lambda I \notin \Phi(X)\}.$$

L^2 - Hartman and Wintner (1954), L^p - Simonenko (1968)

ℓ^p - Böttcher and Silbermann (1990)

THEOREM (S.T. 2023)

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. If $a \in M^\Phi$ and $T(a) \in \Phi(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+))$, then $a \in GM^\Phi$. Consequently,

$$\mathcal{R}(a) \subset \text{sp}_{M^\Phi} a \subset \text{sp}_{\Phi(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+))} T(a).$$

Navigation icons: back, forward, search, etc.

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JULY 11, 2024

28 / 34

COBURN'S LEMMA

L^2 - Coburn (1966)
 L^p - Simonenko (1968)
 ℓ^p - Duduchava (1975)

THEOREM (S.T. 2023)

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. If $a \in M^\Phi$ and if a does not vanish identically, then the kernel of $T(a) \in \mathcal{B}(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+))$ or the kernel of $T(\bar{a}) \in \mathcal{B}(\ell^\Psi(\mathbb{Z}_+))$ is trivial.

THE CLASS \mathcal{C}_Φ

\mathbb{T} - unit circle

\mathbb{P} - set of trigonometric polynomials

If $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ satisfy the δ_2 -condition, then we have that

$$\mathbb{P} \subset W \Leftrightarrow M^\Phi.$$

Let \mathcal{C}_Φ denote the closure of the set of trigonometric polynomials \mathbb{P} with respect to the norm of M^Φ .

By definition, \mathcal{C}_Φ is a closed subalgebra of M^Φ .

ℓ^p - Krein (symbols in W) (1962)

Gohberg and Feldman (symbols in C_p) (1974)

THEOREM (S.T. 2024)

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. If $a \in C_\Phi$, then $T(a) \in \Phi(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+))$ if and only if a does not vanish identically on \mathbb{T} and

$$\text{Ind } T(a) = -\text{ind } a.$$

Moreover, $T(a)$ is invertible if and only if $T(a)$ is Fredholm with index zero.

$\text{ind } a$ denotes the winding number of a .

FIGURE: Example - winding number

THE CLASS $C_\Phi + \overline{H_\Phi^\infty}$

Let $\overline{H_\Phi^\infty} = \overline{H^\infty} \cap M^\Phi$, where

$$H^\infty = \{a \in L^\infty : a_n = 0 \text{ for } n < 0\}$$

and

$$\overline{H^\infty} = \{\bar{a} : a \in H^\infty\}.$$

Define

$$C_\Phi + \overline{H_\Phi^\infty} = \{a + b : a \in C_\Phi, b \in \overline{H_\Phi^\infty}\}.$$

ℓ^p - Böttcher and Silbermann (1989)

THEOREM (S.T. 2024)

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. Then $\mathcal{C}_\Phi + \overline{H_\Phi^\infty}$ is a closed subalgebra of M^Φ .

THEOREM (S.T. 2024)

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. If $a \in \mathcal{C}_\Phi + \overline{H_\Phi^\infty}$, then

$$T(a) \in \Phi(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+)) \iff a \in G(\mathcal{C}_\Phi + \overline{H_\Phi^\infty}).$$

ℓ^p - Böttcher and Silbermann (1989)

THEOREM (S.T. 2024)

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. Then $\mathcal{C}_\Phi + \overline{H_\Phi^\infty}$ is a closed subalgebra of M^Φ .

THEOREM (S.T. 2024)

Let $\Phi \in \mathcal{N}$ with Matuszewska-Orlicz indices satisfying $1 < \alpha_\Phi \leq \beta_\Phi < \infty$. If $a \in \mathcal{C}_\Phi + \overline{H_\Phi^\infty}$, then

$$T(a) \in \Phi(\ell^\Phi(\mathbb{Z}_+)) \iff a \in G(\mathcal{C}_\Phi + \overline{H_\Phi^\infty}).$$

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About the faculty

As a unit of a research centre, the Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science of Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan has continued an over 100 years old tradition of mathematics in Poznan. It is also one of the best academic centres in the field of computer science in Poland. At present the faculty offers study programmes in four fields: mathematics, computer science, data analysis and data processing, teaching mathematics and computer science. The latter one is unique for the whole country. The faculty also offers postgraduate study programmes.

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